

D3.1 PCP preparation outcomes

WP3 – PCP Preparation

CORVERS PROCUREMENT SERVICES BV

Funded by
the European Union

Document title	PCP preparation outcomes
Project acronym	PCP WISE
Project title	The customisation/pre-operationalisation of water management innovations from space for European climate resilience
Thematic priority	HORIZON-CL6-2024-GOVERNANCE-01
Type of action	Pre-commercial Procurement (PCP)
Deliverable number and title	D3.1 – PCP preparation outcomes
Task	Task 3.1 - Use cases, end user technical and functional requirements. Task 3.2 – Capitalising on PROTECT project results.
Work package	WP3
Due date	August 2025 (M7)
Submission date	25 July 2025
Start date of the project	01/01/2025
End date of the project	31/12/2027
Deliverable responsible partner	CORVERS PROCUREMENT SERVICES BV
Version	1.0
Status	Final
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Document type	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> R – Report <input type="checkbox"/> O – Other
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU – Public <input type="checkbox"/> SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement

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Versioning and contribution history			
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
0.1	15.04.2025	Maria Kampa, Egli Rrokaj, Abed El Majid Nasser, Hans van Leeuwen	ToC prepared
0.2	15.5.2025	Maria Kampa, Egli Rrokaj, Abed El Majid Nasser, Hans van Leeuwen, Nadya Ben Bekhti-Winkel	50% of the document sections filled in
0.3	06.06.2025	Maria Kampa, Egli Rrokaj, Abed El Majid Nasser, Hans van Leeuwen, Nadya Ben Bekhti-Winkel	Almost final version of the document (sections 3, 4). Draft version presenting the work done for sections 2, 5, 6, 7
0.4	11.6.22025	Maria Kampa	First consolidated draft version of the deliverable submitted to EC
0.6	03.07.2025	Nils Winter, Tobias Hellmund	Integration Technical Requirements
0.7	15.07.2025	All Authors & contributors	Updated requirements and USL based on test site visits
0.8	23.07.2025	Tobias Hellmund, Hans van Leeuwen, Antonia Matthies	Review and updated requirements in Annex 7 based on interactions.
0.9	24.07.2025	Tobias Hellmund, Hans van Leeuwen, Maria Kampa	Final updates in Annex 7
1.0	25.07.2025	Maria Kampa	Final version ready for submission

Document abstract

This deliverable presents the outcomes of the preparatory phase of the PCP WISE project, focused on translating climate resilience challenges into concrete, demand-driven procurement requirements. Developed under Work Package 3 (WP3), the document details the consolidation of initial use cases into five representative clusters through stakeholder engagement, scoping exercises, and a series of collaborative workshops. It also includes the definition of user requirements, technical specifications, and test site criteria, as well as the results of the State-of-the-Art (SOTA) and market analysis. Additionally, it outlines the preliminary business case and cost-benefit analysis to support the feasibility and strategic justification for the forthcoming Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) process.

Keywords

Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP), climate resilience, water management, use cases, user requirements, technical specifications, soil-water-vegetation (SWV), State-of-the-Art (SOTA), market analysis, cost-benefit analysis

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANB	Anomaly-Based
API	Application Programming Interface
BASF	Badische Anilin- und Soda-Fabrik (German chemical company)
BC	British Columbia / Before Christ (context-dependent)
CA	Contracting Authority/ties
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
COTS	Commercial Off-The-Shelf
CPC	Civil Protection Cooperation
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DSS	Decision Support System
EAFIP	European Assistance for Innovation Procurement
EC	European Commission
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
ECV	Essential Climate Variables
EFFIS	European Forest Fire Information System
EIF	European Interoperability Framework
EO	Earth Observation
EPO	European Patent Office
ESG	Environmental, Social, and Governance

Abbreviation	Meaning
ESRI	Environmental Systems Research Institute
ET	Evapotranspiration
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FRA	Federal Railroad Administration / France (country code)
FRAND	Fair, Reasonable, And Non-Discriminatory
GCOS	Global Climate Observing System
GIS	Geographic Information System
GKH	Green Knowledge Hub
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GTN	Global Terrestrial Network
GUI	Graphical User Interface
ICGC	Cartographic and Geological Institute of Catalonia
ICS	Incident Command System
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
INPADOC	International Patent Documentation Center
IPC	International Patent Classification
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
KATI	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LTE	Long-Term Evolution

Abbreviation	Meaning
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NBS	Nature-Based Solutions
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
NETCDF	Network Common Data Form
NPV	Net Present Value
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OMC	Open Market Consultation
PCP	Pre-Commercial Procurement
PDCA	Plan-Do-Check-Act
PI	Principal Investigator
PIN	Prior Information Notice
PNG	Portable Network Graphics
PPI	Public Procurement of Innovation
QGIS	Quantum GIS (Geographic Information System)
RGB	Red, Green Blue
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
SOTA	State Of The Art
SWV	Soil-Water-Vegetation
SWVA	Soil-Water-Vegetation-Atmosphere
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UC	Use Case
USA	United States of America
USGS	United States Geological Survey

Abbreviation	Meaning
VIIRS	Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite
VNIR	Visible and Near Infrared
WFS	Web Feature Service
WIPO	World Intellectual Property Organization
WMO	World Meteorological Organization
WMS	Web Map Service
WP	Work Package
WW	Wastewater

1. Introduction

The PCP WISE project—Pre-Commercial Procurement for Water-related Innovation Supporting European climate resilience—operates within the framework of the Horizon Europe programme, aiming to bridge the gap between research-driven innovation and operational deployment of advanced water management technologies. Focused on addressing the pressing challenges posed by climate-induced extremes such as droughts and floods, PCP WISE leverages a structured, demand-driven procurement process to source and validate solutions that enhance the resilience of Europe's soil-water-vegetation (SWV) systems.

This deliverable (D3.1) reports on the key preparatory activities carried out under Work Package 3 (WP3 – PCP Preparation), specifically Tasks 3.1 and 3.2. The work has focused on translating identified climate adaptation challenges into concrete procurement needs through the collaborative efforts of a consortium of public buyers and user organisations spanning diverse European regions. The outcomes presented herein reflect the co-creation process aimed at shaping representative and actionable use cases, grounded in the operational realities of local authorities and stakeholders.

Initial activities centred on consolidating and refining over twenty preliminary use cases—derived in part from the preceding PROTECT CSA project—into five final clusters. This was achieved through an iterative funnel process involving bilateral interviews, user workshops, and scoping exercises. These five representative clusters reflect diverse urban and rural settings and address a range of climate resilience challenges, including groundwater depletion, excess surface water, and vegetation stress. Each use case was documented through a detailed scoping template, outlining user needs, technical requirements, validation criteria, test sites, and expected benefits.

To support the development of a robust and informed procurement strategy, Task 3.2 undertook an extensive State of the Art (SOTA) and Market Analysis. This included reviews of existing technologies, scientific literature, patent landscapes, and commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) products. The goal was to identify the maturity (Technology Readiness Level), gaps, and innovation potential of current solutions, and to assess whether they align with the operational requirements defined in the use cases. In parallel, an Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and standards analysis was performed to anticipate potential legal, technical, and interoperability constraints.

Additionally, a preliminary Business Case and Cost-Benefit Analysis was developed. Drawing from user data, public buyer input, and financial modelling techniques (Monte Carlo simulations), the analysis aimed to quantify the economic impact and anticipated value of investing in innovative climate resilience solutions. This economic assessment is critical for ensuring the feasibility and sustainability of the forthcoming PCP procedure.

In summary, this deliverable lays the foundation for the next stages of the PCP WISE project, including the Open Market Consultation (OMC) and the drafting of the PCP tender documentation. By combining user-driven requirement engineering with comprehensive

market intelligence and economic justification, D3.1. ensures that the procurement process is both technically sound and strategically aligned with climate adaptation goals.

2. Use cases, end user technical and functional requirements

2.1. Fine tuning Use Cases

As a continuation of the work initiated under the PROTECT CSA project, and in preparation for the PCP-WISE initiative, a comprehensive set of use cases was developed through close collaboration with the project's BUYER partners and USER organisations. These use cases reflect the real-world challenges caused by extreme climate events across Northern, Eastern, Southern, and Western Europe—particularly those impacting the local Soil-Water-Vegetation (and Atmospheric) systems. Such challenges include recurring, irregular, and often prolonged episodes of drought or water excess that disrupt environmental balance and local infrastructure.

The objective of the first phase of the project was to review, update, and consolidate the initial set of use cases into a focused group of five representative cases. This refinement process was carried out through intensive engagement with the participating BUYER and USER organisations, with the goal of identifying the most relevant and cross-cutting information and operational requirements to inform the forthcoming PCP procurement process.

The overall process began with a series of one-to-one interviews with each one of the public buyers, followed by six targeted workshops held on 18 February, 5 March, 18 March, 23 April, 14 May, and 26 May 2025. These sessions provided a platform for buyers and users to align their perspectives, refine their priorities, validate their needs, and co-develop common ground across diverse operational environments. The outcomes of these workshops were instrumental in shaping the final structure and content of the use cases and scoping documents that will guide the PCP tender process—ultimately supporting local and regional stakeholders in effectively managing the impacts of climate change over the short, medium, and long term.

2.1.1. Original use cases

Following the initial definition of use cases, STOWA engaged in targeted interactions with the BUYERS and USERS to better align proposed concepts with local needs. These early discussions revealed opportunities for refinement and consolidation.

Use cases PCP-WISE	Fast Onset Crises (FOC)	Slow Onset Crises (SOC)
RURAL (R)	RFOC1 Flash Flood Summer 2021 in Ahr Valley, GER, Limburg NL	RSOC1 Slow Onset River Flood 2023/24 in Lower Saxony, GER Rural
	RFOC2 Vegetation and peat fire 2023/24 lower Saxony, GER	RSOC2 Drought Impact Model on Agricultural Production - Catalonia region, Andalusia or other (Spain)
	RFOC3 Wild Fires @SK: Slovak republic (National level), Self-governing regions Banska Bystrica, (Regional level)	RSOC3 SOIL MOISTURE: Spatiotemporal surface & root zone soil moisture determ. Catalonia eo region (Ebro Delta Spain)
	RFOC4 Floods @SK: Slovak republic (National level), Self-governing regions Banska Bystrica, (Regional level)	RSOC4 Drought: Subsidence in rural agricultural grass/peatlands in the water management area of waterauthority HDSR (NL)
	RFOC5 Floods:civil protection initiative for the Mygdonia catchment area (Central Macedonia)	RSOC5 Wild Fires: Nature area Kalmthoutse Heide (NL Belgium)
URBAN (U)	UFOC1 Flash Flood Summer 2021 in Ahr Valley, GER	RSOC6 Nature/Rural: control ecosystem/residential area on groundwater/greening (in former airport region of Helsinki)
	UFOC2 Wild Fires @ SK: Spisska Nova Ves (District level), Bratislava (Local City level)	USOC1 Slow Onset River Flood 2023/24 in Lower Saxony, GER Urban Heat Island/subsidence: Multi Climate change scenario's in existing urban area's (Haarlem city, NL)
	UFOC3 Floods @ SK: Bratislava (Local City level), Spisska Nova Ves (District level)	USOC2 Soil saturation: Shallow ground water, Demvig, Denmark
	UFOC4 Floods/Stormwater: City critical watermanagement Helsinki	USOC3 Subsidence: Terrain subsidizing Lemvig Denmark
		USOC4 Subsidence: City Infrastructure Rotterdam

Figure 1 Original use cases

After first interactions, a second version of the use cases was realized. In this regard, our Slovak partners opted to merge the urban use case for Bratislava City with the rural use case from the Spišská Nová Ves region, creating a unified approach that addresses challenges across both urban and rural environments. Similarly, our partners from Catalunya decided to consolidate their initially separate use cases related to rural drought management and agricultural resilience, recognizing the strong interdependencies between the two.

Use cases PCP-WISE	Fast Onset Crises (FOC)	Slow Onset Crises (SOC)
RURAL (R)	RFOC1 Flash Flood Summer 2021 in Ahr Valley, GER, Limburg NL	RSOC1 Slow Onset River Flood 2023/24 in Lower Saxony, GER Rural
	RFOC2 Vegetation and peat fire 2018 lower Saxony, GER	RSOC2a Drought Impact Model on Agricultural Production - Catalonia region, Andalusia or other (Spain)
	RFOC3a Wild Fires: Slovak republic (National level), Self-governing regions Banska Bystrica BB (Regional level), Spisska Nova Ves SNV (District level)	RSOC2b SOIL MOISTURE: Spatiotemporal surface & root zone soil moisture determ. Catalonia region (Ebro Delta Spain)
	RFOC3b Floods: Slovak republic (National level), Self-governing regions Banska Bystrica BB (Regional level), Spisska Nova Ves SNV (District level)	RSOC4 Drought: Subsidence in rural agricultural grass/peatlands in the water management area of waterauthority HDSR (NL)
	RFOC5 Floods:civil protection initiative for the Mygdonia catchment area (Central Macedonia)	RSOC5 Wild Fires: Nature area Kalmthoutse Heide (NL Belgium)
URBAN (U)	UFOC1 Flash Flood Summer 2021 in Ahr Valley, GER	RSOC6 --> USOC6
	UFOC2a Wild Fires: Slovakia Bratislava (Local City level)	USOC1 -->RSOC1
	UFOC2b Floods: Slovakia Bratislava (Local City level)	USOC2 Heat Island/subsidence: Multi Climate change scenario's in existing urban area's (Haarlem city, NL)
	UFOC4 Floods/Stormwater: City critical watermanagement Helsinki	USOC3 Soil saturation: Shallow ground water, Lemvig, Denmark
		USOC4 Subsidence: Terrain subsidizing Lemvig Denmark
		USOC5 Subsidence: City Infrastructure Rotterdam
	USOC6 Nature/Rural: control ecosystem/residential area on groundwater/greening (in former airport region of Helsinki)	

Figure 2 First adaptation use cases.

Furthermore, the USOC1 use case (Urban, THW) was found to be sufficiently covered by RSOC1 (Rural, THW), eliminating the need for separate development. At the same time, FVH confirmed its focus on the urban use case USOC6, which also integrates rural elements

through RSOC6, demonstrating a more holistic approach to addressing interconnected urban-rural challenges.

All the abovementioned refinements, led to the finalised list of use cases (Figure 3), based on which all participating BUYERS and USERS were asked to prepare an individual use case document. This document served as a foundational input to the next phases of the use case development, aimed at aligning innovation activities with practical needs on the ground.

2.1.2. Funnel process

Based on the individual use case documents, the funnel process towards representative use cases was facilitated by conducting interviews, wherein besides the needs (resulting in information requirements), general criteria for clustering and cooperation between BUYERS was also discussed.

Figure 3 Funnel process from original use cases towards Representative use Cases

The clustering of use cases was carried out using a two-layered approach, guided by a set of clearly defined criteria. The first level of clustering was based on general attributes such as whether the use case addressed an urban or rural setting, the existence of a physical test site candidate, and the geographical location of the partner within Europe (North, East, South, or West).

Table 1 provides an initial overview of the general characteristics of the proposed test sites, highlighting the diversity across cases in terms of urban/rural balance, geographic spread, and thematic focus.

TESTSITE Data														
Acquisition	THW	SEA	RCM	THW	ICGC/IEEC	HDSR	KHH	SEA	FvH	Haarlem	Lemvig	Lemvig	Rdam	FvH
	RFOC2	RFOC3_4	RFOC5	RSOC1	RSOC2_3	RSOC4	RSOC5	UFOC2_3	UFOC4	USOC2	USOC3	USOC4	USOC5	USOC6
Regular	G	BB/SNV	Gr	G	Sp/Cat	NL	NL/B	Bratislava	Finl	NL	Dk	Dk	NL	Finl
Soil moisture (10yrs)	n	pot	y (during)	n	yes	y	y	pot	y	n	y	y	n	y
groundwater (10yrs)	n	pot	y (during)	n	yes	y	y	pot	y	n	y	y	n	y
evapotranspiration	n	?	?	n	n	y	y	?	n	n	y	y	n	?
Meteorology (local)	y	y	y (during)	y	yes	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y
Hydrological model	n	?	?	n	yes	y	y	?	y	n	y	y	n	y
Vegetation (growt) data	y	pot	y (during)	y	yes	y	y	pot	park	park	yes	yes	park	yes
Landuse	y	pot	y (during)	y	yes	y	y	maps	maps	maps	yes	yes	maps	yes
Crisis info														
Flood		yes	yes	yes				yes	yes	yes	yes			yes
Drought/Fires	yes	yes			yes	yes (subs)	yes	yes		yes		yes (subs)	yes (subs)	
Cluster proposal					C	C	C	C				C		C
EU region	N	E	S	N	S Eur	W Eur	W Eur	E Eur	N	W	N	N	W	N Eur

Table 1 First overview of general testsite characteristics

Test site requirements (funnel)

During the interview process and the first BUYER workshop held on 18 February 2025, the selection of test sites emerged as a key criterion in shaping the final use case clustering. Discussions focused on both local contextual factors and technical criteria relevant for the validation of future solutions. Since validation is a critical element in assessing contractors R&D results, the designation of test sites—and the identification of lead stakeholders responsible for hosting them—was carried out in close consultation with all BUYERS and project partners.

This process led to the identification of five representative test sites to be used in Phases 2 and 3 of the PCP process for testing, validation, and demonstration activities. These sites, indicated by red stars in Figure 4, will serve as central points for solution evaluation. Additionally, partner sites, shown in green, will be involved in Phase 3 demonstration activities, further supporting the project’s scalability and relevance across different European regions.

Figure 4 Testsite locations per Groupelead (red) & partners (green), see left. On the right the same testsite with group colors and validation/BenchMark points (STEMMUS-SCOPE) in Europe

The test sites representing the five groups have been designated by the BUYERs and will be examined throughout the PCP-WISE project at both the local and regional (sub-watershed) scale (Figure 5).

Figure 5 Testsite scale definition in urban and rural local and regional site scales

In the second layer, the clustering process was further refined by applying additional qualitative criteria. These included the nature of the problem addressed—such as whether the use case focused on flooding or drought—its representativeness in terms of regular operations versus crisis response scenarios, and the overall suitability of the use case in terms of the partner’s commitment. The latter considered factors such as long term planned actions, and the partner’s willingness and capacity to lead the PCP process.

Based on this layered analysis, a preliminary grouping was proposed that divides the use cases into five representative groups. Each group includes thematically, or operationally related use

cases and suggested a potential lead candidate that could represent the group during further development phases. These proposed clusters are detailed in Table 2.

Group	Domain	Lead	Other partners	Lead UC	Other UCs
G1 Urban	(F/D)	FVH	City Rotterdam, City Haarlem, STOWA	USOC6	USOC5, USOC2
G2 Urban	F(D)	SEA/Mol	FVH, Klimatorium, THW	UFOC2_3	UFOC4, USOC3, RSOC1
G3 Rural	D/F	Grenspark (Benego)	SEA, STOWA	RSOC5	RFOC3_4
G4 Rural	D/F	ICGC/IEEC	RCM	RSOC2_3	RFOC5
G5 Rural	D/F	Klimatorium	THW, STOWA (supported by HDSR)	USOC4	RSOC4, RFOC2

Table 2 First use case clustering

The rationale for this clustering is further supported by the arguments summarised in Table 3. These include the:

- Urban vs Rural
- Test site compliancy (Table 1)
- Position in Europe (N,E,S,W)
- Thematic issues comparable within the group.

Group	Lead	partner 1	partner 2	partner 3		
G1 Urban	(F/D)	USOC6	USOC5	USOC2	City waterbalance, drought, subsidence, heat, infra instability	
G2 Urban	F(D)	UFOC2_3	UFOC4	USOC3	RSOC1	City waterbalance, flooding, crisis (fast), risk assessment, etc.
G3 Rural	D/F	RSOC5	RFOC3_4		Rural Waterbalance, Drought, risk assessment, crisis (fire, floods)	
G4 Rural	D/F	RSOC2_3	RFOC5		Rural Waterbalance, Flooding, Drought, Agriculture, risk assessment, crisis (floods, fire)	
G5 Rural	D/F	USOC4	RSOC4	RFOC2	Rural Waterbalance, Drought, Rural Subsidence, Risk assessment, Peat fires	

Table 3: Reasoning of clustering of use cases with main themes

2.1.4 Clustering results

As a result of the interactions outlined above and the specific information needs identified by the sectors involved, comprehensive final descriptions were developed for each use case, detailing the key challenges related to soil, water, and vegetation conditions. This effort culminated in the final clustering of use cases, as presented in the table below.

Cluster / Group	Lead	Partner 1	Partner 2	Partner 3	Original use cases
G1 urban	FVH Rotterdam & Haarlem				USOC5 USOC2 USOC6
G2 urban	SEA /Mol	FVH	Klimatorium	THW	UFOC2/3 UFOC4 USOC3 RSOC1

G3 rural	Grenspark	SEA	STOWA		RSOC5	RFOC 3/4		
G4 rural	ICGC/IEEC	RCM			RSOCC2/3	RFOC5		
G5 rural	Klimatorium	STOWA & HDSR	THW		USOC4	UROC4	RFOC2	

Table 4: WISE 5 Use cases clusters/groups

In this regard, the final focus of the five groups was selected as follows:

Group 1 Urban Drought (N-W EU)

Group 1 is dealing with Urban problems in the local city context in terms of spatial water distribution in the city underground due to all kind of human and external (regional, climate) factors. The focus is on dealing with the shortage of water due to problems of (local) water storage, infiltration, evapotranspiration, etc. causing too low groundwater levels, impacting infrastructure by subsidence (streets, housing, critical infrastructure like utility sector, etc) or living and green conditions (heat islands, green parks, open water).

Group 2 Urban Water excess (E-N EU)

Group 2 is dealing with Urban problems in the local city context in terms of spatial water distribution in the city underground due to all kind of human and external (seepage, sea level rise, etc) factors. The focus is on dealing with abundance of water due to problems of (local) water storage, infiltration, etc. impacting infrastructure (streets, housing, critical infrastructure like utility sector). Mostly the context (river basin region and regional shallow groundwater) of the city has additional (in)direct impact on the basic city water conditions.

Group 3 Rural Drought (N-E EU)

Group 3 is dealing with rural problems related to extremes in local climate variations (intensive rainfall) and enduring drought periods in the North/Middle European regions having impact on seasonal processes in agriculture/nature and excesses like wildfires and production losses or even failure. Here as opposed to South of Europe it is in general not structural in terms of structural lack of water availability (which differs over the years).

Group 4 Rural Drought/Flooding (S-EU)

Group 4 is dealing with rural problems related to extremes in local climate variations (intensive rainfall) and enduring (structural/over the years) drought periods in the Southern European regions having impact on seasonal processes in agriculture/nature and excesses like wildfires and production losses or even failure.

Group 5 Rural Drought/Flooding (N-EU)

Group 5 is dealing with rural problems due to extremes in low and high (or so called shallow) groundwater conditions resulting in all kinds of problems for the land use, city council

infrastructures, utility sector. A common issue is that due to subsidence and uprise of the soil surface during the season (high fluctuations in height difference, hysteresis) and over the years/decades (structural lowering of soil surface). These (extreme) soil moisture conditions in particularly peat (combined with clay/sand) profiles can cause organic oxidation processes and even underground peat fires.

Table 5 below presents the final clustering outcome, including the composition of each group and the corresponding lead organisation.

Urban		Rural	
G1: Helsinki (F)	D & F	G3: Kalmthout (B/NL)	D
Rotterdam (NL)	D & F	Danube Bratislava region (Sk)	D & F
Haarlem (NL)	D & F	G4: Catalunya (Sp)	D
G2: Bratislava Slovakia	F	Region Central Macedonia (Gr)	F & D
Helsinki (F)	F & D	G5: Lemvig Living Lab (Dk)	D
Lemvig, (Dk)	F	HDSR - Utrecht (NL)	D
Lower Saxony, (G)	F	Lower Saxony (G)	D

Table 5 Final clustering leading to the following groups and partners. The first partner is leader and hosting the testsite representing the other partners (F= Flood issues, D= Drought issues)

Building on the broad spectrum of identified information needs, the above funnelling to representative grouping was refined through a functional and information requirement analysis, providing the underlying rationale for each group.

As a next step, BUYERs within each cluster developed coordinated group scoping documents (see Section 2.1.4), synthesising insights gathered during the interviews and workshops into coherent group-level summaries. This process began with a **functional analysis**, where the expected improvements enabled by operational PCP WISE solutions were prioritised. Based on these priorities, a joint analysis of **information requirements** was conducted, focusing on the data and system functionalities needed to support those key functions within relevant organisations and stakeholder environments (see also Section 2.3.1).

2.1.4 Group Scoping documents

The development of the scoping document based on the template provided was a structured and iterative process facilitated through a series of user workshops and bilateral discussions. This approach ensured that all participating buyers and end-users had the opportunity to collaboratively refine their ideas, align on priorities, and harmonize needs across diverse local and national contexts.

Initially, all BUYERS and USERS were invited to provide a draft outline of their intended common use case, including high-level objectives, known challenges, and preliminary requirements. The starting point for this activity were the **individual use case documents**. Through facilitated workshops, these inputs were collectively reviewed and further detailed

leading a **cluster scoping documents** based on the clustering process described in Section 2.1.3, allowing participants to exchange insights, explore commonalities, and address differences in data availability, stakeholder landscapes, and infrastructure constraints. Iterative feedback loops were essential to gradually evolve individual drafts into a consolidated **cluster-level use case description**, capturing shared goals while also highlighting the grouped needs.

The final documents included several core components:

- A **common use case narrative** describing the urban water excess scenario under regular and crisis conditions;
- A **stakeholder and sector analysis** mapping key actors and their roles;
- A detailed list of **functional requirements and information needs**, both joint and country-specific;
- The identification of **test sites** with relevant monitoring systems and datasets; and
- An outline of **expected benefits** for each participating region.

Importantly, the scoping documents were further fine-tuned to provide targeted input into the Open Market Consultation (OMC) document (Deliverable 3.2. Prior Information Notice for the OMC). This ensured that the market could be clearly and accurately informed about the needs and expectations of the buyers group. The final version of these five scoping documents has been included in **Section 6 -Annex B-** of this deliverable -excluding the test site information which are part of the Deliverable 3.6.

2.2. Physical Factors information criteria/requirements

In this section, the description of the Physical Factors to be monitored by integrated space based remote sensing mechanisms is presented in order to understand the central role of the soil-water-vegetation-atmosphere system in the PCP WISE project.

This results in an overview of physical factors of this system which need to be matched by the results of the functional requirement analysis and consecutive information requirements in Sub Task 3.1.1. and the relevant cluster scoping documents content.

In climate adaptation and mitigation policies of governmental bodies, information mechanisms play a crucial role and can have many functions (see orange process in figure 6):

- Information can help in qualifying (& sometimes quantifying) climate process indicators
- Definition of a Base line of those indicators (Reference year/Situation)
- Definition of goals to be achieved
- Definition/monitoring the path to this goal
- Definition/monitoring of the evaluation of (policy/management) measures to be taken.

Figure 6 Scheme to translate user/organisational needs from policy/management or functional needs towards supporting information requirements leading towards technical information specifications

In Section 2.3.1 the information needs are further elaborated which will be matched with the technical information based on the physical factors identified in this section. Those physical factors are determined either by observations directly or in combination with models or data science mechanisms, which describe the biophysical conditions of the SWVA-system. In figure 8 the SWVA system can be simply described with different (physical, chemical, biological) characteristics in several layers:

- The water distribution in the soil profile (or matrix) as a function of the Soil characteristics, where we can distinguish in general the:
 - phreatic zone (groundwater)
 - percolation zone, which connects the groundwater level with the top soil by macro pore structure of the soil and vertical water transport (depending basically on the governing physical properties, porosity/structure, hydraulic conductivity, texture, capillary rise mechanisms, etc)
 - root zone, where the essential uptake of moisture is possible for different types of vegetation depending on the soil characteristics (porosity, texture, etc.)
 - Top soil zone, where the important interaction between the atmosphere and soil system takes place and often influenced by human processes in general
- The groundwater zone in the soil is saturated with water and the soil matrix on top of that is called the unsaturated (or vadose) zone, which is partly filled (or not) with water.

Figure 7 The simple presentation of a Soil-Water-Vegetation-Atmosphere system

The soil-water-vegetation-atmosphere system is governed by several biophysical processes (Energy balance, hydrology, crop growth, atmosphere) which physical characteristics can be observed and described by the following schematization (see Figure 9, STEMMUS-SCOPE¹).

Figure 8 The STEMMUS-SCOPE model of the UT-Twente describing the SWVA system

The biophysical factors which can be observed by (remote) sensing are only a subset of the above complex SWVA system but help us to actualize the condition/state of this system using

¹ <https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/14/1379/2021/>

different sensors (Optical, Thermal, Microwave) and processing (model interaction) mechanisms.

An (non-exhaustive) overview of remote sensing observation potential can be seen in figure 10 (SCOPE model describing the fundamental biophysical characteristics) and figure 11 (in red) the processes influencing the SWVA system conditions

Figure 9 The processes which affect the SWVA system conditions

The physical factors relevant to the PCP WISE project can be simply summarized and represented by the hydrological description of the soil-water system actualised by its actual conditions as a result of the above complex description of biophysical processes in figure 10.

The simplification of reality is done for pragmatic and operational reasons and has the function of providing managers of practical indicators and trends to take the right decisions and measures in time and space to reduce risks and prevent impacts induced by climate extremes.

A subset of the above spectrum of physical processes described by physical factors can be summarised/translated in the following for PCP WISE relevant parameters set:

- The soil water balance components*
- Soil moisture conditions in the unsaturated zone (0-5cm; root zone; percolation zone); see figure 9
- Actual Evapotranspiration & Evapotranspiration Deficit ($ET_{pot}-ET_{act}$)/Ratio (ET_{act}/ET_{pot})

- Phreatic Groundwater Levels
- Seepage/Deep infiltration

P = Precipitation

I_f = Infiltration

I = Irrigation

Cr = Capillary Rise

ET = Actual Evapotranspiration

Sr = Surface Runoff

Gr = Groundwater Recharge

ΔS = change in storage

These parameters are furthermore represented in the PCP WISE information services as a result of matching with the functional information requirements, see section 2.3.1.

We need to match the information requirements from the demand driven analysis with the technical and bio-physical description of SWV(A) parameters to be determined as basis for our monitoring mechanism. Once we have translated this into physical factors, it is then possible to define the technical tender specifications for the operational solution architecture. Whether these required specifications are realistic to be produced in ('operational') TRL8 fashion or not depends on the State of the Art of the technical potential in the market domain. In chapter 3 the SOTA analysis exhibits the current potential and with that the market & technical readiness to deliver the expected solutions requested by PCP WISE to the consortia/value-adders/modelers/data scientists, etc.

2.3. Requirements, Use Cases and Technical Specs for the tender document

2.3.1. User Story Lines

This section outlines the process for deriving user requirements from the identified cluster groups. At this stage, the focus was on gathering high-level requirements.

To support this effort and the structured development of user stories, Fraunhofer IOSB designed a dedicated template ([User-Story-Lines template.pptx](#)), which was distributed to the cluster groups. These groups completed the templates with support from Fraunhofer IOSB through collaborative workshops where needed. This process ensured that the technical members of the project team could gain a clear understanding of the type of solution to be developed, as well as the key constraints to be considered.

The template was structured in two main parts:

- In the first section, users detailed their primary tasks and overarching objectives, collectively referred to as the mission. They also described current challenges and obstacles in the pain points section. The tools section outlined the existing software solutions used in daily operations, while the data sources section identified the types of data currently leveraged within those tools.
- The second section of the template focused on potential improvements and solution ideas. In the solution field, users proposed how the identified issues might be addressed. Technical requirements and non-technical requirements captured specific needs for future software tools. Further expectations and conditions were described in the acceptance criteria section. Finally, the benefits section summarized the anticipated advantages of implementing the proposed high-level solutions.

Validation of the user stories was carried out during T5.1 end user workshops, where end users had the opportunity to review, correct, and enrich the initial inputs collected by the group leaders with their real-world experiences. These sessions included the development of early pen-and-paper prototypes to further illustrate desired solution features. The prototypes were used to validate and elaborate the USLs, from which the technical requirements were generated. The figure below shows an exemplary pen-and-paper prototype, that was generated during the Bratislava End User Workshop on the 3rd of July, 2025. It shows a mobile application, which allows understanding potential flooded areas under different severity scenarios. It also allows adding points of interest, such as vulnerable groups and objects, or flood-protected evacuation areas. Based on the user-desired prototype, the previously elicited technical requirements can be validated.

In the following sections, summaries of the identified user groups and key findings concerning the desired PCP-WISE solution are presented. The complete list of user stories is provided in the annex A (Section 5).

2.3.1.1. Use Case Group I

Cluster I, headed by FvH (Helsinki) brings together a broad range of public and private stakeholders who share a common interest in protecting water resources and infrastructure. A total of 10 stakeholders were identified, including government bodies, environmental agencies, city departments, construction companies, insurers, and citizens (see Annex A).

Their missions range from regulatory enforcement and sustainable urban planning to risk prevention, property protection, and climate resilience. Despite differing roles, these user groups all require accurate, timely, and accessible water-related data to make informed decisions, respond to environmental changes, and support long-term sustainability goals.

The ideal solution is a comprehensive, interoperable monitoring and decision-support system that combines real-time ground-based and satellite data (e.g., Copernicus) with predictive analytics and user-friendly interfaces. It must enable integration of diverse data sources—soil

moisture, groundwater, runoff, evaporation, and temperature—within a high-resolution geospatial framework (e.g., 5x5 m grids). Core capabilities include event detection, anomaly alerts, scenario modeling, and automated workflows for risk mitigation. Compliance with open standards (SensorThings API, WFS/WMS) ensures scalability and data interoperability, while role-based access and offline functionality support flexible use in field operations, planning, and crisis response.

Technically, the system must support historical data queries, customizable analysis, and real-time data transmission (via REST-API, MQTT/WebSockets). It should ensure data integrity, privacy, and public-sector compliance, and allow scenario planning for both everyday operations and crisis situations (e.g., 30–60 min update intervals). It also supports real-time monitoring of water quality, groundwater, soil moisture, and surface runoff - key to addressing challenges in urban planning, climate adaptation, and environmental protection.

The solution empowers users to reduce reliance on costly consultants, improve environmental supervision, safeguard urban infrastructure, and respond faster to emerging water-related risks—ultimately contributing to more adaptive, sustainable, and resilient water management. With user-friendly interfaces and offline capabilities, the system ensures accessibility for both technical experts and field-based users, promoting data-driven decisions across all levels of governance and operation.

2.3.1.2. Use Case Group II

Cluster II brings together a diverse group of stakeholders from Central and Northern Europe, focusing on the management of urban infrastructure, water systems, and emergency response amidst increasing climate-related challenges. Key contributors include national authorities (e.g., the Slovak Ministry of Environment and Interior), municipal departments (e.g., Bratislava and Helsinki), utilities, private companies, emergency services and citizens. This collaborative effort involves both strategic decision-makers and operational actors working towards climate adaptation, flood risk mitigation, sustainable infrastructure planning and communication with the public.

The ideal solution for enhancing water management and infrastructural resilience should cater to these stakeholders by leveraging national spatial data infrastructures and supporting the implementation of climate adaptation strategies. It emphasizes the need for cities and local institutes to define measurable adaptation levels for green-blue infrastructure, while fostering collaboration among private companies and wastewater utilities to address challenges related to increased rainfall and groundwater ingress. Emergency services, like THW and Spisska Nova Ves, aim to improve their response capabilities for water-related crises in this integrated approach.

Technical requirements for the solution encompass comprehensive data management and advanced analytical and visualisation capabilities. It is essential to enable the storage, editing, and integration of heterogeneous data from both satellite and ground sensors in standardized formats. Analytical functions should support custom algorithms for hazard, risk and scenario

analysis and allow for data export and integration in interoperable formats (OGC based formats). Additionally, user interfaces must provide both machine-readable APIs and user-friendly GUIs to cater to diverse user needs. Governance and security measures must ensure role-based access control and data integrity. The solution should not only adapt to emergency situations but also be scalable and modular for future enhancements.

2.3.1.3. Use Case Group III

Cluster Group III encompasses a diverse set of stakeholders, including terrain managing organizations, farmers, fire and crisis management authorities, drinking water companies, municipalities, region administrations, and the public. Their shared mission focuses on managing natural and agricultural landscapes under increasing drought and wildfire risks, ensuring water resource sustainability, safeguarding public safety, and enhancing ecosystem resilience. These groups require tools to monitor ecological drought, support adaptive management, optimize irrigation, anticipate water availability challenges, and provide timely alerts and risk information to protect people and nature.

To meet these needs, the technical solution centers on comprehensive, high-resolution environmental monitoring combined with advanced analysis and decision-support capabilities. The system integrates multi-source data (e.g., satellite imagery, ground sensors, meteorological forecasts, and historical records) to deliver real-time and near-real-time information on soil moisture, vegetation stress, groundwater recharge, and wildfire risk. It supports scenario simulations for crop yields, water resource recharge, and fire risk mitigation, while allowing customizable thresholds and KPIs tailored to habitats, crops, and operational protocols. User-friendly, multilingual interfaces facilitate access for both technical and non-technical users, with mobile and offline functionality enabling field use by managers, farmers, and emergency teams.

The solution's technical requirements emphasize open standards and interoperability, including compliance with SensorThings API for time-series data, integration of spatial risk layers, and compatibility with GIS, early warning, and emergency dispatch platforms. Governance features ensure role-based access, legal compliance, and data protection, especially concerning private lands and cross-border data sharing. Operational support includes system calibration, training, scenario-based simulations, and geolocation alerts to foster effective adoption and proactive risk management across the cluster's stakeholders.

2.3.1.4. Use Case Group IV

This cluster primarily involves key stakeholders responsible for environmental monitoring, disaster preparedness, and emergency response. The main user groups include environmental and agricultural government agencies, the Region Central Macedonia authorities, and frontline responders such as fire brigades and forest managers. Each group has distinct but interconnected missions: government agencies focus on anticipating and mitigating the impacts of drought and wildfire on agriculture and natural ecosystems, RCM aims to improve

flood mitigation through real-time data and scenario simulations, and fire brigades seek enhanced wildfire prediction and coordinated response capabilities. These missions require timely, accurate, and integrated data to enable proactive risk management and efficient crisis coordination.

To meet these diverse needs, the technical system must handle a broad spectrum of data types and sources. It supports monitoring and analysis of historical, current, and forecasted data with high-resolution satellite inputs like soil moisture and evapotranspiration, combined with crop and vegetation dryness indicators. Data integration spans geospatial and temporal dimensions, incorporating weekly updates from Copernicus and adhering to open standards such as WMS, WFS, and the OGC SensorThings API. The system also fuses data on groundwater quality and hydrology to provide a comprehensive environmental overview. On the intelligence side, it offers predictive modeling and risk analysis algorithms for drought, flood, and wildfire scenarios, enabling scheduled updates and simulations critical for preparedness.

User interaction is facilitated through both machine-readable APIs for automated workflows and intuitive graphical interfaces with real-time dashboards and scenario mapping tools. Governance is emphasized through role-based access control, secure data sharing, and shared decision protocols to ensure seamless communication across agencies. Operational support includes features for data validation, training modes, emergency communication protocols, and automated reporting. Together, these capabilities empower stakeholders to make informed decisions, enhance early warning systems, and coordinate effective responses to environmental threats.

2.3.1.5. Use Case Group V

The main stakeholders involved in Cluster group V include Water and Wastewater Utilities, emergency response organizations such as THW, the Danish Road Directorate, and the agricultural sector represented by both farmers (e.g., Fjordland) and consultants (e.g., SEGES). Water and Wastewater Utilities focus on ensuring a reliable supply of clean drinking water while responsibly managing wastewater and climate-related water risks. Emergency Services aim to improve anticipation and response capabilities to water-related crises to safeguard personnel and communities. The Danish Road Directorate is dedicated to building and maintaining resilient road infrastructure by mitigating risks related to flooding, subsidence, and surface damage. Meanwhile, farmers prioritize operational reliability by addressing local risks like flooding, drought, and subsidence that threaten crop yields, and consultants work toward sustainable agricultural production through research and improved soil management.

To support these diverse missions, a comprehensive solution is needed that integrates robust data handling, advanced analysis, and user-friendly interfaces. This involves managing geospatial and time-series data across heterogeneous sources such as geological surveys, sensors, satellite imagery, and field measurements. Critical features include long-term projections of subsidence integrated into GIS mapping systems, dynamic risk modelling and simulation for floods and wildfires, and customizable risk maps applicable to infrastructure, farmland, and roads. The system must adhere to open data standards (OGC, WFS, WMS),

enable interoperability with existing GIS and command/control tools, and offer secure, role-based access for diverse user groups.

Operationally, the platform should support field data entry, data validation, and quality assurance to maintain reliability, alongside training and safe testing environments. Ultimately, this integrated approach will empower stakeholders with accurate, real-time insights and predictive tools, enhancing decision-making for infrastructure planning, emergency response, agricultural resilience, and environmental sustainability.

Figure 10 Infographic summarising the PCP WISE Use Cases

2.3.2. Functional User requirements

The functional requirements defined by the BUYERS partners and especially related to the needs of its user communities are based on the 5 Groups processes and documentation. The user needs are based on their internal policies (strategical/tactical) and management (operational) processes related to climate induced local problems related to the local/regional soil-water-vegetation conditions (SWV). These can be expressed in (climate) functional indicators supporting local management & measures to be resilient to the climate extreme conditions impacting the local regions interests.

Figure 11 Organisations (people) need to change working procedures from regular to Short Term (crisis) Action mode or to Long Term (climate) Strategy mode

Figure 12 Zoomed into the process of translation policy to information needs to technical specs, which is an iterative and evolving process between users and technology disciplines

The functional requirements from the 5 BUYER/USER groups can be summarised in 6 general categories, which support the following organisation processes (policy/management needs):

- **Urban Regular:** Management/measures: water, infra, green, heat, energy, etc
- **Urban Crisis:** Risk reduction/measures, Risk priorities/crisishandling
- **Urban Climate:** Evaluation/measures (Long Term), adjustment/hindsight, scenario/forecast
- **Rural Regular:** Management/measures: water-soil, nature, agriculture, etc
- **Rural Crisis:** Risk reduction/measures, Risk priorities/crisishandling
- **Rural Climate:** Evaluation/measures (LT), adjustment/hindsight, scenario/forecast

An important observation is that the PCP WISE services are positioned in the **regular and pre-disaster phase of the crisis cycle** and to support organisations in taking measures in regular management (maintenance, inspection and monitoring) and assessing extreme situations by supporting and anticipating on taking crisis related measures (support disaster risk reduction or priority decision making during a crisis).

Figure 13 The crisis cycle with its different phases, wherein WISE services are focused on regular monitoring in the pre-disaster (or cold) phase and building intelligence by providing risk indicators to anticipate on extreme situations as a result of too wet

2.3.3. Information Requirements

Based on the functional requirements identified through user and stakeholder needs, specific information needs—expressed as qualitative or, in some cases, quantitative indicators—have been defined for each category, following engagement with all five groups. This process resulted in a concise and consolidated overview of information requirements for both urban and rural stakeholders/users, as outlined in the scoping documents per group and represented by the respective lead buyer.

The information requirements from the 5 BUYER/USER groups can be summarised in general as follows:

- **Urban Regular:** Soil matrix/groundwater conditions (monitor), short term forecast, specific apps on subsidence, heat islands (evapotranspiration), park/green monitor, water storage
- **Urban Crisis:** spatial (weighted) risk mapping (sector limits)
- **Urban Climate:** Historical Trends, input to long term forecast/scenarios
- **Rural Regular:** Soil matrix/groundwater conditions (monitor), short term forecast, specific apps on agriculture, nature
- **Rural Crisis:** spatial (weighted) risk mapping (sector limits)
- **Rural Climate:** Historical Trends, model-based inputs to long term forecast/scenarios

2.3.4. Technical information requirements

Building on the identified user information requirements, the next step is to define the corresponding technical requirements for each category. These should be both realistically feasible and suitable for integration into the operational PCP tender process. This will result in a set of technical information categories relevant to the PCP-WISE framework, which will be described in this section.

It is essential to distinguish between urban and rural soil-water systems, as they exhibit fundamentally different water balance mechanisms (see figure below).

Figure 14 Urban and rural soil-water systems with each their fundamental differences in water balance mechanisms

In general, the soil-water-vegetation system can be schematised as:

Urban Regular technical information specifications

The soil water balance components*

- Soil moisture conditions in the unsaturated zone (0-5cm; root zone; percolation zone); see figure 1
- Actual Evapotranspiration & Evapotranspiration Deficit ($ET_{pot} - ET_{act}$)/Ratio (ET_{act}/ET_{pot})
- Phreatic Groundwater Levels
- Seepage/Deep infiltration

Urban Crisis (always in terms of risk indicators)

The below mentioned risk indicators should be derived from 1 or more of the Urban Regular Information Products.

- Soil Drying & Wetting (in terms of severity, magnitude, duration, and spatial extent; Risk maps: where does it become drier, where does it become wetter in the unsaturated zone)
- Saturated soil moisture conditions (prior to heavy rainfall)
- City infrastructure (street/building) subsidence
- Green vegetation health (biomass productivity)
- (open) Surface Water temperature
- Infrastructure temperature (Urban Heat Island Effect)

Urban Climate

A re-analysis* dataset (2000-2025) of:

- The soil water balance components
- Soil moisture conditions (0-5cm; root zone; percolation zone)
- Soil Drying & Wetting (in terms of severity, magnitude, duration, and spatial extent; [...] In other words: We want grid-based maps that gives us information about where it become drier and where it becomes wetter in the unsaturated zone)

A climate forecasted (based on standard European climate scenarios) dataset (2026-2050/2070) of:

- The soil water balance components
- Soil moisture conditions (0-5cm; root zone; percolation zone)
- Soil Drying & Wetting (in terms of severity, magnitude, duration, and spatial extent; In other words: We want grid-based maps that gives us information about where it become drier and where it becomes wetter in the unsaturated zone)

**: A historical reconstruction of the past hydrology using a combination of model data & satellite data.*

Rural Regular

The soil water balance components

- Soil moisture conditions (0-5cm; root zone; percolation zone)
- Actual Evapotranspiration & Evapotranspiration Deficit/Ratio (ETact/ETpot)
- Phreatic Groundwater levels
- Seepage/Deep infiltration

Rural Crisis (always in terms of risk indicators)

The below mentioned risk indicators should be derived from 1 or more of the Urban Regular Information Products.

- Soil Drying & Wetting (in terms of severity, magnitude, duration, and spatial extent)
- Saturated soil moisture conditions (prior to heavy rainfall)
- Risk for wildfires
- Floodrisk
- Structural rural subsidence (caused by enduring drought) / or top surface uprise (shallow water or seepage pressure)
- Risk of Crop failure or (significant) reduction in yield
- Risk lack of irrigation water
- Risk Water quality of (surface/ground) water systems due to enduring drought

- Risk Desiccation of environment² (of natural areas by definition)
- Risk Biodiversity Loss (habitat and species loss)

Rural Climate

A re-analysis dataset (2000-2025) of:

- The soil water balance components
- Soil moisture conditions (0-5cm; root zone; percolation zone)
- Soil Drying & Wetting (in terms of severity, magnitude, duration, and spatial extent; In other words: We want grid-based maps that gives us information about where it becomes drier and where it becomes wetter in the unsaturated zone)

A forecasted dataset (2026-2050/2070) of:

- The soil water balance components
- Soil moisture conditions (0-5cm; root zone; percolation zone)
- Soil Drying & Wetting (in terms of severity, magnitude, duration, and spatial extent; In other words: We want grid-based maps that gives us information about where it becomes drier and where it becomes wetter in the unsaturated zone)

The above technical information requirements are related to the physical processes of the soil-water-vegetation (and atmosphere) system and the observation process (potential) to monitor this system. For a more complete description of the technical specification in the context of the tender, also with more references and context, see Annex C (Chapter 7) of the current document.

2.4. Use Case Dataset development

In this section the data strategy and description of the BUYER/USER groups is presented. This is the basis for internal and external activities of PCP-WISE. The attributes of these data provide input to Task 1.5. Data Management strategy of the project.

2.4.1. Use case datasets strategy

The various use cases are presented and analysed in Section 2.1. resulting in information requirements, leading to the relevant technical information categories and feasible technical specs to be ingested into the technical tender documents. To support the internal (validation, testing, demonstration) processes and the external supplier activities we need to structure and organise the (prior) information and data from the different user groups and their test sites. Important is that we start to define and 'create' a PCP-WISE data strategy based on European standards.

² Soil Desiccation: Soil can dry out due to factors like evaporation, plant uptake of water, and lack of rainfall, leading to changes in soil properties and impacting plant growth.

Figure 15 Base Layer

For cross (admin/country) border cooperation between regional and local (water, city, nature, agriculture, etc) sector managers it is necessary to guarantee the standardisation of information exchange on our soil-water-vegetation conditions. The 4-layer information structure strategy is therefore proposed and further designed for this project:

1. Base layer (I):

- i. serving as information carrier for the users
- ii. a standard description of our (static) world provides us with base information such as location, elevation, weather, soilmaps, administrative boundaries, infrastructure
- iii. These common information carriers provide a basis for our dynamic changing world.

2. Soil-Water (taxonomy) base layer

- a. The regular water cycle processes can be described/modeled with key variables which can be partly measured/observation by EO and partly modeled:
- b. Observed by EO: rain, evapotranspiration, soil moisture, temperature
- c. Modeled: see hydrological cycle on the left (model either common applied centralised standard model instrumentarium or local modeling/knowledge/tailored instrumentarium; e.g. leading to degree of saturation of soil profile)

Figure 16 Standard presentation of hydrological processes

3. Water dynamics layer

- a. Climate/weather related extremes of this Soil-water system
- b. Due to extreme climate events the regular water cycle transforms into different categories of crises/hazards

- c. Extreme changes to the water cycle cause drought, flooding and have consequences on the short and long term for our soil-water-atmosphere system of our living world (water dynamics layer)
- d. Critical thresholds are passed (like the saturation of top soil causing runoff or e.g. critical combustion factor of biomass/nature vegetation or critical groundwater level for irreversible subsidence of infrastructure)

M Reichstein et al. Nature 500, 287-295 (2013) doi:10.1038/nature12350

Figure 17 Processes and feedback triggered by extreme climate events.

4. Risk assessment layer per sector as a result of these extremes

- a. The risk of too dry or too wet conditions is partly determined by the potential impact (physical damage) to various sectors, apart from even important if not more alpha factors such as social/economic/community coping/resilience
- b. Risk = chance × impact or even more practical: Risk is a result of the vulnerability of (a sector) to a certain exposure to the occurring hazard category. Risk-related factors often can be estimated by Earth Observation!
- c. EO also helps in creating data for learning/training processes (AI e.g. for vulnerability assessment) and development of a better uniform Risk Language

Figure 18 Risk Assessment methodology

2.4.2. Interoperability

In the PCP WISE project data and soil-water-vegetation (SWV) information play in all aspects an important role. From top left to right the data flow from satellite observation and according to value chain will lead to SWV information supporting user related (regular, crisis, climate) functions in selected regions in Europe. For mutual understanding of each other’s problems of organisations in similar river basin regions, we need to have clear agreement on what and how the information is shared. This requires standards and definitions which can be carried across any type of border (administrative, organisation, country, etc).

Figure 19 PCP WISE Information Flow

The PCP WISE project needs to prepare this type of interoperability not only for internal and user reasons but also for specification of the services to be procured. In the next figure the EIF (European Interoperability Framework³) gives a nice overview of the various dimensions we need to traverse when we want to serve the public/users/policymakers in an operational manner (reaching the according needed TRL levels).

³ https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/sites/default/files/eif_brochure_final.pdf

Figure 20 European Interoperability Framework

With the PCP WISE project we aim to produce a blueprint for future operational procurement of daily intelligence on ‘soil-water’ system conditions to enable local managers and policy makers to take right measures and decisions to anticipate on climate induced problems in our society. From bottom to top in figure 16: SWV-system Intelligence is a result of technical (1) thematical (2) products delivered by the market (in this context) under the right legal & contractual (3) conditions to support users and organisations (4) in their work in the context of climate adaptation & mitigation policies (5).

Applying standards in the interoperability chain is of utmost importance in the context of cooperation between organizations but also when we need to scale in space and time (climate).

2.4.3. Base Data Layer 1

The information carrier in layer 1 is important for future user interoperability and internal project consistency reasons. Relevant to mention is that this base layer should subsequently support the thematical information and related climate sectorial risks.

We have to comply to European standards (if available) on:

1. Information carrier standards (spatial, topographical)
2. Meteorology standards

- 3. Soil-water data standards
- 4. Sectorial base data standards (urban, agriculture, hydrology, nature/biodiversity, water quality, etc.)

These data standards are defined and created by institutions in European or global context by various organisations relevant to our thematic problem domain (meteo/hydrology/climate) and our monitoring domain (spatial observation & geography).

Figure 21 Overview of relevant institutions is presented in the GTN framework

Within this context many relevant programmes (Copernicus, WMO, ECWMF, UN, etc.) provide data and supports information standards. In the figure above relevant segments have been identified to serve our PCP WISE project data standards.

Figure 22 The Value chain (vertical) of WISE, with all the disciplines involved and interoperability within the chain stakeholders

In order to funnel these data standards towards a useful set for PCP-WISE relevant information standards we need first to assess the thematical layer in more detail.

2.4.4. Thematical layer

The thematical information layer concerning soil-water-vegetation system conditions need to be based on the standard data layers available see section 2.4.2. The SWV system conditions information provided by the market should facilitate the users and stakeholders and need to be interoperable.

Achieving effective hydrological interoperability is a key objective within the PCP-WISE project, ensuring that innovative market solutions can be meaningfully adopted, validated, and scaled across diverse user needs and environmental conditions. Interoperability refers to the ability of systems, stakeholders, and data to work seamlessly together across different contexts—supporting better decision-making, more accurate hydrological insights, and increased alignment between suppliers, users, and broader policy frameworks. The following dimensions outline how interoperability is addressed in PCP-WISE, from local implementation to European-level harmonisation.

- 1. Interoperable between suppliers & users within the Project PCP-WISE:**
In order to create a bridge between the supply & demand we need to have an intermediate hydrological representation and representative generalisation of the soil-water-vegetation conditions of our local region/management area

2. **Interoperability in the validation process**, where local hydrological insights (of sites of users) can be compared to market solutions (WISE)
3. **Interoperability between users & stakeholders** (in challenges) within the PCP-WISE project within the same river basin or across (admin management or country) borders
4. **Creating/developing a common future water taxonomy on European scale**, linking to Copernicus (e.g., EU-HYDRO)

Based on the identified functional and corresponding information requirements (see Section 2.2), a set of technical information products has been defined (see Section 2.3). These products vary in spatial and temporal scale (see figure below) and can be linked to relevant datasets from the test sites, service outputs, and the needs of the user groups they are intended to support.

Figure 23 The 2 spatial scales for the 5 Leader Testsites: local test site (detailed in 10-30m) in urban and rural and the surrounding (sub)watershed (100m)

After the general requirements analysis, the identified problem areas across user groups must be demonstrated through WISE services. These demonstrations are defined along spatial and temporal dimensions, reflecting the complexity and variability of soil-water-vegetation systems in different contexts.

Spatial Scale:

- Lead test site: Represents the core problem area or issues per group at the local scale (Scale I) with high-resolution detail (1 m to 10 m, or best available data).
- Context of the lead test site: Includes areas with direct or indirect impact on the problem, covering the watershed/regional scale (Scale II) with a detail level of 100 m.
- Group or all partner test sites: Encompasses broader problem areas within the watershed region, non-validated at Scale II (100 m detail).

Temporal Scale:

- Lead test site (Scale I): Focuses on within-season processes, providing daily monitoring of the water balance (short-term period and 3-day forecast).
- Lead test site (Scale II): Targets historical trends (spanning 20 years, with daily resolution) and includes climate scenario-based forecasts for the next 20 years (long-term period).
- Group/partner test sites (Scale II): Include non-validated daily monitoring of water balance during the within-season period (ST period and 3-day forecast) as well as the long-term period (LT).

The standards in producing these information services/products need to be defined and if available based on existing European (or global) mechanisms in the meteo-hydrology context.

For the definition of SWV information on local management level (about 100m detail) in Europe there are not yet international accepted mechanisms in place in terms of interoperability. We therefore selected for our European context a globally accepted hydrology model system MODFLOW describing groundwater (flow) and the soil-water system conditions, which can as a basis system easily be connected to other model systems (like runoff/flooding/inundation modelling, unsaturated zone (vadose) modelling, aquifer (hydrogeological) modelling, etc.

In the figure hereafter one can see the role of MODFLOW (and its graphical presentation mode iMOD Suite) in the PCP-WISE process steps.

Figure 24 The Role of MODFLOW (general accepted and industrial global standard) hydrological model within the project, between users and interchange between suppliers and users

Without going into detail in this context it is important that the inputs to this so-called interoperable hydrological model MODFLOW4 (as part of the WFLOW family) are based on the earlier mentioned standards in section 2.4.2.

The thematic base data (Layer 2) supporting these modelling exercises can be presented in full model parameter sets, see tables 5 below. However, these parameters are not standard, many of these parameters can be provided by European and global institutions active in the Hydrosphere domain, see Figure on GTN and in particular the Copernicus, WMO, ECWMF, UN, programmes in this context, etc.). An inventory of relevant parameters has been compiled to serve as input for the tender preparation.

Symbol	Description	Unit	Wflow.jl name
S_{canopy}	Canopy storage	mm	canopystorage
S_{snow}	Snow storage	mm	snow
$S_{snow,liquid}$	Amount of liquid water in the snowpack	mm	snowwater
$S_{glacier}$	Glacier storage	mm	glacierstore
$S_{unsat, n}$	Amount of water in the unsaturated zone, for layer n	mm	ustorelayerdepth
S_{sat}	Amount of water in saturated store	mm	satwaterdepth
S_{res}	Storage of reservoir	m^3	volume
S_{lake}	Lake storage	m^3	storage
H_{lake}	Water level lake	m	waterlevel
P	Precipitation	$mm\ t^{-1}$	precipitation
I_{total}	Total interception	$mm\ t^{-1}$	interception
$P_{throughfall}$	Throughfall	$mm\ t^{-1}$	throughfall
$F_{available}$	Infiltration rate of available water	$mm\ t^{-1}$	avail_forinfiltr
F_{excess}	Infiltration excess water rate	$mm\ t^{-1}$	infiltrate
$F_{excess, sat}$	Rate of water that cannot infiltrate due to saturated soil	$mm\ t^{-1}$	waterexcess
F_{act}	Actual infiltration rate	$mm\ t^{-1}$	actinfiltr
$R_{exfiltr, sat}$	Water exfiltrating under saturation excess conditions	$m\ t^{-1}$	exfiltrwater
$R_{exfiltr, unsat}$	Water exfiltrating from unsaturated store because of change in water table	$mm\ t^{-1}$	exfiltrstore
R_{river}	Runoff from river fraction	$mm\ t^{-1}$	runoff_river
$R_{open\ water}$	Runoff from open-water fraction (excluding rivers)	$mm\ t^{-1}$	runoff_land
$E_{open\ water}$	Evaporation from open waterbodies (excluding rivers)	$mm\ t^{-1}$	ae_openw_l
E_{river}	Evaporation from rivers	$mm\ t^{-1}$	ae_openw_r
$E_{act, sat}$	Soil evaporation from the saturated store	$mm\ t^{-1}$	soilevapsat
$E_{act, soil}$	Soil evaporation from the unsaturated store	$mm\ t^{-1}$	-
$E_{trans, sat}$	Transpiration from the saturated store	$mm\ t^{-1}$	actevapsat
$\sum_{n=1}^m E_{trans, unsat, n}$	Transpiration from the unsaturated store for m unsaturated soil layers	$mm\ t^{-1}$	ae_ustore
C_{act}	Actual capillary rise	$mm\ t^{-1}$	actcapflux
L	Leakage	$mm\ t^{-1}$	actleakage
R_{input}	Net recharge to the saturated store	$mm\ t^{-1}$	recharge
$Q_{subsurface}$	Subsurface flow	$m^3\ d^{-1}$	ssf
$Q_{transfer, act, m}$	Transfer of water from unsaturated soil layer m to saturated store	$mm\ t^{-1}$	transfer
Q	Surface flow in the kinematic wave	$m^3\ s^{-1}$	q_{av}^*
$Q_{in, lake}$	Lake inflow	$m^3\ t^{-1}$	inflow
$Q_{out, lake}$	Lake outflow	$m^3\ t^{-1}$	totaloutflow
P_{lake}	Lake average precipitation	$mm\ t^{-1}$	precipitation
E_{lake}	Lake average evaporation	$mm\ t^{-1}$	evaporation
$Q_{in, res}$	Reservoir inflow	$m^3\ t^{-1}$	inflow
$Q_{out, res}$	Reservoir outflow	$m^3\ t^{-1}$	totaloutflow
P_{res}	Reservoir average precipitation	$mm\ t^{-1}$	precipitation
$E_{pot, res}$	Reservoir average evaporation	$mm\ t^{-1}$	evaporation

Figure 25 WFLOW_ hydrological parameters (MODFLOW is part of this family), state and flux

⁴ <https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/17/3199/2024/>
<https://www.deltares.nl/en/software-and-data/products/wflow-catchment-hydrology>
⁵ <https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/17/3199/2024/#section6>

Symbol	Description	Unit	Wflow.jl name	Default value
P	Precipitation	$\text{mm } t^{-1}$	precipitation	-
$E_{\text{pot, total}}$	Potential evapotranspiration	$\text{mm } t^{-1}$	potential_evaporation	-
T_{air}	Mean air temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	temperature	-
z_{soil}	Soil depth	mm	soilthickness	2000.0
θ_s	Saturated soil water content	$\text{mm } \text{mm}^{-1}$	θ_s	0.6
θ_r	Residual soil water content	$\text{mm } \text{mm}^{-1}$	θ_r	0.01
f_{paved}	Fraction of compacted soil (or paved)	-	pathfrac	0.01
$f_{\text{open water}}$	Open-water fraction (excluding rivers)	-	waterfrac	0.0
f_{river}	River fraction	-	riverfrac	-
$c_{\text{infiltration, unpaved}}$	Infiltration capacity of non-compacted soil	$\text{mm } t^{-1}$	infiltrcapsoil	$100.0 \text{ mm } d^{-1}$
$c_{\text{infiltration, paved}}$	Infiltration capacity of compacted soil	$\text{mm } t^{-1}$	infiltrcappath	$10.0 \text{ mm } d^{-1}$
z_{rooting}	Rooting depth	mm	rootingdepth	750.0
E_{int}	Gash interception model parameter	-	e_r	0.1
LAI	Leaf area index	$\text{m}^2 \text{ m}^{-2}$	leaf_area_index	-
S_{leaf}	Specific leaf storage	mm	sl	-
$S_{\text{canopy, max}}$	Canopy storage capacity	mm	cmax	1.0
$f_{\text{canopygap}}$	Canopy gap fraction	-	canopygapfraction	0.1
$S_{\text{wood, max}}$	Storage capacity, woody parts of vegetation	mm	swood	-
k	Extinction coefficient	-	kext	-
c_{rd}	Model parameter controlling the sigmoid function, for the fraction of wet roots	mm^{-1}	rootdistpar	-500.0
$z_{\text{cap, maxdepth}}$	Critical water depth beyond which capillary rise ceases	mm	cap_hmax	2000.0
n_{cap}	Empirical coefficient controlling capillary rise	-	cap_n	2.0
K_{v0}	Vertical saturated hydraulic conductivity at the soil surface	$\text{mm } t^{-1}$	kv0	$3000.0 \text{ mm } d^{-1}$
f_{kv}	Scaling parameter for vertical saturated hydraulic conductivity	mm^{-1}	f	0.001
c_n	Brooks-Corey power coefficient	-	c	10.0
h_b	Air entry value	cm	hb	10.0
L_{max}	Maximum allowed leakage	$\text{mm } t^{-1}$	maxleakage	$0.0 \text{ mm } d^{-1}$
f_{kh0}	Multiplication factor applied to K_{v0} (for lateral subsurface flow)	-	-	1.0
$f_{\text{kv, n}}$	Multiplication factor (correcting vertical saturated hydraulic conductivity)	-	kvfrac	1.0
s_{ddf}	Degree-day-melt factor snow	$\text{mm } t^{-1} \text{ } ^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$	cfmax	$3.75653 \text{ mm } d^{-1} \text{ } ^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$
$s_{\text{fall, } T \text{ threshold}}$	Temperature threshold for snowfall	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	tt	0.0
$s_{\text{fall, } T \text{ interval}}$	Temperature threshold interval for snowfall	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	ttoi	1.0
$s_{\text{melt, } T \text{ threshold}}$	Temperature threshold for snowmelt	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	ttn	0.0
s_{whc}	Water-holding capacity of snow	-	whc	0.1
$s_{\text{melt, } T \text{ threshold}}$	Temperature threshold for glacier melt	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	g_tt	0.0
s_{ddf}	Degree-day-melt factor glacier	$\text{mm } t^{-1} \text{ } ^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$	g_cfmax	$3.0 \text{ mm } d^{-1} \text{ } ^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$
f_{glacier}	Fraction covered by a glacier	-	glacierfrac	0.0
S_{glacier}	Glacier storage	mm	glacierstore	5500.0
$\beta_{\text{snow to firm}}$	Fraction of snow that is converted into firm	t^{-1}	g_sifrac	0.001 d^{-1}
w_{soil}	Weighting coefficient for near-surface soil temperature	t^{-1}	w_soil	0.1125 d^{-1}
$f_{\text{red, frozen}}$	Controlling infiltration reduction factor	-	cf_soil	0.038
$c_{\text{land slope}}$	Slope of the land surface	$\text{m } \text{m}^{-1}$	β_l	-
$c_{\text{river slope}}$	Slope of river	$\text{m } \text{m}^{-1}$	sl	-
A_{res}	Reservoir area	m^2	area	-
$Q_{\text{min req.}}$	Minimum flow requirement downstream of the reservoir	$\text{m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$	demandrelease	-
$Q_{\text{max, res}}$	Maximum release capacity spillway	$\text{m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$	maxrelease	-
$S_{\text{res, max}}$	Maximum storage of the reservoir	m^3	maxvolume	-
$f_{\text{res, min}}$	Target minimum storage fraction	-	targetminfrac	-
$f_{\text{res, max}}$	Target maximum storage fraction	-	targetmaxfrac	-
A_{lake}	Lake area	m^2	area	-
$H_{0, \text{lake}}$	Water level lake threshold (below this threshold no outflow occurs)	m	threshold	-
H_{lake}	Water level lake	m	waterlevel	-
α_{lake}	Lake rating curve coefficient	$\text{m } \text{s}^{-1(a)}, \text{ m}^{\frac{2}{3}} \text{ s}^{-1(b)}$	b	-
β_{lake}	Lake rating curve exponent	-	e	-
n_{land}	Manning's roughness (overland flow)	$\text{s } \text{m}^{-\frac{1}{3}}$	n	0.072
n_{river}	Manning's roughness (river flow)	$\text{s } \text{m}^{-1/3}$	n	0.036
l_{river}	River length	m	dl	-
w_{river}	River width	m	width	-
h_{bankfull}	River bankfull depth	m	bankfull_depth	1.0

Figure 26 WFLOW_hydrological parameters (MODFLOW is part of this family), wflow_sbm model inputs and parameters

3. State of the Art & Market Analysis update

3.1. The State-of-the-Art in a Pre-Commercial Procurement

The EAFIP step-by-step methodology, developed in the context of the European Assistance for Innovation Procurement (EAFIP)⁶ initiative of the EC, offers a structured and consistent process to help public sector organizations plan and implement innovation procurement projects. It is designed to support public buyers through all key phases: preparation, contract award, and execution. A strong emphasis is placed on thorough preparation to ensure that procurement activities are feasible, aligned with the actual needs of the organization, and make efficient use of public funds.

The methodology is built on the PDCA cycle—Plan, Do, Check, Act. It begins by identifying and understanding the specific problems or needs within the organization, followed by planning potential solutions. This often involves creating a demand plan that outlines short- and medium-term needs. The demand plan serves two purposes: prioritizing which needs should be addressed first and informing technology suppliers about upcoming needs so they can prepare accordingly.

After defining a specific need, the next step is to assess whether innovation procurement is the appropriate approach. This involves exploring market capabilities, engaging with potential vendors, and performing a cost-benefit analysis. If no existing market solutions fully meet the need and the project is financially viable, the organization can proceed with innovation procurement.

The subsequent steps involve preparing and publishing the tender, selecting suppliers, and executing the contract(s).

The methodology outlines five key preparatory steps essential to building an effective procurement strategy. These include identifying procurement needs, conducting a State-Of-The-Art (SOTA) analysis to evaluate available market solutions and relevant Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs), validating findings through an Open Market Consultation (OMC), and conducting a business case to determine economic feasibility. The insights from these steps are crucial for shaping the tender's technical and functional requirements, as well as defining appropriate selection and award criteria.

Overall, the EAFIP methodology helps ensure that public innovation procurement is strategic, transparent, and aligned with both organizational needs and market capabilities.

⁶ <https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/strategy/support-policy-making/shaping-eu-research-and-innovation-policy/new-european-innovation-agenda/innovation-procurement/eafip>

EAFIP methodology step-by-step

Figure 27 Summary of the EAFIP step-by-step methodology

In this process, assessing the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of potential solutions derived from the State-Of-The-Art (SOTA) analysis and market consultation, is essential for shaping the procurement strategy. The TRL helps determine how mature a technology is and guides decisions on whether further development is needed before commercial deployment. The accompanying image illustrates the full innovation cycle, from early development through to product commercialization.

Figure 28 Technology Readiness Level and development maturity. Adapted from EAFIP. (2018). European Assistance for Innovation Procurement (Eafip) Module 2 Toolkit

The TRL plays a key role in determining the appropriate procurement strategy. When a solution falls within a lower TRL range (3–6), it indicates that significant R&D is still needed. In such cases, if no market-ready solutions exist to meet the identified needs, a PCP procedure may be appropriate.

Conversely, if the TRL is higher (7–9), meaning the solution is close to market readiness but not yet widely commercially available, then a PPI can be pursued using the legal procedures set by the European Public Procurement Directives.

3.2. The SOTA in the PCP WISE context

3.2.1. Task Description & Strategy

The description of this task, as provided in the PREVENT PCP Grant Agreement, is provided below in *Italic*:

This task will focus on updating the state-of-the-art (SOTA) analysis conducted under PROTECT 15 Associated with document Ref. Ares(2024)7479606 - 21/10/2024 Project: 101182917 — PCP WISE — HORIZON-CL6-2024-GOVERNANCE-01 project. After identifying the requirements specified by public procurers in T.3.1.1., a comprehensive examination will be carried out through a SOTA analysis leading to a feasibility study. This aim is to verify whether the identified requirements genuinely address an "unmet" need. The process involves scrutinising existing products, reviewing published ideas, and conducting a literature review of scientific, technical, and policy publications. The primary goal is to expand on the activities undertaken within the PROTECT project, assessing various technical solutions existing in the market. This

assessment includes gathering information, providing detailed descriptions of solutions, and evaluating their alignment with the operational requirements outlined in T.3.1.1.

Fraunhofer will support these activities by providing scientific assessment and advice. Using data driven foresight methods and desktop research based on publications and patent data, the objective is to identify which technologies, institutions and innovations could be of particular interest for the project. Therefore, Fraunhofer will perform a quantitative and qualitative analysis using various methods, e.g. Fraunhofer in-house system KATI (Knowledge Analytics for Technology and Innovation). The use of KATI and other tools regularly employed or co-developed at Fraunhofer ensures that state of the art methods are applied. In addition to the SOTA analysis, the market trends and key players (including possible competition) within the topics of interest will be identified.

As previously mentioned, the EAFIP methodology outlines five key steps in the preparation phase of an Innovation Procurement project. The second step, the State-of-the-Art (SOTA) analysis, consists of two core activities: a Prior Art Analysis and an Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) search. In the context of the PCP WISE project, these activities are carried out under Task 3.2.1. State of the Art & Market Analysis update.

To execute this task, the partners agreed to divide the activities based on the strategic approach previously applied in the PROTECT CSA project for the same task, while leveraging each partner's expertise and technical capabilities.

Accordingly, Task 3.2.1 is structured around three main activities:

- Identification of available Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) products capable of addressing the use cases developed under Task 3.1.
- Analysis of the complete set of relevant patents, standards, and standard-essential patents to gather insights on their type, scope, breadth, content, degree of innovation, and technical relevance, as well as information on the associated institutions and suppliers holding intellectual property rights (IPRs).
- Literature review conducted using the KATI (Knowledge Analytics for Technology and Innovation) system.

In addition to the State-of-the-Art (SOTA) analysis, this task will also identify market trends and key players (including potential competitors) in the relevant areas of interest.

Figure 29 Task 3.2.1 strategy

3.2.2. Allocation of Efforts

Below the allocations of efforts are outlined for each participating partner.

Task	Corvers (Task leader)	Corvers Greece	AV	Fraunhofer	Technical Experts
The analysis of the Intellectual Property Rights (using the IP Intelligent tool IPlytics) → Listing the existing patents, standards	✓	✓			
Market analysis	✓	✓	✓		
COTS mapping			✓		
literature review			✓		
Analysis of the material collected, transforming this into a list of technologies and assessment of the TRL level of these technologies (KATI, Patents, COTS)	✓		✓	✓	✓

Table 6: Task 3.2.1. Allocation of Efforts

3.2.3. Task dependencies

Task 3.2.1 serves as a preliminary and essential step aimed at updating the results of the PROTECT CSA and preparing both the Open Market Consultation (Task 3.4) and the development of the procurement strategy (Task 3.5). It builds upon the PROTECT project's previous work, specifically the state-of-the-art analysis related to the four main challenges: floods, fires, water resilience, and sustainable resilient infrastructure. These elements will be updated based on the selected use cases and the requirements defined by public procurers in Task 3.1.1, as well as insights from the end user's workshops.

3.2.4. From CSA to PCP

The update of the State-of-the-Art (SOTA) in PCP WISE builds upon an iterative process initiated during the PROTECT CSA and further advanced in the context of PCP WISE. During the CSA phase, partners developed a set of scenarios addressing key environmental and climate resilience challenges, such as floods, wildfires, water resilience, and sustainable infrastructure. These scenarios were designed to reflect the critical capability gaps and operational needs faced by public authorities.

Through a stepwise approach, an initial longlist of potential challenges was refined into four priority domains. Based on these domains and the specific needs identified by public procurers, the partners investigated technological solutions capable of addressing these issues. To support the decision-making process for innovation procurement, a comprehensive State-of-the-Art (SOTA) analysis was conducted.

The objective of this analysis was to assess the maturity level (TRL) of relevant technologies and determine the availability and suitability of existing COTS products. Technologies with lower TRLs were considered more appropriate for PCP, as they would require further research and development before being ready for deployment.

Within PCP WISE, the SOTA analysis serves several key functions:

- To determine whether the required technological solutions already exist on the market or whether additional R&D is needed to develop them.
- To inform the procurement strategy, helping to decide between a PCP, a PPI, or direct procurement of available COTS products.

In the PROTECT CSA, the SOTA process was structured around two core activities:

- Prior Art Analysis focused on identifying and evaluating existing COTS solutions.
- IPR Search examined the patent landscape, relevant standards, and academic literature tied to the technologies.

These efforts culminated in the PROTECT CSA Deliverable 3.3, a comprehensive report detailing the current state of COTS availability and the intellectual property landscape related to the technologies under review.

Key findings included:

- A macro-level analysis of patent activity by geography, organization, and technological domain.
- A compiled and annexed list of relevant documents (patents, standards, and academic literature).
- A technical review assessing the relevance and implications of identified IPR, conducted in parallel with the COTS analysis.
- A preliminary financial assessment of the solutions to support cost-benefit analysis and guide subsequent procurement decisions.

3.3. Patents & Standards Analysis Methodology

3.3.1. Rationale for an IPR Search

The Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) search carried out by Corvers and Corvers Greece produced three key outcomes:

- A broad analysis covering aspects such as patenting companies, their activities, geographic distribution, and more. Complete lists from each search are included as annexes to this report.
- A detailed compilation of relevant documents. The list of patents is provided in a spreadsheet annex, along with the full list of standards.
- A detailed list of the relevant technologies from the shortlisted patents.

Fraunhofer, together with other project partners, conducted an in-depth technical review of the IPR search results. Using their technical expertise, they identified which technologies are most relevant to the scope of the project, helping to refine and enhance the initial findings from the IPR search.

3.3.1.1. Rationale for examining intellectual property (patents)

An Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) search is a critical step in innovation procurement, combining both patent and literature reviews to identify existing protected knowledge relevant to the technology or solution being considered. Registered intellectual property refers to rights granted by official authorities and published as part of the grant process, but not all intellectual property requires registration to be effective. Patent applications can be as significant as granted patents, and intellectual property also includes academic publications, agreements, and trade secrets.

Patent searches are especially important in Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) because patents are often the most relevant form of registered intellectual property for technological

research and development. A patent legally grants its owner the exclusive right to prevent others from marketing the protected invention. Filing a patent also demonstrates a strong commitment by the inventor or organization to the development of that technology. Globally, patent laws follow the principle of “absolute novelty,” meaning that all publicly available inventions worldwide define the current state of technology, regardless of when or where they were disclosed. Because of this, it is essential to conduct patent searches using international databases rather than limiting searches to national patent offices.

To meet this requirement, the IPR search described was conducted using the IPlytics platform, which covers data from over 67 patent offices and approximately 120 million patents from 98 countries dating back to 1980.

The purpose of the IPR analysis is twofold: first, to confirm the level of advancement of the technology or R&D activities (especially for PCP projects) or the innovative solutions being procured (for PPI projects), including the potential for protecting new developments through intellectual property rights; second, to identify existing market players holding essential intellectual property rights necessary to address the identified needs, and to evaluate whether their licensing terms could introduce risks or costs that might negatively affect the business case for innovation procurement.

In summary, a thorough IPR search provides a comprehensive understanding of the technological landscape, helps verify innovation maturity, and assesses the strategic IP risks that could impact procurement decisions.

3.3.1.2. Rationale for examining standards

Standardization is a process where stakeholders reach consensus, either informally through de facto standards or formally through de jure standards to establish agreed-upon designs, performance criteria, processes, or information. Technical standardization specifically involves setting common features across technologies to ensure interoperability among devices, data formats, or software systems. Examples of such standards include popular document formats like .docx and .pdf, communication protocols such as 4G LTE and WiFi, and image compression formats like JPG and PNG.

When planning innovation projects, an initial step should include searching for relevant standards related to the intended innovation. These standards help meet user requirements, particularly by addressing interoperability challenges. In PCP or PPI, procurers can require suppliers to demonstrate compliance with applicable standards, which serves as verification of key solution qualities. Additionally, standards that define how to measure, test, and validate technologies are important throughout the R&D phases and can be applied at various stages of the procurement process.

In the context of innovation procurement, the relationship between innovations and standards can be visualized as a network where each innovation (node) is connected by lines representing the standards it uses. This network reflects a healthy market environment where

procurers have access to a wide range of solutions that are interoperable, interchangeable, and competitively priced.

Figure 30 Characteristics space for innovation with standards and standardization. Adapted from Rainville, A., 2017. Standards in green public procurement--A framework to enhance innovation. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Volume 167, pp. 1029-1037

Even when relevant standards exist, public procurers may find them lacking in openness, applicability, or completeness. This can create a need to develop new standards or testing procedures to ensure quality products and a healthy market with diverse options. Often, multiple competing or proprietary standards exist, and in cases of radical innovation like PCP, there may be no applicable standards at all.

PCP can help speed up standardization by first establishing market-driven de facto standards that can later become formal de jure standards. Suppliers might also be required to work with official standardization bodies such as ETSI, CEN, or ITU to develop formal standards. These steps help build a solid foundation (“the trunk”) for commercializing innovations.

Voluntary standards that exceed regulations can also influence new policies, especially in emerging areas. When introducing breakthrough innovations into fragmented or new markets, PCP specifications can mandate interoperability of key components and require suppliers to license intellectual property rights under Fair, Reasonable, and Non-Discriminatory (FRAND) terms, encouraging competition and market adoption.

3.3.1.3. Interpretation

This section outlines the strategic implications of the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) search results and how they may influence the direction of an innovation procurement project. Three main scenarios can arise from the IPR findings:

- Partial Solutions Exist:**
 If some companies already offer components that meet part of the user requirements (e.g., low-power modules for interoperable systems), then the PCP should target the remaining unmet needs. In some cases, integrating an existing proprietary component could be considered, depending on cost implications.
- Solutions Cover Specific Needs Separately:**
 When different patents address individual user needs, the procurement process might focus on integrating or adapting these components. If significant development work is needed, this may warrant a PCP. If only minor modifications are required, a PPI could be more appropriate.
- Complete Solutions Are Already Available:**
 If full solutions exist that meet the identified needs, an innovation procurement may not be necessary. Instead, standard COTS procurement can be pursued. However, if a PCP is contractually required, the project scope may need to shift to a different user need that lacks a solution.

In addition to determining the procurement path, identifying relevant IPRs may indicate the user need lacks novelty, thereby disqualifying it from PCP or PPI funding. Moreover, existing patents might act as "novelty-destroying" elements, complicating the path for new IPR registrations or market commercialization.

To mitigate IPR risks:

- Tender requirements and R&D solutions should be designed to avoid infringing on existing patents.
- Early licensing negotiations with patent holders may secure the necessary rights to commercialize solutions.

If neither approach is viable and IPR obstacles are significant, it may be advisable to abandon or rethink the project due to the high risk.

Extent to Which User Needs Are Met	Each need is met...		Some needs are covered	No needs are covered
	By a single patent	By multiple patents		
Number of patents meeting the needs	By a single patent	By multiple patents	By some patents	No relevant patents exist

Recommended action	Procure a market-ready (COTS) solution if the patent is embedded in it	Launch a PPI to integrate patents into a unified solution with necessary design modifications	Start a PCP at higher TRLs to develop a complete solution	Initiate a full PCP starting at low TRLs (e.g., TRL 3–4); indicates a novel need
IPR Risk Level	Low – Buy from a single supplier	High – Multiple patent holders, complex integration, potential IPR saturation	Moderate – Existing IPR must be integrated or designed around	Low – No existing IPR; innovation-friendly "white space"

Table 7: Summary of the relevance of IPR Search findings to an innovation procurement project

3.3.2. Search Platform & Coverage

Corvers and Corvers Greece carried out the patent search using IPlytics, an advanced IP and market analytics platform. Developed by a company that partners with four universities globally, IPlytics integrates academic research into its big data tools for enhanced analysis and visualization.

The platform relies solely on publicly available data sources, maintaining transparency and allowing users to trace information back to its original documents. Its databases are regularly updated for accuracy and stored within IPlytics' own secure system. All searches are performed within IPlytics' internal database, without accessing external third-party sources.

3.3.2.1. Security

The IPlytics Platform is built using industry-standard security protocols and follows strict policies to protect user search queries and client data. As a German-based company acquired by Lexisnexis, IPlytics is subject to some of the world's most stringent data protection and privacy laws. Compliance with these national legal requirements ensures a high level of data security and confidentiality.

3.3.2.2. Patents

IPlytics obtains patent documents directly from individual patent offices, allowing for the immediate inclusion of newly published patents from around the world. Some data sources,

like the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO, WO) and the European Patent Office (EPO, EP), offer details on filings across multiple countries. As a result, the IPlytics Platform provides comprehensive global coverage of patent documents.

- Covers more than 67 patent offices worldwide
- Contains approximately 120 million patent documents
- Includes over 24 million patent families
- Spans 98 countries
- Covers the period from 1980 to the present

Detailed full-text information on:

- Full text: Title, abstract, description, claims
- Patent application number and date
- Patent publication number and date
- Patent priority number and date
- INPADOC family information
- INPADOC legal status information (active, lapsed, revoked, expired)
- Patent office / document type
- Reassignment information
- IPC and CPC classifications and description
- Industry Field Cluster
- Applicant / Assignee information
- Inventor information
- Patent citation information
- US litigation

3.3.2.3 Standards

IPlytics collects standards documents directly from individual standard-setting organizations, enabling the immediate inclusion of newly published standards from around the world. As a result, the IPlytics Platform offers comprehensive global coverage of standards documents.

- Coverage of 96 standard-setting organizations
- Approximately 4 million standards and contribution documents
- Published by more than 700 working groups and standards committees
- From 1990 to the present day

IPlytics ensures comprehensive data in standards documents, covering both textual and bibliographic details. It offers in-depth information on:

- Title, Abstract, Keywords
- Standard document number

- Standard issuing date
- Standard ICS classification
- Standard version history
- Document status (active, withdrawn)
- Working Group / Committee
- Referencing Standards Documents
- Referencing Patents Documents
- Declared Standard Essential Patents

3.3.3. Search Methodology

Like other online search platforms, IPlytics requires users to input keywords to retrieve targeted results. Consequently, the first step in conducting an IPR search is to define and select the most relevant keywords to use in the platform's search engine.

The following steps summarize the search methodology process.

Step 1: The results of PROTECT CSA were thoroughly studied and analysed.

Step 2: Task 3.1 selected five representative groups based on criteria defined by the layered approach and relevance to climate impact. Using these clusters, the initial list of keywords was compiled. Each end user, based on their respective scoping documents, also had their own set of keywords. These keyword lists were categorized into three groups: sector, hazard type, and use case-specific keywords.

Step 3: The compiled keywords were sent to each cluster for validation. Once validated, these keywords were used to initiate the first round of searches, which served as input for the PIN.

Step 4: Engagement with project partners (AV and Fraunhofer) took place to further discuss the keywords and the related technologies in more detail.

Step 5: As the use cases evolved and user stories were developed, a unified list of keywords was created for each cluster.

Step 6: Final IPR searches were conducted using the updated keyword lists for each cluster. These searches also considered results from the initial search phase in Step 2.

Step 7: The keyword lists were refined throughout the search process to remove terms that were too specific and might exclude relevant results. The refinement also aimed to eliminate outliers' entries that were irrelevant and could increase review workload or distort search analytics.

Despite this effort, due to the non-technical nature of the refinement process, some irrelevant patents may still remain in the final results.

Please note the following considerations:

- Non-granted patents (i.e., pending patents) were included. These patents, although awaiting formal approval, still provide insight into ongoing research and development efforts and offer a certain degree of legal protection.
- Lapsed patents were also included. These may lapse due to unpaid fees, outdated technology, or being superseded. However, they still offer value as indicators of innovation in a particular timeframe or field.
- Multiple jurisdiction filings may inflate the patent count, as the same patent can be filed in different countries for broader protection.
- Patents were grouped by patent family, which consists of applications covering the same or similar technical content. Only patent family data was extracted to simplify subsequent technical analysis.

Step 8: The lists of patents and standards were compiled in separate spreadsheets and attached as annexes to this report. The search was intentionally limited to the 2020–2025 timeframe to ensure the focus remained on up-to-date technologies and research outputs.

Step 9: After generating the final list of patents for each cluster, the most relevant ones for PCP WISE were identified. These were further categorized by:

- Relevance (highly relevant or moderately relevant)
- Geographic origin (Europe vs. non-Europe)

This distinction enables the project to assess the current State-of-the-Art (SOTA) in Europe while also capturing global developments.

Step 10: Key technologies related to PCP WISE were extracted from the shortlisted patents (as listed in the annexes), again split into European and non-European categories.

Step 11: An in-depth technical review of these technologies was performed by Fraunhofer and external partners. Using their domain expertise, they:

- Estimated the TRL of each technology.
- Assisted in refining IPR-related conclusions for each.

Step 12: A final list of technologies with their corresponding TRL levels was compiled, along with a summarizing matrix.

It is important to highlight that the IPR analysis aimed to assess the overall maturity of the technology landscape. As a result, some of the identified patents may not directly pertain to the core focus areas but instead relate to comparable technologies applied in other sectors particularly in civilian contexts. This broader perspective enables the IPlytics analysis to capture a more comprehensive view of technological innovation and maturity.

This wide-ranging approach is especially useful for evaluating early-stage or developing technologies. By examining their use across multiple sectors, we gain valuable insights into their potential for adaptation and commercialization within the WISE framework. For instance, radio frequency technologies developed by telecommunications companies may also hold relevance in different domains.

The technical partners involved in the analysis can navigate the annexed spreadsheets to pinpoint patents of interest. While the initial search strategy deliberately covered a broad range of domains to ensure inclusivity, it was later refined to limit the impact of unrelated keyword matches and sharpen the focus of the analysis.

3.3.4. Common Keywords for The IPR & Standard Searches

In this section, you can see the common keywords for each group. These keywords were the basis of our IPR search. The consolidated list was developed through a structured and collaborative process. Initially, keywords were extracted from the use cases and associated cluster documents for each use case. These preliminary keyword lists were then shared with the respective groups for review and verification. Following this, each group conducted internal consultations to refine and agree on a final common list of keywords. To support this effort, ad hoc one-on-one calls were held as needed to provide clarification and assist with the compilation process. This approach ensured that the final keyword lists were both accurate and representative of all relevant stakeholders.

G1 Common keywords	
Regular management keywords	
Sector	City
Keyword rank	
Kw 1	Groundwater levels
Kw 2	Infrastructure risks
Kw 3	Building foundations risks
Kw 4	Neighbourhoods/green
Kw 5	Heat island
Kw 6	Green spaces
Kw 7	Ground instability/subsidence
Kw 8	Soil moisture
Kw 9	Water management
Kw 10	Enviromental observation
Kw 11	Data science
Kw 12	Urban
Kw 13	Satellite data

Table 8. Common keywords Group 1

Keyword rank	UFOC2_3	UFOC4	USOC3	RSOC1 (migrate to G2)	Summary	G2 common keywords
Kw 1	Water management	Flooding	Groundwater levels	Floods	Water management, flooding, groundwater levels, floods	Water abundance
Kw 2	Floods	Climate change	Rainfall	Crisis management	Floods, climate change, rainfall, crisis management	Floods
Kw 3	Fire	Stormwater management	Climate change	Agricultural	Fire, stormwater management, climate change, agricultural	Fire
Kw 4	Climate change	Infrastructure	Storms	Soil saturation	Climate change, infrastructure, storms, soil saturation	Climate change
Kw 5	Disaster management	Soil moisture	Flooding	Disaster management	Disaster management, soil moisture, flooding	Disaster management
Kw 6	Prediction	Urban planning	Infrastructure	Coordination	Prediction, urban planning, infrastructure, coordination	Prediction
Kw 7	Analysis	Mapping	Water supply	Planning	Analysis, Mapping, water supply, planning	Soil moisture
Kw 8	Prevention	Groundwater	Sea levels	Maps	Prevention, groundwater, sea levels, maps	Prevention

Keyword rank	UFOC2_3	UFOC4	USOC3	RSOC1 (migrate to G2)	Summary	G2 common keywords
Kw 9	Data collection	Risk management	Soil	Water levels	Data collection, risk management, soil, water levels	Data collection
Kw 10	Analytics	Real-time	Risk areas	Prediction	Analytics, real-time, risk areas, prediction	Analytics
Kw 11	Visualisation	Maintenance	Wastewater	Water management	Visualisation, maintenance, wastewater, water management	Visualisation
Kw 12	Water management	Water management	Water management	Data	Water management, data	Water / Risk management
Kw 13	Environmental observation	Environmental observation	Environmental observation	Rural	Environmental observation, rural	Environmental observation
Kw 14	Data science	Data science	Data science	Satellite data	Data science, satellite data	Data science
Kw 15	Urban	Urban	Urban		Urban	Urban
Kw 16	Satellite data	Satellite data	Satellite data		Satellite data	Satellite data

Table 9. Common keywords Group 2

Keyword rank	G3 common keywords
Kw1	Soil-Water-Vegetation System
Kw2	Drought Risk Management
Kw3	Wildfire Risk Mapping
Kw4	Soil Moisture Analysis
Kw5	Vegetation & Biomass Monitoring
Kw6	Water Management
Kw7	Early Warning Systems
Kw8	Rural Climate Resilience

Kw9	Climate Change Adaptation
Kw10	Groundwater Monitoring
Kw11	Wildfire Fuel Monitoring
Kw12	Emergency & Civil Protection
Kw13	Environmental Observation
Kw14	Data Integration & Visualization
Kw15	Satellite Data & Intelligence

Table 10. Common keywords Group 3

Categories	RSOC2_3	RFOC5
Regular management keywords		
Sector	Agriculture	Urban governance
	Forestry	Regional administration
		National Administration
		Civil protection
		Agriculture
		Environmental management
Crisis management keywords		
Sector	Agriculture	Civil protection
	Water management	
	Wildfires	
Hazard type	Drought	Floods
Keyword rank/Use case		
Kw 1	Drought	Flood
Kw 2	Agriculture protection	Flood prevention
Kw 3	Soil moisture	
Kw 4	Crop evapotranspiration	River basin streambed changes
Kw 5	Water availability	Risks
Kw 6	Water management	Digital management tool
Kw 7	Irrigation efficiency	Water management
Kw 8	Forestry monitoring	Agriculture
Kw 9	Wildfire risk maps	Irrigation efficiency
Kw 10	Climate resilience planning	
Kw 11	Long – term trends	
Kw 12	Reducing vulnerabilities	
Kw 13	Remote sensing	
Kw 14	Mediterranean basis	

Table 11. Common keywords Group 4

Categories	G5 common keywords
Sector Kw	Water management in rural areas

Keyword rank / Use Case	
Kw 1	Ground water and surface water levels
Kw 2	Soil moisture
Kw 3	Flooding
Kw 4	Drought
Kw 5	Peatlands
Kw 6	Subsidence
Kw 7	Fire
Kw 8	Risk/Hazard maps
Kw 9	Infrastructure risks
Kw 10	Planning/decision making
Kw 11	Historical data
Kw 12	Prediction models/early warning
Kw 13	Environmental observation
Kw 14	Satellite data
Kw 15	Climate adaption

Table 12. Common keywords Group 5

3.4. IPR & Standards Search Results

This section outlines the findings related to each of the five challenges addressed by the PCP WISE project, with a particular emphasis on patent analysis. A separate section (3.4.2) is dedicated to the analysis of standards. For each challenge, key data such as the total number of patents, the top 10 patent applicants, and their geographical distribution are presented, along with additional relevant analytics among others.

The most significant patent documents were selected based on their level of technical relevance, using key indicators provided by the IPlytics platform. These indicators include:

- Technical Relevance (measured by the number of forward citations),
- Radicalness (based on backward citations),
- Legal Relevance (determined by the jurisdictions in which the patents are protected),
- and the Market Coverage indicator.

Together, these metrics offer a comprehensive view of each patent's importance and potential impact within its respective challenge area.

3.4.1. Patents

The patent analysis conducted for the 5 groups plays a vital role in understanding the current technological landscape. It enables the monitoring of emerging innovations, assesses how ready these technologies are for practical use, identifies existing gaps in available solutions, and uncovers potential for future collaboration and commercialization.

This in-depth analysis serves as a strategic tool for guiding research efforts, shaping policy, and informing planning decisions. By examining the spectrum of patented technologies, public sector actors seeking to procure advanced Climate Services gain valuable insights into the state-of-the-art relevant to their specific challenges. This understanding allows them to assess proposed or existing solutions with greater precision, ensuring that the services align with both the latest technological developments and their operational needs. Ultimately, such insight supports the adoption of high-impact, forward-looking solutions aimed at boosting resilience and sustainability in the face of climate-related threats.

3.4.1.1. Group 1 Urban Drought (NW-EU)

Patents

The analysis revealed research on the following aspects, among others:

- Thermal & vegetation indices from satellite imagery
- Radio frequency (RF) & electromagnetic scanning
- SAR & flood mapping integration
- Machine learning for soil moisture estimation
- RF & optical soil composition analysis
- Evapotranspiration & moisture modeling
- Environmental event detection & notification
- Satellite-sensor disaster data fusion
- Multispectral disaster severity estimation
- Gravity satellite for water storage & ET estimation

Keywords used: city, groundwater, satellite, urban, infrastructure, heat island, green spaces, soil moisture, water management, earth observation, subsidence, neighbourhood, hydrology.

To conduct our patent research, we started with the main keywords from the consolidated list provided by the end users: “city,” “groundwater,” “urban,” and “infrastructure.” These were first paired with related keywords such as “satellite,” “heat island,” and “water management,” and then combined with additional terms like “soil moisture,” “hydrology,” and “green spaces” to further broaden the research. Using different combinations of these keywords (see table below), we identified more than 1,400 patents. Some of these patents are duplicates across the combinations. For the purposes of this report, we focused on the main keywords and identified over 1,450 patents related to Group 1. This number reflects a steady flow of patent applications from 2021 onward, across various fields including civil engineering.

Count	Full Query	Number of Results
1	(all:(city)) AND (all:(groundwater)) AND (all:(infrastructure)) AND (publication_date:(["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO *]))	1450
2	(all:(city)) AND (all:(groundwater)) AND (all:(satellite)) AND (all:(urban)) AND (publication_date:(["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO "2025-03-26T23:59:59Z"]))	400
3	(all:(infrastructure)) AND (all:(groundwater)) AND (all:(satellite)) AND (all:(urban)) AND (publication_date:(["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO "2025-03-26T23:59:59Z"]))	238
4	(all:(soil moisture)) AND (all:(water management)) AND (abstract_english_search:(satellite)) AND (all:(earth observation)) AND (publication_date:(["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO "2025-03-26T23:59:59Z"]))	192
5	(all:(soil moisture)) AND (all:(infrastructure)) AND (abstract_english_search:(satellite)) AND (publication_date:(["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO "2025-03-26T23:59:59Z"]))	127

Table 13: Example of search queries Group 1.

A closer examination of the patent research results shows that these patents apply to several industry domains and fields, such as technologies for adaptation to climate change and the production, distribution, and transport of energy. The majority, however, are related to civil engineering and climate change adaptation technologies.

Current Assignee	Patent Applications Count	Patent Families Count	Share	Market Coverage (MC)	Technical Relevance (TR)
Carbon Technology Holdings	48	5	0.033 103	8.429178	1.637832
SNIPR Biome	46	1	0.031 724	9.582115	3.189696
KITECH	41	7	0.028 276	0.919774	4.877829
Rondo Energy	29	1	0.02	19.19926	1.135587
FedEx	24	3	0.016 552	10.67548	3.63469
Crystal Lagoons (Curaçao)	23	1	0.015 862	17.16031	1.143617

Current Assignee	Patent Applications Count	Patent Families Count	Share	Market Coverage (MC)	Technical Relevance (TR)
PowerChina	18	18	0.012 414	0.685698	1.276503
China Communications Construction Group	17	16	0.011 724	0.86808	1.599747
China Railway Construction	17	17	0.011 724	0.615468	1.239342
Ministry of Water Resources of PRC	16	15	0.011 034	0.735615	1.525252

Table 14: Top 10 patent Group 1

The table above also shows that patent applicants in this field are quite dispersed. The leading applicant holds about three percent of the total patents, which suggests there is no clear market leader in this domain. This indicates that there may still be significant room for innovation.

This observation is further supported by the following figures, which reveal the total number of patents and industry trends over the selected timeframe. The number of patent filings in this field has steadily increased over the past four years. However, less than half of the filed patents have actually been granted. We also observe a notable rise in patent activity in the last full year, following a period of stagnation after 2022. It remains unclear whether this upward trend will continue into 2025. If it does, this would reinforce the earlier conclusion that the technology is not yet fully mature and that opportunities for innovation remain.

Figure 31: Trendline of Patents overtime Group 1 (2020-2025).

Figure 32. Industry trend Group 1 (2020-2025).

Analyzing the geographical distribution of patents in this area provides additional insights. China leads the world in innovation by a wide margin, followed by the United States, the Republic of Korea, and Japan, with India rounding out the top five. It is important to highlight that the European Union is lagging behind, which supports the previous argument that there is still considerable room for innovation in the region.

Figure 33. Patenting geography group 1 (2020-2025).

3.4.1.2. Group 2 Urban Flood (N-Central EU)

Patents

The analysis revealed research on the following aspects, among others:

- Hydrological and hydraulic modelling
- Remote sensing & satellite data processing
- Machine learning & AI models
- Flood monitoring, early warning & crisis management
- Climate data integration & analysis
- Water quality, soil moisture & groundwater monitoring
- Urban & ecological water management
- Data fusion, integration & visualization
- Advanced statistical & computational methods
- Soil and terrain analysis
- Sensor networks & IoT infrastructure
- Flood and drought risk indices

- Crop and agricultural monitoring
- Disaster response & emergency management
- Ecological & environmental assessment
- Urban climate resilience & thermal regulation

Keywords used: water abundance, floods, climate change, satellite, earth observation, water, fire, prediction, prevention, soil moisture, urban, disaster management, flood, hydrology, meteorology, water management.

To conduct our patent research, we began with the primary keywords from the consolidated list provided by end users: “water abundance,” “floods,” “fire,” and “climate change.” These were initially paired with related terms such as “satellite,” “urban,” and “prevention,” and then further combined with additional keywords like “soil moisture,” “hydrology,” and “meteorology” to expand the scope of the research. By using various combinations of these keywords (see table below), we identified over 1,350 patents, some of which were duplicates across the different combinations. For the purpose of this report, we focused on the main keywords and identified more than 780 patents related to Group 2. This total reflects a gradual decline in patent applications since the peak in 2021, spanning multiple fields including technologies for adaptation to climate change.

Count	Full Query	Number of Results
1	(all:(Water abundance)) AND (all:(flood)) AND (all:(climate change)) AND (publication_date:(["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO *]))	782
2	(all:(Water abundance)) AND (all:(urban)) AND (all:(hydrology)) AND (publication_date:(["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO "2025-04-11T23:59:59Z"]))	105
3	(all:(Water)) AND (abstract_english_search:(fire)) AND (all:(Satellite)) AND (all:(climate change)) AND (all:(Soil moisture)) AND (publication_date:(["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO *]))	63
4	(all:(Water abundance)) AND (all:(Floods)) AND (all:(Climate change)) AND (all:(Satellite)) AND (publication_date:(["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO *]))	44
5	(all:(Water abundance)) AND (abstract_english_search:(fire)) AND (all:(Satellite)) AND (all:(climate change)) AND (publication_date:(["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO *]))	14

Table 15: Example of search queries Group 2

A closer analysis of the patent research results reveals that these patents span multiple industry domains and fields, including the analysis of biological materials and computer

technology. However, as anticipated, the majority are focused on technologies related to climate change adaptation.

Current Assignee	Patent Applications Count	Patent Families Count	Share	Market Coverage (MC)	Technical Relevance (TR)
Evogene	174	26	0.222506	2.916288	0.141575
Lone Gull	25	2	0.031969	8.967536	4.660767
LFP	20	2	0.025575	6.9982	0.966109
Ministry of Water Resources of PRC	19	19	0.024297	0.391343	3.694429
Chinese Academy of Sciences	14	13	0.017903	0.462649	2.429579
Indigo Agriculture	12	3	0.015345	12.86542	3.836951
PI Industries	12	4	0.015345	3.700715	0.129221
Locus Oil Lcc	11	4	0.014066	3.241565	2.438415
HYDROGREEN INC	10	1	0.012788	4.980923	0.889579
PROJECT VESTA	10	1	0.012788	6.431845	1.165306

Table 16: Top 10 patent Group 2

The table above also indicates that while there is a clear market leader holding 23% of the patents in this field, the overall technical relevance of these patents is quite low. This suggests that despite one dominant player in the patent landscape, there remains substantial room for innovation, as existing patents may not fully address the most critical or advanced technical challenges. In other words, the technology space appears underdeveloped, offering opportunities for new entrants or current players to innovate and advance the field.

This conclusion is further supported by the following data, which highlights industry trends and patent activity over the selected timeframe. Patent filings in this area have slightly declined over the past four years. However, less than half of the filed patents have been granted, indicating possible issues with the quality or novelty of applications. Additionally, we observe a modest increase in patent activity in the last full year after a consecutive decline following 2021. It remains uncertain whether this upward trend will persist into 2025.

These patterns may reflect a slowing or maturation of the field, with fewer new technologies being formally protected. Yet, the low patent grant rate points to continued opportunities for more impactful and innovative developments. The recent uptick in patent filings could signal renewed interest or emerging technologies, though the uncertainty surrounding this trend warrants cautious optimism.

Figure 34 Trendline of Patents overtime Group 2 (2020-2025).

Figure 35 Industry trend Group 2 (2020-2025).

Analysing the geographical distribution of patents in this field offers further insights. The USA leads global innovation by a significant margin, followed by China, Australia, and Brazil, with Canada completing the top five. It is important to note that the European Union is trailing behind, reinforcing the earlier point that there remains substantial room for innovation within the region.

Figure 36 Patenting geography group 2 (2020-2025).

4.4.1.3. Group 3 Rural Drought (NW-Central EU)

Patents

The analysis revealed research on the following aspects, among others:

- Climate and socio-economic impact integration
- Evapotranspiration and water balance modelling
- Drought index and monitoring models
- Hydrological and watershed modelling
- Remote sensing and satellite-based analysis
- Machine learning and AI for drought modelling
- Drought risk, early warning, and decision support systems
- Wildfire risk prediction and mitigation
- Climate and socio-economic impact integration

Keywords used: soil-water-vegetation, drought, risk management, soil moisture, vegetation, water management, rural, climate change, groundwater, satellite, hydrology, meteorology, wildfire, risk mapping.

To carry out our patent research, we started with the primary keywords from the consolidated list provided by end users: “soil-water-vegetation,” “drought,” “risk management,” and “soil moisture.” These were initially paired with related terms such as “vegetation,” “water management,” and “rural,” and then further combined with additional keywords like “groundwater,” “hydrology,” and “mapping” to broaden the research scope. Using various combinations of these keywords (see table below), we identified over 1,400 patents, some of which were duplicates across different combinations. For this report, we concentrated on the main keywords and found more than 1,200 patents related to Group 3. This total reflects a gradual increase in patent applications starting from 2020, with a notable surge between 2022 and 2024, driven largely by a steady rise in patents within fields such as IT methods for management.

Count	Full Query	Number of Results
1	(all:(Soil\ -Water\ -Vegetation)) AND (all:(Drought Risk management)) AND (all:(soil moisture)) AND (publication_date:(["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO *]))	1225
2	(abstract_english_search:(Soil\ -Water\ -Vegetation)) AND (abstract_english_search:(Drought)) AND (abstract_english_search:(Vegetation)) AND (publication_date:(["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO "2025-04-11T23:59:59Z"]))	143
3	abstract_english_search:(Soil\ -Water\ -Vegetation)) AND (all:(Drought)) AND (all:(satellite)) AND (publication_date:(["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO "2025-04-11T23:59:59Z"]))	52
4	(all:(Soil-Water-Vegetation)) AND (abstract_english_search:(Wildfire)) AND (publication_date:(["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO "2025-04-11T23:59:59Z"]))	27
5	(all:(hydrology)) AND (all:(Wildfire)) AND (all:(Risk Mapping)) AND (publication_date:(["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO "2025-04-11T23:59:59Z"]))	27

Table 17: Example of search queries Group 3.

A closer analysis of the patent research results shows that these patents cover multiple industry domains and fields, including biological material analysis and technologies focused on climate change adaptation.

Current Assignee	Patent Applications Count	Patent Families Count	Share	Market Coverage (MC)	Technical Relevance (TR)
FMC Corporation	114	22	0.093061	1.222146	0.826497
Bayer	104	28	0.084898	6.272426	0.496203
Pivot Bio	50	7	0.040816	2.930019	2.8342
Indigo Agriculture	41	6	0.033469	11.27231	3.521791
PI Industries	40	10	0.032653	0.837572	0.146552
BASF	36	14	0.029388	2.254165	0.790673
Chinese Academy of Sciences	20	19	0.016327	0.686019	1.490671
Ministry of Water Resources of PRC	19	18	0.01551	0.337806	3.49336
Elemental Enzymes	15	1	0.012245	2.166663	0.653717
Deere & Co	14	3	0.011429	17.39187	2.662356

Table 18: Top 10 patent group 3.

The table above indicates that there is no clear market leader, and the top patent applicants demonstrate very low technical relevance. This suggests that there is substantial room for innovation in the market. The lack of a dominant player points to a competitive and open field, where no single company controls the landscape. Furthermore, the low technical relevance of leading applicants implies that existing patents may not fully tackle the most critical or advanced technological challenges. Together, these factors highlight opportunities for both new entrants and established players to introduce more impactful and novel innovations.

This conclusion is reinforced by the following data, which outlines patent activity and industry trends over the selected timeframe. Patent filings in this area have steadily increased over the past five years, indicating ongoing interest but possibly not focused on the most essential innovations. This gap presents a valuable opportunity for innovators to make significant breakthroughs. In essence, the data supports the view that considerable potential exists for advancements, enabling new or current players to address unmet technical needs and position themselves as market leaders.

Figure 37 Trendline of Patents overtime group 3 (2020-2025).

Figure 38 Industry trend group 3 (2020-2025).

Analyzing the geographical distribution of patents in this field provides additional insights. China leads global innovation by a wide margin, followed by the USA, Australia, and Korea,

with Brazil rounding out the top five. Notably, the European Union is lagging behind, which further supports the earlier observation that there is considerable potential for innovation in the region.

Figure 39 Patenting geography group 3 (2020-2025).

3.4.1.4. Group 4 Rural Drought & Flooding

Patents

The analysis revealed research on the following aspects, among others:

- Soil sensing and diagnostics
- Water retention and soil-water interaction systems
- Weather and climate data integration
- Machine learning and AI for prediction
- Remote sensing and satellite-based monitoring
- Flood and water management infrastructure
- Hydrological modelling and water systems analysis
- Vegetation and land use monitoring
- Risk mapping and decision support systems

Keywords used: Drought, agricultural, soil moisture, crop, water availability, irrigation, remote sensing, satellite, hydrology, meteorology, civil engineering, forestry monitoring, climate resilience, risk map, flood, mitigation, prevention, river basin, agriculture.

To conduct our patent research, we began with a set of primary keywords derived from the consolidated list provided by end users: “floods,” “drought,” “agricultural,” and “crop.” These core terms were initially paired with related concepts such as “water availability,” “mitigation,” and “hydrology,” and later expanded with additional keywords like “climate resilience,” “civil engineering,” and “river basin” to widen the scope of the search. By applying various combinations of these terms (see table below), we identified over 1700 patents, though some were duplicates appearing across multiple queries. For the purposes of this report, we focused on the most relevant combinations and identified more than 1600 unique patents associated with Group 4. This dataset reflects a consistent level of patent activity since 2020, particularly in areas addressing climate change adaptation technologies.

Count	Full Query	Number of Results
1	(all:(drought)) AND (abstract_english_search:(agricultural)) AND (all:(Soil moisture)) AND (all:(crop)) AND (all:(Water availability)) AND (publication_date:["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO *])	589
2	(all:(flood)) AND (all:(mitigation)) AND (all:(prevention)) AND (all:(River basin)) AND (publication_date:["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO *])	200
3	(all:(drought)) AND (all:(agricultural)) AND (all:(Soil moisture)) AND (abstract_english_search:(hydrology)) AND (publication_date:["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO *])	22
4	(all:(drought)) AND (all:(agricultural)) AND (all:(Soil moisture)) AND (abstract_english_search:(Climate resilience)) AND (publication_date:["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO *])	10
5	(all:(flood)) AND (all:(mitigation)) AND (all:(prevention)) AND (abstract_english_search:(hydrology)) AND (publication_date:["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO *])	7

Table 19: Example of search queries Group 4

A closer analysis of the patent research results shows that the identified patents span multiple industry domains and fields, including basic material chemistry and technologies aimed at climate change adaptation.

Current Assignee	Patent Applications Count	Patent Families Count	Share	Market Coverage (MC)	Technical Relevance (TR)
Evogene	158	26	0.089114	2.677192	0.241199
Bayer	96	54	0.054146	1.500441	1.184796
FMC Corporation	84	25	0.047377	1.71886	0.538106
Locus Oil Lcc	81	20	0.045685	1.886867	2.466714
PI Industries	75	19	0.042301	0.899198	0.255481
Elemental Enzymes	71	7	0.040045	4.680385	0.893739
Deere & Co	35	4	0.019741	17.59686	1.938293
Chinese Academy of Sciences	34	31	0.019177	0.797687	3.471271
American Vanguard	29	5	0.016356	1.930708	0.074185
Ginkgo BioWorks	28	5	0.015792	0.960921	0.870351

Table 20: Top 10 patent group 4

The table above shows that there is no clear market leader, indicating that the technological landscape remains fragmented and competitive. This absence of a dominant player suggests that the field is still open, offering substantial room for innovation. Both new entrants and established players have the opportunity to introduce novel and high-impact solutions without the constraint of entrenched incumbents setting the direction.

Further insights emerge when we consider the accompanying data on patent activity and industry trends. Patent filings in this area have remained relatively flat or show a slight decline over the selected timeframe. While this could suggest a plateau in innovation or reduced investment, it also reinforces the earlier point: the combination of low patent growth and a lack of market consolidation may reflect a field that is underdeveloped rather than saturated.

In such contexts, innovation opportunities often lie in untapped or underserved niches. This opens the door for disruptive technologies, interdisciplinary applications, or solutions that address long-standing technical challenges that current players have not prioritized. In essence, the conditions are ripe for a strategic breakthrough to redefine the market and establish leadership.

Figure 40 Trendline of Patents overtime group 4 (2020-2025).

Figure 41 Industry trend group 4 (2020-2025).

Analyzing the geographical distribution of patents in this field provides additional insights. China leads global innovation by a wide margin, followed by the USA, Australia, and Brazil, with Canada rounding out the top five. Notably, the European Union is lagging behind, which further supports the earlier observation that there is considerable potential for innovation in the region.

Figure 42 Patenting geography group 4 (2020-2025)

3.4.1.5. Group 5 Rural Drought & Flooding (N-EU)

Patents

The analysis revealed research on the following aspects, among others:

- Water storage and drainage systems
- Water level management systems
- Pumped storage and energy optimization
- Meteorological data and predictive analytics
- Plant health monitoring systems
- Hybrid soil moisture estimation
- Multi-source soil moisture data fusion
- Real-time environmental monitoring and early warning
- AI-driven root zone and irrigation optimization

Keywords used: Water level, flooding, drought, soil moisture, peatland, wetland, hydrology, meteorology, subsidence, satellite, earth observation, map, historical data, prediction model, climate adaptation, groundwater level, surface water level, and flood.

To conduct our patent research, we began with a set of primary keywords derived from the consolidated list provided by end users: “water levels,” “drought,” “floods,” and “soil moisture.” These core terms were initially paired with related concepts such as “peatland,” “subsidence,” and “satellite,” and later expanded with additional keywords like “infrastructure,” “prediction models,” and “climate adaptation” to widen the scope of the search. By applying various combinations of these terms (see table below), we identified over 1350 patents, though some were duplicates appearing across multiple queries. For the purposes of this report, we focused on the most relevant combinations and identified more than 1000 unique patents associated with Group 5. This dataset reflects a slightly declining patent activity since 2020, particularly in areas addressing climate change adaptation technologies.

Count	Full Query	Number of Results
1	(abstract_english_search:(water level)) AND (all:(Flooding)) AND (all:(Drought)) AND (publication_date:(["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO *]))	268
2	(abstract_english_search:(water level)) AND (all:(Subsidence)) AND (all:(soil moisture)) AND (publication_date:(["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO *]))	116
3	(abstract_english_search:(groundwater level)) AND (abstract_english_search:(soil moisture)) AND (publication_date:(["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO *]))	57
4	abstract_english_search:(water level) AND (abstract_english_search:(Historical data)) AND (all:(soil moisture)) AND (publication_date:(["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO *]))	50
5	(abstract_english_search:(water level)) AND (all:(hydrology)) AND (all:(Subsidence)) AND (publication_date:(["2020-01-01T00:00:00Z" TO *]))	45

Table 21: Example of search queries Group 5

A closer analysis of the patent research results shows that the identified patents span multiple industry domains and fields, including organic fine chemistry and technologies aimed at climate change adaptation.

Current Assignee	Patent Applications Count	Patent Families Count	Share	Market Coverage (MC)	Technical Relevance (TR)
Evogene	158	26	0.158317	2.677192	0.241199
FMC Corporation	80	25	0.08016	1.71575	0.563763

Current Assignee	Patent Applications Count	Patent Families Count	Share	Market Coverage (MC)	Technical Relevance (TR)
Locus Oil Lcc	67	16	0.067134	2.004447	2.825414
Elemental Enzymes	60	4	0.06012	5.339744	0.942344
Deere & Co	32	2	0.032064	19.49338	2.113076
Bayer	31	20	0.031062	1.813793	0.964254
American Vanguard	25	5	0.02505	1.938559	0.077717
PI Industries	19	11	0.019038	0.796467	0.077554
Louisiana State University	15	11	0.01503	0.95162	0.331697
Indigo Agriculture	14	6	0.014028	11.46985	4.343988

Table 22: Top 10 patent group 5

The table above reveals a clear market leader; however, this dominance is not supported by high technical relevance. This indicates that the leader's position may stem more from market dynamics, such as early entry, brand recognition, or distribution advantages, than from technological superiority. As a result, while the market appears consolidated, the underlying innovation landscape remains relatively weak, leaving space for more technically advanced solutions to emerge and challenge the status quo.

This dynamic is further underscored by the declining patent activity in the field. A drop in new filings may signal waning innovation efforts or reduced R&D investment, potentially due to complacency from the incumbent or a lack of competitive pressure. However, this also highlights a strategic opening: the combination of low technical relevance from the current leader and a slowdown in patent activity suggests that the field is far from saturated. New entrants with disruptive technologies or interdisciplinary approaches could redefine the competitive landscape and seize leadership through genuine innovation.

Figure 43 Trendline of Patents overtime group 5 (2020-2025).

Figure 44 Industry trend group 5 (2020-2025).

Analyzing the geographical distribution of patents in this field provides additional insights. USA leads global innovation by a wide margin, followed by the China, Australia, and Brazil, with Canada rounding out the top five. Notably, the European Union is lagging behind, which further supports the earlier observation that there is considerable potential for innovation in the region.

Figure 45 Patenting geography group 5 (2020-2025).

3.4.2. Standards

To identify relevant standards, we applied the same set of keywords used during the patent search. In total we found 52 standards (See annex D-Standards) relevant to PCP WISE, this many standards provide a stable foundation for technical quality and compatibility in the project, but their domain-specific focus and limited adaptability to integrated, future-facing solutions leave ample room for innovation. The standards identified encompass a broad range of technical elements including geographic information systems (GIS), remote sensing data acquisition and processing, environmental management frameworks, digital infrastructure security, and specialized fields such as geotechnical monitoring, hydrology, and stormwater system design. Many of these standards provide well-established methodologies and protocols. For example, for accurate risk assessment through advanced sensing (e.g., SensorML, WMS), environmental data management (ISO 19165-2, ISO 14001), or secure

digital system operations (ISO/IEC 27001). However, their prescriptive nature typically leaves significant room for innovation, particularly in integrating novel data analytics, AI-driven decision-making, and modular technology deployment, which aligns closely with PCP WISE goals that emphasize breakthrough, scalable, and adaptable climate resilience solutions. Notably, several standards are highly specialized and applicable only to specific technical domains or components within a larger system which means they are not intended to cover the full scope of a PCP Wise project but rather address discrete parts of the solution. This selective applicability ensures that while foundational guidance is maintained, innovators can tailor and combine standards flexibly, fostering creative approaches to climate resilience that meet evolving and diverse needs.

3.4.3. Results Gap analysis of Patents

3.4.3.1. Results of technologies relevant for the challenges

As part of the analysis presented in this chapter, we first identified the patents most relevant to each of the five groups (for the complete list please refer to Annex F-Patents). From each group, a shortlist was developed to highlight those patents most aligned with the objectives of each group. To further refine the analysis and assess the regional distribution of intellectual property rights, the shortlisted patents were subsequently divided into two categories: those originating within Europe and those from outside the region. This distinction provides a clearer view of the geographical spread of innovation and IPR concentration. The full breakdown is provided in the table below.

Group	Total shortlisted patents	Shortlisted patents - Europe	Shortlisted patents - World
Group 1 Urban Drought (NW-EU)	103	16	87
Group 2 Urban Flood (N-Central EU)	130	11	119
Group 3 Rural Drought (NW-Central EU)	120	10	110
Group 4 Rural Drought & Flooding	75	8	67
Group 5 Rural Drought & Flooding (N-EU)	149	10	139

Table 23: Shortlisted patents per group

Following the regional shortlisting of relevant patents, the next step involved extracting the associated technologies from each patent that aligned with PCP WISE and the specific objectives of each individual group. After eliminating duplicates and merging similar technologies, the process yielded 106 unique technologies identified within Europe across all five groups, and 432 unique technologies globally. Subsequently, technical experts from

Fraunhofer, in collaboration with specialists from the broader consortium, conducted a TRL assessment for each of these technologies, this assessment is still in progress.

The resulting catalogue of technologies, derived from both patent analysis and scientific publications and accompanied with their respective TRL estimates, served as the foundation for the development of the technology matrix (see Chapter 3.8.1). This matrix plays a central role in the prioritization and selection process, ultimately guiding the identification of the most promising and relevant technologies in support of the PCP WISE project and the targeted innovation goals of each group.

3.5. State of the art _ Literature Review

3.5.1. Methodology

For this Survey of the State-of-the-Art, the focus is on the identification and evaluation of scientific publications. Together with Patents they are very important sources of information for technology foresight and technology intelligence. For example, Mühlroth & Grottke (2018) find that publications and patents, are the most important sources for identifying emerging topics. The reason is, that they mirror the underlying sub-processes in different phases of a comprehensive innovation process. Publications capture the emergence and further development of an idea or scientific discovery, which might result in an invention. Correspondently patents are assumed to reflect the subsequent diffusion process, which transforms the acquired scientific knowledge into technologies or even products. Thus, publications are suitable for observing the process of (scientific) knowledge production, while patents are more helpful, when it comes to catch the process of technology development. Consequently, there are different information producers: While scientific papers are mainly written by scientists affiliated at universities or research organizations, most patent applications are submitted by companies. Of course, this distinction is somehow artificial and there is considerable overlap, especially if one is interested in the process of knowledge diffusion.

The following paragraphs present the results of the publication and patent analyses and describe the underlying methodology.

Publications and Technologies

With the help of desk research, data-based foresight methods, existing studies, publications, and institutions, important technologies for the PCP WISE project were identified, collected, structured, and their TRL was estimated. The Fraunhofer AVIATION & SPACE project team also used the KATI system (Knowledge Analytics for Technology & Innovation System) developed at Fraunhofer INT for the research. KATI uses state-of-the-art methods from the fields of data mining, visualization and bibliometrics to open up new possibilities in the indexing and analysis of scientific sources. KATI is an assistance tool for literature research, bibliometric and scientometric analyses with a special emphasis on technology foresight. The first version of

KATI was made available in 2017. Since then, updates and new features have been provided on a regular basis.

The core of the KATI system forms a so-called graph database, which is especially well suited to store the bibliographic information of scientific papers, which are highly interconnected. The data base stores the data of about 60 million publication and holds among other the following information about a certain information:

- Author names
- Institution names
- Country names
- Abstract, if available
- Keywords
- References
- Citations
- Journal name
- (other)

The database is updated on a regular (weekly) basis.

The project team uses KATI to gain a clear overview of the state of the art in the topic fields interesting for PCP WISE and enables the identification of key technologies and players.

Figure 48 displays KATI's system architecture and Figure 49 shows a section of the KATI search interface with an exemplary search query.

Figure 46 KATI's system architecture.

The screenshot shows the KATI search interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Fraunhofer INT KATI' logo and buttons for 'Overview', 'Actors', 'Topics', 'Personalize', 'My dashboard', and 'Tables'. Below the navigation bar, there is a table with columns for 'Dashboard', 'Document set', 'Created', and 'Modified'. The first row shows 'Overview - Intro 1', 'PCP WISE_Group2_Urban and Flood', '2025-4-7', and '2025-4-7'. Below the table, there is a 'Documents' section with a 'Query' field containing a complex Boolean search query. The query is: `((title:"water" OR manual_tag:"water" OR auto_tag:"water") AND ("flood**") AND ("urban" OR "city" OR "cities") AND ("groundwater" OR "sea level**" OR "storm**" OR "rainfall" OR "soil moisture" OR "water level" OR "water management"-2 OR "water suppl**")) AND ("data science" OR "satellite data" OR "disaster management" OR "prevention**" OR "urban planning" OR "environmental observation" OR "real time**" OR "infrastructure" OR "crisis management" OR "civil protection" OR "urban development" OR "emergency response" OR "maps" OR "coordination")) NOT ("drought" OR "drink**" OR "produced water" OR "dry out" OR "bioreactor" OR "bio reactor") AND year:[2010 TO 2025])`. To the right of the query, there is a 'Collection Web of Science' label.

Figure 47 Section of the KATI search interface with an exemplary search query.

Use of KATI

The greatest challenge of a "good" search is to find and identify all relevant publications on a specific topic in a large and growing pool of knowledge within a reasonable period of time. This results in a trade-off between maximizing the coverage of all relevant publications in the database and minimizing irrelevant publications in the hit list. If the search query to the database is formulated too broadly, many irrelevant publications are also obtained, which are later included in the analysis. If the search query is formulated too narrowly, relevant publications may be missing from the hit list. In order to ensure a high quality of results, the search queries and the generated hit lists were developed and checked one by one. The relevance of the publications provided was checked by our experts.

As mentioned above, the KATI system developed at Fraunhofer INT was used for the PCP WISE project research. KATI supported the development of the search query and enabled the generation of analyses and visualizations. The iterative steps for the search and analysis process are described in the following paragraphs.

The first step was to identify the most important facts or groups of terms associated with the topic. These formed the basis for a specific query of the database on scientific publications. In KATI, these search terms are linked with the Boolean operators "AND", "OR" and "NOT" (see Figure 50 for example). In the case of PCP WISE, key words have already been defined for the five defined groups in other WPs, which have greatly assisted in the creation of suitable search queries.

Nevertheless, the development of a search query is always an iterative process. Based on the initial search results, new and more precise search terms were determined at the start of the project. These specifications were then incorporated into a new search query. The results of the new search query were carefully checked for unsuitable content in order to be able to make any further restrictions and sort out new irrelevant publications.

This could be done, for example, by excluding irrelevant fields of research. These steps were repeated until a satisfactory quality of results was achieved.

KATI provided lists of potentially important publications for the five defined groups and carried out statistical analyses (see the next section). It is a challenging and time-consuming task to assess the quality of a publication. However, a residual uncertainty remains due to the described trade-off. The final and most important step is for an expert in the relevant field to study the publications in detail and carry out a further quality check.

After discussions with project partners of other WPs, the five identified search queries for the five use case groups were subdivided into subsets using additional specific search terms like “hydrological”, “atmospheric”, and “meteorology” to expand the search space even further. In addition, the search query can also be narrowed down to publications from a specific year in order to reduce the publications considered to technologies that are relevant from a current perspective and to derive current trends, whereby scientific publications usually have long lead times from basic research to commercialization.

The described iterative procedure for developing the search query ensures a high quality of the hit list so that the subsequent analyses and visualizations are highly informative.

With the help of the KATI system, various analyses and visualizations have been created that provide information on the development of the topic of small satellites in the scientific research landscape. The results are presented in the next section.

3.5.2. Survey Outcomes

The following sections present the most important results of the publication analyses per user group. All analysis results are also provided in a separate Power Point file.

The **yearly distribution of publications** is a popular way of assessing scientific productivity in a descriptive way. Figure 50 to Figure 54 display the publication dynamic for the identified publications with potential relevance regarding the PCP WISE Project. All identified papers per group are attached to this document in separate Excel lists (incl. abstracts) in Annex E- Papers. The x-axes depict the years, and the y-axes the number of publications. The corresponding **keyword clouds** shown in Figure 55 to Figure 59 display the most frequently occurring keywords that were manually identified by the authors.

(title:"urban" OR manual_tag:"urban" OR auto_tag:"urban") AND ("flood*") AND ("urban" OR "city" OR "cities") AND ("soil saturation" OR "soil moisture" OR "flooding" OR "green spaces" OR "ground instability" OR "groundwater levels" OR "subsidence" OR "underground" OR "building foundations") AND ("analysis of trends" OR "maintenance" OR "satellite data" OR "urban planning" OR "mapping" OR "environmental observation" OR "water management") AND year:[2010 TO 2025]

- Number of publications: 1.080

Figure 48 KATI-Publication dynamics and the corresponding search query for group 1 (years 2010 to today). The data for 2024 and 2025 are not yet fully available (black square).

(((title:"water" OR manual_tag:"water" OR auto_tag:"water") AND ("flood*") AND ("urban" OR "city" OR "cities") AND ("groundwater" OR "sea level*" OR "storm*" OR "rainfall" OR "soil moisture" OR "water level" OR "water management"~2 OR "water suppl*") AND ("data science" OR "satellite data" OR "disaster management" OR "prevention*" OR "urban planning" OR "environmental observation" OR "real time*" OR "infrastructure" OR "crisis management" OR "civil protection" OR "urban development" OR "emergency response" OR "maps" OR "coordination")) NOT ("drought" OR "drink*" OR "produced water" OR "dry out" OR "bioreactor" OR "bio reactor") AND year:[2010 TO 2025])

▪ Number of publications: 942

Figure 49 KATI-Publication dynamics and the corresponding search query for group 2 (years 2010 to today). The data for 2024 and 2025 are not yet fully available (black square).


```
(((title:"rural" OR manual_tag:"rural" OR auto_tag:"rural") AND ("drought" OR "low saturation" OR "low water saturation" OR "intensive rainfall" OR "rainfall" OR "heavy rain*" OR "enduring rain*" OR "soil moisture" OR "water level" OR "water management"~2) AND ("risk area*" OR "data science" OR "satellite data" OR "disaster management" OR "prevention*" OR "agriculture" OR "crops" OR "harvest" OR "agricultural production losses" OR "agricultural production failures" OR "prediction" OR "analysis*" OR "environmental observation" OR "real time*" OR "infrastructure" OR "crisis management" OR "climate change" AND "response" OR "maps" OR "coordination")) AND year:[2010 TO 2025]
```

- Number of publications: 1.060

Figure 50 KATI-Publication dynamics and the corresponding search query for group 3 (years 2010 to today). The data for 2024 and 2025 are not yet fully available (black square).

`(((title:"rural" OR manual_tag:"rural" OR auto_tag:"rural" OR "agricult*") AND ("drought*") AND ("crop evapotranspiration" OR "crop productivity" OR "vulnerability" OR "water management"~2) AND ("data science" OR "satellite data" OR "urban management" OR "environmental observation" OR "real time*" OR "infrastructure" OR "crisis management" OR "spatial resolution" OR "AI" OR " irrigation system maps")) AND year:[2010 TO 2025])`

▪ Number of publications: 404

Figure 51 KATI-Publication dynamics and the corresponding search query for group 4 (years 2010 to today). The data for 2024 and 2025 are not yet fully available (black square).

Document Set: PCP Group 5 (used for Export)
 Date: May 20, 2025
 Source: KATI developed by Fraunhofer INT

((title:"rural" OR manual_tag:"rural" OR auto_tag:"rural" OR title:"urban" OR manual_tag:"urban" OR auto_tag:"urban" OR "peatland" OR "peat soil" OR "peat mass") AND ("drought" OR "peat fire*" OR "water balance" OR "water scarcity" OR "hysteresis" OR "subsidence" OR "soil uprise" OR "groundwater level*" OR "ground water level*" OR "soil moistur*" OR "water infrastructure" OR "water level" OR "water management"~2 OR ("dry weather")) AND ("risk map" OR "data science" OR "earth observation" OR "satellite data" OR "remote sens*" OR "planning" OR "prediction" OR "map*" OR "environmental observation" OR "decision mak*" OR "sensor" OR "crisis management" OR "emergency response" OR "nature conservation" OR ("real time") OR ("real-time") OR ("realtime") OR ("utility network") OR ("vegetation fire*")) AND year:[2010 TO 2025])

- Number of publications: 3263

Figure 52 KATI-Publication dynamics and the corresponding search query for group 5 (years 2010 to today). The data for 2024 and 2025 are not yet fully available (black square).

Figure 53 KATI Manual keyword cloud (top 200) for group 1.

Figure 54 KATI Manual keyword cloud (top 200) for group 2.

Figure 55 KATI Manual keyword cloud (top 200) for group 3.

- chosen keywords are used more frequently.

The following paragraph provides deeper analyses and assessment of the identified publications.

The reference-citation plots (Figure 60- Figure 64) map the number of incoming citations of a document with the number of referenced publications. Each paper in this plot is represented by an orange dot. This results in a distribution of points that can be used to identify review articles that themselves cite a particularly large number of publications and therefore most likely summarize the research area well, as well as highly cited (key) publications that have been taken up more frequently in research.

Most of the publications gather in the lower left corner of the graph, they have an average number of citations and references. There are two ways to find interesting publications:

- Firstly, one can look at the publications in the upper half. The higher the value on the y-axis, the more frequently the publication was cited. This suggests that it must be an influential article that has been referenced by many authors over the years.
- The higher the value on the x-axis, the more references are included in the article. In the lower right part of the plot, one finds publications that use a very high number of references (sometimes several hundred). These are likely to be so-called review papers, which are well-suited to gain an overview of the field.

However, the most cited publications are often relatively old publications, so that a high number of citations could accumulate. Nevertheless, one can often find particularly interesting papers with this analysis, and it offers good orientation for search queries with a high number of hits. Figure 65 to 68 show the reference citation plot with examples of publications for the five groups.

Figure 58 Reference-Citation plot for the search query shown in Figure a for group 1.

Figure 59 Reference-Citation plot for the search query shown in Figure a for group 2.

Figure 60 Reference-Citation plot for the search query shown in Figure a for group 3.

Figure 61 Reference-Citation plot for the search query shown in Figure a for group 4.

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 Date: May 20, 2025
 Source: KATI developed by Fraunhofer INT

Figure 62 Reference-Citation plot for the search query shown in Figure a for group 5.

Figure 63 Reference citation plot with examples of publications for group 1.

Figure 64 Reference citation plot with examples of publications for group 2.

Reference Citation Plot

Figure 65 Reference citation plot with examples of publications for group 3

Figure 66 Reference citation plot with examples of publications for group 4.

In addition to content analyses, the KATI system also provides various **analyses of the actors** in the sector of interest. Actors can be considered in KATI at the three levels of countries, organizations, and authors.

The analyses of actors at country levels are shown in Figure 69 to Figure 73. China and the United States are the most active countries in the field of scientific publications for the defined search queries. The most active European country is the United Kingdom followed by the Netherlands, Italy, Germany, Spain and France.

It is important to note that KATI uses a full counting approach, i.e. if an article is co-authored by several researchers that are affiliated to institutions in more than one country, each country will be considered. Hence the publication count in the country analysis will not correspond to the actual number of papers, it will be higher. Example: A paper is published by three US-based researchers and one German researcher, the US count will be one and so will be the count for Germany.

In addition to the analysis of players at country level, the analysis of players at organizational level provides information about particularly active organizations in the sector of interest. Actors whose countries publicize less at country level can stand out here.

Figure 67 Publication activity of the countries for group 1.

Figure 68 Publication activity of the countries for group 2.

Figure 69 Publication activity of the countries for group 3.

Figure 70 Publication activity of the countries for group 4.

Document Set: PCP Group 5 (used for Export)
Date: May 20, 2025
Source: KATI developed by Fraunhofer INT

Figure 71 Publication activity of the countries for group 5.

Technology identification and TRL estimation

The resulting papers were then used to identify potentially important technologies for the PCP WISE project and to estimate their TRL. It was important that each of the five groups was worked on by a different person from the Fraunhofer AVIATION & SPACE team. This ensured neutrality in the identification of the technologies. The technologies were then consolidated at a later date.

For the TRL estimation of the technologies the following TRL definitions apply:

HORIZON 2020 – WORK PROGRAMME 2014-2015
General Annexes

G. Technology readiness levels (TRL)

Where a topic description refers to a TRL, the following definitions apply, unless otherwise specified:

- TRL 1 – basic principles observed
- TRL 2 – technology concept formulated
- TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept
- TRL 4 – technology validated in lab
- TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
- TRL 6 – technology demonstrated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
- TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment
- TRL 8 – system complete and qualified
- TRL 9 – actual system proven in operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies; or in space)

Figure 72 TRL definitions (reference: h2020-wp1415-annex-g-trl_en.pdf)

The following steps were taken into account when estimating the TRL level.

1. Identify the stage of development described

Look for descriptions about:

- Theoretical studies or simulations (lower TRLs)
- Laboratory experiments or prototypes (TRL 3–5)
- Field tests or demonstrations (TRL 6–7)
- Deployment in real operational conditions (TRL 8–9)

2. Check for validation and testing

- Has the technology been tested only in the lab or also in relevant environments?
- Are there pilot projects or real-world deployments?
- Is performance data from actual operational use provided?

3. Look for maturity indicators

- Are system-level integrations and scalability discussed?
- Is there mention of certification, standardization, or regulatory approval?
- Are issues of reliability, maintainability, or robustness addressed?

4. Assess the paper's context and claims
 - Is the paper focused on proof-of-concept, or does it describe a near-market or commercial product?
 - Are limitations and future work discussed, indicating that the technology is not fully mature?

5. Summarize and map findings to TRL

Based on the evidence, estimate which TRL best fits the current maturity. For example:

 - A paper describing only simulations → TRL 2–3
 - Lab prototype tests with promising results → TRL 4–5
 - Pilot field demonstrations → TRL 6–7
 - Fully deployed operational system → TRL 8–9

6. Cross-reference other sources: Papers often cite or are cited by others that may indicate the technology's readiness.
7. Consider the publication date: More recent papers might show higher maturity.
8. Look for follow-up studies: Technology might have progressed after the paper was published.

Consolidated final technology list

Based on the results of the individual analyses from the five groups, the following 172 technologies were identified as having a high potential for the PCP WISE project and could meet the existing needs of the stakeholders (the list is also attached as a PowerPoint version. The papers with the corresponding references (DOI or list number) are also listed there).

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
1 Sentinel	Sentinel provide high-resolution, global real-time data for monitoring water levels and flooding	9	Private Conversation with ESA and DLR Project HydroSAR – GEORESEARCH: Project HydroSAR - GEORESEARCH	A wide range of data is made available as part of Copernicus. This includes the satellite data from the Sentinel fleet (https://www.copernicus.eu/en/about-copernicus/infrastructure-overview/discover-our-satellites) and the products of the 6 Copernicus Services, which are created on the basis of this (and other) data (https://www.copernicus.eu/en/copernicus-services). In addition, there are the so-called Thematic Hubs for cross-cutting topics (https://www.copernicus.eu/en/news/news/observer-exploration-copernicus-thematic-hubs). ESA procures further satellite data as part of the Copernicus Contributing Missions (https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/explore-data/data-collections/copernicus-contributing-missions). The data are open and freely available. The main point of contact for obtaining the data is the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem (CDSE). All Sentinel data is stored here and can be searched. A good starting point is the Copernicus Browser (https://browser.dataspace.copernicus.eu/), in which the data can also be visualised online. There are also various other ways of using the data. There are various options (also from the CDSE) for cloud-based processing of the data (some of which incur costs). The data can also be downloaded and processed locally, but for reasons of efficiency DLR recommends processing in the cloud (see also next point). Copernicus Services provides various high-quality products (as mentioned). Of particular interest for our specific requirements are the Land Service (https://land.copernicus.eu/en/dataset-catalog) and the Emergency Management Service (https://emergency.copernicus.eu/data/). Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem Europe's eyes on Earth ESA Copernicus Open Access Hub: Earth Observation: Copernicus Sentinel Satellite Data – Open Access at ESA Copernicus Emergency Management Service (EMS): https://www.copernicus.eu/de/dienste/katastrophen-und-krisenmanagement EUMETSAT Copernicus Online Data Access Point: Access Copernicus data EUMETSAT All Sentinel data is open and freely available, as is the Copernicus Services data (with the exception of the Security Service). Details on the terms of use can be found at: https://sentinel.esa.int/documents/247904/690755/Sentinel_Data_Legal_Notice EFTAS Fernerkundung Technologietransfer GmbH Einzelansicht Innovationsatlas Wasser Sentinel data used in project HydroSAR

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
2 Landsat	Provides earth observation data (multispectral – SWIR) → Detection and delineation of flood areas, separation of floodwater from soil, vegetation and built areas, extent and duration of flood events, Land cover and impervious surface monitoring, vegetation and water indices, etc.	9	Private Conversation	United States Geological Survey: https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/ https://glovis.usgs.gov/ https://landsatlook.usgs.gov/ https://eros.usgs.gov/doi-remote-sensing-activities/2022/usgs-demand-provisional-landsat-actual-evapotranspiration-global-extent#:~:text=The%20U.S.%20Geological%20Survey%20%28USGS%29%20EROS%20Science%20Processing,provides%20higher-level%20science%20products%20derived%20from%20Landsat%20data. NASA: Landsat Science https://search.earthdata.nasa.gov/

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
3 SAR	Synthetic aperture radar (SAR) data from satellite images is used worldwide to monitor floods and water volumes	9	Private Conversation	ESA → see slide 62 and ESA Hydrology TEP: https://hydrology-tep.eu/guest/ Sentinel-1: C-Band SAR Data Sentinel-2: Multispectral optical data as a supplement for SAR EUMETSAT → see slide 62 Zentrum für satellitengestützte Kriseninformation (ZKI)/DLR: https://www.zki.de/de/zki Capella SPACE (USA): https://www.capellaspace.com/ https://ip42.com/marketplace/data/archive/capella-gec?utm_source=chatgpt.com https://skywatch.com/capella-space-selects-skywatch-as-first-aggregation-platform-partner/?utm_source=chatgpt.com ICEYE (Finland) https://www.iceye.com/satellites https://geosat-space.com/blog/geosat-esas-third-party-missions-tpm/#:~:text=The%20Third-Party%20Missions%20%28TPM%29%20programme%20%28EarthNet%29%20consists%20of%20of%20worldwide%20of%20which%20GEO%20AT%20is%20a%20part. TerraSAR-X & TanDEM-X (Germany, DLR) https://sss.terrasar-x.dlr.de (Science) Planet Labs (Germany) https://www.planet.com/ Viridien (UK) https://www.viridiengroup.com/expertise/satellite-mapping#1702591434-3769649131 MAXAR (USA): https://www.maxar.com/

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
4 GOES-R → Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellites	Most sophisticated Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellites (GOES), is known as the GOES-R Series (NOAA). The GOES-R Series provides critical atmospheric, hydrologic, oceanic, climatic, solar and space data, significantly improving detection and observation of environmental phenomena that directly affect public safety, protection of property, and our nation's economic health and prosperity.	9 7-8 integration of AI	10.3390/rs16040675	NOAA (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration), USA Together with NASA https://www.goes.noaa.gov https://www.nesdis.noaa.gov GOES data via the EUMETCast service: https://user.eumetsat.int/data-access/eumetcast-europe
5 Spatial reduction attention	Special technology in the field of deep learning, in particular vision transformers (ViTs) and other image-processing neural networks. The model compares each pixel or patch element with each other to recognise relevant relationships (e.g. 'where is water in the image?')	4-6 for real-time monitoring	10.1109/JSTARS.2024.3455891 (Use of Sentinel-1 SAR data)	(Paper: China) There are companies and organisations that develop and offer similar technologies for remote sensing and environmental monitoring → Slide 64 but it is not commercially available

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
6	LiDAR	Used to create high-precision terrain models, which are essential for flood analyses and flood hazard mapping	9	10.1007/s11273-025-10032-9	<p>Airbus (Frankreich) https://www.airbus.com/en/newsroom/stories/2024-11-inside-atlid-mastering-atmospheric-lidar-technology-for-space#-:text=Let%E2%80%99s%20focus%20on%20the%20inner%20workings%20of%20EarthCare%E2%80%99s,atmospheric%20LiDAR%2C%20Atlid%2C%20designed%20and%20built%20by%20Airbus.</p> <p>Leica Geosystems (Schweiz) https://leica-geosystems.com/products/airborne-systems/topographic-lidar-sensors</p> <p>Riegl (Österreich) http://www.riegl.com/</p> <p>Fugro (Netherlands) https://www.fugro.com/news/long-reads/2022/sense-lidar-enabling-better-decisions-with-better-data-fugro-longread</p>

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
7	MODIS (Moderate resolution Imaging spectroradiometer), VIIRS (Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite) → higher resolution than MODIS	Satellite-based earth observation systems, which are primarily used for large-scale environmental monitoring MODIS: Large-scale flood monitoring, vegetation analyses*, land use change, surface temperature and water stress, cloud cover and precipitation monitoring VIIRS: Similar to MODIS but with higher res. and night light observation for e.g. assessing power outages during disasters	9	<p>https://darktarget.gsfc.nasa.gov/viirs-vs-modis-sensor</p> <p>https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/</p>	<p>NASA (Terra and Aqua satellites, which observe the Earth in different spectral bands): https://modis.gsfc.nasa.gov/data/ https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/data/instruments/viirs</p>
8	Geographical information systems (GIS), z. B. ArcGIS, QGIS	Tool for analysing spatial data and flood risks. It is often used to identify areas at risk of flooding and to create flood modelling maps	9	<p>10.1016/j.jidrr.2017.11.003</p> <p>10.1016/j.landurbplan.2019.103703</p>	<p>Environmental Systems Research Institute (ESRI), USA: https://www.esri.com/en-us/home ArcGIS leading provider of commercial GIS solutions</p> <p>QGIS: Open-Source-Software https://qgis.org/</p> <p>Trimble (USA) https://geospatial.trimble.com/de</p> <p>Hexagon (Sweden) https://geospatial.trimble.com/de</p> <p>Climate Innovation Window - FREEWAT</p>

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
9	Hydrological models (e.g., HEC-RAS, SWMM (Storm Water Management Model))	Software tools for hydrological modelling used in water resource management and flood analysis. Both are used to model rivers, streams, canals and urban water systems and to assess flood risks (calibration-dependent)	<p>8-9 (HEC-RAS) 9 Standard-SWMM 7-8 SWMM with real-time contrl (RTC) 6-7 SWMM with coupling to weather or climate models</p>	<p>10.1007/s13753-023-00465-2</p> <p>10.1016/j.jhydrol.2021.127269</p>	<p>HEC-RAS (US Army Corps of Engineers): Open Source https://www.hec.usace.army.mil/software/hec-ras/</p> <p>SWMM (US Environmental Protection Agency): Open Source https://www.epa.gov/water-research/storm-water-management-model-swmm</p> <p>MIKE: DHI (Danish Hydraulic Institute): commercial https://www.dhigroup.com/</p> <p>Delft3D, SOBEK (Netherlands): commercial https://www.deltares.nl/en</p> <p>Flood Modeller (UK): Commercial https://www.deltares.nl/en</p> <p>Hydrotec (Germany, Austria) Commercial https://www.hydrotec.de/</p>

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
10	AI/machine learning for flood forecasts	Data analysis and modelling Lots of research, but still at pilot stage in some cities, complement or improve classical hydrological models with fast, data-driven forecasts based on large amounts of historical and current data	5-7	10.1029/2019WR027038 https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2403.10625	AI4Flood (Spanien, Frankreich, Andorra, founded by EU): https://ai4flood.com/ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/whats-new/newsroom/17-02-2025-cohesion-policy-project-deploys-artificial-intelligence-to-anticipate-and-mitigate-flood-risks_en?utm_source=chatgpt.com FORSIGHT (founded by EU): https://coro.is.europa.eu/project/id/1012102967?utm_source=chatgpt.com SaferPlaces (Global) https://saferplaces.co/?utm_source=chatgpt.com FlodWaive (Germany) Enterprise Europe Network - Nordrhein-Westfalen: Flood forecasting software DeepWaive: FloodWaive uses ESA funding for feasibility study Address + Hauser (Netilion Flood Monitoring), Germany https://changes.endress.com/de/schnelle-r-am-start
Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
11	Digital twins (urban flooding)	Data analyses and modelling, virtual representation of a real urban environment that integrates real-time data, simulation models and visualisation tools to support the prediction, monitoring and management of flood events in cities, Fast-growing topic, but often still in test/pilot phases	4-6	10.1016/j.envsoft.2021.105120	VRVis Zentrum für Virtual Reality und Visualisierung (Austria): scenariify is a visualization and simulation software for flood and heavy rain. Nelen&Schuurmans (Netherlands, Germany) https://nelen-schuurmans.nl/en/case/flood-early-warning-in-a-3d-digital-twin/ Telespazio (Italy): e-GEOS https://www.telespazio.com/en/press-release-detail/-/detail/sure 3Di Water Management (UK) https://3diwatermanagement.com/case/flood-early-warning-with-3di-in-a-3d-digital-twin/
Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
12	IoT-based water level and weather stations	Sensors continuously monitor water levels, rainfall and meteorological conditions and can be linked to an early warning system in real time	7-9	10.1088/1742-6596/2319/1/012020 10.56532/mjsat.v4i2.293	Float IoT (Netherlands) https://www.float-iot.nl/?utm_source=chatgpt.com MERATCH (Germany) https://meratch.com/?utm_source=chatgpt.com Vertical M2M (Czech Republic) https://www.vertical-m2m.com/cs-smartwater/?utm_source=chatgpt.com Vaisala (Finland) https://www.vaisala.com/en/digitalization Metomatics (Swiss) https://www.meteomatics.com/
13	IoT-based Smart City Flood Warning Systems	Smart early warning systems that provide automated notifications in real time when flood hazards are detected. They integrate sensors, weather forecasts and models	6-9	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijotcp.2023.04.005 10.1109/ICEMPS60684.2024.10559355	Sectron (Czech Republic): https://www.sectron.eu/en/smart-city/a-101/ Emitel (Poland) https://emitel.pl/en/products-and-services/smart-city/ Aeonics (France): https://www.aeonics.io/en/blog/cas-dusage-surveillance-ge-cruet@ggpr Brunata (Denmark) https://brunata.com/smart-sensors-a-new-defense-against-flooding-and-heavy-rain/ Melita.io (Germany) Modern technology for water monitoring - melita.io

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
14	Smart Water Level Sensors	Sensors & IoT Intelligent, networked devices that measure the water level in real time and automatically transmit the data, e.g. to a central platform, an app or an early warning system. They are increasingly being used in urban drainage, flood monitoring, water level monitoring and water resource management. Partly in urban use	7-9	https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-91166-5.00011-2	Milesight (Germany) https://www.milesight.com/ot/product/lorawan-sensor/em500-sw/ Sentinum (Germany) https://sentinum.de/en/apollo-q Brunтана (Denmark): https://brunтана.com/smart-sensors-a-new-defense-against-flooding-and-heavy-rain/ Smart Well (Czech Republic): https://www.smartwell.cz/en/home/ Emitel (Poland) https://www.smartwell.cz/en/home/
15	Soil moisture sensors (urbanen context)	Sensors & IoT Electronic measuring devices that monitor the water content in the soil - especially in urban areas, where they are used for flood prevention, green infrastructure planning, irrigation control and urban climate adaptation	6-8	Soil Moisture Sensor Technology: An Overview https://www.livetoplant.com/explorimg-smart-sensors-for-soil-moisture-management/	SENSOTERRA (Netherlands) https://www.sensoterra.com/ AquaSpy (Germany): Unsure https://aquaspy.com/ IMKO (Germany): Unsure https://www.imko.de/ Delta T (UK) https://delta-t.co.uk/ Copernicus (EU) https://www.copernicus.eu/en/news/news/observer-monitoring-soil-moisture-space-copernicus

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
16	Dense heavy rain sensor networks	Sensors & IoT Close-meshed, locally distributed systems of rain gauges that record short-term, intensive precipitation events (e.g. heavy rainfall) with high spatial and temporal resolution. They are primarily used for early warning of urban flooding, hydrology, climate monitoring and sewer network control. Research + pilot cities, no standard yet	5-7	https://ethz.ch/content/dam/ethz/pecial-interest/conference-websites-dam/urbanrain-dam/papers/UrbanRain23_ABSTRACT_Jahnke-Bornemann.pdf https://een.ec.europa.eu/partnerimg-opportunities/urban-heavy-rainfall-sensor-networks-and-forecasting https://www.hannovermesse.de/a/poll/hannover_messe_2021/obs/Binary/A1089789/25square_EN.pdf	ACS (Germany): https://www.acs-controlsystem.de/?utm_source=chatgpt.com Brunтана (Denmark): https://brunтана.com/smart-sensors-a-new-defense-against-flooding-and-heavy-rain/?utm_source=chatgpt.com HD Rain (France) https://www.hd-rain.com/en/local-authorities?utm_source=chatgpt.com FloodCitiSense (Belgium) http://www.floodcitisense.eu/home/project heavyRain (Germany) https://www.oceanos.ai/heavyrain/
17	Blue-Green Urban Planning	Holistic approach to urban development in which water infrastructure and vegetation/nature are planned in an integrated way to make urban spaces more climate-resilient, liveable and ecological	7-9 (Multifunctional retention parks (e.g. Rotterdam, blue-green corridors, open water instead of underground pipes, etc.)	10.1080/1573062X.2017.1279190 10.1016/j.ufug.2024.128320	West 8 (Rotterdam, Netherlands) https://www.west8.com/projects/a16-highway/ SymbioCity (Sweden) https://symbiocity.org/about/ Drees & Sommer (Germany) https://www.dreeso.com/at/en/services/blue-city Sieker (Germany) https://www.sieker.de/en/projects-and-references/research-and-development/project/blue-green-cream-93.html

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
18	Crowdsourcing-Tools (e.g. OSM Flood Maps)	Digital platforms or apps that collect data from citizens to gather information about flooding, heavy rainfall, damage or infrastructure failures - often in real time. This data can be used for mapping, decision support, emergency response or model calibration	7-9	10.3390/ijgi5050055 https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/927f836eaa1343688ca690f9ca667410 10.13140/RG.2.2.35313.07527 https://www.preventionweb.net/publication/crisis-mapping-and-crowdsourcing-flood-management	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA): FloodCitiSense (EU) https://iiasa.ac.at/models-tools-data/floodcitisense?utm_source=chatgpt.com Geo-Wiki (EU): https://pure.iiasa.ac.at/id/eprint/8836/1/remotesensing-01-00345.pdf https://www.geo-wiki.org/ Missing Maps (EU) https://www.missingmaps.org/ Ushahidi (EU and Africa) https://www.ushahidi.com/ STURM (EU) https://sturm-weo.github.io/?utm_source=chatgpt.com Numerous available in the USA

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
19	Emergency apps/coordination tools (e.g. NINA (DE), KATWARN (DE), GDACS (UN))	Digital applications and platforms that provide real-time information, coordinate communication between emergency services, authorities and the population, and enable warnings, situational awareness and resource management	8-9	10.1088/1757-899X/1009/1/012049	Germany: Nina https://www.bmi.bund.de/SharedDocs/app/DE/nina.html#:~:text=Mit%20der%20Notfall-Informationen-%20und%20Nachrichten-App%20des%20Bundes%2C%20kurz.Gro%C3%9Fbrand%20erhalten.%20Optional%20auch%20f%C3%BCr%20hren%20aktuellen%20Standort. KATWARN https://www.bmi.bund.de/SharedDocs/app/DE/nina.html#:~:text=Mit%20der%20Notfall-Informationen-%20und%20Nachrichten-App%20des%20Bundes%2C%20kurz.Gro%C3%9Fbrand%20erhalten.%20Optional%20auch%20f%C3%BCr%20hren%20aktuellen%20Standort. FR-Alert (France) https://fr-alert.gouv.fr/ GDACS (Global) https://www.gdacs.org/
Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
20	3D/AR flood visualisations	Visualisation of flooding events and their effects on urban environments in three-dimensional or augmented reality-based (AR) representations	4-6	https://doi.org/10.1080/17538947.2019.1711210 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ensoft.2023.105810 https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-1912-3_25	FLOOD AR (France, EU): https://jacquiod.github.io/FLOODAR/ University of Sheffield (UK) https://www.mdpi.com/2414-4088/3/2/43 Flood control (UK) https://www.floodcontrol2015.com/enhancing-flood-preparedness-through-augmented-reality-visualisation-and-decision-support/ VRVis (Austria) https://www.vrvis.at/en/research/research-projects/hoia-3d?utm_source=chatgpt.com GeoSmart (UK) https://www.vrvis.at/en/research/research-projects/hoia-3d?utm_source=chatgpt.com Climate Innovation Window (EU) https://climateinnovationwindow.eu/innovations/climate-change-ready-an-augmented-reality-mobile-app?utm_source=chatgpt.com
Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
21	Dynamic real-time heatmaps	Visual representations that show the distribution of flood events, water levels, discharge velocities or other relevant parameters in a city or a specific area in real time → Use colour gradients to mark heavily flooded zones, for example → Enable rapid situation assessment and decision-making during a flood event	6-8		Meteotracker (Italy) https://meteotracker.com/index.php/projects/ CityCLIM (EU) https://www.cityclim.eu/de ECOTEN (EU) https://www.euspa.europa.eu/newsroom-events/news/using-copernicus-data-climate-proof-cities?utm_source=chatgpt.com URBAN Heat Watch (EU, Greece) https://www.interregeurope.eu/good-practices/urban-heat-watch-urban-green-climate-resilience-observatory?utm_source=chatgpt.com DYNAMIC DISPLAY OF URBAN HEAT ISLAND (Slovenia) https://www.envirodual.com/projects/dynamic-display-of-urban-heat-island?utm_source=chatgpt.com
22	U-FLOOD	Innovative model that uses deep learning to quickly and accurately predict the maximum water height for urban pluvial flooding → reduce the calculation times of existing hydrodynamic models while providing comparable prediction accuracy	5-6	10.1016/j.jhydrol.2021.126898	Denmark The source code and associated data are publicly available and can be downloaded here: https://data.dtu.dk/articles/code/U-FLOOD_-_computer_code_and_data_associated_with_the_article_U-FLOOD_topographic_deep_learning_for_predicting_urban_pluvial_flood_water_depth_14206838

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
23	SUDS (Sustainable/Smart Urban Drainage Systems)	Drainage systems that aim to manage rainwater efficiently while minimising environmental impact.	Green roofs: 8 Infiltration Basins and swales: 8 Permeable Pavements (footpaths, car parks or roads are made of materials that allow rainwater to pass through and drain into the ground): 8 Rainwater Harvesting Ponds: 8 Constructed Wetlands and vegetated filters (Natural purification of rainwater by plants and microorganisms): 7-8 Bioswales (Planted drainage areas that collect, filter and infiltrate rainwater): 7-8	10.1016/j.jenman.2017.09.075 10.1016/j.scs.2023.104856 10.1016/j.ufug.2024.128320 LIFE CERSUDS (Spain, EU): https://www.lifecersuds.eu/en?utm_source=chatgpt.com LIFE UrbanStorm (Estonia, EU): https://www.lifecersuds.eu/en?utm_source=chatgpt.com C19 (Denmark): https://www.c2ccc.eu/english/subprojects/c19-sustainable-urban-drainage-systems?utm_source=chatgpt.com IRIDRA (Italy) https://www.iridra.eu/en/nature-based-solutions/sustainable-drainage-systems?utm_source=chatgpt.com Ramboll Studio Dreiseitl (Germany) https://regenwasseragentur.berlin/anbieter/ramboll-studio-dreiseitl/ Ökan (Germany) https://www.oekon-vegetationstechnik.de/ueber-uns?utm_source=chatgpt.com ESWEG (EU) https://www.esweg.eu/de/esweg.php?utm_source=chatgpt.com SpongeWorks (EU) https://www.ecologic.eu/de/19776?utm_source=chatgpt.com Kingspan Group, Otto Graf GmbH, Wisy AG, System UVEX Ltd, Boxall Ward Limited Optigrün, Green Roofs Direct, ZinCo Green Roof Systems https://www.greenroofs.org/green-pages/industry-directory lists manufacturers and suppliers Polypipe, Thames Water, Hydro Water Management Solutions, ACO Technologies, Advanced Drainage Systems (ADS), Greenblue Urban https://www.sudrain.org/

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
24	Smart Drainage Systems	Infrastructure & city planning Intelligent, networked drainage systems that use sensors, automation, data analysis and communication technology to efficiently control the flow of rainwater and wastewater in urban areas - in real time and adapted to current weather or system conditions	5-7	https://hsnarman.github.io/CONF/21-EMCON-Sewer.pdf https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2023.222 10.11109/IEMCON53756.2021.9623149	Hydroscan (Germany, Belgium): https://hydroscan.eu/en/proactive-urban-drainage?utm_source=chatgpt.com Permavoid (Netherlands) https://www.permavoid.com/ Wienerberger (PIPELIFE), Norway, Germany https://www.pipelife.com/ De Urbanisten (Watersquare Benthemplein (Netherlands) https://www.urbanisten.nl/work/benthemplein

25	i-Tree Canopy (Part of i-Tree Suite)	Quantitative analysis of tree canopy cover and land use in a given area, developed by the US Forest Service	7-9	10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121421 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/376721806_The_use_of_I-Tree_in_Europa	Forest Research (UK) https://www.forestresearch.gov.uk/research/i-tree-eco?utm_source=chatgpt.com Karlsruher Institut für Technologie (KIT) & Technische Universität München (TUM) (Germany) https://www.forestresearch.gov.uk/research/i-tree-eco?utm_source=chatgpt.com Università Neapel Federico II (Italy) https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/22797254.2022.2125833%4010-1080infocoll.2023.0.issue-PCFS?utm_source=chatgpt.com
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Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
26	LID (Low impact development)	Planning and drainage measures aimed at minimising the impact on natural water and material cycles in urbanised areas. They are similar to SUDS, but originally come from North America and are strongly geared towards decentralised, nature-based rainwater management	Rain Gardens: 8 Tree Box Filters (tree irrigation with filter function): 7-8 Green façades & rain gutters (vertical greening): 6-7	10.1016/j.scs.2020.102373 10.1016/j.ufug.2024.128320 https://doi.org/10.1007/s43832-024-00090-0 https://doi.org/10.2166/hydro.2024.123	SINTEF (Norway) https://waponline.com/jh/article/26/11/2781/105364/SWMMLIDopt-a-tool-for-optimization-of-low-impact?utm_source=chatgpt.com Suderbyn Ecovillage (Sweden) https://suderbyn.se/ HCU (Germany) https://www.hcu-hamburg.de/research/forschungsgruppen/reap/reap-projekte/bluegreentree/ BlueGreenCities (UK) http://www.bluegreencities.ac.uk/about/about.aspx GreenBlue (UK) http://www.bluegreencities.ac.uk/about/about.aspx Ramboll Studio Dreiseitl (Germany) https://regenwasseragentur.berlin/anbieter/ramboll-studio-dreiseitl/

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
27 Urban Projection Scenarios	Real-world urban projection scenarios' are model-based future scenarios that forecast real urban developments under various conditions. They are based on current data and attempt to realistically depict future changes in cities	<p>Geodata Processing & GIS Systems (e.g., ArcGIS, QGIS, CityGML): 9</p> <p>Climate Models and Downscaling (e.g., CMIP6, WRF): 7-8 (still being adapted)</p> <p>Urban Simulation & Land Use Modelling (e.g. UrbanSim, Land Change Modeler): 6-7 (Adapted to specific projects and locations)</p> <p>Real-time data and IoT: 7-9 (Technologies are mature but their integration into urban projections is often still under development)</p> <p>AI/ML for predicting urban dynamics: 5-6 (Validation and customisation phase)</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-71709-4</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.3389/fbuil.2023.1194813</p> <p>DOI:10.2208/jscejhe.76.2_1_103</p>	<p>TU Delft (Netherlands) https://www.tudelft.nl/onderwijs/opleidingen/masters/aus/msc-architecture-urbanism-and-building-sciences/master-tracks/architecture/programme/studies/the-why-factory/</p> <p>Urbanista (Germany) https://urbanista.de/en/project/the-city-of-the-day-after-tomorrow?utm_source=chatgpt.com</p> <p>UrbanSim (Swiss) https://www.urbansim.com/</p> <p>ENVI_MET (Germany) https://envi-met.com/de/</p> <p>CLUEmodel (EU, Netherlands) https://www.environmentalgeography.nl/site/data-models/data/clue-model/</p>

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
28 Sponge Cities	<p>The Sponge City concept is an urban planning and infrastructure concept that aims to absorb, store, clean and reuse rainwater in cities like a sponge instead of immediately draining it away via sewers</p> <p>Using:</p> <p>Green infrastructure (parks, green roofs, wetlands, permeable pavements)</p> <p>Blue infrastructure (Retention basin, open water areas)</p> <p>Decentralised rainwater management (infiltration troughs, cisterns, unsealing)</p>	7-8 (Monitoring & impact measurement is only in pilot stages and very project-specific, Positive effects known, but not yet systematically recorded or evaluated)	10.1016/j.envsci.2017.11.016	<p>Umweltbundesamt (Germany): https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/schwammstadt?utm_source=chatgpt.com</p> <p>"Skybrudspan"-Projekt (Denmark) https://planer.kk.dk/spildevandsplan-2018/maalsaetninger/plangrundlag/skybrudspan/</p> <p>Sponge City Fribourg (Swiss) https://www.spongecity.ch/de</p> <p>Seestadt Aspern (Austria) https://www.wien.gv.at/stadtplanung/aspern-seestadt</p> <p>„ecoQuartier“ (Germany) https://www.green-city.de/die-schwammstadt?utm_source=chatgpt.com</p> <p>Nature-project (Germany) https://nature-project.eu/de/schwammstadt-leipzig?utm_source=chatgpt.com</p>

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
29 Green multifunctional infrastructure	Urban or landscape infrastructures that simultaneously fulfil several ecological, social and technical functions	<p>Multifunctional parks (Retention basins, recreation, biodiversity, urban cooling): 7-9</p> <p>Blue-green corridors (Water flow, species corridors, microclimate, cycle/footpaths): 7-8</p> <p>(Bio)Retention & infiltration e.g. in sports facilities (Rainwater storage, leisure use, flood protection bioretention basins): 7-9</p> <p>Photovoltaics on green (Energy production plus biodiversity plus recreation): 6-8 (PV is 9 but not the integration in green spaces)</p> <p>Urban trees with root space (Tree Trenches) → Stockholm solution: 7-8</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2023.127975</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1038/s42949-024-00145-0</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-65181-7_28</p>	<p>Institut für sozial-ökologische Forschung (Germany): https://www.isoef.de/</p> <p>West 8 (Netherlands) https://www.west8.com/</p> <p>MEA (Germany) https://www.mea-group.com/de/de/</p> <p>Fraunhofer ISE (Germany) https://www.ise.fraunhofer.de/de/geschaeftsfelder/solarkraftwerke-und-integrierte-photovoltaik/integrierte-photovoltaik/biodiversitaets-photovoltaik-bioxiv-pv.html</p>

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
30	Mangrove reforestation for coastal protection	Planting and restoring mangrove (natural barriers by absorbing wave energy and stabilising sediments) forests along coastlines to reduce erosion, buffer storm surges, and support biodiversity → improves water quality, carbon sequestration, etc.	6-8	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wse.2022.10.004 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.121673	Initiative Mangroves du FFEM (France) https://initiative-mangroves-ffem.com/initiative/ Utrecht University (Netherlands): https://initiative-mangroves-ffem.com/initiative/ Deltares (Netherlands) https://www.deltares.nl/en/expertise/projects/mangrove-coasts-under-threat?utm_source=chatgpt.com
31	River restoration (natural riverbeds, floodplains)	Return rivers and their surrounding ecosystems to a more natural state	7-8	https://doi.org/10.1002/rra.3529 https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.aecr.2016.08.010	European Centre for River Restoration (ECRR) https://www.ecrr.org/ WWF RESTORIVER https://www.wwfadria.org/what_we_do/all_initiatives/restoriver/ DANUBE4all (EU) https://www.danube4allproject.eu/ REFORM (EU) https://www.reformrivers.eu/start.html

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
32	Agroforestry (integrating trees into farming)	Integrate Trees and shrubs into agricultural landscapes, combining crops or livestock with forest elements	6-8	ISBN : 978-93-58995-97-8 DOI:10.56201/ijaes.v10.no7.2024.pg94.121	EURAF (EU) https://euraf.net/ Agromix Project (EU) https://agromixproject.eu/about/ REFOREST (EU) https://agforeforest.eu/#-:text=Reforest%20s%20a%20Horizon%20Europe-funded%20project%20aimed%20at%20multiple%20objectives%3A%20food%20production%2C%20carbon%20capture%2C%20and%20biodiversity. FOREST4EU https://www.forest4eu.eu/
33	Erosion control (e.g. hedgerows, terracing)	Preventing soil erosion, especially on slopes or in areas with heavy rainfall, by stabilising the soil and reducing the impact of water and wind	8-9	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iswcr.2021.03.002 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228581261_A_review_of_the_effect_of_terracing_on_erosion	European Soil Bureau Network (EU) https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/soil-atlas-europe ECOSLOPES (EU) https://www.forestresearch.gov.uk/research/eco-engineering-and-conservation-of-slopes-ecoslopes/ Greenfix (UK) https://www.forestresearch.gov.uk/research/eco-engineering-and-conservation-of-slopes-ecoslopes/ SOLUTIONOMA (Spain) https://solutionoma.com/?utm_source=chatgpt.com

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
34	Restoration of natural carbon sinks (e.g. peatlands)	Process of rehabilitating ecosystems that store large amounts of carbon, such as peatlands, forests and wetlands, to improve their ability to capture and store carbon dioxide (CO ₂) from the atmosphere.	6-8	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.171218 https://carbonneutralbritain.org/blogs/news/the-power-of-peatlands-nature-s-hidden-carbon-sinks https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-022-00547-x	ICOS – Integrated Carbon Observation System (Finland) https://www.icos-cp.eu/ Landcare Europe (EU) https://www.landcare-europe.org/ NACAO (EU) https://www.interregeurope.eu/nacao CARBOREAL (Finland) https://www.interregeurope.eu/nacao
35	Biodiversity corridors and habitat connectivity	Creation or restoration of contiguous natural areas that allow wildlife to move freely between fragmented habitats	6-8	DOI:10.1177/0309133315598713 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeog.2023.103098	Natura Connect (EU) https://naturaconnect.eu/ Rewilding Europe (EU) https://rewilding-europe.com/ EURAC (EU) https://www.eurac.edu/en/institutes-centers/institute-for-regional-development/projects/eurobiocor Fondazione Capellino (EU) https://fondazionecapellino.org/en/eu-biodiversity-corridors

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
36	Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA)	Systematic method for decision-making when several, often contradictory criteria have to be taken into account	7-9	10.1007/s11269-018-1943-3 EU Floods directive https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-16-1019-2016	European Flood Awareness System (EU) https://www.copernicus.eu/en/european-flood-awareness-system Greece https://www.copernicus.eu/en/european-flood-awareness-system Germany https://doi.org/10.1007/978-90-481-9917-4_12 Kalypso (Germany) https://kalypso.bjoernsen.de/ Flood Modeller (UK) https://www.floodmodeller.com/ D-Sight (Belgium) https://www.d-sight.com/
37	Urban surface water flood modelling	Drainage network model (focus on urban stormwater drainage and the surface runoff process simulation by hydrological methods) Shallow-water-based model (development of computer and remote sensing technology → most widely used tool for urban flood risk management) Hydrogeomorphic approaches (inundation are is clearly recognisable by using terrain data analyses, which can only predict an approximate inundation are but cannot simulate the dynamik processes) Cellular automata models Artificial neural network models	6-9	https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-25-2843-2021	HydroAS (Hydrotec, Germany), commercial https://www.hydrotec.de/software/hydroas/ ITWH (Germany), commercial Urban Flash Floods https://itwh.de/en/software-products/desktop/urbane-sturzfluter/ TUFLOW (Australia), commercial https://www.tuflow.com/ Itzi (open source) https://www.itzi.org/?utm_source=chatgpt.com Flood4Cast (Belgium), commercial https://hydroscan.eu/en/flood4cast/
38	Biochar-augmented biofilters	Environmentally friendly filtration systems that use biochar (a special form of carbon produced by pyrolysis of organic materials) combination with biological filtration methods to purify water or wastewater	5-9	10.1039/d0ew00027b	Carboflex (Finland) https://carboflex.fi/ BIOCHAR (Poland) Biochar Europe sp. z o.o. (Polen) Soler group (France) https://soler-group.com/ Interreg (EU) https://www.interreurope.eu/good-practices/innovative-biochar-based-approaches-to-soil-regeneration-and-fertilisation
39	Model predictive control (MPC)	Method of process control that is used particularly in complex and dynamic systems → Rule-based control approach	7-8	10.1016/j.watres.2023.119825	Spain https://www.iti.upc.edu/publications/how/1255?utm_source=chatgpt.com France https://axa-research.org/funded-projects/dimate-environment/ensuring-water-security-under-climate-change-on-the-seine-river-multi-reservoir-multi-purpose-reservoir-management-by-use-of-model-predictive-control Netherlands, Italy https://www.politesi.polimi.it/handle/10589/188272 MIKE: DHI (Danish Hydraulic Institute): commercial DHI - We enable a sustainable future for water

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
40	Deep Learning (e.g. from Traffic Images, CCTV, etc.)	Recognising urban flooding from traffic surveillance cameras or CCTV using deep learning --> based on artificial neural networks (CNNs) automatically learning from image data	6-7	10.1007/s11269-023-03669-9	<p>FLORIA (France) https://www.camot-tsn.fr/en/detecter-les-inondations-grace-a-lintelligence-artificielle/</p> <p>DeepFlood (Sweden) https://www.digitalfutures.kth.se/p/roject/deepflood-enhancing-large-scale-flood-detection-and-mapping-using-polsar-metaheuristic-and-deep-learning-algorithms/</p> <p>STURM (EU, Luxemburg) https://sturm-weo.github.io/</p> <p>Kinesense (Ireland) https://www.kinesense-vca.com/</p> <p>Waterview (Italy) https://www.waterview.ai/products/click</p> <p>Noema (UK) https://noema.tech/flood/</p>

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
41	Deep Tunnel Sewer systems	Large-scale underground sewage systems	9	<p>https://library.ita-aies.org/view/1671-shaft-and-tunnel-construction-for-deep-sewer-systems.html</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2019.10.5011</p>	<p>Thames Tideway Tunnel (UK) https://www.thameswater.co.uk/about-us/projects/thames-tideway-tunnel</p> <p>Herrenknecht (Germany) https://www.herrenknecht.com/de/</p> <p>Ghella (Italy) https://ghella.com/en</p>
42	Satellite imagery, combined with machine learning methods	Effectively captures the spatio-temporal dynamics of groundwater-related flooding → Automated detection of flooding caused by groundwater Prompt response and early warning systems Support for urban planning, water management and crisis management	6-7	10.1016/j.jhydrol.2025.132907	<p>FLORIA (France) → Sentinel https://www.camot-tsn.fr/en/detecter-les-inondations-grace-a-lintelligence-artificielle/</p> <p>GFZ (Germany) https://www.gfz.de/en/press/newsdetail/s/artificial-intelligence-learns-continental-hydrology</p> <p>Vindien (UK) https://www.vindiengroup.com/expertise/satellite-mapping#1702591434-3769649131</p> <p>EU https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35093341/</p> <p>KEYE (Finland) https://www.keye.com/satellites https://geosat.space/blog/geosat-esas-third-party-missions-tpm/#-text=The%20Third-Party%20Missions%20%28TPM%29%20programme%20%28EarthNet%29%20consists%20of%20of%20organisations%20working%20%20of%20which%20GEO%20AT%20%20a%20part</p>

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
43	Integrated hydrological and hydrodynamic models	Combinations of simulation systems that realistically depict both the water cycle on land (hydrological) and the flow of water (hydrodynamic)	8-9	<p>https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2017.09.057</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2023.129515</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2024.131768</p>	<p>MIKE: DHI (Danish Hydraulic Institute): commercial https://www.dhigroup.com/</p> <p>Hydrotec (Germany, Austria) Commercial https://www.hydrotec.de/</p> <p>Nelen&Schuurmans (Netherlands, Germany): 3Di https://3diwatermanagement.com/</p> <p>GR-Consult (Austria) https://www.gr-consult.at/</p> <p>HydroLogic (Netherlands) https://www.hydrologic.com/?utm_source=chatgpt.com</p> <p>Syke (Finland) https://www.hydrologic.com/?utm_source=chatgpt.com</p> <p>SUMODEL (Turkey) https://sumodel.net/</p>

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
44	Combination of Human-Water Interaction (HWI) and Crowded Evacuation Models (CEW) → MASSEVAC (Mass Evacuation Model), EXODUS (by FSEG, University of Greenwich), FLOOD-ABM, etc.	Linked concepts that model the behaviour of people in interaction with water hazards.	5-9 (depending on the model type)	10.1016/j.jhydrol.2025.132876	<p>EXODUS (UK) https://fseg.gre.ac.uk/exodus/</p> <p>Flood-ABM https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=5180214</p> <p>https://github.com/uofgsimlab/flood_abm</p> <p>EGU https://hess.copernicus.org/articles/24/5329/2020/?utm_source=chatgpt.com</p> <p>FloodEvac (Germany) https://www.researchgate.net/publication/351176426/FloodEvac</p> <p>EvacuAid (Netherlands) https://www.researchgate.net/publication/351176426/FloodEvac</p> <p>Uppsala University – Centre of Natural Hazards and Disaster Science (CNDS) (Sweden) https://www.kau.se/en/cnds</p>

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
45	Social-Ecological-Technological systems (SETS)	Integrated systems that consider the interplay of social, ecological and technological components in order to develop sustainable solutions to complex, systemic challenges such as flooding, natural disasters, climate change or urbanisation. Especially in the context of water resource management, floods and urban planning, this approach is used to analyse the vulnerability and resilience of cities and societies.	7-8	10.1016/j.ecolind.2025.113334	<p>Stockholm Resilience Centre (Sweden) https://www.stockholmresilience.org/research/planetary-boundaries.html</p> <p>Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering (UK) https://www.imperial.ac.uk/civil-engineering/</p> <p>Wuppertal Institute (Germany) https://wupperinst.org/en/index/</p> <p>SDEWES (Croatia) https://www.sdewes.org/</p>

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
46	Interpretive Structural modelling (ISM), Cross-Impact Matrix Multiplication Applied to Classification (MICMAC)	Systemic modelling techniques that are primarily used to analyse complex causal relationships and dependencies in systems. They are useful for structuring complex problems and understanding the influences and relationships between different factors	6-9	10.1007/s00477-025-02960-y	<p>University of Greenwich (UK) https://fseg.gre.ac.uk/</p>
47	Combination of Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI), Modified Normalized Difference Water Index (MNDWI), and the Water Ratio Index (WRI) with Satellite	Remote sensing-based water indices that are based on spectral reflectance values and are calculated using satellite data (e.g. Landsat, Sentinel-2). They are used to recognise and delineate water areas, including in urban areas or in the event of flooding	9 (NDWI, MNDWI) 8 (WRI)	10.1007/s11273-025-10032-9	<p>Copernicus Emergency Management Service https://emergency.copernicus.eu/</p> <p>Lancaster University (UK) https://eprints.lancs.ac.uk/id/eprint/80036/?utm_source=chatgpt.com</p> <p>ESA Charter Mapper https://docs.disasterscharter.org/services/dinsar/service-specs/</p> <p>Creodias https://creodias.eu/cloud/cloudferro-cloud/</p> <p>Viridien (UK) https://www.viridiengroup.com/expertise/satellite-mapping#1702591434-3769649131</p>

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
48	Convection-permitting climate models (CPCMs), eg. COSMO-CLM, WRF (Weather Reserach and Forecasting Model), UKCP18, etc. → Very computationally intensive	Class of high-resolution climate models that are able to explicitly simulate deep convective processes (e.g. thunderstorms, heavy rain) - i.e. without having to resort to highly simplified approximations (so-called parameterisations), as is the case with classic climate models	7-8 10.1002/asl.1264	CMCC – COSMO-CLM (EU) https://www.cmcc.it/models/cosmo-clm-climate-limited-area-modelling-community#:~:text=COSMO-CLM%20it%20is%20the%20climate%20version%20of%20the%2028WD%29%20and%20then%20by%20the%20European%20consortium%20COSMO. Weather Research & Forecasting Model (WRF), opensource https://www.mmm.ucar.edu/models/wrf#:~:text=The%20Weather%20Research%20and%20Forecasting%20%28WRF%29%20Model%20is,for%20both%20atmospheric%20research%20and%20operational%20forecasting%20applications. UK Climate Projections (UKCP) https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/research/approach/collaboration/ukcp/index KNMI (Netherlands) https://www.knmi.nl/home Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum (Germany) https://www.dkrz.de/de

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
49	Convolutional neural network	Type of artificial neural network that is particularly well suited to processing image data, spatial structures and patterns. → Automatically recognisation of water areas from satellite images Detecting buildings or infrastructure affected by flooding	8-9 10.1002/asl.1264	DLR (Germany) https://elib.dlr.de/188078/ ISPRS (EU) https://elib.dlr.de/188078/ SEN12-FLOOD https://clmmb.github.io/SEN12-FLOOD/ PlanetLabs (Germany) https://www.planet.com/ Vizzuality (Spain) https://www.vizzuality.com/ SARMAP (Swiss) https://www.sarmap.ch/ E-Geos (Italy) https://www.e-geos.it/en/

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
50	Media Data Approach	Systematic analysis of media content (e.g. news articles, social media posts, photos, videos, reports) to gain information about natural events, social reactions, infrastructure damage or risk perception	7-8 6-7 Automated damage detection through social media 5-7 Integration in early warning systems with machine learning	10.1016/j.jhydrol.2024.131471 CMCC, ETC (European Topic Centre on Disaster and Risk Management (EU)) https://www.cmcc.it/projects/etcca-european-topic-centre-on-climate-change-impacts-vulnerability-and-adaptation#:~:text=The%20ETC%20CA%20assists%20the%20EEA%20in%20supporting%20EU,quality%20assessment%20and%20exchange%20of%20data%20and%20for%20informati. Sentinel Hub https://www.sentinel-hub.com/ CrisisMappers https://crisismapping.ning.com/ Vizzuality (Spain) https://www.vizzuality.com/

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
51	Bibliometric analysis	Quantitative analysis of scientific publications to gain insights into: Research trends, important topics, co-operation networks, influential authors, institutions or countries, as well as frequently used technologies and methods	9 Standard 7 Research strategy or policy advice 6-7 Automated, AI-supported bibliometrics	10.3390/rs16020350 10.1007/s10668-023-03094-3 University of Cambridge (UK) https://www.cam.ac.uk/ Fraunhofer INT https://www.int.fraunhofer.de/en.html Helmholtz Zentrum für Umweltforschung (Germany) https://www.ufz.de/ University Utrecht https://www.ufz.de/ FloodRisk II (Germany, EU) https://www.bmwi.gv.at/themen/verkehr/wasser/hochwasserschutz/publikationen/floodrisk.html

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
52	Random Forst Model	Machine learning method for classification, regression and feature selection. Flood risk classification (e.g. based on land use, slope, precipitation) Water quality forecasts Prediction of infrastructure failures in the event of natural disasters Fire or flood risk modelling based on geospatial data	7-9 10.1016/j.jhydrol.2018.01.044 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2015.06.008	ESA Copernicus → previous slides https://isprs-annals.copernicus.org/articles/X-4-W1-2022/201/2023/ https://nhess.copernicus.org/articles/21/807/2021/ Universität Freiburg (Germany) https://uni-freiburg.de/unir/fakultaet/institute/institut-fuer-umweltsozialwissenschaften-und-geographie/
Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
53	Hydrological-hydraulic modeling (e.g. InfoWorks ICM)	Combined technical approach to simulating water movements - both above and below the earth's surface - with the aim of realistically modelling and predicting natural and urban water cycles	6-9 10.3390/su131810259	InfoWorks ICM https://aquamod.eu/infoworks-icm-en.html https://www.autodesk.com/learn/onde-mand/curated/getting-started-with-infoworks-icm/4K7XDUIQEUtoZiDQCKvUnI7msoc?cid=332cid6a2652620b02cidc9e227f863e7 HR Wallingford (UK) https://www.hrwallingford.com/ Deltares (Netherlands) https://www.deltares.nl/en https://hydrosolutions.github.io/caham_book/hydraulic_hydrological_modeling.html#~:text=Hydrological,hydraulic%20models%20are%20used%20for%20different%20purposes%2C%20including,study%20of%20basin-scale%20climate%20impacts%20and%20their%20 repercussions. UK Gov https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/river-modelling-technical-standards-and-assessment/hydraulic-modelling-best-practice-model-approach WSP https://www.wsp.com/en-gl/services/hydrology-and-hydraulic-modelling
Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
54	Probability Distributed Moisture (PDM) model	Precipitation-runoff-based hydrological model used to simulate runoff formation in catchment areas → Storage capacity of the soil is modelled as a probability distribution	9 10.3390/su131810259	Deltares (Netherlands) https://www.deltares.nl/en/expertise/projects/mangrove-coasts-under-threat?utm_source=chatgpt.com UK Center for Ecology & Hydrology https://www.ceh.ac.uk/data/software-models/pdm-probability-distributed-model EGU (EU) https://nhess.copernicus.org/articles/11/483/2007/
55	Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar	Remote sensing-based method with which changes in the height of the earth's surface can be measured very precisely	9 https://doi.org/10.1117/1.JRS.19.021007 https://proceedings.spiedigitallibrary.org/journals/Journal-of-applied-remote-sensing/volume-19/issue-02/021007/Improved-urban-flood-detection-in-reeper-floods-using-synthetic-aperture/10.1117/1.JRS.19.021007.full#~:text=Detection%20of%20flooding%20in%20rural%20areas%20is%20now,to%20SAR%20shadow%2C%20a%20yover%2C%20and%20double%20scattering%20effects. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-022-05509-2 https://doi.org/10.1007/s11004-021-09948-8 https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0443-5	→ Slide with SAR ARSET (NASA, USA) https://appliedsciences.nasa.gov/get-involved/training/english/arset-disaster-assessment-using-synthetic-aperture-radar Copernicus ISPRS https://isprs-archives.copernicus.org/articles/XLII-4-W16/291/2019/ Capella Space (USA) https://www.capellaspace.com/blog/advancements-in-interferometric-synthetic-aperture-radar

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
56	Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM)	Powerful and efficient machine learning method is based on the concept of gradient boosting. It was specially developed to process large data sets with high speed and low memory consumption, while at the same time achieving high model accuracy	8-9	10.1007/s13753-023-00465-2	Copernicus Emergency Management Service (EMS): https://www.copernicus.eu/de/dienste/katastrophen-und-krisenmanagement Deltares (Netherlands) https://www.deltares.nl/en/expertise/projects/mangrove-coasts-under-threat?utm_source=chatgpt.com UltraLytics (Germany) https://www.ultralitics.com/de/glossary/lightgbm
57	Personal Computer Storm Water Management Model (PCSWMM)	Software solution for the hydrological and hydraulic modelling of rainwater runoff	6-8	10.1007/s13753-023-00465-2 https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-32556-x	Innovyze (UK) https://innovyze.com/products/stormwater-sewer-flood-modeling/xpswmm/ Marisa (USA) https://www.midatlanticrisa.org/data-tools/water-model/items/pcswmm.html#:~:text=Personal%20Computer%20Storm%20Water%20Management%20Model%20%28PCSWMM%29%20is,overflow%20mitigation%20%20water%20quality%20and%20integrated%20catchment%20analyses. CHI PCSWMM (Canada) https://www.pcswmm.com/ EPA (USA) https://www.epa.gov/water-research/storm-water-management-model-swmm

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
58	GPM (Global Precipitation Measurements)	Use of satellites for precipitation monitoring → Spatial and temporal resolution are not sufficient to monitor small to medium-sized urban areas	9	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-72583-3_7 https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.3313 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hydrol.2023.129124	NASA (US) https://gpm.nasa.gov/#:~:text=During%20the%2010-day%20period%20from%20Oct%2026%20through,over%20200%20fatalities%2C%20according%20to%20the%20Associated%20Press. https://gpm.nasa.gov/missions/GPM Copernicus → previous slides
59	Satellites: Cloud cover (as a proxy for propensity of urban precipitation, urban air quality (measuring the overall aerosol loading))	Satellites: Cloud cover (as a proxy for propensity of urban precipitation, urban air quality (measuring the overall aerosol loading))	6-9	https://doi.org/10.1016/S1352-2310(99)00159-4 https://doi.org/10.1038/s44284-024-00120-x https://doi.org/10.1002/2013RG000441	ESA Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring service https://atmosphere.copernicus.eu/ EUMETSAT https://atmosphere.copernicus.eu/

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
60	Networks of weather stations (incl. Mobile) to be representative → Private weather stations	Networks of weather stations, including mobile and private stations, enable the detailed and representative collection of weather data in different geographical regions. These networks extend traditional data collection with additional measuring stations and contribute to the improvement of weather forecasts and early warning systems.	7-9		OpenWeatherMap (https://openweathermap.org/stations) Sencrop https://sencrop.com/en/private-network/ The Weather Network https://www.theweathernetwork.com/en
61	Urban micro-climate data using sensors mounted on bicycles	Sensors on bicycles record mobile microclimate data such as temperature and air quality in urban areas. This enables flexible and cost-effective monitoring of the urban climate.	7-8	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112847 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/365682035_Validating_a_cycle-based_IoT_sensor_for_mapping_intra-urban_air_temperature_and_humidity	TomTom (Netherlands) https://www.tomtom.com/
62	Sensors in smart devices (Phones, wearables, etc.) → exponential rise in their use	Sensors in smart devices such as smartphones and wearables (e.g. smartwatches) measure various environmental influences and personal data. They can monitor movement, temperature, humidity, air quality, etc. to provide the user with real-time information or monitor the environment.	6-8	10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2986329 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iotcps.2023.04.005 https://blog.flux.id/en/iot-sensors-for-flood-monitoring-real-time-information/ https://connectedsensors.com/blog/smart-flood-sensors/	

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
63	Multi-city comparisons of UHI via satellite	8-9	DOI:10.1080/03736245.2014.924864 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2005.05.003 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2016.01.005	ESA → see previous slides
64	Urban modelling (observation-derived statistical Relationships, simplified bulk urban parameterizations, or slab urban models embedded in standard surface-layer schemes, etc.	4-6	DOI:10.1007/s00376-021-1371-9 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.str.2024.100181 https://doi.org/10.1002/2018JD028377	IAC (Swiss) https://iac.ethz.ch/ Hereon (Germany) https://www.hereon.de/ CMCC (EU) https://www.cmcc.it/lectures_conferences/advancing-urban-modelling-in-regional-atmospheric-models-insights-challenges-and-applications

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
65	Long-term urban observations → meteorology, air pollution, and biogeochemical cycles incl. all kind of sensors (fixed regional and moving, remote and in-situ)	7-9	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11783-016-0877-3 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2017.05.004	ICOS (EU) https://www.icos-cp.eu/ Deutscher Wetterdienst (Germany) https://www.dwd.de/DE/Home/home_node.html IPSL (France) https://www.ipsl.fr/ RIVM (Netherlands) https://www.rivm.nl/ ACTRIS (EU) https://www.actris.eu/

Several key urban processes and components, like urban hydrology and vegetation, and their interactions and feedbacks to urban weather and climate are still missing or simplistic in current models.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advwatres.2012.09.001>

<https://www.nature.com/articles/s43017-024-00599-x>

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
	Improving the description of urban landscapes and urban model parameters are important for mitigating urban modeling uncertainties. Developing or improving scale-aware urban parameterizations will also be helpful to more accurately predict urban impacts across scales. In the last few years, several attempts at incorporating vegetation and hydrology in urban canopy models have shown promising results		https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2017.10.006 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2021.100847	
	Systematic assessment of coupled models in extreme conditions (extreme heat, hurricane, extreme precipitation, etc.) is necessary		https://doi.org/10.1029/2024GL113021 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2025.106171	
66	Application of machine learning (ML) and data assimilation techniques → better understand the complexities of the urban environment	6-8	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocs.2021.101525 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2022.104050 https://geoscienceletters.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s40562-024-00347-5	Cordis – DANTE (EU) https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101115741 ML4Earth (Germany) https://ml4earth.de/research/ ESA – Gragon 5 https://gragon5.esa.int/projects/eo-aid-urban-earth-observation-big-data-and-deep-learning-for-sustainable-and-resilient-cities/?utm_source=chatgpt.com

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
	Advance the knowledge transfer between observations and urban modeling → Satellite observations can be particularly useful in this regard since they provide spatially continuous estimates of the radiative and thermodynamic properties of the urban surface, which are currently poorly constrained in models.		https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2024.105995 https://doi.org/10.1007/s41748-020-00193-3	

Nature-based solutions (NBS)

→ See previous slides green infrastructure

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
67	Unsupervised graph deep learning model	4-6	https://arxiv.org/abs/2309.14610 https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-32548-x DOI:10.2139/ssrn.4631611 https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-68857-y	TU Delft (Netherlands) https://research.tudelft.nl/en/publications/rapid-spatial-temporal-flood-modelling-via-hydraulics-based-graph-7utm_source=chatgpt.com EGU (EU) https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU21/EGU21-13375.html?utm_source=chatgpt.com

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
68	Time series analysis eitreihenanalyse (K-Means)	8-9	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nhres.2023.10.001 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2023.103329 10.1109/WISPNET54241.2022.9767102	TU Delft (Netherlands) https://research.tudelft.nl/en/publications/a-time-series-analysis-framework-for-the-flood-wave-method-to-est University Kiel (Germany) https://www.math.uni-kiel.de/stochastik/de/lehre-frueherer-semester/lehre-2019/nichtparametrische-statistik
69	Combination SAR + optical data	7-8 (automatisierte Analyse)	https://doi.org/10.1080/19475705.2025.2493225 https://doi.org/10.3390/w17020177 10.3390/rs12233980 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.srs.2025.100203 10.1109/IGARSS53475.2024.10641764	→ See previous slides Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CMS) DLR (TerraSAR-X & TanDEM-X) University of Twente (Netherlands) EUMETSAT
70	GeoDetector-Dematel	5-6	https://doi.org/10.3390/w16182636 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.120308 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2022.104138	→ See previous slides ESRI HR Wallingford DHI Group
71	GNSS-R (Reflectometry)	6-7	10.1109/LGRS.2022.3161409 https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12040614 10.1109/LGRS.2024.3417426	CORDIS (EU) https://cordis.europa.eu/article/d/202830-using-gnss-reflectometry-to-map-soil-moisture MAGDA (Italy) https://www.magdaproject.eu/knowledge/soil-moisture-estimation-using-ground-based-gnss-reflectometry-a-magda-implementation-by-gre/
72	Hyperspektral-/LIDAR-remote sensing	Highest accuracy in atmospheric particle analysis and urban topography	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arconrol.2021.03.003 https://doi.org/10.1016/C2018-0-01850-2	→ See previous slides DLR (Germany) Fraunhofer (Germany) Airbus (France) TNO (Netherlands) https://www.tno.nl/nl/ Teledyne (UK) https://www.teledyneoptech.com/
73	Machine Learning for precipitation forecasts	AI-supported modelling of heavy rainfall & flooding based on atmospheric data	https://doi.org/10.1007/s12524-025-02143-w https://doi.org/10.1016/j.grets.2024.100104 https://doi.org/10.1038/s41612-023-00388-1	Ruhr West University of Applied Sciences, Germany https://ethz.ch/content/dam/ethz/special-interest/conference-websites-gam/urbanrain/gam/papers/UrbanRain23_ABSTRACT_KoellermannSilva.pdf ECMWF (EU) https://www.ecmwf.int/ Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CMS), EU → previous slide KIT (Germany) https://www.kit.edu/english/
74	Data Fusion / Multi-Source-Integration	Combination of weather, soil and urban infrastructure data for risk modelling	https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20032528 https://ink.springer.com/article/10.1007/s40808-024-02223-9 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2024.109173 10.3390/ijerph20032528 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.147842	Department of Engineering and Geology (InGeo), University (Italy) https://www.ingeo.unich.it/home-ingeo-12729 University of Iceland https://english.hi.is/ EGU (EU) https://soil.copernicus.org/articles/5/107/2019/ TECHGEO Mapping https://techgeo.org/geoai-multi-source-fusion/

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
75	Atmosphere-hydrology coupling	Model integration of weather (rain, storm) with water flow models	6-8	https://doi.org/10.1029/2023JD040335 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosres.2019.03.029 https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-014-1204-6 <a href="https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0450(2000)039<0931:CARHMF>2.0.CO;2">https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0450(2000)039<0931:CARHMF>2.0.CO;2 https://doi.org/10.3390/su15032803	EGU (EU) https://hess.copernicus.org/articles/24/7457/2020/ WRF-Hydro® Modeling System https://ral.ucar.edu/projects/wrf-hydro PIK (Germany) https://www.pik-potsdam.de/en HR Wallingford (UK) → previous slide DHI Group (Denmark) → previous slide https://www.dhigroup.com/de KIT (Germany) See previous slide

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
76	Edge AI for local sensor processing	Data processing directly on the device where the data is generated - e.g. weather station, rain gauge, water level sensor with Local analysis of the data with machine learning/deep learning models without first sending the data to a central cloud.	4-5	https://doi.org/10.3390/s20216076 https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-69904-2_32 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measen.2023.101013	IABAC https://iabac.org/blog/data-engineering-for-internet-of-things-iiot-managing-sensor-data-at-scale TNO Fraunhofer University of Cambridge

77	Quantum Weather Modeling	Simulation of complex, non-linear processes in the atmosphere using quantum computers	2-3	https://arxiv.org/abs/2503.23408 https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-22-0031.1 https://www.heymeanalytics.com/blog/quantum-computing-5/next-gen-quantum-algorithms-for-climate-modeling-501 https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-73350-5_8 https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-443-21905-4.00012-2 https://arxiv.org/abs/2404.08737 https://quantumcomputingreport.com/quantum-for-ai-weather-forecasting-are-we-there-yet/ https://www.bmcoder.com/the-future-of-quantum-computing-in-weather-forecasting-and-climate-modeling	First steps: IBM (USA, UK) https://www.ibm.com/quantum D-WAVE (Canada) https://www.dwavequantum.com/ TU Delft (Netherlands) https://www.tudelft.nl/over-tu-delft/strategie/vision-teams/quantum-computing/impact/weather-forecasting-an-unexplored-field-for-quantum-computing Pasqal https://www.pasqal.com/newsroom/potential-of-quantum-scientific-machine-learning-applied-to-weather-modeling/ https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2024PhRvA.110e2423J/abstract
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Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
77	Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP)	Technique to model and predict the magnitude of flood risk areas	Is not a technology in the classical sense ~ 7	Expert Choice Software
78	Urban Flood Risk Index (UFRI)	Index determined by the degree of vulnerability and exposure	4-7	GEOTERRA IMAGE
79	TOPSIS	Decision-making tool for urban flood vulnerability analysis, based on socio-economic factors such as building density, population density, building history, and socio-economic conditions	7-8	Siemens
80	Surface Flood Control Model (SFCM)	Model to assess storm events, detect drainage outlets hindered by high river network water levels during extreme rainfall, and evaluate how river backflow affects drainage overflow and surface flooding	6-8	Flowsolve, Bentley Systems, FEMA
81	Flood Source Area (FSA) Identification	New approach for FSA identification in complex urban flood models using interpretable deep learning (IDL). Deep Convolutional Neural Networks (DCNNs) and Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping (GradCAM) were used to develop a surrogate model for the Distributed Hydrodynamic Model for Urban (DHM Urban), which includes a rain-on-grid overland flow mechanism	6-8	DataVerify, FloodMapp
82	Neighborhood-scale InfoWorks ICM model	Model to analyze the full-process impacts of urban flooding under six rainfall return periods	9	Autodesk

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
84	GEOBIA approach to tree-canopy mapping	Tree-canopy mapping that relies on existing public investments in LiDAR, multispectral imagery, and thematic GIS layers	6-8	Trimble eCognition, L3Harris Geospatial ENVI, Esri ArcGIS Pro, PCI Geomatics Geomatica
85	Groundwater-city classification	Classification of relationships between cities and underlying groundwater	5-7	https://www.academia.edu/99635630/Opening_up_the_subsurface_for_the_cities_of_tomorrow_considering_access_to_subsurface_knowledge_Evaluation_of_practices_and_techniques?utm_source=chatgpt.com HPC AG, iFLUX, National Ground Water Association (NGWA)
86	Drought-related Nature-Based Solutions (NBS)	Effective solutions to cope with the future impacts of drought events	6-8	RSK Group
87	Multiple Regression Model	Model applied to predict possible future urban water demand	9	John Galt Solutions
88	New hydro-economic model	Model based on system dynamics and agent-based simulation to enhance the sustainability of urban groundwater	5-7 (more indepth study is necessary)	IIASA
89	Monte Carlo Simulations	To find the set of conditions in the future for which water demand is predicted	9	GoldSim, Lumivero, Cambridge Water

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
90	Multi-city comparisons of UHI via satellite	Multi-city comparisons of UHI via satellite refers to the use of satellite data to compare the urban heat island (UHI) phenomenon in different cities. Satellites measure surface temperatures and provide high-resolution data on temperature differences between urban and rural areas. By comparing multiple cities, researchers can better understand the intensity and distribution of UHI to analyse the implications for urban planning and climate adaptation strategies.	8-9	DOI:10.1080/03736245.2014.924864 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ag.2005.05.003 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2016.01.005 Arup (developer of Uheat), Cleantech Group https://www.urbanheatislands.com/external-links lists mitigation initiatives
91	Resilience Index for Urban Drainage Systems	Single metric which combines the failure magnitude and duration	6-7	Tools and models using this index: SWMM, GIS-based analysis
92	Evapotranspiration (ETo) model	Model for small-scale outdoor irrigation to support water and vegetation management in semi-arid urban households	9	University of Patras, Greece
93	Regional Climate Model (RegCM)	Model for dynamic/meteorological forecasting	7-8	IBM, CORDEX

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
94	ALOS-2	ALOS was launched in January 2006 and its main mission was to collect data for topographic mapping, regional observation, disaster monitoring, and resource investigation. The satellite carried three instruments: the Panchromatic Remote-sensing Instrument of Stereo Mapping (PRISM) for creating accurate topographic maps, the Advanced Visible and Near Infrared Radiometer type 2 (AVNIR-2) for observing land and coastal regions, and the Phased Array type L-band Synthetic Aperture Radar (PALSAR) for observation during the day and at night, as well as in all weather conditions. The ALOS mission officially ended in May 2011, and ALOS-2 was launched in May 2014 to continue the work of the original satellite.	9	http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/rs161630059
95	SPOT	SPOT (French: Satellite Pour l'Observation de la Terre,[1] lit. "Satellite for observation of Earth") is a commercial high-resolution optical Earth observation satellite system operating from space. It is run by Spot Image, based in Toulouse, France. It was initiated by the CNES (Centre national d'études spatiales – the French space agency) in the 1970s and was developed in association with the STC (Belgian scientific, technical and cultural services) and the Swedish National Space Board (SNSB).	9	http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/rs161630059 CNES (FR) Airbus Defence and Space (USA)
96	high-resolution commercial satellites (e.g., QuickBird, WorldView, GeoEye-1, IKONOS)	GeoEye-1: Provides high-resolution images (up to 0.41m resolution) WorldView-3: Offers extremely high resolution imagery (up to 0.31m) Pleiades 1A & 1B: Supplies high-resolution images (up to 0.5m) QuickBird: Delivers fairly high-resolution images (up to 0.61m) IKONOS: Can provide images with up to 0.82m resolution.	9	http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/rs161630059 Maxar Technologies (USA) Airbus Defence and Space (USA)

	Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
97	Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost)	XGBoost (eXtreme Gradient Boosting) is an open-source software library which provides a regularizing gradient boosting framework for C++, Java, Python, R, Julia, Perl, and Scala. It works on Linux, Microsoft Windows, and macOS. From the project description, it aims to provide a "Scalable, Portable and Distributed Gradient Boosting (GBM, GBRT, GBDT) Library". It runs on a single machine, as well as the distributed processing frameworks Apache Hadoop, Apache Spark, Apache Flink, and Dask.	9 and ongoing research	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.puhe.2024.11.013	Open Source
98	SHAP Algorithm	For example, Chubin et al. used support vector machines, artificial neural networks and XGBoost to assess the risk of ruptured cerebral aneurysms and applied SHAP algorithm analysis to improve the explainability of the machine learning model; the results showed that SHAP analysis can effectively improve machine learning transparency.	9 and ongoing research	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jenman.2023.117357	Open Source
99	Logistic Regression	Logistic Regression is one of the ten most popular ML algorithms, initially borrowed from the field of statistics. LR is named after its core function, the logistic function (also known as sigmoid function). LR is a parametric model (i.e., with a finite number of parameters) and is commonly used for classification problems in order to predict solutions based on the concept of probability.	9 and ongoing research	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.earscrev.2020.103225	Open Source
100	Artificial Neural Network	An Artificial Neural Network (NNET) is a "black-box model" defined according to Garrett (1994) as a "computational mechanism able to acquire, represent, and compute a mapping from one multivariate space of information to another, given a set of data representing that mapping". Artificial Neural networks are inspired by the human brain, which is adept at recognizing patterns. Neural network models are mostly composed of simple circuits of neurons or nodes that are connected each other.	9 and ongoing research	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.earscrev.2020.103225	Open Source
101	Support Vector Machine	Support Vector Machine is a non-parametric supervised ML algorithm that uses mathematical tools for solving non-linear solutions to classification and regression problems. Unlike the loose analogies that found in neural networks, SVM's are based on statistical learning theory developed by Cortes and Vapnik (1995). The desired output in SVM models are achieved by transforming the input data into a high-dimensional space, using kernel tricks (functions), then trained and brought back into the 2-Dimensional space	9 and ongoing research	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.earscrev.2020.103225	Open Source

	Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
102	Extremely Randomized Trees	Extremely Randomized Trees models are an ensemble learning method built in the same platform as DT models. In EXT, "the randomness goes one step further in the way splits are computed". Like RF, EXT randomizes some decisions and subsets the data to curtail overlearning and overfitting. This results in building several trees and splitting the nodes using a random subsets, but differently as shown in RF: there is no bootstrapping (i.e. EXT samples without replacement), and nodes are split randomly, not according to quality.	9 and ongoing research	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.earscrev.2020.103225	Open Source
103	Naive Bayes	Naive Bayes one the simplest form of Bayesian model are defined as "supervised probabilistic machine learning algorithms built on applying Bayes theorem with the 'naive' assumption of conditional independence between every pair of features given the value of the class variable". According to Bayes Rule, given class variable y and dependent feature vector x1 through xn Eq.	9 and ongoing research	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.earscrev.2020.103225	Open Source
104	Linear and Quadratic Discriminant Analysis	Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) and Quadratic Discriminant Analysis (QDA) are two classic ML models which have recently been used in a variety of fields including landslide susceptibility mapping. In binary or multi-class problems, discriminant analysis (DA) is applied to understand which conditioning factor discriminates better between two or more naturally occurring groups.	9 and ongoing research	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.earscrev.2020.103225	Open Source
105	K-Nearest Neighbors	k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) is among the simplest of all ML algorithms, and has recently been used in a variety of fields including landslide susceptibility mapping. Essentially, in KNN the input consists of the k closest training instance in the feature space.	9 and ongoing research	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.earscrev.2020.103225	Open Source
106	Gradient Boosting algorithms	Gradient Boosting (GB) is a framework that uses a tree-based learning algorithm, similar to RF and EXT models, and is an ensemble of Weak Learners (WL). WL are learning algorithms capable of producing classifiers with a probability of error strictly (but only slightly) less than that of random guessing, i.e. 0.5, in the binary case), and include classification and regression trees (i.e. decision trees).	9 and ongoing research	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.earscrev.2020.103225	Open Source

	Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
107	Adaptive network-based fuzzy inference system (ANFIS)	An adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system or adaptive network-based fuzzy inference system (ANFIS) is a kind of artificial neural network that is based on Takagi-Sugeno fuzzy inference system. The technique was developed in the early 1990s. Since it integrates both neural networks and fuzzy logic principles, it has potential to capture the benefits of both in a single framework.	9 and ongoing research	http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/and11060884	Open Source
108	Four-dimensional Variational Doppler Radar Analysis System (VDRAS)	VDRAS relies on data assimilation, a technique for combining real-world observations and computer model output to create a more accurate forecast. VDRAS has a very fast update cycle, providing new data from real-time radar and other sources for assimilation every 6–12 minutes. The mathematical technique it relies on, called 4DVar (Four-Dimensional Variational), is the gold standard for the field of data assimilation. The system uses freely available observations from the National Weather Service's Doppler radar network, so it can be run anywhere in the country without requiring new and costly instrumentation.	9 and ongoing research	http://dx.doi.org/10.1029/2021JD034839	NSF National Center for Atmospheric Research National Center for Atmospheric Research
109	fuzzy and analytic hierarchy process (AHP)	The analytic hierarchy process (AHP) introduced by Thomas Saaty (1980) is a modern tool for dealing with complex decision-making and may help the decision maker to set priorities to make the best decision. Due to its simplicity, ease of use, and great flexibility, the AHP has been studied extensively and used in nearly all applications related to multiple criteria decision-making (MCDM) since its development. Besides being applied to the finance actor, the AHP has been adopted in education; engineering; government; industry; management; manufacturing; personal, political, and social systems; and sports.	9 and ongoing research	http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/rs16071200	

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
110	hillslope-link model (HLM)	9	http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/atmos1108-0774	Hydroinformatics Lab at UIOWA - UIHILab
111	hydrologic model Vflo	9	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosres.2016.06.009	Vflo@Distributed Hydrologic Model - Vieux & Associates
112	semi-distributed HBV-light (a recent version of Hydrologiska Byråns Vattenbalansavdelning model)	9	http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/app111149-research01	research
113	Nash-Sutcliffe-Effizienzindex	9	http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/app111149-01	Open Source

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
114	XPSWMM	9	http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/w14233836	Autodesk XPSWMM Stormwater & Wastewater Management Software Firma XP Solutions
115	USGS's MODFLOW One-Water Hydrologic Model	9	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2019.105717	MODFLOW One-Water Hydrologic Flow Model (MF-OWHM) U.S. Geological Survey
116	Crop growth models (CGMs)	9	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2019.105717	AgriLogicAI (CA) Deere&Company (John Deere) (USA) APSIM (Agricultural Production Systems Simulator)
117	S-band (NEXRAD/88D)	9	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosres.2016.06.009	NEXRAD (USA)
118	Collaborative Adaptive Sensing of the Atmosphere (CASA)	9	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosres.2016.06.009	CASA (USA)

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
119	Remotely sensed thermal infrared imagery	8-9	High-Resolution Satellite Imagery Solutions for Precision Projects	SatVu (UK) Albedo (USA) Lytro (FR) OroraTech (DE) L3Harris (USA) EarthDaily (CA/USA) NASA/USGS Hydrosat (USA) GEOSAT (PR)
120	Analyzing Satellite Data for Plant health and needs (for Example Landsat data to quantify the strength and timescales of vegetation responses to interannual variability in drought status)	8?	Vegetation Stress Monitor	Companies providing similar services: Planet (USA) Vegetation Stress Monitor (DE) VITO Remote Sensing (BE) Sinergise (SI) Kayrros (FR)
121	High-precision Versatile Ecosphere (HIVE) (+LiSR)	7-8	HIVE InCube / constellr	Constellr (DE)

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
122	Microwave-based Soil Moisture	For Example used in Study 6. More info: Soil moisture estimation with microwave remote sensing 1 , and Soil moisture estimation with microwave remote sensing 2	9	6	EOSDA (USA/JA) Saire (USA) Copernicus (ESA) Balamis (ES)
123	Estimating (maize) root zone soil moisture -> WOFOST-HYDRUS Model	"couple crop and hydrology models through daily dynamic parameter transfers to estimate the RZSM per centimeter throughout the crop growing season.". Combines the two Models WOFOST and HYDRUS	3-5	4	Mostly Scientific Model, but potentially usable for new products. WOFOST Model from Wageningen Environmental Research (NL)
124	Copula model integrating atmospheric moisture demand and supply for vegetation vulnerability mapping	"A copula-based bivariate joint probability model to investigate the effects of various aspects of meteorological drought on vegetation (vegetation drought)." – Using MODIS Satellite Data.	4-5	A4	Mostly Research, referenced Study from Korea
125	GMIE: Global Maximum Irrigation Extent dataset	Provides high-resolution (100 m) map of irrigated croplands, on a global level (about 23.4% of global cropland). The dataset was created by using deep learning methods and satellite data to assess irrigation performance during drought stress periods.	6-7	12	Research Model
126	Downscaling Soil moisture products.	Integrating Moderate-Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) optical and SAR data, using machine learning. The Platform used was the Google Earth Engine (GEE). The result was a downscaling from 10 km to 1 km and 100 m.	4-6	13	Current Research
127	DIRECTORS model	A reference evapotranspiration (ETref) prediction model based on pattern mining. The goal is to offer easier and more accurate predictions.	3-5	10	Research Model
Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
128	Surface soil moisture (SSM) using multiple sources	In Study from Reference 5 (Spatiotemporal continuous Surface Soil Moisture): Generated through data fusion and random forest models, as well as remote sensing, reanalysis, and in situ data, resolution at 30 m x 30 m.	4-5		Farmers Edge (CA) GeoVista (AT) HydroLogic (NL) EUMETSAT Copernicus
129	German drought monitor	Provides daily maps showing current drought status in Germany. Focus: Soil moisture anomalies, down to 1,8m. Started in 2014. Partly based on satellite data.	9	German drought monitor	Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ (DE)
130	Priestley-Taylor Jet Propulsion Laboratory (PTJPL) model for estimating Evapotranspiration (ET) combined with moisture divergence index (SMDI) and microwave-based SM	"Our results illustrate that the incorporation of the SWIR-based soil moisture divergence index (SMDI) and microwave-based SM into monthly soil evaporation led to 6% and 5% increase in explained ET variances and reduced RMSE by 23.2% and 13.1% for cropland and grassland, respectively, as compared to PT-JPL using atmospheric reanalysis data only."	5-6		University of Twente (NL) -> Research model
131	SEBAL (Surface Energy Balance Algorithm for Land)	One of the important models of the hydrological cycle, measuring evapotranspiration, biomass growth, water deficit and soil moisture. Satellite data is the basis of the algorithm.	9		Using SEBAL: eEAF (NL) WaterWatch (NL) LandMOD ET Mapper
132	Measuring Human Influence on Hydrological Drought, using the PCR-GLOBWB model	"How human activities have altered hydrological droughts (streamflow deficits) in China during the past five decades (1961-2016) is investigated using the latest version (v2.0) of PCR-GLOBWB model at high spatial resolution (similar to 10 km)."	4-6		Utrecht University (NL) -> Mostly research model
Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
133	(In)SAR, Persistent Scattered Interferometry Synthetic Aperture Radar (PS-InSAR),	Changes/Deformations of Ground water Reservoirs etc. to monitor land surface deformation, subsidence and to assess relationships with groundwater levels, Remote Sensing & satellite data	9	https://doi.org/10.1002/2017J014676 https://www.georesearch.ac.at/en/areas/research/research-projects/project-hydrosar/p23_hartmeyer.pdf https://radar.theicircularlab.com/empesa/detekta/ 10.5194/sprsr-archives-XLIII-B3-2022-277-2022 https://doi.org/10.2166/nh.2019.030	Tre Altamira (SPMT) Projekt HydroSAR, u.a. AUGMENTERRA GmbH Detektia (EyeRADAR) European Space Agency (ESA) Gamma Remote Sensing Esri Partner
134	ClearSky	Product from Aspia Space: AI algorithm, able to provide hyperspectral data, independent of weather conditions. -> Not use-case specific.	6-8	https://aspiaspace.com/	Aspia Space (UK)
135	Triggering SAR acquisitions based on flood forecasts	System that is able to trigger the SAR acquisitions based on flood forecasts and to take advantage of the various satellite SAR sensors that are presently operating. On behalf of the Italian Civil Protection Department (DPC), a prototype of this kind of system has been setup and preliminary tested, using COSMO-SkyMed (CSK) and Sentinel-1 (S-1) data.	5-7	4	Many of the players above apparently have corresponding systems
136	DeepLab - image-based flood segmentation system	The system uses a deep learning algorithm which to detects and segments floods. The neural network was trained using satellite images and some ground data.	5-6	10	Research Model
Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
137	PERSIANN-CCS (Precipitation Estimation from Remotely Sensed Information using Artificial Neural Networks-Cloud Classification System) -> Model for hourly Validation	Satellite precipitation products such as PERSIANN-CCS (Precipitation Estimation from Remotely Sensed Information using Artificial Neural Networks-Cloud Classification System) could be used to complement the automatic rain gauge networks and so help solve this problem. However, the PERSIANN-CCS product has only recently become available, so its operational validity for areas such as south-eastern Spain is not yet known. In this work, a methodology for the hourly validation of PERSIANN-CCS is presented.	6-7	M1	Center for Hydrometeorology and Remote Sensing (USA) -> Research Model
138	Deep Reinforcement Learning for Multi-Objective Real-Time Pump Operation in Rainwater Pumping Stations	Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL)-based method to optimize real-time pump operations at rainwater pumping stations. Aiming to prevent flooding while also minimizing pump wear and maintenance costs by reducing the number of on/off switches. The method uses observable data (e.g., rainfall, inflow, basin level).	5	9	Mostly Research Topic
139	Real-time dynamic inundation risk assessment approach on paddy fields during typhoons	Very specific approach for typhoon flooding, using satellite data and AI-based forecasts.	4-6	8	Research
140	Hybrid framework for reservoir inflow forecast	Integrating new quasi-globally available observation-, satellite-, or model-based datasets using machine learning models to forecast inflow at the local scale	5-6	6	AFRY (SE) HYDROGRID (AT) GoldSim (USA)

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
141	Combination Gravity Recovery And Climate Experiment (GRACE) satellite data and the higher order (fourth order cumulant) statistical independent component analysis (ICA) method	5	3 + GRACE	NASA (GRACE)
142	Precipitation Measurement	9	https://gpm.nasa.gov/	NASA/JAXA (similar services from other agencies) Climavision (USA) Spire.(USA)
143	Hydrological Models -> Forecast of Flood Spread etc.	5-7	Vflo	Vflo
144	Thermal Satellite Imagery for e.g. Water Table Depth Monitoring	6-7 (water table depth monitoring)	http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/rs12121980	US Geological Survey (USGS) USGS – MODFLOW and Related Programs U.S. Geological Survey
145	UAV based monitoring	8-9	http://dx.doi.org/10.20944/preprints202401.0819.v1	DJI ScienceDirect – DJI delivers UAVs (e.g. Phantom 4 Pro RTK) for divers sensor integration. Black Swift Technologies Black Swift F2™ UAS - Black Swift Technologies
Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
146	UAV photo gammetry	9		Pix4D ScienceDirect(MDPI) – Pix4D provides software to evaluate UAV-photogrammetry data
147	Sensor networks and IoT	7-9 (for the purpose in this project)		Libelum Comunicaciones Distribuidas 5 L Water Management in Green Areas - Libelum
148	Predictive modelling of groundwater levels, peatfires, risks of flood/drought	6-7		Deltares 1st high-resolution, time-dependent groundwater model Deltares
149	Groundwater Flow patterns using numerical modelling	5-7		USGS ModFlow Software - MODFLOW U.S. Geological Survey
150	Decision Support Tools for urban nature based solutions (using Multi objective optimization)	8-9	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.123380	Vrije Universiteit, Univ Montpellier, Univ of Bordeaux, Sabom
151	Deep learning enhanced optimization algorithms (e.g. genetic algorithm)	5-7	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asr.2024.03.033	IUBAT Dhaka, Kunsan National University, Ghulam Ishaq Khan Institute
152	Shallow groundwater level prediction	7-9	Machine learning for predicting shallow groundwater levels in urban areas - GEUS' publications	Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland (GEUS), Univ Copenhagen, KU Leuven, Thünen Inst.
Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers
153	nonlinear autoregressive modeling approach with exogenous input (NARX) neural networks for modeling groundwater level fluctuation	Tbd		MATLAB Toolbox Design Time Series NARX Feedback Neural Networks - MATLAB & Simulink
154	Water Table Depth Estimation using ENVISAT Advanced Synthetic Aperture Radar (ASAR) C-band backscatter	6-7	https://doi.org/10.3390/rs10040536	ESA Envisat Data - Earth Online KU Leuven, Thünen Institute of Climate-Smart Agriculture
155	Soil monitoring IoT e.g. Plant Spike: A Low-Cost, Low-Power Beacon for Smart City Soil Health Monitoring	>=7	Plant Spike: A Low-Cost, Low-Power Beacon for Smart City Soil Health Monitoring IEEE Journals & Magazine IEEE Xplore	Columbia Univ
156	Capacitance Sensors for Soil Moisture Monitoring in urban soils	9	An Investigation of the Accuracy of EC5 and STE Capacitance Sensors for Soil Moisture Monitoring in Urban Soils: Laboratory and Field Calibration	capacitance sensors EC5 and STE, TEROS (METER Group)
157	Evaluation of soil pH and soil moisture with different field sensors: Case study urban soil	7-8		Hanna Instruments Deutschland ph-/soil moisture sensors

Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
158	Land Surface Temperature-Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (LST-NDVI)	The triangle method based on LST-NDVI scatterplot analysis is a promising tool for establishing moisture conditions over urban areas	8-9	http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/f14030578	Warsaw Univ Technol, Fac Bldg Serv Hydro & Environm Engrn, Nowowiejska St, PL-00653 Warsaw, Poland
159	UAV optical data for soil moisture quantification using partial least square regression		6-7	http://dx.doi.org/10.20944/preprints202401.0819.v1	MicaSense Altum Camera Comparison of MicaSense Cameras – MicaSense Knowledge Base
160	LoRa IoT	Connecting ground sensors piezometer via IoT to implement adapted canadian fire weather index to tropical peatlands	8-9	L. Li et al., "Estimation of Ground Water Level (GWL) for Tropical Peatland Forest Using Machine Learning," in IEEE Access, vol. 10, pp. 126180-126187, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3225906.	Semtech LoRa and LoRaWAN Integrated Into Water Monitoring System Semtech
161	Shallow water model (SWM)		7-9	10.1016/j.jhydrol.2018.07.069	HI Water & Environment AS MIKE SHE Integrated Hydrological Modeling Software
162	decision-making multi-objective optimization framework	regionally locating and sizing low impact development-best management practices (LID-BMPs) for green infrastructure, Optimizing low impact development techniques to fight urban runoff	4-6	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2025.133044 https://doi.org/10.1155/2024/9480522	Western Sydney Univ, Univ of Techn. Sydney London Imperial College: Overview of Deep Learning Applications in Groundwater Level Modeling
Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
163	Active Stormwater Control	swmm_mpc, software developed for simulating model predictive control (MPC) for urban drainage systems using open source software (Python and the EPA Stormwater Management Model version 5 (SWMM5))	~4-6	10.1016/j.envsoft.2019.07.009	University of Virginia, Univ of Cairo
164	Surrogate machine learning	Replicating SWMM with high computational efficiency enables real-time prediction updates crucial for emergency response planning and flood management strategies	(6-7) → more indepth analyses necessary	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2025.106277	University of Alabama Tuscaloosa
165	UAS thermal mapping	Sensors	7-8	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2024.112587	DJI UAVs (z. B. Matrice 300) mit Zenmuse-Thermokameras für thermale Kartierungen. Charles University, Czech Academy of Sciences
166	Land Subsidence Forecasting using advanced machine learning	e.g. eXtreme Gradient Boosting Regressor (XGBR), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)	5-6	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvma.2024.120078	Central South University, Hunan Key Laboratory of Nonferrous Resources and Geological Hazards Exploration (Changsha); Guangdong Geological Bureau, CIRAD
167	Low-Cost, High-Resolution Camera System for Measuring Peat Subsidence and Water Table Dynamics	The stool and camera thus moved with the peat surface, and took photographs of the meter ruler on the fixed subsidence pole	9	http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2021.630752	Wingscapes TimelapseCam Pro https://wingscapes.com.au/product/wingscapes-timelapsecam-pro/
Technology	Short description	TRL estimation	Referenz	Relevant Actors/Suppliers	
168	Soil-Moisture Sensors	irrigation treatments based on different soil moisture -based thresholds to reduce water demand	9	Univ of California Riverside http://rix.doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2024.108906	Acclima Inc. Idaho, USA TDT sensors, Acclima CS3500 smart irrigation controller https://acclima.com/digital-tdr-soil-moisture-sensors/?srsltid=AfmBOoQKmAoRkDqhaeWz29HhjmajDx4NzFoie7a5JfXmKtEjB65
169	Optimizing Vegetation Health Assessment With UAS NVDI	For green space maintenance and sustainable city planning	9	http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/GARSS53475.2024.10641824	Warsaw University of Life Science SZ DJI Technology Co., Ltd. https://www.dji.com/de/support/product/phantom-4-rtk
170	Evapotranspiration mapping using sentinel-1 data with Random Forest Regression	To optimize the trade-off between urban greening and water security, reliable and up-to-date maps of ET for cities are urgently needed	6-7	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2023.113487	Free Univ of Berlin, Tech Univ Berlin, Univ Aberdeen, Leibniz Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries, Humboldt Univ Berlin
171	Optical TRapezoid Model (OPTRAM), Thermal-Optical TRapezoid Models	Models to derive soil moisture indices using Landsat imagery	5-6	http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/rs12121980	Univ Leuven
172	Water Table Depth Estimation	Peatland water table depth (WTD) and wetness have widely been monitored with optical and synthetic aperture radar (SAR) remote sensing	7-8	http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2021.630752 http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/rs12121980 http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/rs12101566 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2020.111805 http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2022.102866 http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/rs11141659	KU Leuven Natural Resources Institute Finland University of Tartu United Kingdom Centre for Ecology and Hydrology University of Palangka Raya

Remarks on some of the identified technologies

The following section contains some important remarks on some of the technologies identified.

Technology Earth Observation & Satellite Remote Sensing	Remark
Sentinel, Landsat, MODIS, VIIRS	Sentinel spatial resolution may not be fine enough for detailed assessments in densely built-up areas. Landsat satellites provide high-resolution optical imagery, but their revisit time is approximately 16 days. This interval may result in outdated data during rapidly evolving flood events. MODIS provides global coverage but at a spatial resolution of approximately 250 meters. This resolution may not capture fine-scale flood details, especially in urban areas with complex topography. Additionally, cloud cover can hinder optical observations, affecting the accuracy of flood detection. Similar to MODIS, VIIRS offers global coverage with a spatial resolution of around 375 meters. While it provides valuable data, the resolution may be insufficient for detailed flood monitoring in certain regions.
SAR, InSAR, PS-InSAR, GNSS-R	Sentinel-1's Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) can penetrate cloud cover, making it valuable for flood monitoring. However, its spatial resolution may not be fine enough for detailed assessments in densely built-up areas.
ALOS-2, SPOT, WorldView, QuickBird	ALOS-2 has a limited overflight frequency (typically 14 days), which means that it does not provide continuous or very short-term data needed for quick decisions in case of sudden events such as floods or storms.
Thermal Infrared imagery	Cloud and weather dependency: Thermal infrared images can be obstructed by clouds or smoke, which often occurs during storms or natural disasters. Revisit time & temporal resolution: Many thermal satellites have limited overflight times (e.g. Landsat Thermal), which limits real-time monitoring. Complexity of interpretation: Temperature data alone does not provide complete information on e.g. water levels or damage - it often needs to be combined with other data sources. Limited direct use for acute flood detection: Thermal images tend to show temperature differences, not directly water surfaces or flooding.

Technology UAVs & Drones (Remote Platforms)	Remarks
UAV photogrammetry, UAV-based monitoring	Flight restrictions: In acute crisis situations, airspace may be closed by authorities (e.g. rescue or fire-fighting helicopters), which hinders UAV deployment. Weather dependency: UAVs are heavily dependent on the weather - heavy rain, wind or poor visibility can make flights impossible. Limited flight time and range: Battery life and range limit their use to smaller areas. Data processing: High-resolution images have to be extensively processed after the flight, which takes time - the results are often not available in real time. Logistics & personnel: UAV missions require trained personnel, suitable equipment and logistical preparation, which are not always guaranteed in sudden crises.
UAV thermal mapping, NDVI assessment	Weather dependency: Bad weather (rain, fog, wind) restricts UAV flights. Flight restrictions: Airspace restrictions in crisis situations can prevent UAV missions. Data processing time: Thermal data must be analysed after the flight, no real-time data availability. Limited range and flight time: Limited to smaller areas

Technology Ground-Based & IoT Sensor Systems	Remarks

Capacitance sensors, Plant Spike	Point measurement: These sensors only measure locally at the point where they are installed - they do not provide large-scale data for rapid crisis assessment. Installation & maintenance: Requires physical access to the measurement location, which can be problematic in acute crises (e.g. flooding).Data latency: Often part of an IoT network that can send data in real time, but depending on the infrastructure, networks are not always reliable or comprehensive. Weather and environmental influences: Sensors can be affected by extremely wet, frozen or dirty ground.
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Technology	Remarks
AI, Machine Learning & Data Analytics	
AI/ML for flood/drought prediction (RF, XGBoost, ANN, SVM)	Model training takes time: AI/ML models have to be trained and validated with extensive historical data, which is time-consuming - training usually takes place before the crisis. Model interpretation and uncertainties: Models provide probabilities, not certain predictions - during an acute crisis, a quick, unambiguous decision is often required. Real-time data availability: The accuracy of predictions depends heavily on up-to-date, high-quality data; delays or missing data can affect performance. Computing resources: Complex models sometimes require considerable computing capacity, which is not always available in real time. Adaptation to new events: Extreme or rare events can fall outside the training dataset, so models can lose their predictive power.
Surrogate ML models, Deep Reinforcement Learning	Approximation: Surrogate models are always approximations and cannot perfectly depict complex physical processes, which can lead to errors in critical situations. Training data requirement: Must be trained with comprehensive simulations that are created in advance - new, previously unknown situations can limit the quality of the model. Adaptability: In case of sudden changes (e.g. new obstacles, unexpected events) surrogate models are less flexible. Validation & trust: Decision-makers need verified, trustworthy models; approximate surrogate models can cause scepticism.

3.6. State of art of the COTS (Commercial off-the-shelf) products

3.6.1. Methodology and Results

This section presents the analysis carried out to identify relevant Commercial Off The Shelf (COTS) solutions for the PCP WISE project. The objective of this research was to assess existing market-ready products and technologies that align with the project's scope and can potentially be leveraged without the need for extensive customization or development.

The analysis revealed that open data platforms like Copernicus, are among the most commonly utilized COTS offerings by service providers.

To perform this mapping of technology providers, two complementary approaches were employed:

- **Desk Research**, which involved reviewing publicly available materials such as published reports, online databases, and preexisting survey data.

- **Survey Research**, which gathered direct input from internal and external stakeholders of the consortium to gather their feedback on potential COTS solutions.

These above methods were ensuring a comprehensive overview of the current market landscape.

Survey Research formed an important foundation for identifying relevant COTS. This step was guided by the following key parameters:

- Awareness and usage of COTS tools relevant to PCP WISE
- Information on how and where these tools were applied, including:
 - In combination with space data
 - For civil services
 - In research and development or scientific contexts
 - Within hydrology applications
 - For governmental services such as meteorological offices
- Additional use cases and recommendations for COTS tools, along with justifications for their relevance and utility

The list of COTS products and key players was further refined and finalized based on input from the OMC and suppliers within the KATI system. The results of the OMC played a reinforcing role by providing feedback on what currently exists in the market, important technologies or solutions that we need to consider, what is achievable, and what is not, based on current capacities and capabilities.

The objective was to identify suitable COTS solutions and evaluate their potential application within the context of the PCP WISE project. In addition, we conducted a general market mapping by including crisis software COTS solutions that help provide a broader understanding of the market. These solutions are not considered direct competitors, as the project focuses on the pre-crisis phase. The full lists of COTS solutions identified are provided in the tables below.

SECTOR	COTS	OPEN SOURCE	DATA/SOFTWARE/SERVICE/HW	COUNTRY	APPLICATION (water, hydro, space only)	SHORT DESCRIPTION
Space	ESRI /ArcGIS	no	software & services	USA	for hydro: ArcHydro, Floodplain Mapping, Hec-GeoHMS, HEC-RAS, Watershed	Groundwater Resources Management, water quality, Stormwater modelling, Hydrological simulations ...
Space	QGIS	yes	software		for hydro: SAGA GIS, GRASS GIS, QGIS hydrological, Hec-GeoHMS, TauDEM, QSWAT	tool kit for SIG luding modules for drainage modulization, Simulation of surface water flow, Cartographie des zones de recharge des nappes ... (see modiles Qwater, MNT)
Space	Mapinfo	yes	software		no specific module for hydrology	similar fonctionalities with QGIS
Space	AutoCAD	no	software	USA	no specific module for hydrology	computer-aided design (CAD) is primarily used for creating 2D and 3D technical drawings. It could be used to manage water infrastructure
Space	Geographic Ressources Analysis Support System (GRASS GIS)	yes	software		see qgis above	allows you to define and calculate watersheds from field data, analyze drainage and study water flow in a region. It includes tools to identify and analyze river networks, groundwater recharge areas, flood zones and stormwater management.

SECTOR	COTS	OPEN SOURCE	DATA/SOFTWARE/SERVICE/HW	COUNTRY	APPLICATION (water, hydro, space only)	SHORT DESCRIPTION
Space	Google earth engine	no but free access	software	USA	no specific module for hydrology	including soil moisture calculation algorithms, water quality (temperature, turbidity, chlorophyll concentration, and the presence of pollutants), Groundwater monitoring, Modelling of water flows and watersheds, Rainfall and drought monitoring
Space	Manifold GIS	no	software	USA	no specific module for hydrology	Modelling of water flows and watersheds, Monitoring of reservoirs and water tables, water quality
Space	GVSIG	yes	software		for hydrology: gvSIG Hydrology Extension, saga gis, Taudem	monitoring water level, water quality, flood modelling ...
Space	SuperGIS	no	software	Taiwan	no specific module for hydrology	Watershed modelling, flood risks area, water quality ...
Space	FME	no	software	Canada	no specific module for hydrology	monitoring soil moisture index,
Space	Hexagon Geospatial	no	software	USA	no specific module for hydrology	hydrological models of watersheds, monitoring water infrastructure, water quality, Groundwater modelling
Space	Carto	no some modules are free	software	USA	no specific module for hydrology	monitoring water quality, flood risk, water level ..
Space	NASA earth observing System Data and Information System	no	data	USA	no specific module for hydrology	MODIS provides satellite data that includes soil moisture indices

SECTOR	COTS	OPEN SOURCE	DATA/SOFTWARE/SERVICE/HW	COUNTRY	APPLICATION (water, hydro, space only)	SHORT DESCRIPTION
Space	Copernicus Sentinelle	yes	data	EU	Sentinel 1, 2 and 3 for data on flood, lakes and reservoirs levels C3S for precipitation, CMS for flood event monitoring, CLMS for Watershed mapping	The use of Sentinel-1 radar data allows monitoring of soil moisture through soil deformation measurements and reflection analyses. S2 provides high-resolution images to monitor water bodies, water level variations and water quality
Space	SMAP (Soil Moisture Active Passive) de la NASA	no	data	USA	similar to Copernicus in term of data type	SMAP is a NASA mission that directly measures soil moisture on a global scale.
Space	Landsat	no	data	USA	similar to Copernicus in term of data type	The Landsat program provides historical and current remote sensing data, which can be used to analyze soil moisture in combination with other environmental indicators but also monitor surface water stocks, including lakes, reservoirs, artificial water reservoirs and water storage areas
Space	SMOS from ESA	yes	data	EU	essentially soil moisture	The SMOS satellite measures soil moisture globally using microwave radiometry to analyze moisture at the land surface and in the ocean
Space	TerraSAR-X	no	data	Germany	flood detection with high resolution (1m) groundwater, soil moisture	high-resolution radar satellite that can measure variations in soil moisture by analyzing the reflection of electromagnetic waves on the Earth's surface.
Space	Hydrosat	no	data & services	USA, Luxembourg & Netherlands	many data for hydrology	Land surface temperature and reflectance (Thermal infrared satellites) for agriculture, aquaculture

SECTOR	COTS	OPEN SOURCE	DATA/SOFTWARE/SERVICE/HW	COUNTRY	APPLICATION (water, hydro, space only)	SHORT DESCRIPTION
Space	Planet Labs	no	data	USA	data used for hydrology with high resolution	High-resolution satellite images (via its Dove satellites)
Space	GRACE (Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment)	no	data	USA + Germany	water reserve in glaciers, rivers, lakes and groundwater	Measure variations in Earth's gravity, allowing them to track changes in groundwater reserves, glaciers and ice caps, and the levels of surface water reservoirs.
Space	SWOT	no	data	USA + France	several data for hydrology with high resolution (30 cm to 1m)	Scientific mission that measures with unprecedented precision the height of water in rivers, lakes, reservoirs and oceans
Space	Aquarius	no	data	USA	specific for hydrology	Monitors the interaction between fresh and saltwater supplies
Space	GNSS/Galileo	yes	data	EU	no specific data for hydrology	Allow to measure infrastructure movement
Space; Water	HEC-RAS Hydrologic Engineering Center - River Analysis System	no	software	USA	Hydrology	Modelization of water behaviour in the rivers
	PCSWMM - Personal Computer Storm Water Management model	no	software	Canada	Hydrology	Simulate the behaviour of rainwater
N/A	Wisystation or Wisporca	no	HW	Netherlands	HW to determine the biophysical parameters of water with its color	

SECTOR	COTS	OPEN SOURCE	DATA/SOFTWARE/SERVICE/HW	COUNTRY	APPLICATION (water, hydro, space only)	SHORT DESCRIPTION
N/A	gSMS sensor (gamma Soil Moisture Sensor)	no	HW	Netherland	Spectrometer	
Space; Water	SCALGO	no	Software	Danmark	Tool	Tool for visualization or simulation (floods ...)
N/A	Fluidit	no	Software	Finland	tool for modulization and simulation	Water distribution, stormwater, wastewater, and district energy systems to gradually develop into digital twins
N/A	OpenGeoSys (OGS)	yes	Software	Germany	application	Model tool
N/A	MIKE SHE (OpenMI Coupled)	no	Software	Danmark	applications	Applications and resources
N/A	HydroGeoSphere	no	Software	Canada	applications	Waterflow modernization
N/A	hydo-AS-2D, INFONETZ, HYDRO-GIS, HYDRO-FLOOD	no	Software	Germany	model	Water
N/A	Scenarify	no	Software	Austria	tool	Simulation for hydrology
N/A	Kaypso	yes	Model	Germany	Model	Water management(hydrology, flood)

Table 24: COTS products identified

Figure 73: Country of COTS

Figure 74: Source of COTS

Software	Description	Organization/Project	Known Uses	OpenSource/License
Sahana Eden	Humanitarian platform used to provide solutions for Disaster Management, Development and Environmental Management sectors	Sahana Foundation	Nepal Earthquake Response Kashmir Floods	MIT
Zivilschutz-Karte	... designed for creating detailed situation maps for disaster management	Swiss civil defense	Swiss civil defense	MIT
ResOp	Tool for first response in crisis situation, to anticipate and plan resources			MIT
CrowdMapper	Real-time collaborative application for tagging streams of geospatial data			X
ReadyResponder	Local incident management system, used for tracking resources			AGPL-3.0

Software	Description	Organization/Project	Known Uses	OpenSource/License
climate_indices	Python library providing algorithms that classify precipitation and temperature anomalies		Droughts, Precipitation	BSD-3-Clause License
WNTR	Python package to simulate and analyze water distribution networks under disaster scenarios	U.S. Environmental Protection Agency	Water networks	Revised BSD License
QGIS	Cross platform (lin/win/mac) geographical information system; spatial visualization and decision-making tools for everyone			GPL-2.0
InaSAFE	QGIS plugin for estimating impact from natural disasters		Floodings, Tsunamis, Earthquakes	GPL-3.0
GeoNode	Web-based application and platform for developing geospatial information systems (GIS) and deploying spatial data infrastructures (SDI)			GPL-3.0
Giro3D	JS framework to visualize geospatial data (2D, 2.5D and 3D) in browser	Funded as part of <i>France 2030</i>	Floodings, Droughts	MIT
Atlas	Geoportal to display maps, search addresses and measure distances			EUPL-1.2
GeoGirafe (GeoMapFish)	Simple viewer to explore web maps and geographical data	GeoMapFish	Used by multiple administrative districts in central europe	Apache License 2.0
spatial.IO	Integrated cloud-ready geospatial data management system	Helmholtz Center for Environmental Research	Droughts, Precipitation	EUPL-1.2
Ushahidi	Web-application that makes information collected via crowdsourcing available on a situation map			GNU-GPL
allReady	Solution to increase awareness, efficiency and impact of preparedness campaigns as delivered by humanitarian and disaster response organizations in local communities			MIT

Software	Description	Organization/Project	Known Uses	OpenSource/License
Lagekarte.info	Free online tool for local firefighters to create situation maps in operations			X
ESRI ArcGis	Comprehensive SaaS solution for map creation and analysis workflows			X
metropolyBOS	Modular system for crisis management teams with flexible solutions			X
Fireboard	Comprehensive overall solution for operational management and documentation, from alerting and operational planning through to full reporting			X
GRASS GIS	GRASS GIS is a Geographic Information System used for geospatial data management and analysis, image processing, graphics/map production, spatial modeling, and visualization			GPL-2.0
ProMaIDes	Provides a risk-based assessment of flood protection measures for river, urban and coastal flooding	Hochschule Magdeburg-Stendal		GPL-3.0-only
Delft-FEWS	"Expert data handling and model integration software for flood forecasting, drought and seasonal forecasting, and real-time water resources management"	Deltares	Multiple Forecasting locations around the globe (See also: https://fewsmat.deltares.nl/topology/node/all_systems/map)	Unclear, About-Page says "freely available", but there are terms and conditions
DioVISTA/Flood	Flood-simulator for evacuation planning and education for disaster-prevention.	Hitachi power solutions		proprietary
FloodRisk2		rse-web.it		GPL-2.0

Software	Description	Organization/Project	Known Uses	OpenSource/License
	The Floodrisk Plugin can be used to calculate the flood consequences in terms of direct economic damages and loss of lives. The probability of each scenario is estimated separately and consequences are calculated deterministically	In support by the Research Fund for the Italian Electrical System		
Python GIS Flood Tool	"This tool was designed to process stream, catchment, and elevation datasets in order to assess the extent and depth of flooding for each stream reach."	U.S. Geological Survey		CC0 1.0 Universal

Table 25: COTS-Software in crisis management

3.7. Market analysis

3.7.1. Market Overview and Key Trends

The climate resilient technologies sector is witnessing strong and accelerating growth, driven by the mounting challenges posed by climate change and the urgent demand for adaptive solutions. The market, estimated at \$19.56 billion in 2024, is forecast to expand significantly, reaching \$71.34 billion by 2031, with a healthy compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 20.3%.⁷

During the period from 2024 to 2025, the market is set to grow from \$15.21 billion to \$17.31 billion, showing a CAGR of 13.8%.

Factors Fuelling Future Expansion (2025–2029 and beyond):

- Accelerated transition to renewable energy sources
- Heightened concerns over environmental pollution (air, water, and soil)
- Increasing global awareness and urgency around environmental sustainability

On the supply side, the climate resilience field is experiencing a significant shift, driven by progress in artificial intelligence, data analytics, and digital systems. Cutting-edge tools like smart sensors, digital twins, and real-time monitoring are enabling more accurate risk analysis and targeted responses. Meanwhile, blockchain technology is introducing greater transparency and traceability in financing and insurance for climate resilience.

Governments are playing a key role by enacting supportive policies and fostering collaboration between the public and private sectors, encouraging flexible and scalable technological solutions. Innovations in energy storage and decentralized microgrids are boosting the reliability of energy systems, linking physical infrastructure with intelligent digital controls for improved responsiveness.

Businesses and institutions are embracing these technologies not only to manage climate risks but also to reduce operational costs and strengthen stakeholder confidence. This reflects a broader strategic alignment between climate resilience, digital transformation, and sustainable development.

On the demand side, public authorities and communities worldwide are seeking better information and tools to protect lives, infrastructure, and water resources from climate threats. International initiatives underscore this trend, for example, the UN's Early Warnings for All ⁸campaign aims to ensure everyone on Earth is covered by early warning systems by 2027, reflecting the global priority on climate resilience. More specifically on the demand side,

⁷ <https://www.globenewswire.com/news-release/2024/07/16/2913882/0/en/Assessment-of-the-Global-Market-for-Climate-Resilient-Technologies-2018-to-2031-3M-TerraFuse-and-ClimateAI-Dominating-the-Industry-Projected-to-Surpass-71-Billion-by-2031.html>

⁸ <https://www.un.org/en/climatechange/early-warnings-for-all>

the PCP WISE project targets a wide range of public and semi-public organisations across Europe that rely on improved EO data and services to carry out their responsibilities and respond effectively to climate-related challenges. These organisations are vital for managing natural resources, protecting communities, and advancing Europe’s environmental sustainability and resilience goals.

One key group includes water management organisations at both local and national levels. These authorities are responsible for monitoring water resources, ensuring sustainable supply, managing flood risks, and adapting to changing hydrological conditions.

Agricultural organisations also represent an important part of the demand side. This group covers individual farmers, farming cooperatives, agricultural unions, and national ministries that oversee agricultural policy. They increasingly depend on advanced data and tools to optimise farming practices, use water efficiently, monitor soil and crop conditions, and build resilience to drought.

City administrations are another major target group. Urban departments such as groundwater management, street and building maintenance, asset management, and the teams responsible for parks and green spaces all benefit from improved EO data. Municipal utilities in the energy and water sectors, as well as public health services, also rely on environmental information to guide planning, maintain infrastructure, and adapt to changing climate conditions.

Crisis management organisations and civil protection agencies also play a significant role on the demand side. These organisations use risk assessments and environmental information to strengthen preparedness for floods, droughts, and other climate hazards. Better data and tools can support early warning systems, enhance coordination, and help protect communities when extreme events occur.

Climate policy makers form another key user group. Civil servants, urban and regional planners, and policy analysts use EO data to design, monitor, and adjust climate strategies in line with national and European targets.

Nature conservation organisations complete this diverse demand landscape. Agencies and non-governmental organisations that manage wetlands, forests, parks, and other protected areas rely on high-quality EO data to monitor ecosystems, safeguard biodiversity, and guide restoration and conservation activities.

By focusing on the needs of these groups, PCP WISE ensures that the solutions developed are relevant, practical, and capable of delivering real value in multiple policy areas and communities. This strong demand-driven approach is essential to achieving the project’s ambition of supporting Europe’s climate resilience and sustainability goals.

European Market Landscape

Europe represents a significant and dynamic subset of the global climate resilience market. As climate change impacts intensify across the continent, the European demand for climate and water management services is rising in tandem. Europe has endured some of its costliest

extreme events in recent years – for instance, weather and climate-related extremes caused an estimated €738 billion in economic losses in EU countries from 1980–2023, with 22% of those losses occurring just in 2021–2023⁹. Floods are the largest driver, accounting for ~44% of total losses, followed by storms (~29%) and heatwaves (~19%, which also caused the majority of fatalities). This escalating impact has put climate adaptation high on the agenda for European governments at all levels.

Key Drivers

1. Heightened Global Concern over Climate Change

The increasing urgency surrounding the effects of climate change—such as extreme weather patterns, ecosystem degradation, and global temperature rise—is pushing governments, industries, and communities to adopt innovative solutions. This rising awareness is fueling demand for resilient technologies capable of supporting mitigation and adaptation efforts.

2. Tighter Environmental Regulations and Policy Support

Climate-related policies are becoming more rigorous, with national and international authorities enforcing stricter emissions standards and sustainability goals. Measures like carbon pricing, clean energy mandates, and energy efficiency guidelines are encouraging broader adoption of environmental and climate-resilient technologies across sectors.

3. Stronger Public Advocacy and Societal Pressure

Public sentiment increasingly favors climate action, with citizens calling on institutions to prioritize sustainability. This demand is influencing corporate strategies and public policy, creating an environment where resilient infrastructure and smart environmental solutions are both expected and supported.

4. Rapid Technological Progress

Breakthroughs in digital technologies—including AI, machine learning, satellite imagery, and cloud computing—are significantly enhancing climate modeling, environmental monitoring, and decision-making capabilities. These advancements make it easier to deploy scalable, intelligent solutions for risk assessment and management.

5. Rising Economic and Social Costs of Climate Disasters

The growing frequency and intensity of climate-related events such as floods, wildfires, and droughts are impacting economies and infrastructure. As the risk profile worsens, there is increasing investment in technologies that can predict, withstand, and recover from environmental shocks.

6. ESG Commitments Driving Market Behaviour

⁹ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/indicators/economic-losses-from-climate-related#:~:text=Weather,losses%20will%20reduce%20by%202030>

Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) considerations are becoming a strategic priority for organizations. Companies are under pressure to show they are actively addressing climate risks, which is boosting investment in systems that support sustainability, resilience, and transparency.

7. Integration of Digital Tools with Climate Resilience Strategies

The market is seeing a merging of environmental resilience efforts with digital transformation. Tools like real-time monitoring, IoT, and digital twin technologies are enabling more adaptive and data-driven solutions that support climate preparedness and long-term planning.

8. Alignment of Global Goals with Local Implementation

There is a growing emphasis on aligning international sustainability frameworks—such as the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the Paris Agreement—with locally tailored solutions. Companies that offer adaptable, region-specific innovations while meeting global standards are emerging as key players.

9. Transformative Potential of Climate Resilience Technologies

Beyond adaptation, emerging technologies are playing a transformative role—redefining infrastructure, urban planning, and resource management for long-term systemic change. These solutions are not just reactive but foundational to building entirely new models of sustainability and resilience.

3.7.2. Key Players

To identify key players in the market, including potential competitors, a multifaceted approach was employed. This involved analyzing companies listed in the COTS catalog, conducting comprehensive desk research, incorporating data from the COTS survey, reviewing supplier lists that Fraunhofer generated from KATI system along with the results of the OMC questionnaire and the internal stakeholders database.

key players	Country	Activities linked with water	generalist or specialist	Description
ESRI	USA	Editor of GIS tools	generalist	Esri is the global market leader in geographic information system (GIS) software, location intelligence, and mapping. Esri's GIS software is the most powerful mapping & spatial analytics

key players	Country	Activities linked with water	generalist or specialist	Description
				technology available.
Autodesk, Inc	USA	Editor of GIS tools	generalist	Autodesk provides advanced design and modeling software such as AutoCAD, Civil 3D, and InfraWorks, which are highly relevant for the infrastructure and environmental planning aspects of PCP WISE. Their tools support digital twin development, hydrological modeling, and integration with GIS and BIM environments, making them valuable for analyzing, simulating, and visualizing water-related infrastructure and natural systems within the project's scope.
Google earth	USA	Images and agriculture services	generalist	Google Earth is a software and web application developed by Google that allows users to explore the Earth in a 3D environment, using satellite and aerial imagery, topography, and geographic data

key players	Country	Activities linked with water	generalist or specialist	Description
Manifold Software Limited.	Hong Kong	Editor of GIS tools	generalist	Manifold combines the visual and spatial power of GIS with the massive data science power of built-in parallel DBMS. It enables users to accomplish what GIS or traditional DBMS tools cannot, being both a parallel DBMS and a powerful GIS system.
Supergeo Technologies Inc	Taiwan	Editor of GIS tools & solutions for defense, Health, transport, agriculture, tourism or security	generalist	Supergeo is a professional GIS vendor providing GIS-related users with complete GIS solutions for desktop, mobile, server, and Internet platforms.
Safe Software Inc	Canada	Supply an integration platform specialized in space data	generalist	Safe Software is the developer of FME (Feature Manipulation Engine), a powerful data integration platform widely used for converting, transforming, and integrating geospatial data.
Hexagon AB	Sweeden	HW and software in particular for agriculture	specialist	Hexagon AB is a global leader in digital reality solutions, combining sensor, software, and autonomous technologies. Hexagon's geospatial and industrial metrology tools offer valuable capabilities for high-resolution terrain analysis, hydrological modeling, and

key players	Country	Activities linked with water	generalist or specialist	Description
				infrastructure monitoring.
CARTO	Spain	HW and Software - Monitor water infrastructure	specialist	CARTO is a company that provides a cloud-based location intelligence platform. Their service helps businesses analyze and visualize spatial data through interactive maps and advanced analytics, enabling better decision-making across industries like retail, telecommunications, real estate, and government.
NASA	USA	Images supplier and algorithm for hydrology, oceans, water reserve, flood, drought, agriculture	generalist	NASA (USA) is a government agency that conducts space exploration, scientific research, and aeronautics development.
HEC-RAS	USA	hydrology	specialist	HEC-RAS is a software developed by the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers for hydraulic modeling. It helps engineers analyze river and floodplain hydraulics, simulate water flow, and design flood control and management systems.

key players	Country	Activities linked with water	generalist or specialist	Description
Computational Hydraulics Inc.	Canada	stormwater management, wastewater and watersheds	specialist	Computational Hydraulics specializes in developing advanced software for stormwater, wastewater, and watershed modeling. Their flagship product, PCSWMM, is a spatial decision support system that integrates with the U.S. EPA's SWMM5 model, enabling engineers to analyze flooding and facilitate responsible urban and natural drainage planning and design.
DHI A/S	Danemark	MIKE editor : hydrology and water mangement consulting	specialist	DHI provides expert consultancy, advanced modelling software, and digital solutions to address challenges in marine, freshwater, and urban water systems. Their flagship software suite, MIKE Powered by DHI, is widely used for water modelling applications.
World Wildlife Fund (WWF)		Sustainable agriculture, industrial & urban practices, water manegement consulting	generalist	As the world's leading conservation organization, WWF works in nearly 100 countries. At every level, they collaborate with people around the world to develop and deliver innovative solutions that protect

key players	Country	Activities linked with water	generalist or specialist	Description
				communities, wildlife, and the places in which they live.
Water Insight	Netherland	HW & Software - monitoring of water quality	specialist	Water Insight was founded to commercialize and operationalize water quality remote sensing products and services. They developed “close sensing” water quality spectrometers (WISP-3 and WISPstation) to bridge the gap between satellite monitoring and in situ sampling.
Medusa Radiometrics	Netherland	HW & Software - water quality, soil moisture	specialist	Medusa Radiometrics specializes in the development and production of high-resolution gamma-ray sensors for geophysical applications. Established as a spin-off from the University of Groningen, their sensors are used worldwide for mineral exploration, environmental monitoring, agricultural studies, and radiation safety.

key players	Country	Activities linked with water	generalist or specialist	Description
Scalgo ApS	Danemark	soil moisture, simulation tools	specialist	Scalgo ApS is a technology company specializing in advanced terrain data processing and hydrological modeling. Their software transforms high-resolution digital elevation models into actionable insights for urban planning, environmental management, and infrastructure development.
fluidit Oy	Finland	soil moisture	specialist	Fluidit Oy is a technology company specializing in hydraulic modeling software for urban water and energy systems.
MEOSS	France	agriculture	specialist	MEOSS is a startup specializing in geospatial solutions derived from satellite imagery. They develop decision-support tools aimed at helping public authorities manage territories sustainably by leveraging Earth observation data.
MURMURATION	France	agriculture	generalist	Murmuration provides indicators to integrate environmental issues into decision-making processes for governments, businesses, and the public.

key players	Country	Activities linked with water	generalist or specialist	Description
Aquanty Inc	Canada	hydrology	specialist	Aquanty is a science and technology company leading in predictive analytics, simulation, forecasting, and research services for water resources.
Blue Water Intelligence	France	watersheds	specialist	BWI provides basin digitization services supporting climate resilience for public authorities and businesses through hydrological forecasts accessed via virtual stations.
I-sea	France	Costal resilience, water trbidity	specialist	I-Sea specializes in environmental monitoring solutions using satellite Earth Observation data and artificial intelligence.
BLUEMAPPING	France	Flood	specialist	Bluemapping deploys ultra-fast runoff flooding models on high-performance cloud servers, enabling flood risk prediction and resilient infrastructure design.
VORTEX IO	France	hydrology	specialist	Vortex IO is a climate-tech startup offering real-time hydrological monitoring solutions using space-inspired technology and AI.
MAGLLIUM	France	hydrology, snow, ice	generalist	Magellium specializes in data and image processing technologies for space, defense, environment, and infrastructure sectors.

key players	Country	Activities linked with water	generalist or specialist	Description
LIFELIDAR	France	water quality	specialist	LIFeLiDAR is a French startup specializing in compact, high-resolution LiDAR systems measuring water quality and surface properties using laser-induced fluorescence.
AQUAFIN	Belgium	wastewater	specialist	Aquafin is a utility company specializing in the design, financing, operation, and maintenance of regional wastewater collection and treatment systems across Flanders.
Acciona Agua	Spain	wastewater, desalination	specialist	The company leads the water treatment sector through design, construction, and operation of drinking water and wastewater treatment plants.
Aqalia	Spain	water management	specialist	Aqalia is a leading international water management company offering end-to-end solutions for the complete water cycle, including supply, wastewater treatment, reuse, and desalination.
Landia	Danemark	wastewater	specialist	Landia supplies pumping and mixing solutions to different industries - the most important ones being agriculture, wastewater, biogas plants and the fish industry.

key players	Country	Activities linked with water	generalist or specialist	Description
Satways	Greece	monitoring of hydrolic infrastructure , flood and water management	specialist	Satways focuses on geospatial command and control systems for security, public safety, and critical infrastructure.
HydroLogic 25	Netherland	hydrology	specialist	HydroLogic researches and develops advances in hydroinformatics such as simulation models, data analytics, AI, remote sensing, GIS-based modelling, web services, and mobile ICT.
eleaf	Netherland	water management, agriculture	specialist	eLEAF provides satellite-based data and services for agricultural, water management, and crop index insurance domains.
Eomap	Germany	coastal resilience	specialist	EOMAP offers Earth Observation solutions providing key environmental intelligence insights to industry and governmental clients.
H2O Geomatics	Canada	agriculture, hydology, ice	generalist	H2O Geomatics specializes in big geospatial data analytics for informed decision-making related to water resources.
GeoVille GmbH	Austria	agriculture, water management	generalist	GeoVille GmbH specializes in Earth observation (EO) and geospatial information systems (GIS), delivering satellite-based data analytics and land monitoring solutions worldwide.

key players	Country	Activities linked with water	generalist or specialist	Description
3M	USA	water filter	specialist	3M offers a wide range of water filtration solutions for residential, commercial, and industrial use, focusing on improving water quality through advanced filter technologies.
red bird	USA	watering system	specialist	Red Bird is a company that specializes in innovative watering systems designed for efficient agricultural and livestock management. Their products help farmers optimize water usage, improve animal welfare, and reduce labor costs.
climate.AI	USA	weather forecast, flooding risk forecast ...	generalist	ClimateAI is a climate resilience and adaptation platform using AI-powered weather and flood risk forecasting tailored for agriculture, food & beverage, finance, and water management.
Climavision Inc	USA	Hydrological forecasting & water risk management	generalist	Climavision specializes in advanced hydrological and weather forecasting, delivering actionable water and weather risk insights for sectors like energy, agriculture, insurance, and public safety.

key players	Country	Activities linked with water	generalist or specialist	Description
Arup Group Limited	UK	resources & supply, treatment, wastewater management, flooding and stormwater, and watershed health	generalist	Arup Group Limited is a global professional services firm specializing in comprehensive water and environmental solutions across the full water cycle .
Kingspan Group	Ireland	waste water	specialist	Kingspan Group is a global leader in sustainable water and wastewater solutions under its Water & Energy division. With over 65 years of engineering experience, they design, manufacture, monitor, and service a wide range of systems—including sewage treatment plants, septic tanks, pump stations, oil/water separators, rainwater harvesting units, and sustainable drainage systems (SuDS)—for both residential and commercial applications across Ireland, the UK, and Europe .
Saint-Gobain Group	France	waste water	specialist	Saint-Gobain Group is a global leader in sustainable building materials widely active in water infrastructure and wastewater treatment.

key players	Country	Activities linked with water	generalist or specialist	Description
Gro Intelligence Inc	USA	water ressource management	generalist	Gro Intelligence is a U.S. & Kenya-based AI-driven agri-climate data platform founded in 2012. It aggregated satellite, weather, trade, government, and financial datasets to model global agriculture, climate risk, and crop yield forecasts
GIKI Social Enterprise Ltd	UK	application to manage water consumption	specialist	Giki Social Enterprise is a UK-based B Corp and social enterprise founded in 2017. The organization aims to make sustainability accessible and actionable for individuals and businesses alike.
Evoqua Water Technologies	USA	water desalination	specialist	Evoqua Water Technologies is a leading provider of advanced water treatment solutions, specializing in desalination technologies for both municipal and industrial applications.
Brightfarms Inc	USA	aquaponics	specialist	BrightFarms is an indoor farming company specializing in hydroponic greenhouses that produce fresh, non-GMO, pesticide-free salad greens. Their facilities are strategically located to supply local supermarkets with high-quality produce year-

key players	Country	Activities linked with water	generalist or specialist	Description
				round, reducing transportation emissions and ensuring freshness.
Ceres Imaging Inc	USA	agriculture - irrigation	specialist	Ceres Imaging is a precision agriculture firm that utilizes aerial imagery and AI analytics to optimize irrigation practices. Their tools help farmers detect water stress, system inefficiencies, and crop health issues, enabling more sustainable and profitable farming operations.
Arbonaut Ltd	Finland	water quality monitoring (platform)	specialist	Arbonaut is a company specializing in environmental data analytics, offering platforms for monitoring water quality, forest resources, and land use. Their solutions provide actionable insights for sustainable resource management and environmental protection.
Clean Maine Carbon (CMC)	France	vegetal carbon production to improve soil water retention and water filtration	specialist	CMC produces vegetal carbon (biochar) aimed at enhancing soil water retention and improving water filtration, supporting sustainable

key players	Country	Activities linked with water	generalist or specialist	Description
				agriculture and ecosystem health.
CarbonCapture Inc	USA	CO2 capture in the air (and product water)	specialist	CarbonCapture develops technology to capture CO ₂ directly from the air, producing not only carbon removal but also clean water as a byproduct, addressing climate and water challenges simultaneously.
NCX	USA	Forest credit carbon	specialist	NCX operates a platform for forest carbon credits, enabling landowners to monetize carbon sequestration by protecting and managing forests, contributing to climate mitigation.
Deltares	Netherland	flood, drought, hydrology	specialist	Deltares is a major technological institute in the Netherlands specialising in hydraulic engineering research and consulting, along with water management, geotechnics, and infrastructure. The organisation's research mainly focuses on rivers and river deltas, coastal regions, and offshore engineering.

key players	Country	Activities linked with water	generalist or specialist	Description
earthpulse!	Spain	platform to use EO data	generalist	earthpulse! offers a platform leveraging earth observation data to monitor environmental variables for better resource management and climate adaptation.
Gisaia	France	platform to use EO data	generalist	Gisaia offers advanced platforms using earth observation data and AI to support environmental monitoring, agriculture, and forestry management.
Geopredict	Germany	earth atmosphere digital twin and rainfall forecast	specialist	Geopredict develops a digital twin of the Earth's atmosphere, providing hyper-local rainfall forecasts to improve weather prediction and disaster preparedness.
Rainbow sensing	Netherland	hydrology	specialist	Rainbow Sensing specializes in hydrology solutions, delivering real-time water monitoring and analytics for better water resource management.
RSS-hydro	Luxembourg	flood modelization	specialist	RSS-Hydro provides advanced flood modeling and forecasting tools to support flood risk management and emergency response planning.
soil data	Netherland	agriulture	specialist	Soil Data offers agricultural data services focused on soil health and management,

key players	Country	Activities linked with water	generalist or specialist	Description
				helping optimize crop production and sustainable land use.
iceeye	Finland	flood and ice	specialist	Iceeye operates a satellite constellation offering radar imaging focused on flood detection, ice monitoring, and disaster management worldwide.
Leica Geosystems	Switzerland	coast area and hydrology	generalist	Leica Geosystems provides precision measurement solutions including coastal area mapping and hydrological surveying using advanced geospatial technologies.
Riegl	Austria	HW - sensor bathymetry or hydrology	generalist	Riegl designs and manufactures high-performance LiDAR sensors for bathymetry and hydrology applications, enabling detailed 3D mapping of underwater and terrestrial environments.
Fugro	Netherland	coastal monitoring, hydrology	specialist	Fugro specializes in coastal monitoring and hydrological services, offering geotechnical, geophysical, and environmental data to support infrastructure and water management projects.

key players	Country	Activities linked with water	generalist or specialist	Description
hydrotec	Germany	hydrodynamic model	specialist	Hydrotec develops hydrodynamic models and software for simulating water flow and flood risk, aiding decision-making in water resource management and flood prevention.
trimble	USA	wastewater and canalization monitoring	specialist	Trimble provides technology solutions for wastewater and canalization monitoring, improving infrastructure management and environmental compliance.
Telspazio	Italy	digital twin (flooding)	generalist	Telespazio offers digital twin solutions for flood modeling and environmental monitoring, integrating satellite data and advanced analytics.
3Di Water Management	Netherland	several topics on water	specialist	3Di develops integrated water management software covering flood risk, drainage, water quality, and urban water systems for comprehensive decision support.
VRVIS	Austria	hydrology	specialist	VRVIS is a research center focusing on hydrology and environmental visualization, creating digital tools to analyze and predict water-related phenomena.

key players	Country	Activities linked with water	generalist or specialist	Description
Nelen Schuurmans	Netherland	flood	specialist	Nelen & Schuurmans specializes in flood monitoring and management solutions, providing real-time data and decision-support tools to mitigate flood risks.
float-iot	Netherland	IOT (censor)	specialist	Float-iot develops IoT sensors for water monitoring, enabling remote measurement of water quality, levels, and environmental parameters.
MERATECH	slovakia	IOT (measure water level)	specialist	MERATECH offers IoT-based solutions focused on measuring water levels and monitoring hydrological conditions for improved water management.
Vertical M2M	France	water distribution management	specialist	Vertical M2M delivers smart water distribution management systems, enhancing operational efficiency and reducing water loss through IoT and digital tools.
irridra	Italy	water drainage	specialist	Irridra specializes in water drainage equipment and solutions for agricultural and urban applications, improving water flow and preventing flooding.
hydroscan	Belgium	water drainage	specialist	Hydroscan provides advanced water drainage systems and consultancy for

key players	Country	Activities linked with water	generalist or specialist	Description
				flood prevention and stormwater management.
ITWH	Germany	urban water management	specialist	ITWH offers urban water management services, including planning, engineering, and modeling for sustainable city water systems.
Tuflow	australia	water quality, flood, coastline	specialist	Tuflow develops software for water quality modeling, flood simulation, and coastal management, widely used by engineers and planners globally.
Sarmap	Switzerland	water resources for Tchad	generalist	Sarmap uses satellite data to monitor water resources and environmental changes, with projects including water management support for Chad.
aquamod	Bulgaria	drinking water management	specialist	Aquamod specializes in drinking water management, offering tools and systems for water quality monitoring and distribution network optimization.
Arcadis	Netherlands	water-sector engineering and consulting	generalist	Arcadis is a global engineering and consultancy firm whose water practice—powered by ~2,000 water specialists—addresses the full water lifecycle: from source to treatment, conveyance, urban

key players	Country	Activities linked with water	generalist or specialist	Description
				water management and restoration. Services span design, project management, asset operations and environmental compliance .

Table 26: List of key players

Figure 75: Country of key actors

3.8. Conclusions

3.8.1. State-of-the-Art of identified technologies -TRL assessment

In the following paragraph, the technologies identified from publications and the European patents are **clustered** into a **matrix structure**. The matrix assesses crisis phases and application areas of the identified technologies using the clustering that the project team agreed on during a joint workshop. We utilize a binary yes or no distinction. The matrix is designed to allow an easy filtering tailored to the users requirements or information needs.

The matrix consists of 17 columns, which are defined as follows:

1. Identified Technologie (from publications and patents)
2. The estimated TRL for all the technologies TRL definition according to NASA, see Figure 74
3. Notes on the TRL estimation of necessary. Possible explanatory comments etc.
4. The Crisis “Phase”
5. It is assessed whether the technologies are used **before, during or after (post) a crisis** (flood, drought, wildfire)
6. Early detection and monitoring (before crisis) Using ground/air/space/etc. sensors etc.
7. Prevention & Protection
 - Concrete measures for prevention and prevention (not data etc. that can serve as a basis for these measures)
8. Water management
 - Planning, use and control of water resources. Sustainable use, supply, protection from environmental damage (flooding)
9. Drought management
 - Preparation, monitoring, response to periods of drought. Technologies that minimize the negative effects of drought/water scarcity on the environment, agriculture and society
10. Wildfire management
 - Preparedness, monitoring, response to forest fire hazards. Technologies that help detect and fight forest fires, minimize damage and support post-fire rehabilitation
11. Climate management
 - Strategies and measures to combat climate change and adapt to its consequences
12. Emergency Management (during crisis)
 - Technologies that serve in the concrete response (to minimize the impact of disasters) and minimize damage to the civilian population and infrastructure
13. Data Science
 - No data provision/sensors, everything from data preparation, training/models, usage. Includes machine learning, data models, optimization algorithms, etc. No data provision/sensors, everything from data preparation, training/models, usage. Includes machine learning, data models, optimization algorithms, etc. Used for decision support.
14. Governance
 - Everything that is superordinate and specifically aimed at decision making. No specific technologies.
15. Rural
 - Applicable for rural regions
16. Urban
 - Applicable for rural regions
17. Cluster Notes

updated matrix includes relevant metadata such as technology clusters, TRL estimations, and the associated crisis “phase” to provide a well-structured overview of the current technology landscape.

Finally, the most important technologies and their respective TRL levels were identified as targets for the upcoming tender. To achieve this, the final version of the technology matrix was shared with all members of the five groups and with the lead procurer, HWH, so they could highlight the technologies most relevant to their needs. Based on this input from end users and the lead procurer, common priority technologies were identified to determine the key targets for the upcoming tender, along with other relevant technologies that need to be addressed.

These findings are presented in the two tables below: the first table shows the technologies common to all five groups, while the second table shows the technologies common to both the five groups and the lead procurer. The technologies listed below are not the only ones that will be targeted in the upcoming tender, as this is a complex project that requires an integrated solution involving various elements and technologies. However, they represent a good reflection of the current needs and priorities of the end users and the lead procurer.

Relevant technologies	Trl
Soil composition and moisture estimation for infrastructure risk analysis	6-7
Integration of on-site sensor data, satellite imagery, and climatic data	6-9
Combined use of on-site measurements, satellite data, and climate forecasts	6-7
Satellite-based multi-spectral imaging	8-9
Satellite-derived bare surface soil moisture estimation by soil texture/type	6-8
Real-time environmental monitoring and anomaly detection using sensor networks	7-8
Real-time meteorological data collection through sensor networks with online data transmission	8-9
Sentinel	9
LIDAR	9
Geographical information systems (GIS), z. B. ArcGIS, QGIS	9
Combination SAR + optical data	7-8
High-resolution commercial satellites (e.g., QuickBird, WorldView, GeoEye-1, IKONOS)	9

UAV optical data for soil moisture quantification using partial least square regression	6-8
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Table 27: Shortlisted technologies for the 5 groups

Relevant technologies	Trl
Soil composition and moisture estimation for infrastructure risk analysis	6-7
Integration of on-site sensor data, satellite imagery, and climatic data	6-9
Combined use of on-site measurements, satellite data, and climate forecasts	6-7
Satellite-derived bare surface soil moisture estimation by soil texture/type	6-8
Real-time meteorological data collection through sensor networks with online data transmission	8-9

Table 28: Shortlisted technologies of the 5 groups and the lead procurer

3.8.2. State-of-the-Art of identified technologies – Innovation gap

The analysis of COTS solutions, IPRs, and scientific publications reveals a rich ecosystem of mature and emerging tools relevant to the PCP WISE objectives. Many core components, such as satellite-based remote sensing (e.g., Sentinel, Landsat, SAR, MODIS, GOES-R), GIS platforms, IoT-based weather and water monitoring systems, and advanced hydrological models, have achieved high TRL levels (TRL 7–9), demonstrating proven performance in environmental monitoring and risk assessment. Similarly, several patented technologies show strong potential, including AI-based flood prediction models, soil moisture estimation under vegetation cover, wildfire risk detection systems, and integrated multi-source disaster monitoring platforms.

Complementing this, scientific publications underscore the validated effectiveness of many of these technologies and highlight ongoing research into emerging methods like digital twins, AI-driven dynamic heatmaps, advanced evapotranspiration modelling, and integrated social-ecological-technological systems. While many of these approaches have achieved high TRLs in others remain in mid-development stages (TRL 4–7), representing active innovation frontiers.

However, despite this technological maturity in individual domains, no existing solution provides a comprehensive, integrated approach that fully meets the multifaceted demands of the PCP WISE project. The project requires a unified platform capable of real-time, multi-hazard monitoring (including droughts, floods, and wildfires), intelligent early warning generation, soil and water management under climate stress, and decision support tailored

for diverse end-users. Current technologies tend to be domain-specific, fragmented, or limited in scalability and interoperability.

This gap highlights a clear opportunity for innovation. There is room in the market for an integrated solution that bridges high-TRL technologies with emerging capabilities such as dynamic heat maps, digital twins, graph-based flood modelling, AI-enhanced decision tools, and integrated data fusion systems currently at TRL 4–7. PCP WISE can play a leading role in bringing these components together into a single, interoperable, and user-friendly system.

In conclusion, while individual technologies are mature and field-proven, no all-encompassing integrated solution exists today that addresses the full scope of the PCP WISE. This creates a well-defined innovation space and a clear room for innovation validating the need for PCP to develop the PCP WISE solution.

4. Business Case & Cost/Benefit Analysis Update

4.1. Introduction

Developing a business case is an essential part of organizational decision-making, especially when launching new projects, introducing changes, or investing in initiatives. One commonly used and effective approach for this process is Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA). CBA is a systematic approach that assesses the potential costs and benefits associated with a proposed project, allowing decision-makers to make informed choices based on economic feasibility. However, for complex, innovative initiatives like PCP-WISE, which integrates advanced climate services and environmental observation data, traditional CBA methods reveal notable limitations. These projects operate in environments characterized by high uncertainty, dynamic risks, and interconnected variables. As a result, relying on single-point estimates and limited sensitivity analyses is insufficient. To address these challenges, advanced techniques like Monte Carlo Simulation (MCS) can complement traditional approaches by incorporating uncertainty, modelling multiple scenarios, and offering a more comprehensive and realistic understanding of potential outcomes.

In this context, the Business Case and Costs Analysis (BC&CA) methodology plays a vital role in the preparatory phase of Pre-Commercial Procurement. Its purpose is to provide key insights into the procurer's innovation needs and the ability of private sector actors to meet those needs. The BC&CA process involves a thorough analysis of the following aspects:

- Analysis of the anticipated costs and benefits of WISE solution, considering all relevant and interrelated factors.
- Performing financial assessments to demonstrate the investment viability of WISE solution.

This section details the steps followed for the identification of the costs and benefits connected with WISE solution as well as the calculations made in order to conclude on the profitability of such investment.

4.2. Business Case Development Methodology

The initial step in developing a business case is to clearly articulate the objectives and scope of WISE. Within the context of an innovation procurement initiative, this step aligns with the process of identifying and analyzing the underlying need. It primarily focuses on gaining a clear understanding of the problem or opportunity that WISE project aims to tackle, recognizing the key stakeholders, and setting specific, measurable objectives. A clearly defined scope is essential, as it lays the groundwork for a comprehensive cost-benefit analysis. The business case has been developed using data from the Netherlands. This is because the Netherlands

presents a representative blend of urban and rural contexts and has experienced a wide spectrum of climate-related risks, including floods, land subsidence, droughts, and wildfires. Crucially, it also offers the most comprehensive and accessible data, enabling the development of an integrated and robust models. While other countries in the consortium face similar challenges, limitations in comparable data availability constrained the ability to conduct equivalent modeling within the current scope.

- A. Identification of Costs and Benefits:** Following the definition of the project scope, the next phase focuses on identifying and categorizing the costs and benefits linked to PCP WISE. Costs can be either direct or indirect, as well as tangible or intangible. Direct costs include items like equipment, labour, and materials, whereas indirect costs might cover areas such as training and maintenance. On the other hand, benefits can be quantifiable, such as increased revenue or reduced expenses, or qualitative, including improvements in customer satisfaction or employee morale.
- B. Quantification and Evaluation:** Quantifying costs and benefits is a critical component of the cost-benefit analysis methodology. Tangible elements, such as equipment and labour expenses, are typically straightforward to measure. However, assessing intangible factors requires more refined methods. Techniques like discounted cash flow analysis and Net Present Value (NPV) calculations are used to assign monetary values to future costs and benefits, taking into account the time value of money. According to Dutch government guidelines, public investments should use a real discount rate of 2.25% per year for cost-benefit analyses¹⁰. This rate reflects a combination of a –1.0% real risk-free return and a 3.25% risk premium to account for societal opportunity costs and typical project risks. In our business case, we applied a 3.0% real discount rate to reflect a slightly more conservative stance, considering the 20-year analysis period and the uncertainties inherent in long-term innovation and pre-commercial procurement. To ensure robustness, a sensitivity analysis was conducted using 2.0% and 4.0% discount rates. This range captures both the lower bound of the official discount rate (2.25%) and the upper bound of the embedded risk premium (3.25%), ensuring the analysis reflects a realistic spectrum of time preference and risk tolerance.
- C. Monte Carlo Simulations:** To conduct a cost-benefit analysis using Monte Carlo simulations for the PCP WISE project, the process begins with identifying and defining all relevant costs and benefits. This includes categorizing expenditures such as project-related costs, capital investments, and ongoing operational expenses, as well as quantifying the expected benefits, such as reduced flood impact, enhanced crisis response, and improved infrastructure resilience. Each of these costs and benefits is further classified into fixed or variable components, where fixed values remain stable over time and variable components are subject to uncertainty.

A critical focus is placed on studying the variable costs and benefits in detail, as these require the assignment of probability distributions to accurately represent

¹⁰ <https://zoek.officielebekendmakingen.nl/kst-29352-10.html#:~:text=De%20werkgroep%20adviseert%20een%20risico,gevolg%20van%20een%20verbeterde%20methodologie>

uncertainty. For each variable component, an appropriate statistical distribution must be chosen, whether triangular, lognormal, uniform, or others, based on available data or expert judgment. This ensures that the model realistically reflects possible fluctuations in future outcomes.

Once all inputs are defined and distributions are assigned, the simulation model is built. A large number of simulation (1k –10K simulations) runs are executed, where average and random values are drawn from the defined distributions for each variable. In each run, total costs and benefits are calculated by combining fixed and realized variable values, generating a wide range of potential scenarios.

The final step is to analyze the simulation results by calculating the net benefit after applying various percentage reductions to the current costs. This analysis will also identify the best-case and worst-case scenarios. The accuracy and credibility of the entire analysis depend on the initial step of properly studying and assigning probability distributions to variable costs and benefits.

- D. Risk Assessment:** To strengthen the reliability of the cost-benefit analysis, it is crucial to conduct a risk assessment. By identifying potential internal and external risks linked to the project, decision-makers can better anticipate uncertainties and make more informed decisions.
- E. Sensitivity Analysis:** This involves examining how variations in key input variables influence the overall outcomes of the project. By analysing the sensitivity of the results to changes in factors such as cost estimates, benefit assumptions, or interest rate, decision-makers gain insight into which variables have the most significant impact. This understanding allows for more informed planning and prepares the consortium to respond effectively to potential changes or uncertainties in the project's performance.

4.3. Preliminary Calculations: Information Collected from Public Buyers and End Users

Based on the finalization of the SOTA and the implementation of the Open Market Consultation (OMC), the consortium concluded that there are no existing solutions to cover in full range the WISE requirements. Moreover, the starting Technology Readiness Level (TRL) is estimated to be around 5 to 6. In this framework, the BC&CA will proceed by identifying, quantifying, and monetizing the anticipated costs and benefits of the WISE solution in order to assess its economic impact and long-term viability.

4.3.1. Innovation Drivers

The drawbacks identified by the procurers of group one in the current operations and led to the need for a new solution are the following:

1. Cities may struggle to effectively monitor and manage shallow groundwater, leading to inefficient water use, unaddressed waterlogging or scarcity issues, and increased vulnerability to urban flooding.
2. Urban planners will lack accurate data on water dynamics under future climate scenarios, resulting in suboptimal infrastructure investments and reduced preparedness for long-term water-related challenges.
3. Without continuous monitoring, subsidence risks may go undetected, potentially causing structural damage to buildings and infrastructure, with higher costs and safety concerns over time.
4. Urban areas may face reduced resilience to droughts and climate variability, as water resource management remains reactive and less adaptive to changing conditions.
5. An incomplete understanding of the urban water balance may impair local decision-making, leading to inefficient irrigation, stormwater mismanagement, and an inability to optimize green infrastructure design.

The drawbacks identified by the procurers of group two in the current operations and led to the need for a new solution are the following:

1. Urban planning and decision-making may suffer from a lack of comprehensive flood risk data, leading to ill-informed infrastructure development and higher vulnerability to flood damage.
2. Delayed or missed identification of high-risk areas could result in preventable damage and loss, as authorities remain unprepared for sudden water-related events like flash floods.
3. Inefficient city and district management may persist, hindering sustainable growth and increasing exposure to environmental and infrastructural stress.
4. Unequal access to flood-related information can create coordination gaps among stakeholders, weakening collective response efforts and increasing the likelihood of inconsistent or ineffective action.
5. Without real-time flood data, cities may respond slowly and inefficiently during crises, escalating the extent of damage and putting lives and critical infrastructure at greater risk.
6. Floods may cause greater harm to infrastructure and communities, due to missed opportunities for proactive mitigation and adaptive design.
7. Wastewater utilities may struggle to manage groundwater crises, potentially leading to uncontrolled sewage leaks, overwhelmed treatment facilities, and further contamination of urban areas.

The drawbacks identified by the procurers of group three in the current operations and led to the need for a new solution are the following:

1. Wildfire preparedness: Without real-time fire risk assessments, first responders may be forced to react instead of prevent, leading to slower responses, greater fire spread, and higher costs in damage and containment.

2. **Water resilience:** Lacking dynamic soil moisture and groundwater tracking may result in inefficient water use, over-extraction, and a weakened ability to adapt to droughts or changing water availability.
3. **Conservation strategies:** Conservation efforts may remain generic and less effective without data-driven insights, risking poor habitat restoration outcomes and reduced ecosystem resilience.
4. **Public safety:** In the absence of risk-aware visitor management, recreational activities could unknowingly increase wildfire ignition risks, endangering both people and natural areas.
5. **Cross-border learning:** Without shared data platforms, Belgium and the Netherlands may duplicate efforts, miss opportunities for joint action, and remain fragmented in their approach to climate resilience.
6. **Public awareness:** Without accessible tools, citizens may remain uninformed or disengaged, leading to lower individual contributions to water conservation and fire risk reduction, and higher vulnerability during crises.

The drawbacks identified by the procurers of group four in the current operations and led to the need for a new solution are the following:

1. Without improved monitoring, surface soil conditions may be misjudged, leading to delayed responses to drought or excess moisture and reduced situational awareness.
2. Inefficient water use in agriculture and nature management may persist, potentially wasting water and compromising crop and ecosystem health.
3. The absence of clear risk maps may result in overlooked threat zones, poor emergency preparedness, and increased vulnerability to natural disasters.
4. Without integrated risk-reduction measures, these hazards may cause greater damage to ecosystems, agriculture, and rural communities.
5. Rural regions may suffer from poorly planned water distribution, leading to shortages, overuse, or conflict among users.
6. Planning decisions may inadvertently increase exposure to environmental hazards, raising long-term costs and risks.
7. Farmers and policymakers may lack timely insight into drought impacts, reducing their ability to plan for losses or adapt practices effectively.

The drawbacks identified by the procurers of group five in the current operations and led to the need for a new solution are the following:

1. Planning may be based on outdated or incomplete data, leading to inefficient infrastructure investments and vulnerability to environmental changes.
2. Without data-driven support, financial decisions may be riskier, less efficient, and lead to higher long-term costs due to poorly timed or misdirected investments.
3. Lack of reliable data can result in unsustainable irrigation, ineffective drainage, and increased land degradation or crop loss.
4. Policy effectiveness and cross-sector collaboration may suffer without integrated data, weakening the impact of adaptation strategies.

5. Utilities may remain stuck in reactive maintenance cycles, leading to more frequent failures, higher costs, and reduced service reliability.
6. Disjointed data and communication silos may hinder coordinated action and lead to inconsistent or delayed responses during crises.
7. Emergency responses may be less effective due to poor prioritization, wasting resources or missing critical areas.
8. Response teams may lack clear direction, leading to slower emergency declarations, misallocation of resources, and ineffective containment efforts.
9. Without such estimates, authorities may be blindsided by the scale of events, leading to insufficient protection for at-risk communities.
10. Evacuation efforts may be delayed or misdirected, increasing danger for residents and first responders.
11. Prevention and preparedness measures may be poorly targeted, increasing exposure to wildfire threats.
12. Lack of real-time monitoring could delay alerts and reduce the time available for proactive measures, increasing the likelihood of damage and loss.

4.3.2. Buyers' Clustered Benefits

The next logical step in our analysis involved identifying the impacts and corresponding benefits of implementing the WISE solution for buyers, particularly in relation to the previously identified drawbacks. These benefits have been categorized based on the five groups.

Benefits for Group 1: Urban Drought (North Europe):
Empower cities to manage shallow groundwater more effectively by integrating Earth Observation and ground-based data.
Support long-term planning with an improved understanding of urban water dynamics under various climate scenarios.
Enable continuous monitoring and prevention of subsidence-related risks.
Enhance urban water resource management, strengthening resilience to drought and climate impacts.
Better understanding of the local (urban) water balance by measuring soil moisture, evaporation, transpiration, precipitation

Table 29: Benefits Group 1

Benefits for Group 2: Urban Flooding (North-Central Europe):
Data driven decision making <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Drive more efficient management and sustainable development of cities and districts.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Deliver a comprehensive overview of flood risks to improve decision-making and urban planning.
<p>Lowering damages and life losses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Enable early identification of high-risk areas and prediction of potential water-related events. ○ Equip cities with real-time flood overviews for faster and more effective crisis responses
<p>Improved resilience for sea & wetlands areas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Provide actionable insights on where drainage is needed, where water can be stored, and how soil moisture evolves with flood and sea-level risks. ○ Improve understanding of shallow groundwater availability, efficient drainage locations, and impacts on wetlands and biodiversity.
<p>Increasing overall awareness and preparedness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Ensure equal access to information for all stakeholders, fostering coordinated actions. ○ Minimize the impacts of floods on infrastructure and communities
<p>Increased urban climate resilience</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Support for climate change resilience and adaptation measures. ○ Improved climate water management and adaptation planning.

Table 30: Benefits Group 2

<p>Benefits for Group 3: Rural Drought (Northwest-Central Europe):</p>
<p>Wildfire preparedness: Improve wildfire preparedness with real-time fire risk assessments, enabling first responders to take proactive mitigation actions.</p>
<p>Water resilience: Support better water management through dynamic tracking of soil moisture and groundwater, ensuring sustainable resource use.</p>
<p>Enhance conservation strategies with data-driven insights, optimizing habitat restoration and ecosystem protection.</p>
<p>Increase public safety by enabling risk-aware visitor management to reduce human-induced wildfire risks.</p>

Cross-border learning: Strengthen cross-border cooperation between Belgium and the Netherlands through joint data platforms for shared climate resilience efforts.

Public awareness: tools for citizens and recreational users to support smart water management, enhance drought resilience at the personal and property level, and navigate fire risk.

Table 31: Benefits Group 3

Benefits for Group 4: Rural Drought & Flooding (Southern Europe):

Improve monitoring of surface soil moisture in time and space, enhancing situational awareness.

Provide operational methods to assess root zone soil moisture, supporting efficient water use in agriculture and nature management.

Deliver risk maps for floods and wildfires, highlighting threat levels, exposure, and vulnerabilities conservation strategies with data-driven insights, optimizing habitat restoration and ecosystem protection.

Reduce risks of droughts, floods, and wildfires, safeguarding livelihoods and ecosystems.

Support better water resource management and allocation in rural areas.

Better risk-mitigation practices during infrastructure and land-use planning.

Provide operational methods to assess the impact of drought on agricultural production

Table 32: Benefits Group 4

Benefits for Group 5: Rural Drought & Flooding (Northern Europe)

Improve identification of damaged infrastructure and reduce water losses.

Improve long-term planning and decision-making with detailed data on terrain settlements, hydrological changes, and environmental impacts.

Unlock financial benefits by supporting water companies, municipalities, and infrastructure stakeholders in risk management and infrastructure investment decisions.

Support sustainable water management and agricultural practices with better data on subsidence and soil moisture, enabling informed drainage and land-use planning.

Strengthen policy evaluation and climate adaptation strategies across sectors.

Satellite data will enable utilities to move to a more condition-based maintenance of water infrastructure, as opposed to reactive maintenance strategy. This will improve the sustainability of utilities' economy and strengthen security of supply
Provide a unified information base for all stakeholders, improving coordination.
Enable smarter prioritization of response and resource allocation.
Support fire and flood response decisions with data-driven insights, helping to deploy resources, declare states of emergency, and create fire breaks.
Estimate the potential extent and spread of fires and floods and assess populations and infrastructure at risk.
Facilitate effective evacuation planning based on real-time situational awareness.
Improve fire hazard and risk mapping to support pre-event decision-making.
Enable continuous situation monitoring for early warnings and preparation.
Support disaster protection planning by validating resource availability (firefighters, equipment, etc.).

Table 33: Benefits Group 5

4.3.3. Buyers' Group Costs

The types of costs associated with the implementation of the WISE solution for buyers are summarized in the following table:

Type of cost	Impact
Investment costs (Procurement Cost)	€ 500,000 (Known from RFIs)
Initial or Setup Costs (One-time cost)	€ 100,000
Operational Cost (Annually)	€ 500,000
Risk Indicator Map (Annually)	€ 25,000
Climate Forecast for two decades (One time cost since the BC is over 20years)	€ 2,381
Total One-Time Costs	€ 602,381
Total Annual Cost (Operational + Risk Indicator Map)	€ 525,000

Present Value of Annual Costs	€ 7,810,674
Total PV of All Costs for 1 water authority	€ 8,413,055
Total PV of All Costs for 21 water authorities	€ 176,674,160

Table 34: Costs of PCP WISE Solution for 21 water authorities

4.4. Cost Analysis & Monte Carlo Simulations

This section outlines the data collection process, which involved desk research, input from partners, state-of-the-art analysis, and contributions from the OMC and Requests For Information. It also provides a summary of the resulting calculations and sensitivity analysis.

Below are the main costs induced due to floods, droughts and land subsidence in the Netherlands.

Costs related to land subsidence and droughts	Costs related to floods
Building Maintenance	Building Damage
Infrastructure Damage & Maintenance	Infrastructure Damage
Emergency repairs (unplanned failures) - URBAN Areas	Crop and agricultural losses
Emergency repairs (unplanned failures) - Rural Areas	
Additional costs for the water authorities for water management up to 2040	
Economical damage due to droughts (without Crop loss)	
Crop Loss due to Droughts	
Cost of combating wildfires and site restoration	

Table 35: Main costs related to land subsidence, droughts and floods

This section details the methodology and calculations applied to derive each data point presented in the preceding table.

Costs related to land subsidence and droughts

Building maintenance due to land subsidence

To assess the potential future cost of building maintenance resulting from land subsidence, we developed a probabilistic model using Monte Carlo simulation. Given the uncertainty in both the cost of repairs/maintenance and the timing of required interventions, this approach (MCS) provides a more realistic and robust estimate than single-point forecasting.

According to Council for the Environment and Infrastructure (RLI)¹¹ it is currently estimated that approximately 400,000 buildings are at risk of damage due to land subsidence over the coming decade. Each of these buildings is expected to require a one-time maintenance intervention to address structural issues. Based on a review of available sources^{12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17}, the expected cost of this maintenance ranges from €40,000 to €135,000 per building. Among these estimates, €80,000 appears to be the most likely cost.

To represent this cost uncertainty, we modelled the per-building maintenance cost using a triangular distribution, with the parameters set to a minimum of €40,000, a most likely value (mode) of €80,000, and a maximum of €135,000. The timing of the maintenance intervention was also treated as uncertain, with the assumption that damage could occur at any time over the next ten years. A uniform distribution was used to simulate the year in which maintenance would be required, assigning an equal probability to each year from year 1 to year 10.

For each simulated scenario, the randomly generated maintenance cost was discounted based on the randomly selected year of intervention to present value using a 3% annual discount rate, reflecting the time value of money.

This process was repeated 1,000 times to generate a distribution of possible present values (PV) for the maintenance cost per building. The resulting data set allowed us to analyse not just the average expected cost, but also the range of uncertainty, including lower and upper estimates. The final per-building estimates were then scaled to reflect the full population of 400,000 buildings, enabling a projection of the total national financial exposure to subsidence-related maintenance. Through this simulation, we obtained a comprehensive view of the potential costs under varying assumptions.

¹¹ <https://en.rli.nl/publications/2024/advice/firm-foundations#:~:text=The%20foundations%20problem%20currently%20affects,becomes%20unsettled%2C%20both%20literally%20and>

¹² [Subsidence entails high costs - Articles - De Ingenieur](#)

¹³ [Verdroging bestrijden | Groenblauwe Netwerken](#)

¹⁴ <https://www.ecorys.com/app/uploads/files/2019-10/20190221%20Rapport%20Economische%20schade%20door%20droogte%20in%202018.pdf>

¹⁵ https://www.alliance4water.org/wr4er-cases/kingdom-of-the-netherlands-from-floods-to-droughts?utm_source=

¹⁶ [Beantwoording Kamervragen over 1 miljoen verzakkende huizen door bodemdaling – PONT Omgeving](#)

¹⁷ [Sinking feeling: 425,000 properties have bad foundations - DutchNews.nl](#)

Figure 77: Results of 1,000 simulations showing the various building damages due to land subsidence

Figure 78: Graph showing the triangular distribution of building damage due to land subsidence

Emergency repairs (unplanned failures) in rural areas

To assess the financial impact related to land subsidence for infrastructure failures in rural areas, we developed a MCS model to estimate the range and likelihood of emergency repair costs over a 20-year horizon. This approach accounts for uncertainty in annual costs due to land subsidence.

According to available data¹⁸, the estimated infrastructure costs in rural areas of the Netherlands range from €300 million to €1 billion over a 40-year period (2010–2050). To derive an annual estimate, we divided this range evenly across the 40-year span. Where the lower bound and upper bound are €7.5 million and €25 million per year respectively.

¹⁸ <https://edepot.wur.nl/455148>

Given this range and the average value, and in the absence of more detailed historical data, we selected a triangular probability distribution to simulate annual emergency costs. This distribution is widely used in cost modelling where minimum, maximum, and most likely values are known but detailed probability data is not available. Each simulation modelled the emergency repair cost for one year, drawing a random value from the triangular distribution defined by the aforementioned parameters. To project the total cost over a 20-year period, we repeated the simulation for each year, generating a new random cost for each period. Each year's cost was then discounted to present value using a 3% annual discount rate, ensuring that the time value of money was accurately reflected.

A total of 1,000 simulations were performed, generating a distribution of possible total discounted costs across the 20-year analysis period. This output provides a probabilistic view of the financial risk posed by unplanned land subsidence-related infrastructure failures in rural areas, helping to inform the cost-benefit analysis.

Figure 79: Results of 1,000 simulations of total emergency repairs in rural areas over a 20-year period

Infrastructure Damage and Maintenance

According to a study conducted by the architectural and engineering consultancy Sweco¹⁹, commissioned by Platform Slappe Bodem, municipalities incur more than €1.7 billion in additional annual costs for the management and maintenance of roads and sewer systems as a result of ground subsidence. To assess the long-term financial impact, we calculated the present value of these additional costs over a 20-year period using a discount rate of 3%. This results in a total present value of €25,291,707,263.

Emergency repairs (unplanned failures) in urban areas

Deltares (2012)²⁰ estimated that urban infrastructure damage (streets, squares, landscaping, sewers, cables, pipes) due to subsidence caused by groundwater level drops amounts to

¹⁹ [Maintenance due to subsidence costs more than 1.7 billion euros per year; Additional investments needed for new construction up to €47,500 per home | Soft soil](#)

²⁰ [Fighting desiccation | Urban green-blue grids](#)

roughly €250 million per year. To assess the long-term financial impact, we calculated the present value of these additional costs over a 20-year period using a discount rate of 3%. This results in a total present value of €3,719,368,715.

Additional costs for the water authorities for water management up to 2040

To reflect the financial impact of increased responsibilities on regional water authorities (water authorities) stemming from land subsidence and climate adaptation, we included an annual cost of €5 million in the cost-benefit model. This figure captures additional expenditures related to water management—such as pumping, dike reinforcement, and system maintenance, as estimated by the Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency (PBL) in their 2016 report *Dalende bodems, stijgende kosten* (PBL publication 1064)²¹. The report projects that, between 2010 and 2050, water boards will face more than €200 million in additional costs.

For the purposes of this analysis, we modeled these additional expenditures as a recurring annual cost of €5 million over the 20-year period from 2025 to 2045, in line with the time horizon of this business case. To express these future costs in present-day terms, we applied a PV calculation using a 3% discount rate. This yields a total present value of €74,387,374.

Economical damage due to droughts (without Crop loss)

Similar to the previous costs, MCS was used to develop a model for the economical damage due to droughts. This allowed us to model a realistic range of possible future scenarios, including both common and rare high-impact events, while accounting for uncertainty in cost estimates over time.

We based our drought cost modeling on data from Mens et al. (2022)²² and historical events like the 2018 summer drought²³. The study estimated that annual economic consequences of droughts currently average around €372 million, rising to approximately €611 million by 2050 if no additional action is taken. However, rare extreme droughts — such as the 2018 event, have caused total quantifiable economic damage between €900 million to €1,650 million.

Initially, we considered modeling these rare extreme events separately, assigning them a fixed probability (e.g., once every 10 years). However, this approach overemphasized the tail risk and distorted the average annual damage. In particular, including the €1.65 billion damage estimate from 2018 directly in the simulation produced unrealistically high average costs.

To resolve this, we revised the model to use a single triangular distribution that incorporates both typical and moderately extreme drought years, while excluding once-in-a-generation outliers like the 2018 event from the main simulation.

We therefore defined the total economic drought damage with triangular distribution with the following parameters (Min: €372M, Mode: €611M, Max: €900M). This captures the

²¹ [Dalende bodems, stijgende kosten](#)

²² [Kingdom of the Netherlands: From Floods to Droughts](#)

²³ <https://www.tweedekamer.nl/downloads/document?id=2019D52600#:~:text=De%20totale%20kwantificeerbare%20economische%20schade,worden%20en%20is%20in%20de>

expected variation in annual damages, while still allowing for high but not catastrophic outcomes. The €1.65 billion extreme event was acknowledged in the analysis, but excluded from the probabilistic model to maintain a credible average cost estimate for planning purposes.

To estimate the long-term economic impact of droughts under uncertainty, we developed a 20-year MCS model that applies a 3% annual discount rate to future costs. However, drought-related damages only occur when a drought actually happens, and in the Netherlands, droughts are not annual events.

As such, simply projecting expected costs over 20 years without accounting for the probability of occurrence would have overstated the financial impact. To address this, we consulted external risk data from the platform ThinkHazard24, which indicates a 20% likelihood of drought occurrence in the Netherlands over the next decade. This equates to an estimated annual drought probability of approximately 2.6%.

In our simulation model, each year in the 20-year horizon was treated independently. For each simulated year, we generated a random number between 0 and 1. If the number was below 0.026 (2.6% probability), that year was treated as a drought year. In those years only, a drought cost was simulated using our previously defined cost distribution (triangular distribution based on realistic minimum, mode, and maximum estimates). In non-drought years, the cost was set to zero.

Therefore, drought damages were only applied in years when droughts were simulated to occur, the timing of the events was randomized, reflecting real-world unpredictability, and costs were appropriately time-discounted, providing an accurate present value across simulations.

Figure 80: Results of 1,000 simulations showing the discounted economic drought damages (excluding crop loss) over 20-years period

²⁴ <https://www.thinkhazard.org/en/report/177-netherlands/DG>

Crop Loss due to Droughts

Because agriculture is a key sector heavily impacted by droughts, we chose to model agricultural crop losses as a distinct component within our simulation framework. Although agricultural losses are embedded within the broader category of economic drought damages, separating them allowed us to better understand the specific contribution of farming-related impacts to the total cost profile.

According to the Climate Damage Atlas²⁵, cumulative agricultural drought damage in the Netherlands between 2018 and 2050 is projected to fall between €24 million and €50 million under current climate conditions. The lower end of the estimate assumes farmers are able to irrigate effectively where possible, while the upper end reflects a scenario with minimal to no irrigation. We expect the actual figure to fall somewhere in between these two bounds.

To reflect this range and its uncertainty, we modelled annual agricultural crop losses using a triangular probability distribution, with parameters (Min: €24M, Mode: 35.5M, Max: 50M) selected to reflect the variability in outcomes based on different adaptation and exposure levels.

Importantly, agricultural damages were only simulated in years where droughts occurred. That is, for each year in the 20-year time horizon, if a drought was triggered based on a 2.6% annual probability (derived from national climate risk data²⁶), then crop damage was simulated using the distribution. In years without drought, crop losses were assumed to be zero.

Additionally, the timing of drought years was randomized across simulations, following the same logic used for general economic drought damages. Each year's loss was then discounted using a 3% annual discount rate to calculate the present value of those damages.

This approach ensured consistency across the model while accurately capturing the probabilistic and time-dependent nature of agricultural risk. It also enabled a clear assessment of agriculture's share of the total drought-related costs.

²⁵<https://klimaatadaptatienederland.nl/en/knowledge-dossiers/themes/drought/what-consequences-increasing-drought/>

²⁶<https://klimaatadaptatienederland.nl/en/knowledge-dossiers/themes/drought/what-consequences-increasing-drought/>

Figure 81: Results of 1,000 simulations representing the different discounted crop loss due to droughts over 20-year period

Cost of combating wildfires and site restoration

Unlike economic and agricultural damages from droughts, which only materialize when drought conditions occur, the cost of combating wildfires in the Netherlands was treated as a fixed annual expense. According to published data from Deltares²⁷, the country incurs an estimated €2.7 million per year in direct wildfire-related costs. These include firefighting operations, emergency response efforts, and post-fire site restoration activities. Given that significant wildfires now occur nearly every year, particularly in areas such as the Veluwe and Noord-Brabant, this cost was modeled as a consistent annual burden, without probabilistic variation. To integrate wildfire costs into the long-term financial framework, we calculated their present value over a 20-year horizon using a 3% discount rate. The result was a total present value of €40,169,182.

Costs related to floods

Building Damage due to floods

To evaluate flood-related risks and their associated damages across Dutch provinces, the flood probability map titled “Probability of a flood from sea, river or lake”, sourced from the Atlas voor de Leefomgeving²⁸, was utilized. This map was downloaded and georeferenced using the open-source GIS software QGIS²⁹, with provincial boundaries provided by the Nationaal Georegister³⁰. The georeferenced flood map was then spatially analyzed using a custom R³¹ script to determine the dominant flood risk category in each province by pixel count (Limburg 1 in 30, Overijssel, Gelderland, Utrecht 1 in 300, Groningen, Fryslân, Drenthe, Flevoland, North Holland, South Holland, North Brabant 1 in 3,000 and Zeeland 1 in 300,000 thanks to the extensive flood defenses and the delta project).

²⁷ [Hundreds of wildfires annually in the Netherlands | Deltares](#)

²⁸ <https://www.atlasleefomgeving.nl/>

²⁹ <http://www.qgis.org>

³⁰ <https://nationaalgeoregister.nl/geonetwork/srv/dut/catalog.search#/metadata/e73b01f6-28c7-4bb7-a782-e877e8113e2c>

³¹ <https://www.r-project.org/>

Figure 82: Map showing the probability of floods of different areas in the Netherlands

Building count per province data were sourced from the Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek (CBS)³². These figures provided the number of buildings per province, which were then used to estimate building-related damages under flood scenarios. Damage estimates assumed a triangular distribution for per-building flood damage with parameters: Minimum €5,000, Mode €35,000, and Maximum €120,000. To support our flood damage distribution parameters, we rely on both empirical damage data and the official Dutch flood damage model (SSM2017). The minimum (€5,000) aligns with small-scale insurance payouts: insurers handled approximately 25,000 claims in the July 2021 Limburg floods, totaling €180–211 million, yielding an average claim of €7,000–8,500, with many minor intrusions in the €5,000–€10,000 range (Verbond van Verzekeraars)³³. The mode (€35,000) reflects the most common damage level for substantially flooded buildings. Although Valkenburg had ~10,116 total buildings, only ~3,000 were flooded, with €200 million allocated to building repair (50% of €400 million total damage), resulting in an average of €66,000 per flooded building, suggesting the modal damage clusters around €30k–€50k. Finally, the maximum (€120,000) corresponds to a near-total structural and contents loss under deep inundation, consistent with the SSM2017 flood damage model used by Deltares and Rijkswaterstaat^{34,35}.

³² StatLine - Housing stock and non-residential properties, 2012-2025

³³ <https://www.verzekeraars.nl/publicaties/actueel/watersnood-limburg-ruim-95-particuliere-schades-afgehandeld-door-verzekeraars#:~:text=Watersnood%20Limburg%3A%20ruim%2095%25%20particuliere%20schades%20afgehandeld%20door%20verzekeraars,-Op%20deze%20pagina&text=Uit%20een%20vijfde%20inventarisatie%20van,de%20zakelijke%20schades%20hebben%20afgehandeld.>

³⁴

https://pure.tudelft.nl/ws/portalfiles/portal/176468041/View_of_Rapid_damage_assessment_caused_by_the_flooding_event_2021_in_Limburg_Netherlands.pdf

³⁵ https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/jfr3.12713?utm_source

StatLine
Stock of dwellings and non-dwellings, 2012-2025
Modified on: 27 June 2025

Function of use		Subject															
Dwelling and non-dwelling total		Dwelling															
Regions	Periods	Starting stock	New construction	Other addition	Demolition	Other withdrawals	Correction	Balance stock	Final stock balance	Starting stock	New construction	Other addition	Demolition	Other withdrawals	Correction	Balance stock	
number																	
Groningen (PV)	2025 April*	333 643	118	35	91	34	-23	5	333 648	295 043	105	21	84	16	-25	1	2
Fryslân (PV)	2025 April*	370 523	148	79	103	38	8	94	370 617	312 742	106	46	92	18	6	48	3
Drenthe (PV)	2025 April*	270 638	196	70	14	41	-8	203	270 841	230 805	177	55	7	13	-13	199	2
Overijssel (PV)	2025 April*	613 957	390	183	68	82	2	425	614 382	532 548	333	119	44	50	0	358	5
Flevoland (PV)	2025 April*	212 104	200	25	31	7	1	186	212 290	187 459	90	20	10	0	0	100	1
Gelderland (PV)	2025 April*	1 100 002	793	328	164	124	-4	829	1 100 834	959 757	674	245	115	68	-11	725	5
Utrecht (PV)	2025 April*	699 621	1 162	378	29	337	13	1 187	700 808	621 385	1 024	51	11	306	5	763	6
North Holland (PV)	2025 April*	1 635 667	1 490	337	139	230	118	1 576	1 637 243	1 423 919	1 243	208	75	116	-8	1 252	14
South Holland (PV)	2025 April*	2 003 013	949	344	328	180	60	845	2 003 858	1 776 471	898	263	258	64	61	900	17
Zeeland (PV)	2025 April*	248 902	237	71	31	46	10	241	249 143	193 871	214	60	7	14	6	259	1
North Brabant (PV)	2025 April*	1 384 906	869	376	253	95	25	922	1 385 828	1 204 492	712	233	199	33	28	741	12
Limburg (PV)	2025 April*	633 304	378	176	56	62	-19	417	633 721	552 210	332	143	25	35	-16	399	5

Source: CBS

Figure 83: Snapshot of the central office of statistics (CBS) of the Netherlands showing the building count per province as per April 2025

An infrastructure damage cost of €51.5 million was included as a conditional cost, incurred only when a flood occurs, based on documented reports from Rijkswaterstaat and ProRail regarding road, bridge, and rail disruptions³⁶.

For agricultural losses, two conditional impacts were included:

- A loss of €170 million if a flood occurs exclusively in North Brabant (based on region-specific data points)³⁷.
- A loss of €600 million if both Groningen and Overijssel are affected; if only one of these provinces floods, the loss is €300 million³⁸.

To capture uncertainty and variability in outcomes, a total of 12,000 Monte Carlo simulations were conducted—1,000 simulations per province. In each simulation, it was randomly determined whether a flood occurred in a given year based on each province’s flood probability. If a flood occurred, a random year within a 20-year time horizon was assigned to reflect the uncertainty in timing. The present value of damages was then calculated accordingly, accounting for the time value of money through discounting.

All expected damage figures, building-related, infrastructural, and agricultural, were aggregated annually and then projected over a 20-year period, incorporating flood probabilities, conditional damage scenarios, and present value calculations.

³⁶ Hoogwaterbeschermingsprogramma | Tweede Kamer der Staten-Generaal

³⁷ Dutch hail horror: a year later

³⁸ <https://www.pbl.nl/sites/default/files/downloads/773001037.pdf>

	Buildings Count	Probability of Flood	Damage Min	5,000	Damage Mode	35,000	Damage Max	120,000	Simulation Province				Infrastructure Add. Cost Simulation		Total Damage across all 12 provinces per a single year in a time frame of 20 years		
									Building Count	Flood Probability	Flood Occurred	Damage Per Building	Total Damage				
Groningen	333,648	0.0003333333333333							1 Groningen	333,648	0.0003333333333333	0	88,949	-	0	1	0.00
Fryslân	370,617	0.0003333333333333							1 Fryslân	370,617	0.0003333333333333	0	39,360	-	0	2	0.00
Drenthe	270,841	0.0003333333333333							1 Drenthe	270,841	0.0003333333333333	0	41,586	-	0	3	0.00
Overijssel	614,382	0.0003333333333333							1 Overijssel	614,382	0.0003333333333333	0	52,328	-	0	4	0.00
Flevoland	212,290	0.0003333333333333							1 Flevoland	212,290	0.0003333333333333	0	25,643	-	0	5	0.00
Gelderland	1,100,834	0.0003333333333333							1 Gelderland	1,100,834	0.0003333333333333	0	59,472	-	0	6	0.00
Utrecht	700,808	0.0003333333333333							1 Utrecht	700,808	0.0003333333333333	0	29,357	-	0	7	0.00
North Holland	1,637,243	0.0003333333333333							1 North Holland	1,637,243	0.0003333333333333	0	52,491	-	0	8	0.00
South Holland	2,003,858	0.0003333333333333							1 South Holland	2,003,858	0.0003333333333333	0	53,683	-	0	9	0.00
Zeeland	249,143	0.0000033333333333							1 Zeeland	249,143	0.0000033333333333	0	23,309	-	0	10	0.00
North Brabant	1,385,828	0.0003333333333333							1 North Brabant	1,385,828	0.0003333333333333	0	38,916	-	0	11	0.00
Limburg	633,721	0.0333333333333333							1 Limburg	633,721	0.0333333333333333	0	26,671	-	0	12	0.00
									2 Groningen	333,648	0.0003333333333333	0	86,720	-	0	13	0.00
									2 Fryslân	370,617	0.0003333333333333	0	70,282	-	0	14	0.00
									2 Drenthe	270,841	0.0003333333333333	0	46,261	-	0	15	0.00
									2 Overijssel	614,382	0.0003333333333333	0	38,211	-	0	16	0.00
									2 Flevoland	212,290	0.0003333333333333	0	50,906	-	0	17	0.00
									2 Gelderland	1,100,834	0.0003333333333333	0	53,977	-	0	18	0.00
									2 Utrecht	700,808	0.0003333333333333	0	56,367	-	0	19	0.00
									2 North Holland	1,637,243	0.0003333333333333	0	52,993	-	0	20	0.00
									2 South Holland	2,003,858	0.0003333333333333	0	70,887	-	0	21	0.00
									2 Zeeland	249,143	0.0000033333333333	0	21,459	-	0	22	0.00
									2 North Brabant	1,385,828	0.0003333333333333	0	27,499	-	0	23	0.00
									2 Limburg	633,721	0.0333333333333333	0	28,361	-	0	24	0.00

Figure 84: Snapshot of the 12,000 simulation pertaining building, infrastructure and crop damage due to floods

The detailed calculations supporting the analysis of this section (4.4) can be found in Annex G.

4.4.1. Calculations

After calculating all fixed and variable costs, where the variable cost components were further modelled using Monte Carlo simulations based on their respective probability distributions and parameters, three scenarios were established based on the simulation results: the most likely, the worst-case, and the best-case. The most likely scenario was determined using the average of all simulated variable cost outcomes. Additionally, an alternative version of the most likely scenario was considered, in which a single value was randomly selected from the simulation results. This approach allows for coverage across the full range of the distribution. However, it is worth noting that over 1,000 simulations, the average of these randomly selected values consistently approximates the original mean-based estimate. Meanwhile, the worst-case and best-case scenarios corresponded to the maximum and minimum simulated costs, respectively.

To estimate the potential net benefit, a 1% reduction was applied to the total cost as an indicative assumption of the future savings that the WISE solution could offer by mitigating damages related to floods, land subsidence, droughts and fires. This adjusted cost (avoided damages) was then compared to the total cost of the 21 water authorities in the Netherlands, resulting in the projected net benefit under each scenario.

Based on the calculations for the most likely scenario, a 1% reduction in current costs results in an estimated net benefit of approximately €427,157,131, with a standard deviation of €11,875,675. In the best-case scenario, the projected net benefit increases to around €728,156,364, with a standard deviation of €188,244,254. Conversely, under the worst-case scenario, the estimated net benefit is approximately negative €43,130,473, with a standard deviation of €5,044,020. These figures represent average outcomes derived from different cost percentage reductions, which produced a range of results based on the probabilistic modeling of variable cost components in addition to the annual costs.

Figure 85: Snapshot of a Representative Summary Table of the Net Benefit Across the Three Scenarios
 Note: The table is dynamically generated using Monte Carlo simulation; results update with each recalculation.

The detailed calculations supporting this analysis can be found in Annex G.

4.4.2. Sensitivity Analysis

A sensitivity analysis was conducted to evaluate the variation in expected net benefits derived from the WISE solution for the water management authorities and end users. This analysis tested a range of cost reduction scenarios to assess the robustness of the projected benefits. Specifically, the expected net benefit was analyzed under cost reduction assumptions of 1%, 3%, 5%, 10%, 15%, and 20%, for each of the three scenarios mentioned above.

In addition to cost reduction scenarios, the sensitivity of the results to changes in the discount rate was also examined. The baseline analysis applied a 3% discount rate; however, we also assessed the impact of lowering this rate to 2% and increasing it to 4%. Under the most likely scenario and assuming a 1% reduction in current costs, lowering the discount rate to 2% increased the estimated net benefit from approximately €427,157,131 (standard deviation €11,875,675) to €442,171,630 (standard deviation €13,455,793). Conversely, increasing the discount rate to 4% reduced the net benefit to approximately €400,031,931, with a standard deviation of €11,069,577. These results illustrate the sensitivity of the projected benefits to variations in the discount rate, further reinforcing the importance of carefully considering the assumptions underpinning the economic evaluation.

4.5. Risks

Embarking on a new project is an exciting venture, but it's important to acknowledge that such initiatives inherently involve risks that can create significant challenges. If not properly identified and managed in advance, these investment risks may lead to delays, cost overruns, and jeopardize the overall success of the WISE project. Therefore, recognizing and addressing

potential risks from the beginning is essential for achieving a more efficient and resilient project execution. Within this framework, a risk assessment has been conducted as part of the business case development.

The table below outlines the identified risks along with their estimated impact and likelihood.

Foreseen risks	Impact	Likelihood of occurrence
Technical solution not reaching expected performance	Medium	Medium
Data availability and quality limitations	High	Medium
Limited end-user adoption or engagement	Medium	Medium
The temporal and or spatial resolution of the soil moisture maps is too coarse	High	Medium
High dependency of ground truth data instrumented sites and problems with the scalability of solution	High	High
The decision makers-end users are not competence on the use-analysis and extract decision from PCP_WISE outputs	High	High
Other geopolitical-territorial factors play a most important role on the decision infrastructures and planning	Medium	Medium
The solution developed during the PCP do not reach TRL8 level	High	Medium
The solution developed during the PCP are not compatible /interoperable with the end users' / buyers' existing systems	High	High
The selected providers are not able to deliver within the defined time frame and/or budget	High	High
Contractors unable to deliver the technical solution	High	Low
False sense of security and over-reliance on technology	High	Low

Table 36: Business case risk table

4.6. Conclusion

The PCP initiative for the WISE project presents a compelling opportunity to address the mounting environmental and infrastructural challenges posed by climate change, land subsidence, droughts, and floods in the Netherlands. Through extensive cost modeling, probabilistic simulations, and sensitivity analysis, this business case has demonstrated both the urgency of the problem and the significant value that an anticipatory and integrated solution like WISE can deliver.

The total present value of all costs for implementing the WISE solution across 21 water authorities is estimated at €176.7 million. When weighed against the staggering projected damages from unmitigated environmental risks, ranging from billions in infrastructure repairs to annual agricultural and economic losses, the financial prudence of investing in the WISE solution becomes clear.

Monte Carlo simulations confirm that even a modest 1% reduction in climate- and subsidence-related costs due to WISE interventions could yield a net benefit of approximately €427 million in the most likely scenario. In the best-case outcome, this benefit increases to over €728 million. These results not only validate the economic viability of the WISE approach but also illustrate the potential scale of savings through risk-informed decision-making and proactive infrastructure management.

Furthermore, the sensitivity analysis confirms that greater reductions in damage costs, achievable through effective deployment and scaling of WISE, could exponentially increase the return on investment, reinforcing the strategic importance of this procurement initiative.

In conclusion, the WISE PCP offers an economically sound strategy for water authorities to future-proof their infrastructure, buildings, agriculture and service delivery.

5. Annex A: User Story Lines

5.1. Cluster Group I

User Group: Government & Ministry of the Environment

Mission	Law and regulations
Benefit	Information for policy development

User Group: Environmental supervision + water protection Finland: ELY-Centre, City of Helsinki Environment Services, SYKE

Mission	Management of water resources, warn society about floods and droughts Adaptation and Mitigation
Pain Points	How to monitor and manage water quality and quantity Warn people and businesses about floods Catchment-based water management
Tools	Water level measurements, flood risk mapping, modelling water quantity changes based on weather, climate model reports SYKE's prognosis for water situation
Data Sources	Water quantity Land use data Some 'social' data about peoples' behaviour
Solution	Real-time / up-to-date data water quantity data Better understanding of water surface flow and percolation to groundwater Updated land-use data and current plans for land use Availability of data between administrative organisations/sharing
Technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Correct measurements of surface temperature - Correct measurements of soil moisture, water level in channels and lakes/reservoirs, soil frost measurements, ground water level monitoring, temperature
Non-technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continuous monitoring to detect anomalies - Alert System: Up-to-date information (not delayed) - Working Calibration - Data space for all the data and an API to access the data - AO model to forecast flood risk and create warnings

Acceptance Criteria (technical + non-technical)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data updates in 1-2h intervals - Crisis management: 0,5-1 hour interval
Benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Warn local residents and businesses when risk of flooding or severe drought is forecasted

User Group: City: Urban planners, engineers, (landscape) architects

Mission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To identify and address groundwater-related issues in urban planning and construction projects, aiming to minimize negative impacts and promote sustainable water management. - Stormwater-related issues - Ecological value of small waters
Pain Points	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Difficulty in accessing and utilizing available groundwater/stormwater information during the planning and construction phases - Reliance on costly and time-consuming consultant services/modelling - Lack of a user-friendly tool to easily model and evaluate different scenarios - Frequent use of estimations
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scalgo, /Fluitit, data files, excel sheets, (models) - (Fluidit or modelling services are not regularly used by the city) - GIS viewing service to monitor land use, nature values, HSY stormwater pipes
Data Sources	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ground water level (riverbeds, streams and ditches, land cover, sewage system areas, weather observations, flood risks) 2. Elevation model
Solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Usability data for planning of mitigation measures - Scenarios based on real data and predictions - (Real-time soil moisture and groundwater level data, land subsidence data, surface runoff + pipes) - Combining different existing data sources in a database - Automated impact assessment of urban planning
Technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integration of satellite imagery and ground-based sensors - Good network of online groundwater level data (daily measurements) - Possibility to use the resulting model in everyday GIS services instead of a new user interface

Non-technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continuous monitoring (daily measurements) - Data updates at least twice a month - A user-friendly tool for scenario planning and impact assessment, enabling proactive problem-solving - Changes of groundwater level, speed is quite slow
Acceptance Criteria (technical + non-technical)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High-resolution data (5x5m grid) – resolution depends on the size of the observed area (100x100km or 2x2km) - Minimum depth should be up to and including the root zone
Benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved access to and utilization of data for better-informed decision-making - Reduced reliance on external consultants - Potential for increased use of sustainable solutions - Better understanding and management of groundwater-related risks

User Group: City: Climate unit

Mission	The city should establish a "desired level of adaptation" in respect to climate risks, this could support scenario work and decision making.
Pain Points	Currently, considerable difficulty in monitoring the true state of urban green infra, esp. on private land, after the construction and monitoring the capacity and state of NBS water management solutions.
Tools	Hydrological model modelled with Fluidit for stormwater management (City Centre)
Data Sources	Surface modelling + sewer network modelling (land cover data, elevation model, sewers)
Solution	Designers would benefit from tools to estimate the mitigation impacts of green structures, to verify that the wanted level is met. Detailed understanding of green elements & their impacts (water+heat) on a detailed planning level is largely lacking.
Non-technical Requirements	Capability to integrate different climate scenarios and historical data.
Benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved understanding of urban water dynamics under various climate scenarios - Impact of drought and flooding on overall city resilience

User Group: City: Maintenance

Mission	Predict and prevent property damage
Pain Points	Difficulty in predicting the impact of flooding/subsidence on building foundations
Solution	Green parks water balance (drought+flood)

Non-technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Alert System and communication for residents - Automated closing of stormwater pipe systems
Benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Effective resource allocation and management - Reduced costs in property & infra damages

User Group: Constructors (e.g. companies)

Mission	Requirement: Keeping the construction site waters clean
Pain Points	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The effect of construction on water management - Where and how to direct the water flow at the construction site
Tools	Scalgo, Fluidit, data files, excel sheets, models
Solution	Help for construction planning: Scenarios of plans and models of water flow during the construction and after
Non-technical Requirements	Real-time data about the effects of construction plans Offline functionality for field use.
Acceptance Criteria (technical + non-technical)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - risks: 0,5-1 hour - Reliable assessment of the impact of drought and flooding on infrastructure and urban spaces
Benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improving compliance with laws and regulations - Enhanced water balance and quality during the construction events

User Group: Rescue Department

Mission	Anticipate and prevent disasters & injuries
Benefit	Effective prediction of crisis areas and resource allocation and management

User Group: Insurance Companies

Mission	Interest in minimizing insurance damages
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User Group: Private property owners

Mission	Interest in protecting own property
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User Group: Citizens

Mission	Interest in local water stability & water quality
Pain Points	Route to work sometimes flooded Water quality of surrounding surface water and sea water (e.g. green & blue algae)
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Web browser on mobile phone - Web browser on desktop
Data Sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FMI sea water level webpage (current status and forecast) - SYKE webpage
Solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Citizen science - Easy to use app for citizens with which they can send observations to some nation-wide system from the field
Technical Requirements	Must work on mobile phone without any additional equipment. Optionally some external probes for most enthusiastic citizens.
Benefit	Better understanding of the state of the environment

5.2. Cluster Group II

User Group: National authorities (e.g. SK Ministry of environment)

Mission	Utilisation of national spatial data infrastructure as well as climate change adaptation strategy implementation support
Pain Points	Lack of availability of relevant data sets as well as demonstration of their usage
Tools	<u>National Geoportal</u> <u>Climate change adaptation platform</u>
Data Sources	<u>Spatial data registry</u>
Solution	Availability of the <u>Cluster 2 output datasets</u> via machine (API) and human readable interfaces (GUI) Integration with the National Geoportal
Technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support for data collection and maintenance - Visualisation and communication
Non-technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - User access management - Usability - Scalability - Reliability - Security

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support - Notifications
Acceptance Criteria (technical + non-technical)	Data updates: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In peace time: Monthly basis - During crisis: 0,5-1 hour interval - With access to previous historical data
Benefit	Delivery a comprehensive overview of flood risks to improve decision-making and urban planning

User Group: Bratislava the Capital City of Slovakia and Metropolitan institute

Mission	Support with defining a measurable level of green-blue infrastructure adaptation thereby facilitating effective planning and decision-making
Pain Points	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring of urban greenery due to private land - Monitoring of urban water balance and runoff due to technical and data support
Tools	Local GIS tools
Data Sources	Spatial data, data files, excel sheets, models
Solution	A tool for validating the application of green-blue infrastructure in the context of climate change adaptation
Technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support for data collection and maintenance - Analytical features - Visualisation and communication
Non-technical Requirements	Concepts and guidelines Capability to integrate different climate scenarios
Acceptance Criteria (technical + non-technical)	Data updates: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In peace time: Monthly basis - During crisis: 0,5-1 hour interval - With access to previous historical data
Benefit	Enable early identification of high-risk areas and prediction of potential water-related events

User Group: Private Companies

Mission	Improved data exchange between public and private sector
Pain Points	Lack of harmonised data flow / integration between governmental and private ICT solutions
Tools	Special modeling systems (Hydrological model, surface runoff modeling, flood modeling and others)
Data Sources	Non structured (pdf) and basic structured data (csv, excel)

Solution	Toll / service allowing simple data transformation and exchange
Technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support for standardise integration interfaces (API, GUI) - ETL transformations availability - Data flow scheduler
Non-technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - User access management - Reliability - Security - Reporting
Acceptance Criteria (technical + non-technical)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documentation of API and GUI, - Availability 24/7 - Integration schedule planner - Reports/Statistics
Benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved data/information transfer between government and business - Higher quality of service - Possible integrations to third parties

User Group: Citizens

Mission	Support in understandable and trustable communication of floods and related climate change aspects
Pain Points	Lack of tools / services able to provide the flood and climate change related information in easy and user attractive way
Tools	GIS, data analytic tools
Data Sources	Bratislava data portal https://data.bratoslava.sk/
Solution	Available relevant datasets and map apps @ https://data.bratoslava.sk
Technical Requirements	Interoperable data and service made available in standardised way
Non-technical Requirements	Intuitive and user friendly interface
Acceptance Criteria (technical + non-technical)	Availability of the app/service for generic citizens
Benefit	Improved awareness about the the floods and climate change for wide public users

User Group: Wastewater (WW) utilities (Denmark)

Mission	Treat wastewater in an environmentally responsible way, and manage technical and climate water
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Pain Points	<p>More extreme weather and increased rainfall causes rising of surface near ground water that seeps into the sewage system, resulting in sludge contamination of natural environments, excess financial expenses on moving and treating water that is not wastewater and wear and tear on the ww infrastructure.</p> <p>Hard to locate where and to what extent the water enters.</p>
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Calculating pump data in dry weather in wells (power consumption) - Sometimes measuring in each manhole how much water passes through - expensive and cumbersome only in problematic locations - Going down wells in rainy weather to find leaks - expensive and cumbersome - TV inspection
Data Sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flow, water level, velocity in wells in specific areas (special cases) - Power consumption data on pumps in sewage wells - Looking down the well in rainy weather - TV inspection - Flow meters where we pump wastewater
Solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visualising groundwater in the context of the pipe network - Potential map where the colour changes the closer the groundwater is to the pipe network, and vice versa when water shortage causes risk of subsidence damage
Technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 50x50 m resolution - Water level with +/- 8 cm

User Group: Emergency services (THW)

Mission	To better anticipate and respond to water-related crisis situations and ensure safety of deployed emergency services
Pain Points	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Availability of relevant data dependent on local administrative structure - Distribution of relevant data on different platforms - Provision of data in a wide variety of formats, often requiring preparation before use - Limited modeling/forecasting capability of existing solutions - Data availability only in the form of a finished map product, but not as a data stream in the form of WMS or WFS, which can be integrated into own GIS
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GIS - in-situ measurements (e.g. from mobile flood levels and drones)

Data Sources	<p>Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - weather data (current and forecast) - flood hazard maps - sometimes satellite images (Copernicus and others) - sometimes drone images (own drone units deployable) => RGB & LIDAR - water masks - sometimes digital terrain model - water level data (own mobile level deployable) and forecasts - data from dike runners (own unit for this deployable) Satellite pictures (e.g. Copernicus, DLR) <p>Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - geodata mostly from local/regional/national authorities (e.g. forestry, water authority, environmental protection agency, national weather authority) - In-situ data (e.g. from own drone measurements, self-assessed dyke runner data)
Solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standardized, openly available data collection - Tool with modelling capabilities (e.g. simulation of effectiveness of potential counter measures (e.g. of deploying a mobile dyke) and simulation of impact of potential dyke damage scenarios) and then being able to export the simulation results into our own system <p>--> a flood hazard and risk and response prediction tool</p>
Technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standardized, openly available data (in line with OGC standard; accessibility as much as possible via services like WFS & WMS) - Data intersection possibility for the integration with locally utilized command and control software/information system - Possibility to enter field site data (e.g. discovery of dyke damages) - Possibility of querying different data sources (APIs), different data formats, normalizing them and making them usable as uniform data
Non-technical Requirements	User-friendly/intuitive handling of core functions
Benefit	Addressing the aforementioned pain points

User Group: City of Helsinki: Urban Planners, engineers, architects

Mission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To identify and address groundwater-related issues in urban planning and construction projects, aiming to
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	<p>minimize negative impacts and promote sustainable water management.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stormwater-related issues <p>Ecological value of small waters</p>
Pain Points	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Difficulty in accessing and utilizing available groundwater/stormwater information during the planning and construction phases - Reliance on costly and time-consuming consultant services/modelling - Lack of a user-friendly tool to easily model and evaluate different scenarios <p>Frequent use of estimations</p>
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scalgo, /Fluitit, data files, excel sheets, (models) - (Fluidit or modelling services are not regularly used by the city) <p>GIS viewing service to monitor land use, nature values, HSY stormwater pipes</p>
Data Sources	<p>3. Ground water level (riverbeds, streams and ditches, land cover, sewage system areas, weather observations, flood risks)</p> <p>Elevation model</p>
Solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Usability data for planning of mitigation measures - Scenarios based on real data and predictions - (Real-time soil moisture and groundwater level data, land subsidence data, surface runoff + pipes) - Combining different existing data sources in a database - Automated impact assessment of urban planning
Technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integration of satellite imagery and ground-based sensors - Good network of online groundwater level data (daily measurements) <p>Possibility to use the resulting model in everyday GIS services instead of a new user interface</p>
Non-technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continuous monitoring (daily measurements) - Data updates at least twice a month - A user-friendly tool for scenario planning and impact assessment, enabling proactive problem-solving - Changes of groundwater level, speed is quite slow
Acceptance Criteria (technical + non-technical)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High-resolution data (5x5m grid) – resolution depends on the size of the observed area (100x100km or 2x2km)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Minimum depth should be up to and including the root zone
Benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved access to and utilization of data for better-informed decision-making - Reduced reliance on external consultants - Potential for increased use of sustainable solutions - Better understanding and management of groundwater-related risks

User Group: City of Helsinki: Climate unit

Mission	The city should establish a "desired level of adaptation" in respect to climate risks; this could support scenario work and decision making.
Pain Points	Currently, considerable difficulty in monitoring the true state of urban green infra, esp. on private land, after the construction and monitoring the capacity and state of NBS water management solutions
Tools	Hydrological model modelled with Fluidit for stormwater management (City Centre)
Data Sources	Surface modeling + sewer network modeling (land cover data, elevation model, sewers)
Solution	Designers would benefit from tools to estimate the mitigation impacts of green structures, to verify that the wanted level is met. Detailed understanding of green elements & their impacts (water+heat) on a detailed planning level is largely lacking.
Non-technical Requirements	Capability to integrate different climate scenarios and historical data.
Benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved understanding of urban water dynamics under various climate scenarios - Impact of drought and flooding on overall city resilience

5.3. Cluster Group III

User Group: Terrain Managing Organizations (ANB, Natuurpunt, Staatsbosbeheer, Natuurmonumenten, private owners)

Mission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preserve and restore heathland, forest, and wetland ecosystems under increasing drought stress - Optimize landscape-level water retention and buffering capacity
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitor ecological drought impact and anticipate wildfire risk in protected Natura 2000 habitats - Improve knowledge-based adaptive management strategies.
Pain Points	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of continuous, spatially explicit insight into soil moisture and vegetation stress dynamics - Unclear correlations between drought parameters, habitat vulnerability, and wildfire occurrence - Limited ability to prioritize restoration and management interventions based on real-time ecosystem conditions. - Current tools rely on sporadic field observations and expert intuition rather than data-driven dashboards.
Tools	GIS systems, management plans, field-based drought indices
Data Sources	Groundwater level networks (e.g. Pidpa/Evides), local meteo stations, Natura 2000 monitoring data, vegetation surveys, past wildfire event records, Sentinel-2 and NDVI from Copernicus
Solution	<p>An integrated decision-support dashboard combining:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Weekly high-resolution (30m) soil moisture, surface water and vegetation stress maps - Real-time indicators for ecological drought and wildfire risk - Historical and seasonal trends for adaptive management planning - Scenario functionality for simulating the effect of water retention infrastructure and drought management measures.
Technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Temporal granularity: weekly updates - Spatial resolution: 30m - Integration of ground truth and remote sensing data - API access for GIS integration - Scenario modelling capabilities - Mobile-compatible interface for field use.
Non-technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Multilingual support (NL/EN) - Inclusion of management-specific KPIs (e.g. habitat condition thresholds) - Co-development with managers to ensure usability - User training and documentation - Data governance arrangements across cross-border stakeholders
Acceptance Criteria (technical + non-technical)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Validated weekly updated maps - Historical trends accessible per habitat type - Usability in-field and in desktop environments - Integration of Natura 2000 management targets into alerting functions - Pilot tested in cross-border context between Flanders and the Netherlands
Benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prioritization of fieldwork and adaptive interventions

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduced ecosystem degradation - Early detection of critical drought conditions and vegetation stress - Proactive wildfire risk planning - Evidence-based support for funding and policy justification (e.g. Blue Deal, LIFE)
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User Group: Farmers and agricultural land users (arable crops and livestock) adjacent to the reserve

Mission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sustain crop production under changing climatic conditions - Optimize irrigation and water storage practices - Comply with environmental regulations (e.g. buffer zones, nitrate rules)
Pain Points	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No within field-level insight into root zone soil moisture trends - Uncertainty about when to irrigate or reduce water use - Current irrigation decisions rely on gut feeling or meteorological proxies - No integration with CAP data or drought forecasting
Tools	Hand-held probes, irrigation calendars, some use of agro apps, weather forecast apps
Data Sources	CAP parcel data, Sentinel-2 NDVI, local weather data, groundwater levels
Solution	Farmer Advisory Dashboard providing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Within parcel-level drought alerts - Weekly soil moisture forecasts at root depth - Seasonal predictions linked to yield risk - Precision recommendations for irrigation timing and volumes
Technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High-resolution ($\leq 30\text{m}$) root zone moisture and vegetation vigour data - Map-based and tabular interface - Mobile access with offline mode - Customizable thresholds per crop type - Compatibility with existing farm data management systems and precision-guided variable rate application systems
Non-technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Multilingual support - Link with agricultural advisory services - Explanation of uncertainty and confidence levels - Data protection for private parcels
Acceptance Criteria (technical + non-technical)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dashboard tested on multiple (types of) farms - Comparison with existing irrigation practices - Feedback from farmers on usability and trust - Demonstrated water use reduction or stabilization

Benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved drought resilience of farming systems - More efficient water use - Reduced friction between conservation and agriculture stakeholders - Support for precision agriculture in vulnerable areas
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User Group: Fire services and crisis management authorities (local fire brigades, provincial crisis cell, ANB)

Mission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Protect human lives and assets from nature and forest fires - Improve pre-crisis planning and early warning - Support proactive fuel management (e.g. mowing, prescribed burning) and targeted patrols
Pain Points	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Current fire risk models are not adapted to local vegetation and soil types - Lack of spatially accurate, timely drought-fire coupling indicators - Manual processes dominate early-warning systems - No integration of vegetation condition or soil dryness with dispatching systems
Tools	Static fire hazard maps, historical fire data, paper-based alert protocols, basic weather apps
Data Sources	Local meteo forecasts (wind, RH, temperature), field observations, EFFIS fire alerts, past fire records, national emergency management systems
Solution	<p>Fire Risk Monitoring System integrating:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Near-real-time vegetation dryness and soil moisture indicators - Dynamic risk maps updated daily or weekly - Alert thresholds linked to operational SOPs - Compatibility with emergency dispatch platforms (e.g. BE-Alert, 112)
Technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Spatial resolution $\leq 100\text{m}$ - Update frequency: daily during high-risk periods, weekly otherwise - Alert API integration - Cloud-based with offline mobile view for field units - Support for threshold calibration per region
Non-technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Involvement in co-design of alerting logic - Cross-border data exchange protocols (BE-NL) - Training for regional fire teams - Inclusion of legal fire ban zones - Trust and adoption from both fire brigades and reserve managers

Acceptance Criteria (technical + non-technical)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fire danger indices specific to heathland, forests and forested residential area conditions validated against historical events - Alert notifications integrated into local emergency workflows - Feedback loop from field users to calibrate the model
Benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduced wildfire occurrence and severity - Timelier response and fewer false alerts - Improved collaboration between land managers and fire services - Prevention-oriented planning (e.g. fuel load reduction)

User Group: Drinking water extraction companies (Evides, Pidpa)

Mission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensure long-term availability and quality of drinking water resources - Monitor recharge zones and groundwater levels near abstraction points - Anticipate the effects of prolonged droughts on yield, recharge and ecological conditions - Contribute to integrated land and water management at the landscape level
Pain Points	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Groundwater recharge estimates are uncertain, especially under climate extremes - Difficult to assess impact of drought on future yield and abstraction permits - No early warnings for critical drawdown in ecologically sensitive zones - Lack of harmonized data with land/nature managers for joint decision-making
Tools	Groundwater monitoring systems, modeling software (e.g. MODFLOW), GIS, environmental reporting tools
Data Sources	Piezometers, satellite evapotranspiration data, soil moisture sensors, precipitation records, land use maps, abstraction permits and volumes
Solution	<p>A hydrological intelligence tool that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maps spatial variation in soil moisture and recharge - Integrates evapotranspiration trends, drought indices, and drawdown risk - Flags potential ecological thresholds near Natura 2000 zones - Provides scenario simulations for yield under different drought conditions
Technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integration with piezometric monitoring and recharge models - Spatial resolution $\leq 100m$ - Monthly to weekly updates - Capability to model recharge scenarios and drought thresholds

Non-technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cross-border interoperability (Flanders–Netherlands) - Agreements on data sharing with nature managers - Support for integrating outputs into environmental reporting to regulators
Acceptance Criteria (technical + non-technical)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consistent alignment of tool outputs with regulatory thresholds - Pilot-tested for at least two abstraction zones in the park - Proven link between tool predictions and real-time observations
Benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Proactive management of groundwater resources - Early warning before recharge deficits become critical - Improved coordination with nature conservation objectives - Long-term safeguarding of potable water availability

User Group: Municipalities and intermunicipal collaborations (Kalmthout, Essen, Stabroek, Woensdrecht,...)

Mission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Protect public safety and infrastructure from drought and fire risks - Implement spatial planning and climate adaptation strategies - Install policies to ensure infrastructure permits are compatible with sustainable water management - Collaborate in regional water management (e.g. drought buffers, infiltration zones) - Inform citizens and align emergency protocols
Pain Points	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Difficulty in integrating nature/climate risks into spatial zoning plans - No real-time spatial risk maps for public communication or safety planning - Disconnect between local policies and regional climate risk data - Emergency response is reactive due to lack of early warning tools
Tools	GIS, municipal risk registers, planning tools, heat stress maps, emergency plans
Data Sources	Soil sealing/infiltration data, meteo and drought records, surface water levels, land use plans, vulnerability maps
Solution	<p>A municipal adaptation dashboard including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Spatialized drought/fire risk layers - Decision-support on where to invest in buffers, green infrastructure, and where infrastructure permits can be granted - Early warnings integrated into communication plans. - Tools to assess how nature-based solutions reduce local risk
Technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Web-based interface tailored to municipal system

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integration with municipal GIS and early warning platforms through API - Open standards (e.g. GeoJSON, WMS/WFS)
Non-technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Multilingual support - Training and capacity-building of municipal staff - Legal alignment with spatial planning requirements - Inclusion of citizen communication tools (e.g. alert apps, signage)
Acceptance Criteria (technical + non-technical)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Used in at least one drought/fire event response exercise - Feedback loop implemented with planning department and crisis coordinators - Risk zoning layer published in official spatial plan viewer
Benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased preparedness and reduced damages - Improved public trust through clear communication - Policy coherence between ecological, safety and climate goals - Evidence-based investment planning and infrastructure permit issuance (e.g. for drought buffers, Blue Deal)

User Group: Inhabitants and visitors

Mission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enjoy safe, accessible, and well-managed natural areas - Be informed about natural risks (fire, drought, access restrictions). - Participate in conservation awareness and responsible recreation.
Pain Points	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Little awareness of drought/fire risk and the reasons behind temporary access restrictions - No personalized or location-specific warnings (e.g. trail closures, smoke hazards) - Confusion about who is responsible during fire or drought events
Tools	Park website, signage, mobile maps, local news outlets
Data Sources	Visitor count sensors, social media posts, trail apps, weather and air quality forecasts
Solution	<p>A visitor interaction and alert module:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Real-time visitor information platform (web/app/signs) - Dynamic alerts on access restrictions, air quality, trail closures - Education on drought/fire risk and conservation needs - Integration with national alert systems (e.g. BE-Alert)
Technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Geolocation-based alerts - Integration with park website and social media - Compatibility with hiking/cycling app APIs

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low bandwidth/ offline capabilities for field use
Non-technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clear communication tone and visuals. - Multilingual messages (NL/FR/EN) - Alignment with park regulations and emergency procedures - Involvement of local tourism offices
Acceptance Criteria (technical + non-technical)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Alerts received by ≥80% of park visitors during test period - Visitor surveys show increased awareness of drought/fire issues - Reduced incidents of unauthorized access during closures
Benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased safety for park users - Higher support for drought/fire restrictions - Improved coexistence between recreation and conservation - Greater public engagement in climate resilience efforts

5.4. Cluster Group IV

User Group: Environmental and agriculture government agencies

Mission	Anticipate drought impact on crop production
Pain Points	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of timely, high-resolution surface and root-zone soil moisture and ET data - Crop/yield declarations outdated. Difficult to estimate drought impact on the agricultural production
Tools	GIS, data files, data visualization tools
Data Sources	Low-res satellite soil moisture and ET data, soil moisture network (XMS-Cat), crop/yield declarations (CAP-UE), meteorological data, water availability data
Solution	Integrated analysis tool (high-res surface soil moisture, soil moisture at root zone, crop/yield declarations, water availability) to assess the impact of drought on crop production at the parcel level.
Technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Soil moisture maps (<100m) - Soil moisture at root zone at the best resolution - ET maps (<20m) - historic values - groundwater monitoring (availability and quality) - operational drought impact model for crop production
Non-technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stakeholder coordination - data sharing agreements - farmer involvement

Acceptance Criteria (technical + non-technical)	Monthly to weekly high-resolution validated soil moisture maps (<100m); similar for soil moisture at root zone maps
Benefit	Early anticipation of drought effects, support water allocation decisions during drought

User Group: Response Preparedness

Mission	Improve flood mitigation works and response preparedness
Pain Points	Lack of timely, high-res soil moisture and water level data; no predictive early warning system
Tools	GIS, data files, data visualization tools
Data Sources	Local streambed maps, historic flood records, soil moisture maps, rainfall data
Solution	Integrated dashboard to monitor current situation and simulate crisis situations with updated soil moisture and predictive flood risk maps
Technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Soil moisture maps (<100m) - real-time water level monitoring - predictive risk model - historic values
Non-technical Requirements	Cross-agency emergency protocols, training in new tools
Acceptance Criteria (technical + non-technical)	Weekly high-resolution validated soil moisture maps (<100m). When tackling the crisis case, preferable to have most recent data
Benefit	Monitor the situation to make predictions, forecasts and planning. Faster, better-coordinated crisis response, reduced flood damage risk

User Group: Environmental and agriculture government agencies

Mission	Anticipate wildfire risk linked to drought
Pain Points	Poor integration of soil moisture and vegetation dryness indicators in fire risk models
Tools	GIS, data files, data visualization tools
Data Sources	Low-res satellite soil moisture and fire risk maps, meteorological data
Solution	Weekly updated risk maps with vegetation dryness and soil data fusion

Technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Soil moisture data (<100m) - integration into fire risk model - historic values
Non-technical Requirements	Fire brigades and forest managers' access to updated risk maps; decision protocols
Acceptance Criteria (technical + non-technical)	Weekly high-resolution validated soil moisture maps (<100m)
Benefit	Improved prevention, better resource allocation, reduced wildfire occurrence

5.5. Cluster Group V

User Group: Water and wastewater utilities

Mission	To ensure customers clean drinking water in sufficient quantities now and in the future. Treat wastewater in an environmentally responsible way and manage technical and climate water.
Pain Points	Excess financial expenditures on waterpipe network maintenance related to subsidence. Often subsidence is not taken into consideration during construction.
Tools	General design tools related to infrastructure planning. Danish standards for the installation of drinking water and wastewater pipelines.
Data Sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Geological data in relation to construction of new pipe infrastructure - Soil samples are sometimes taken if there is a risk of soil contamination, requiring off-site disposal - Employees 'local knowledge of the area
Solution	A planning tool that incorporates projections of future subsidence in the construction area, providing a basis for choosing the best long-term construction, also for justifying a possible increase in the project's financial budget. The objective is to enable long-term planning based on a more robust decision-making foundation.
Technical Requirements	Future subsidence trends projected decades ahead to ensure the longevity of the infrastructure, in compliance with standards defined in the POLKA service life catalogue. Must be integrable as a layer with utilities' mapping systems, e.g. Kortinfo and MicroStation.
Non-technical Requirements	The data layer must be made available through the two main public Danish providers of map system data (dataforsyningen.dk and

	datafordelingen.dk), allowing all utilities and their partners (municipalities and consultants) to access and download it.
Acceptance Criteria (technical + non-technical)	Validation of the quality of data layers (still need to verify acceptance prediction interval). Dynamic update of projections based on historical data.
Benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stronger decision-making foundation for new projects as well as for maintenance and renovation strategies. - Support for justification of increased financial budgets for infrastructure projects. - More robust pipeline systems designed with long-term subsidence in mind. - Improved supply security through better planning and risk mitigation. - Increased visibility of challenges related to subsidence and ground stability.

User Group: Emergency services (from THW's point of view)

Mission	To better anticipate and respond to water-related crisis situations and ensure safety of deployed emergency services
Pain Points	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Availability of relevant data dependent on local administrative structure - Distribution of relevant data on different platforms - Provision of data in a wide variety of formats, often requiring preparation before use - Limited modelling/forecasting capability of existing solutions - Data availability only in the form of a finished map product, but not as a data stream in the form of WMS or WFS, which can be integrated into own GIS
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GIS - in-situ measurements (e.g. from mobile flood levels (both in flood and fire scenario) and drones)
Data Sources	<p>Data: Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - geodata mostly from local/regional/national authorities (e.g. forestry, water authority, environmental protection agency, national weather authority) - In-situ data (e.g. from own drone measurements, self-assessed dyke runner data) - Satellite pictures (e.g. Copernicus, DLR)
Solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standardized, openly available data collection - Tool with modelling capabilities (e.g. simulation of impact of potential counter measures (to better assess where to cut a

	<p>firebreak, drop water or place a mobile dyke) and simulation of impact of potential dyke damage scenarios) and then being able to export it in own system</p> <p>--> a dynamically updated fire/flood hazard, risk and response prediction and tool (based not only on weather data but current vegetation status, past drought factors)</p>
Technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standardized, openly available data (in line with OGC standard; accessibility as much as possible via services like WFS & WMS) - Data intersection possibility for the integration with locally utilized command and control software/information systems - Possibility to enter field site data (e.g. discovery of dyke damages) - Possibility of querying different data sources (APIs), different data formats, normalizing them and making them usable as uniform data
Non-technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - User-friendly/intuitive handling of core functions
Benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Addressing all the pain points

User Group: The Danish Road Directorate

Mission	Building, securing and maintaining the national road infrastructure.
Pain Points	Innundation subsidence cracks and potholes
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interactive tool for simulating flood risks, sensitive areas and precipitation. - SVK precipitation data and analysis
Data Sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SVK gauging network. - KMS – annual survey. - Scalgo, Mike Flood, QGIS, satellite data, DMI (precipitation) and their own data from historical damage records. - Klimaatlas.
Solution	<p>A dynamic tool that visualizes where roads are most at risk against flooding and subsidence by using historical data and Klimaatlas .</p> <p>A tool optimizes planning of new infrastructure which mitigate flooding from impermeable surfaces.</p>
Technical Requirements	<p>Historical or new data on soil moisture, vegetation cover, infiltration capacity and climate change.</p> <p>A risk map that illustrates by colour gradient, where there is a high potential for future damage cause by flooding and drought.</p>
Non-technical Requirements	User-friendly.

Acceptante Criteria (technical + non-technical)	General popularity and quality of solution.
Benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - better for accident aversion. - Less money spent on maintenance. - Increase the lifetime of infrastructure.

User Group: Agriculture – farmers (Fjordland)

Mission	Ensure optimal operational reliability for their customers, including farmers, by taking into account local areas with potential for flooding and subsidence/drought, which may disrupt crop security.
Pain Points	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Drought and local inundation. - Soil moisture content and carrying capacity
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Basic local measurements. - Satellite imagery
Data Sources	GEUS, DMI, municipalities, SEGES. EO data (Earth Observation data – satellite data).
Solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring, modelling and integration of data. - Risk map at farmland level. - A tool that can visualize the effect of climate adaptation.
Technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Precision landbrug
Non-technical Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Specialized consultants. - Knowledge exchange and communication between expert and non-expert users.
Acceptante Criteria (technical + non-technical)	Crop yield and consequential impacts.
Benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - identify farmland with a risk of flooding, subsidence, drought that can affect crop yield - Plan crop selection based on local risks, e.g., drought-resistant crops. - Optimize drainage strategies based on analyses of soil moisture and water balance. - Document where nature-based solutions are needed, e.g., (mini) wetlands

User Group: Agriculture – consultants (SEGES)

Mission	Sustainable and competitive agricultural production.
Pain Points	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Public discontent and political pressure.- Poor economy and regulation.
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Research
Data Sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- All relevant databases
Solution	More research and applied research
Benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- develop improved soil management methods

6. Annex B: Scoping Documents

6.1. Cluster Group I

Group 1 addresses urban slow-onset crises due to drought, soil moisture and subsidence, focusing on groundwater levels, infrastructure, greenery, and heat.

Buyer group members are FORUM VIRIUM HELSINKI OY (FV-Helsinki), City of Rotterdam (The Netherlands), and City of Haarlem (The Netherlands).

The primary objective for Haarlem, Rotterdam, and Helsinki within the PCP WISE project is to enhance urban water management and resilience against climate change by utilising space and Earth Observation (EO) data. This initiative includes monitoring diverse aspects of the urban water cycle, such as soil moisture, groundwater levels, and surface water, with the aim to mitigate risks like flooding, drought, and subsidence. The overarching goal is to develop more sustainable and resilient cities that are better prepared to address the challenges posed by a changing climate

Common Use case description

All three cities share a common interest in utilizing space and Earth Observation (EO) data to enhance their understanding of drought, soil moisture, and subsidence. The focus areas are presented in the following table:

City	Focus Areas
Helsinki	Soil saturation, green spaces, building foundations, underground infrastructure, early warning systems for flooding and ground instability
Rotterdam	Drought, green spaces, relation to infrastructure, groundwater monitoring, heat island mapping
Haarlem	Climate adaptation, water resources, impact of heavy rainfall, data analysis and modelling

The primary objective for Haarlem, Rotterdam, and Helsinki within the PCP WISE project is to enhance urban water management and resilience against climate change by utilising space and Earth Observation (EO) data. This initiative includes monitoring diverse aspects of the urban water cycle, such as soil moisture, groundwater levels, and surface water, with the aim to mitigate risks like flooding, drought, and subsidence. The overarching goal is to develop more sustainable and resilient cities that are better prepared to address the challenges posed by a changing climate.

Common Interests:

Drought:

- The impacts of drought on soil moisture, groundwater levels, and urban infrastructure.
- Monitoring drought and its effects on green areas and settlements.
- Using EO data to predict and monitor drought conditions is of interest.

Soil Moisture:

- Monitoring soil moisture for managing water resources and mitigating risks.
- Soil moisture data is required at various frequencies and resolutions for different purposes.
- Integrating soil moisture data with groundwater models.

Subsidence:

- Soil subsidence caused by changes in groundwater levels.
- Monitoring subsidence of streets and buildings.
- Understanding the influence of measures on soil and water to mitigate subsidence.
- Managing shallow groundwater levels to protect buildings and infrastructure.

Common Concerns:

- Soil subsidence.
- Impact on buildings and infrastructure.
- Waterlogging and its effect on green spaces.

Timeline and Scenario Evaluation:

- Interest in historical data.
- Focus on both regular monitoring and crisis situations.
- Need for continuous monitoring and early warning systems.

Stakeholders & Sector

- National Water boards
- Regional Environmental Institutions
- Cities' Urban management and development departments
- Cities' Management and Rescue Operators
- Sewage system operators
- Construction companies
- Insurance companies

Common Functional needs stakeholder

Integration with Existing Systems:

- Integration of EO data with groundwater models, stormwater flooding modelling tools, and other existing data
- Potential for linking with other projects
 - FVH: Regions4Climate, GreenInCities
 - Rotterdam: Thirsty Cities

Common Required information

Data Requirements short:

- Soil moisture data
- Groundwater levels (data already existing)
- Groundwater flow
- Impact of measures on soil and water

Benefits

Improved management of shallow groundwater:

- By integrating EO data with ground-based systems, the cities gain critical insights for proactive decision-making, protecting building foundations and underground infrastructure.

Early warning systems for water-related risks:

- The project facilitates the development of systems to alert residents and businesses of potential flooding and groundwater drawdown, enabling timely preventive measures.

Enhanced understanding of urban water dynamics:

- By leveraging space and EO data, Cities can analyze multi-climate change scenarios and their impact on the city's water systems. Also, for green areas.

Effective prevention of subsidence:

- The project supports the monitoring and analysis of factors contributing to subsidence, allowing for targeted interventions to protect infrastructure.

Mitigation of soil subsidence:

- By providing insights into soil moisture and groundwater dynamics, the project helps Cities address the challenges of subsidence caused by lowering groundwater levels and drought.

Improved urban water management:

- The project supports the development of strategies to manage water resources effectively, particularly in the face of drought and climate change impacts.

Summary

Code RSOC	Name lead BUYER/User	Support Function	Information specs (based on requirements)
REGULAR	Sector		
	City of Helsinki Environment Unit & Helsinki City Construction Services, Stara	Management of soil saturation levels, preventing damage to infrastructure and ensuring the health of green spaces. Support sustainable urban planning and development.	Real-time data on soil saturation levels, Groundwater level data, Integration of satellite imagery and ground-based sensors.
	Gemeente Haarlem	Refinement of the Use Case titled: SPACE WATER: Multi Climate change scenario's in existing urban area's. Evaluation of the effects of the measurements, including adjustment proposals. Input for scenario's in complex neighborhoods.	Temperature maps of the city, Evapotranspiration maps of the city, % green in the city, # trees, # trees with crown diameter >3meter, Effluent data of rainwater sewage, Surface reflection horizontal, Vertical surface reflection, Reflection and connectivity/heat absorption of surface area, Timeline historic data (multi decade trends on a monthly averages) with soil moisture and stoniness, rainfall, evaporation (etc.), Scenario evaluation and adjustment with the actual and historic data.
	Rotterdam	Urban management, Drought, Groundwater monitoring, Geotechnics, Climate	Mapping of the levels of groundwater, Anticipating the shallow groundwater and risk areas (buildings), Settlements, Green, Anticipating the shallow groundwater and settlements, Planning different kinds of management, Anticipating risk areas (buildings), Heat, Heat islands, risk areas, Subsidence of soil / settlements, Winter: water logging, Summer: drought

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6.2. Cluster Group II

Cluster G2 Urban has been proposed as second cluster, based on the funnel process, where a common set of requirements has been identified following the proposed set of relevant criteria taking into the consideration cooperation between the BUYERS.

Relevant Criteria for the clustering process:

First Criteria to cluster:

- Urban/Rural
- Test site candidates (physical)
- Position in Europe (North, East, South, West)

Deepening using additional Criteria to cluster:

- Problem related (flood/drought related)

- Representative for organization process (regular and/or crises)

Suitability in terms of commitment of partner (budget, actions, process leader, etc.)

Based on that, this cluster is covering four original use cases UFOC2_3 - SK Urban Floods & Fires (Slovak environment agency) Slovakia, UFOC4 - Helsinki 1: Stormwater Management (FORUM VIRIUM HELSINKI) Finland, USOC3 - Measuring shallow groundwater (Klimatorium) Denmark and RSOC1_Slow Onset Flood 2023_23 Lower Saxony, Germany (THW).

Common Use case description

Group 2 (East – North (E-N) EU) is dealing with Urban problems in the local city context in terms of spatial water distribution in the city underground due to all kind of human and external (seepage, sea level rise, surface sealing, etc.) factors. The focus is on **dealing with an abundance of water** due to problems of (local) water storage, infiltration, etc. impacting infrastructure (streets, housing, critical infrastructure like utility sector). Mostly the context (river basin region or near to coast/sea) of the city has additional (in)direct impact on the basic urban water conditions. Differences between coastal and inland locations will be considered since places influenced by maritime waters have additional factors, especially in tidal areas, in terms of drainage during inland tides.

This cluster shall cover use cases focused on urban environments (e.g. Bratislava, Helsinki, Lemvig, Spišská Nová Ves), where water-related hazards, with rising trends like in case of floods or rises in shallow groundwater can significantly endanger society. In some cases, there are available relevant local data, but in some cases, cluster shall count with scenarios of limited availability of such data resources. Cluster shall support the reduction of the floods and improve their prediction with the Intelligence developed by water information system (WISE), able to collect, analyze and distribute relevant data and information necessary to understand the patterns and develop risk map. In case of cities, cluster shall be supporting as river, rising sea levels as well as pluvial flooding, which happens when the rain overwhelms drainage systems or saturates the ground — even if there's no river or body of water nearby to overflow. An inevitable part of the cluster shall be represented by water management, ensuring preventing damage to critical infrastructure, protecting public safety, and ensuring the city's resilience. Aside of preventions, this cluster shall also support potential of utilizing water excess aspects and contributing into the appropriate climate change adaptation measures.

Regular

In the case of regular scenario, appropriate data and solution allowing related information utilization will provide systematic and sustainable support for the environment and civil protection in target areas. Similarly, soil moisture groundwater mapping shall be ensured to anticipate risks to buildings, including continuous monitoring of soil moisture levels, analysis of trends, and identification of potential risk areas. Importance of monitoring of slow deterioration of private and public infrastructure ie: buildings, roads, water and wastewater infrastructure, recreational areas, transport infrastructure – reinforcement. Additionally, soil moisture data is crucial for monitoring construction sites to ensure compliance with water

quality standards. Better tools to ensure compliance before water enters the drainage system are also in scope. This could involve real-time monitoring of sediment levels in runoff. Targeted monitoring of specific locations for maintenance purposes is also needed.

Crisis (extreme conditions)

Crisis scenario is also foreseen to be supported through the improvement of current practice and the provision of new innovative approaches benefiting from the added value generated by the procured data and solution. During extreme events like floods, the Rescue Department utilizes soil moisture data to assess the impact on critical infrastructure and transportation. Real-time monitoring of soil moisture levels in the urban area as well as surrounding rural areas, helps predict flood extent and identify areas at high risk of inundation. This information is used to manage crisis response efforts such as the deployment of mobile pump units and dykes. Soil moisture data also supports flood route estimation and planning, including real-time mapping of flood pathways and inundation areas to aid evacuation and emergency response. The identification of risk areas for both 1-meter floods and localized stormwater floods is also crucial. The simulation of water levels using digital terrain models and hydraulic models also enables the simulation of currents. The height and speed of the water can be used to support decision-making processes, e.g. on the rescue equipment to be used or on rescue and evacuation measures and tactics in general.

Water management: uncontrolled leakage to the environment leading to pollution and destruction of infrastructure and buildings. Stress on sewage infrastructure leads to pollution by sewage water, contamination, and sickness. Sudden destruction of private and public buildings- housing problems. In Helsinki, this also includes managing potential flooding from the rapid melting of snow and the limited capacity of small urban water bodies.

Stakeholders & Sector

The following sectors and stakeholders are going to be addressed with this cluster:

Slovakia

In connection with the scoping in introduction, this use case is focused on the selected key stakeholders operating on district and local city level:

- Bratislava City
- Spišská Nová Ves

Main sectors to be addressed are:

- Environment
- Civil protection
- Integrated rescue system
- Urban development
- Aside from the above-mentioned stakeholders and sectors, use case aims to support communication of the relevant outcomes also towards the other types of potential stakeholders as:
- Other public sector bodies

- Citizens
- Business
- Non-governmental sector
- Research & development
- Education

Finland

Regular:

- Urban Environment Division: Responsible for urban planning, construction, and infrastructure development.
- Helsinki City Construction Services (Stara): Manages construction and maintenance of urban infrastructure.

Crisis:

- City of Helsinki Rescue Department: Responsible for emergency response and crisis management during extreme events.
- The Urban Environment Division is the leading stakeholder, as it utilizes soil moisture data for both regular urban planning and crisis preparedness.

Denmark

Regular:

- Water management
 - Lemvig Water and Waste water utility
 - Lemvig Municipality – Environmental department
 - Private drainage cooperatives
- Climate adaption
 - Lemvig Municipality – Environmental department
 - Coastal protection agency
 - Governmental departments for environment and climate adaption
- Infrastructure
 - Lemvig Municipality
 - Lemvig Water and wastewater utility

Crisis:

Emergency services (collaborative effort between Danish Emergency Management Agency, Lemvig Municipality, Lemvig Water and wastewater utility and Health authorities)

- Lemvig Water and wastewater utility (handling flooding of sewage infrastructure in a crisis situation)

Germany

Regular:

- Water and shipping authorities on city council and municipal level.

Crisis:

- Local command staff on city / municipality level
- Local emergencies respond services
- German Agency for Technical Relief
- Sometimes: Federal armed forces

Common Functional needs stakeholder

Requirements of involved stakeholders are divided into two main categories:

Joint requirements

- Data requirements (e.g. soil moisture, ground water, surface water, sea levels, water stream levels, evapotranspiration, etc.)
- Software system / user interface and functionality requirements (visualisations, dashboards, etc.)
- Access to data and information from past, support for current monitoring and availability of the predictions
- Data delivered via OGC-Standard-API (Open Geospatial Consortium Standard)

Country specific requirements

Slovakia

From the functional point of view, use case aims to cover the following set of requirements:

Functional requirements:

- Support for data collection and maintenance
 - Local data support
 - Integrated access to various data sources
 - Post processing (cleaning, transformation, data quality)
- Analytical support
 - Analytical processing of available data
 - Modelling, predictions
- Visualisation & communication
 - Presentation and publication
 - Dashboarding
 - Notifications (e-mail / sms)

Non-functional requirements:

- Usability: Focus on easy understandable user journey, intuitive interfaces

- Scalability: Ensure the system can handle large volumes of data and scale up as needed during peak flooding / fires seasons,
- Reliability: Design a robust and reliable tool that operates seamlessly under challenging conditions, such as poor connectivity or extreme weather events,
- Usability: Prioritize user-friendly interfaces for emergency responders, decision-makers as well as general public users, allowing quick and intuitive access to critical information,
- Security: Implement stringent security measures to safeguard sensitive data, ensuring the integrity and confidentiality of information shared within the system,
- Support and maintenance: Appropriate training, documentation and efficient service layer assistance,
- Notifications shall be delivered to affected users no later than 5 minutes after their identification.

ICT/Architecture requirements:

- Smartness/modernity:
 - Cloud based design
 - AI/ML support
 - Event driven architecture
- Modularity
 - Containerization
 - Microservices
 - API based design
 - Disconnected data streams
- Scalability
 - Automatic scaling
 - Load balancing & Caching
- Interoperability
 - Legal
 - Organisational
 - Semantic

Finland

Describe the involved stakeholders and the relevant spectrum of their functional needs in the context of above described regular and crisis processes. Priorities in 'wanna haves' of these functional needs.

Regular:

- Urban Environment Division: Needs soil moisture data to assess groundwater levels, anticipate risks to buildings, and inform urban planning decisions.
- Helsinki City Construction Services (Stara): Needs soil moisture data to optimize construction practices and ensure the long-term stability of urban infrastructure.

- Urban Planning and monitoring: monitoring the storm water quality that ends up in rivers and streams
- Information about Snow melting water that is highly polluted

Crisis:

- Rescue Department: Needs real-time soil moisture data to predict flood extent, identify high-risk areas, and plan evacuations.
- Rescue department: emergency in polluted stormwater e.g. from construction sites
- Priorities in 'Wanna Haves':
 - Real-time monitoring of soil moisture levels.
 - Accurate and reliable data.
 - Integration with existing systems and data infrastructure.
 - User-friendly dashboard to visualize real-time data on flooding, including sewer capacity and surface runoff.
 - Integration of WISE data with HSY's updated sewer models for more accurate and dynamic flood forecasting.

Denmark

It is important that the data and their presentation is recognizable between stakeholders to improve collaboration. So we can share data and understand each other's needs and challenges. The stakeholders need to speak the same "water language". This needs to be achieved through harmonization, standardization and categorization if they are to work across national borders. In addition, each data set must contain an expression of quality/accuracy. Combining data of widely varying quality will never be better than the worst common denominator and this means that the overall result can be directly misleading.

More specific functional needs for each of the stakeholders in the use-case of Lemvig-Denmark:

Regular:

- Lemvig Water and Waste water utility:
 - Ability to combine dynamic mapping of surface near ground water levels with water infrastructure placement and sewage data related to extraneous water and overflow. This in order to understand and act on the challenge of extraneous water in the sewage systems – e.g to improve usage of current infrastructure capacity, adapting current infrastructure through renovations and identification of risk areas, plan realistic solutions for sewage overflow, wastewater treatment plants management, etc.
 - Ability to relate predictive models of surface near groundwater to planning and construction of adaptive solutions to urban challenges resulting from rising ground water levels and increasing pluvial storms. (a mitigative/adaptive solution could be a drainage system but could also be construction of wetland

areas outside the urban area, to delay water coming into the urban area) climate change.

- Lemvig Municipality:
 - Ability to assess current climate adaption solutions as well as municipal water management plan in relation to excess water challenges.
 - Ability to relate a predictive hydrological model of the area to planning of land-use, municipal water management, climate change adaptive measures, and mapping of risk-areas in terms of flooding (both from the sea and from the surface near ground water).
- Coastal protection agency:
 - Improve understanding of the effect of changes of sea levels on groundwater levels and quality as well as understanding how the saturation of coastal areas affects the coastline (erosion). This data should be from the past and present to support modelling of predictions of future scenarios to help guide coastal protection actions as well as ground water management
- Private drainage cooperatives:
 - Needs soil moisture data to assess groundwater levels to operate and manage daily operations.
- Governmental departments for environment and climate adaption (miljøministeriet):
 - Ability to assess current climate adaption policies for handling excess water (from the sea, the weather and from below)
 - Ability to relate a predictive hydrological model to planning mitigation/adaptation policies to rising sea levels, rising surface near groundwater and increasing pluvial storms on a national level.

Crisis:

- Emergency services: Needs real-time water level data to predict flood extent, identify high-risk areas, and plan evacuations.
- Lemvig Water and Wastewater Utility: Needs real-time soil moisture data, ground water levels, surface water levels (lakes, streams), and sea level data to manage and predict crisis in relation to flooding of critical water and wastewater infrastructure above and below ground

Germany

Functional requirements from an emergency services end user perspective:

- Needs a flood hazard, risk and response prediction tool with simulation/modelling functionalities whose output can be used in one's own GIS tool

Handling/Technology:

- Interoperability/ Data intersection possibility for the integration with locally utilized command and control software/information systems (first responders probably have

their own software established, it could be helpful if (parts of) our results can be transferred into that)

- Possibility to enter data manually from outside, e.g. discovery of dyke damages
- User-friendly and intuitive handling of core functions (considering that First Responders may use the system infrequently, leading to a gradual development of expertise despite training efforts)

Common Required information

Similarly in connection to the digital content related requirements, two main categories of information will be required:

Joint information requirements

Following types of similar information requirements were identified across the input use-cases:

- Soil moisture
- Ground water
- Surface water
- Water quality
- Risk Indicators
- Flood Extent Predictions
- Climate Data
- Sewer Data
- Sea level

Country specific information requirements

Slovakia

To fulfil the expectations and requirements of the target stakeholder's appropriate information base will have to be secured. In general, required data and information can be classified as follows:

- Temporary perspective
 - Historical information
 - Current data
 - Forecast and estimations
- Source of origin
 - Internal data of the stakeholders
 - Data provided (procured) by the PCP WISE project
- Way of generation
 - Collected manually in the field
 - Measured automatically

- Calculated
- Scope of collection
 - Ground data
 - Air data
 - Earth observation collections
- Thematic scope (Urban focus)
 - Floods
 - Water
 - Infrastructure
- Frequency
 - Regular (periodic / soil water veg)
 - Crisis (on the demand / too dry, too wet)
- Layers approach
 - Base
 - Water regular
 - Water dynamics
 - Risk/Impact/Crisis

Finland

Regular:

- Soil moisture levels (trends and historical data).
- Groundwater level estimations.
- Risk indicators for urban planning and construction.

Water quality parameters (e.g., sediment load).

Crisis:

- Real-time soil moisture data.
- Flood extent predictions.
- Risk indicators for critical infrastructure and transportation.
- Real-time data from HSY's sewer system.

Climate Mode:

- Long-term soil moisture trends and projections.
- Climate-related risk indicators (e.g., drought, extreme rainfall).

Category/Type	When & How	Regular	Crisis	Climate Mode
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Soil Moisture Levels	Daily, seasonal, long-term trends	✓	✓	✓
Groundwater Levels	Indicative levels, trends	✓		✓
Risk Indicators	Per sector (urban planning, infrastructure, transportation)	✓	✓	✓
Flood Extent Predictions	Real-time, short-term forecasts		✓	
Climate Data	Historical trends, future projections			✓
Water Quality Data	Real-time, at construction sites	✓		
Sewer Data	Real-time, network capacity		✓	

Denmark

Category/Type	When & How	Regular	Crisis	Climate Mode
Soil Moisture Levels	Daily, monthly, seasonal, long-term trends, short term trends, real-time	Monthly, long-term trends	Real-time, short-term forecasts	Seasonal, longterm trends
Groundwater Levels	Actual levels, Indicative levels, trends, real-time, Daily, seasonal, short-term forecasts	Daily, seasonal, long-term trends	Real-time, short-term forecasts	Seasonal, long-term trends
Risk Indicators	Per stakeholder:	✓	✓	✓
Flood Extent Predictions	Real-time, short-term forecasts		✓	✓
Climate Data	Historical trends, future projections	✓		✓

Category/Type	When & How	Regular	Crisis	Climate Mode
Water Quality Data (salinity and pollution from sewage overflow)	Actual levels, Indicative levels, Real-time	Actual levels, Real-time	Indicative levels, Real-time	
Sewer Data	Real-time, network capacity	✓	✓	

Germany

- Comprehensive overview of live water levels (water levels also at locations where no level measuring instrument is available – higher resolution of water level information)
- Historical water levels, high and low
- Prediction of future water levels
- Early warning information, that are not based on weather only, but consider the current "water" status (e.g. how saturated is the soil, how was precipitation in the last days/weeks) in combination with expected weather conditions, to be able to determine expected impacts as accurately as possible (essential for preparation and planning)
- High resolution flood hazard maps, that display flooded areas for certain water levels. In Germany, there is currently only a flood hazard map available for 50, 100 and 500-year floods, which cannot be directly assigned to a water level of a specific river. To prioritize response and warning measures it is important to know, from which water level at which river which assets (building, infrastructure etc.) can be expected to be flooded.
- Assessment of the impact on flood protection infrastructure based on the water level predictions (identifying which dikes may be vulnerable to breaching first, determining when certain flood retention basins will reach capacity, etc.)
- Analysis of consequences/exposure on inhabited areas (for prioritizing protective measures and preparing for evacuations) -> Flood risk maps
 - Estimation of affected population, vulnerability factors (age structure, mobility, etc.)
 - Evaluation of affected residences and damage assessment (based on physical vulnerability)
 - Examination of critical infrastructure within the affected areas and possible disruption of functionalities (power supply, roads, affected fire stations etc.)

Benefits

This use case cluster implementation shall ensure achievement of the following benefits:

Use case will support both core stakeholders in getting an overall perspective about floods across the district / city, crisis response as well as decision making activities in urban management. In addition, the following benefits might be generated by the use case:

Regular

- Getting an overall perspective about floods in the city, as well as decision making activities.
- Identification of the riskiest areas and prediction of potential events in advance.
- Improved and efficient management and development of the district / city.
- Equalisation of information base for all involved stakeholders.
- Improvement of climate water management and climate adaptation.
- Better data on shallow groundwater development over time, can support water authorities' climate adaption policies, making sure investments are done in relation to the realities of climate change, and climate adaption plans are based on solid data:
 - Which areas needs to be drained?
 - In which areas can water be stored to reduce effects of droughts and mitigate flooding in urban areas
 - How does soil-moisture develop over time in relation to risks of flooding?
 - How does soil-moisture relate to sea-level rise?
- Better understanding of shallow groundwater as a resource
 - How much water is available and when?
 - Where is it most efficient to drain?
 - What are the consequences to natural wetlands and biodiversity
- The wastewater utilities would be able to react quicker in crisis-situations where shallow groundwater will rise to critical levels and thus prepare by e.g redirecting water to less "at risk" areas and drain certain most "at risk" areas to minimize uncontrolled leakage of sewage water into nature, minimize damage to water and urban infrastructure, minimize load on waste water treatment plants etc. This quick-reaction and targeted action plan would be the result of being able to anticipate crisis-situations and risk-extent from data on shallow ground water levels in relation to current water infrastructure

Crisis

- Improved an overall perspective about floods in the city, crisis response.
- Elimination of floods impact to the greatest extent possible.
- Reduce flooding, reduce sewage overflow, reduce stress on wastewater treatment plants, reduce contamination health risks
- Protect assets (public and private)
- More effective emergency response --> reduce crisis period

Summary

Code RSOC	Name BUYER/User	lead	
Slovakia			
REGULAR	Sector	Support Function	Information specs (based on requirements)
	Bratislava City, Spišská Nová Ves	Data and information collection and maintenance Analytical support Visualisation & communication	<p>Urban regular information made available via API a GUI (Web):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil moisture conditions in the unsaturated zone (0-5cm; root zone; percolation zone); see figure 1 • Actual Evapotranspiration & Evapotranspiration Deficit (ETpot-ETact)/Ratio (ETact/ETpot) • Phreatic Groundwater Levels • Seepage/Deep infiltration <p>Together with: A1 Info carrier:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High Resolution Satellite / orthoimagery • Base topographic layers • Administrative borders • Buildings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Location of the offices ○ Location of crisis centers • Transport network <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Road network ○ Rail network ○ Water transport network ○ Air network ○ Gas stations • Social facilities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Hospitals ○ Schools ○ Assisted living • Demography • Statistical data • Infrastructure data • Water/hydro info <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ River network ○ Water areas ○ Catchments • LandCover <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Vegetation • Agriculture facilities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Farms <p>A2 elevation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LIDAR • Digital terrain model • Digital surface model • Contours • Hill shade <p>A3 climate&weather:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Temperature

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Humidity • Precipitation <p>B1 Evapotranspiration B2 Soil moisture B3 Water level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Surface • Ground <p>C1 Drought/Floods</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flood hazard maps • Affected population • Damage assessments <p>C3 Water quantity & quality C4 Subsidence C5 Water excess C6 Climate adaptation</p> <p>Other</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flood maps • Forecasting • Snow coverage • Sirens location • Shelters location • Copernicus • INSPIRE
CRISIS	Sector	Support (function)	Information (requirements)
	Bratislava City, Spišská Nová Ves	Data and information collection and maintenance Analytical support Visualisation & communication	<p>Urban crisis information made available via API a GUI (Web):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil Drying & Wetting • Saturated soil moisture conditions (prior to heavy rainfall) • Land subsidence • Lack of irrigation water • Water temperature • Urban Heat Island Effect <p>Together with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A1 Info carrier: • High Resolution Satellite / orthoimagery • Base topographic layers • Administrative borders • Buildings • Location of the offices • Location of crisis centers • Transport network • Road network • Rail network • Water transport network • Air network • Gas stations • Traffic information • Social facilities • Hospitals • Schools • Assisted living • Demography • Impacted population

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical data • Infrastructure data • Water/hydro info • A2 elevation: • LIDAR • Digital terrain model • Digital surface model • Contours • Hill shade <p>A3 climate&weather: B1 Evapotranspiration B2 Soil moisture B3 Water level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Surface • Ground <p>C1 Drought/Floods C3 Water quantity & quality</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water sources <p>C4 Subsidence C5 Water excess C6 Climate adaptation</p> <p>Other</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Notifications • Safe places • Flood maps • Snow coverage • Sirens location • Shelters location • Copernicus • INSPIRE
Climate	Sector	Support (function)	Information (requirements)
	Bratislava City, Spišská Nová Ves	Risk assessments and climate change adaptation	<p>Urban climate information made available via API a GUI (Web): A re-analysis* dataset (2000-2025) of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The soil water balance components • Soil moisture conditions (0-5cm; root zone; percolation zone) • Soil Drying & Wetting (in terms of severity, magnitude, duration, and spatial extent) <p>A climate forecasted (based on standard European climate scenarios) dataset (2026-2050/2070)</p> <p>Together with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flood risk assessments • Modelling and predictions • Copernicus • INSPIRE
Finland			
REGULAR	Sector	Support Function	Information requirements
Urban	Urban Environment Division (UED)	Storm water management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storm water modeling dashboard for all storm water in Helsinki - flooding redirection & preparedness level - WISE would add on ground-truth & in-situ data

	UED: Construction services	location of mobile pump units & processes	- Adaptive Control Measures - Planning of the crisis events - Local storage planning
	UED: Planning services	- Urban planning and construction: preparation processes - requirements for processes (construction levels & limits, water quality, etc.)	- enhancing planning & maintenance - storm water quality and actions (f.ex at construction sites, traffic flows) - Stormwater management and control (drainage, infiltration, etc.)
	Rescue department: Rescue services	Avoid major infrastructure crisis (economical, traffic, communication issues, mobility issues, possible drinking water issues)	- Emergency Response Scenario Planning - Risk Mapping - Evacuation plans
	FVH + Data team of Helsinki	Digital twin of Helsinki	- Detailed visualization, simulations - Collaborative Planning Optimizing Nature-Based Solutions
CRISIS	Sector	Support (function)	Information (requirements)
Urban	Rescue department: Rescue services	Action during acute crisis (based on enhancing planning)	- Water flow - Secure drinking water - traffic flow, - etc
	UED	- Avoid major infrastructure crisis (economical, traffic, communication issues, mobility issues, possible drinking water issues)	- communication & information for decision-making
	UED: Planning services + Rescue		storm water effects on traffic disturbances and reporting (practical application: navigation system recommendations/warning/flash update)
Climate	Sector	Support (function)	Information (requirements)
	Urban Environment Division (UED)	Prevention	Prediction: Help cope with the impacts Helsinki is facing and already experiencing
	Centre for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment (ELY)	Policies and management of the environmental protection tasks	Prediction: Help cope with the impacts Finland is facing and already experiencing
Denmark			
REGULAR	Sector	Support Function	Information requirements
<i>Urban</i>	Water management	Optimize operations costs for waste water management; minimize shallow groundwater intrusion/effects of shallow groundwater intrusion into wastewater infrastructure (including waste water plants)	Daily data on shallow ground water levels, in urban and rural areas. Resolution: 25X25m
	Water management	Minimize overspill of sewage water into natural environment. Both from waste-water treatment plants and from pump stations	Daily data on shallow ground water levels, in urban and rural areas. Resolution: 25X25m
	Water management	Plan dimensions of wastewater infrastructure. Anlægsinvesteringer – sseset management	Daily data on shallow ground water levels, in urban and rural areas. Resolution: 25X25m
	Water management	Klimasikre – ny opgave	resolution25x25m

CRISIS	Sector	Support (function)	Information (requirements)
	Emergency services		
Climate	Sector	Support (function)	Information (requirements)
	Municipal environmental department	Pointing out risk areas for shallow ground water flooding (which will then be managed by the local waste water utility)	model of future risk of shallow ground water floodings
	Danish Environmental ministry	Support legislation on climate adaption	
	Danish Environmental Agency	Support legislation on climate adaption and implementation of legislation	
Germany			
CRISIS	Sector	Support (function)	Information (requirements)
	Emergency response	To better anticipate and respond to water-related crisis situations and ensure safety of deployed emergency services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flood Risk/Hazard Mapping to better plan evacuations - Modelling/simulation tool to better assess impact and effectiveness of counter measures

6.3. Cluster Group III

Group 3 addresses rural challenges related to extreme local climate variability, including periods of intense rainfall and prolonged drought in Northwest and Central Europe. These climate extremes affect seasonal natural and agricultural processes, leading to incidents such as wildfires and reduced or failed crop yields. Unlike Southern Europe, where water scarcity is often structural, the challenges in this region are primarily related to uneven water distribution, which varies from year to year. The Group is represented by 2 use cases, with a heathland/forest nature reserve surrounded by agriculture on the border of Belgium and The Netherlands on the one hand, and the rural self-governing region of Banska Bystrica in the Slovak republic on the other hand. There is a shared interest in building knowledge about the soil-water-vegetation conditions leading up to extreme events.

Grenspark Kalmthoutse Heide (GKH) is a cross-border nature reserve situated between Belgium (Flanders) and the Netherlands (Brabant Province). The park, spanning both countries, is an important ecological zone characterized by heathlands, forests, and sandy soils. It plays a crucial role in biodiversity conservation, groundwater infiltration, and climate adaptation. Additionally, the park attracts numerous visitors from the surrounding urbanized regions, serving as a recreational retreat for hiking, cycling, and nature observation.

However, the park faces increasing challenges due to climate change, particularly prolonged droughts and heightened wildfire risks. The delicate balance between groundwater availability, vegetation health, and fire risks is becoming more difficult to maintain. The PCP WISE project offers an opportunity to enhance the park's management by integrating satellite-based Soil-Water-Vegetation (SWV) intelligence. By leveraging advanced monitoring and predictive analytics, the park can develop more effective strategies for mitigating drought effects and preventing wildfires.

The Slovak Environment Agency (SEA) aims to support the Ministry of Environment as well as Ministry of Interior of the Slovak republic (national level), including the Banska Bystrica self-governing region (regional level) in the domain of disaster risk management, particularly via floods and fires documentation, analysis and prevention, considering the aspects of the Water management and climate change adaptation. In 2022 the number of fires in the outdoor environment increased significantly, from 3,823 to 6,889. According to the president of the Fire and Rescue Service, the main cause is related to climate change and people's carelessness. So far, there is very limited availability of the digital data resources to be used in order to document, analyse, react, communicate and predict the occurrence of floods and fires on national and regional level. Main aim of the use case is to support the reduction of the floods and fires impact, whilst improving their documentation and prediction with the support provided by water information system (WISE). The solution should provide water information (actual surface and groundwater levels, water availability, top soil saturation and other aspects), in order to create relevant risk maps. The resulting product will be a tool / system providing access to the relevant data and spatial information, including automated notifications that promptly identifies the risk of floods and fires.

Common Use case description

Group 3 addresses rural drought and wildfire risk in regions experiencing high climate variability—specifically Northwest and Central Europe. These areas are increasingly subject to **extreme weather patterns**, including both **prolonged droughts** and **intense rainfall**. Such variability impacts ecosystems, natural landscapes, and agricultural production, and may cause rapid-onset wildfire events or crop losses due to dry conditions or water surplus events.

The two use cases in Group 3—Grenspark Kalmthoutse Heide (Belgium/Netherlands) and the Banská Bystrica region (Slovakia)—share a need for **advanced soil-water-vegetation (SWV) intelligence** and monitoring systems to improve preparedness and response in both **peace time management** and **crisis situations**.

Both sites are characterized by mixed land use (forests, heathland, and agriculture), and both face increased **fire hazards** driven by vegetation drying, human activity, and unmanaged biomass. Despite differing institutional landscapes, both cases lack integrated, timely data systems for assessing and responding to fire and drought risk.

The unified use case aims to provide:

- **Continuous and historical SWV monitoring** using Earth Observation (EO) and in-situ data.
- **Crisis intelligence for wildfire risk**, integrated into user dashboards and early warning systems.
- **Sector-specific decision-support tools** for nature conservation, agriculture, and emergency management.

Regular

Under regular conditions, both regions depend on the timely understanding of seasonal changes in **soil moisture**, **groundwater levels**, and **vegetation stress**. These data underpin nature conservation, agricultural planning, and hydrological management strategies.

In **Grenspark Kalmthoutse Heide**, regular monitoring supports land and water management in a vulnerable infiltration zone, while in **Slovakia**, data supports risk-aware regional development and early identification of water-related stress. Both sites require **real-time and trend-based indicators** to inform land use, water retention strategies, and vegetation planning.

Crisis (extreme conditions)

During drought-induced fire risk or water scarcity, real-time information becomes essential. In both regions, wildfires are a rapidly emerging hazard, with increased ignition probability linked to vegetation drying, high temperatures, wind, and human activity.

- In **Grenspark Kalmthoutse Heide**, crisis conditions can evolve in days and require fire risk maps to guide first responder deployment and public safety decisions.
- In **Banská Bystrica**, fire response and flood management depend on **district-level intervention coordination**, which currently lacks fine-grained risk intelligence.

Unified needs include **automated early warning systems, real-time crisis dashboards, and scenario-based support tools** for responders and policy makers.

Stakeholders & Sector

Common Stakeholder Groups:

- **National and regional environment ministries/agencies** (BE, NL, SK)
- **Emergency responders** (fire brigades, civil protection, police)
- **Water authorities and drinking water companies**
- **Nature and land managers** (ANB, Staatsbosbeheer, SEA, local offices)
- **Agricultural sector** (local landowners, grazing and farming cooperatives)
- **Recreation and tourism managers**
- **Municipal and provincial governments** (Kalmthout, Woensdrecht, Banská Bystrica)

Sectors involved:

- Environment and Nature Conservation
- Water Management
- Agriculture
- Civil Protection and Emergency Response
- Climate Change Adaptation

Common Functional needs of stakeholders

Stakeholders require a **multi-functional system** capable of serving long-term planning as well as immediate crisis support.

Shared functional needs include:

- **SWV monitoring and predictive analytics** to assess ecosystem and agricultural vulnerability.
- **Fire and drought risk mapping**, with dynamic updates based on environmental triggers.
- **Crisis dashboards** integrating EO and local data for real-time response and communication.
- **Risk assessment tools** to inform zoning, land-use planning, and emergency preparedness.
- **Decision-support layers** tailored to water distribution, biomass management, visitor control, and resource allocation.

Non-functional needs include:

- Intuitive and multilingual interfaces for diverse users
- Modular and scalable system design
- Interoperability with existing national and EU data infrastructures (e.g., INSPIRE, Copernicus)
- Automated notification features

Common Required information

To serve both regular and crisis needs, the system must integrate the following **data categories**:

1. **Data Types:**
 - **EO-based datasets:** soil moisture, evapotranspiration, vegetation indices (NDVI, biomass), land cover
 - **In-situ data:** groundwater and surface water levels, meteorological data, vegetation plots, fire reports
 - **Derived products:** fire ignition probability, biomass drying rates, flood and fire hazard maps
 - **Administrative and infrastructure data:** buildings, roads, safe zones, emergency facilities
2. **Temporal Layers:**
 - **Historical trends** (10–30 years)
 - **Seasonal evolution** (monthly to weekly)
 - **Real-time/crisis response** (daily or hourly updates)
3. **Examples of relevant information layers:**
 - **B2** – Soil moisture
 - **B3** – Groundwater and surface water levels
 - **C1/C2** – Drought and fire hazard maps
 - **A3** – Meteorological indicators
 - **B1** – Evapotranspiration
 - **C3** – Water availability and quality
 - **C6** – Climate adaptation indicators

Summary

Code RSOC	Name lead BUYER/User		
REGULAR	Sector	Support Function	Information specs (based on requirements)
Regular	Terrain Managing Organizations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitoring of groundwater and soil moisture trends • Management of vegetation dynamics and biomass levels • Planning for biodiversity and habitat conservation under changing water conditions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil moisture (surface and root zone) • Vegetation condition and biomass maps (NDVI, LAI) • Groundwater level time series • EO-derived habitat and landscape indicators
	Agriculture and forestry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Irrigation and drainage planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evapotranspiration deficit and crop stress indices

Code RSOC	Name lead BUYER/User		
REGULAR	Sector	Support Function	Information specs (based on requirements)
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adaptation of crop rotations Planning of field operations with heavy equipment Managing forestry fuel loads and planting cycles Optimisation of land-use under variable water availability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil moisture and drought indicators Forest biomass dryness and productivity data Historical trends and scenario datasets
	Drinking water extraction companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring of recharge conditions in groundwater protection zones Infiltration analysis for drought resilience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Groundwater tables and recharge anomalies Surface infiltration and soil saturation maps SWV balance data for catchment zones
	Fire services and crisis management authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Preparedness planning based on seasonal fire risk evolution Integration of fuel load indicators in training and prevention Monitoring of vegetation overgrowth on fire breakways Coordination of drought-related fire prevention campaigns 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fuel dryness indices (LFMC, biomass dryness) Vegetation type Vegetation cover Seasonal fire risk zones and warning thresholds Historical fire occurrences and meteorological triggers
	Municipalities and collaborative organizations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Land-use and spatial planning under drought scenarios Cross-border collaboration for joint ecosystem resilience Policy development support for water and climate adaptation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Combined drought and fire risk maps Hydrological models and EO-derived zoning layers Planning scenarios and adaptation indicators
	Inhabitants and visitors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public awareness on drought and fire risks Support for safe recreational access 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fire warning indicators and visual maps Local water availability and restrictions

Code RSOC	Name lead BUYER/User		
REGULAR	Sector	Support Function	Information specs (based on requirements)
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen science and community feedback mechanisms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EO data visualisations adapted for public dashboards
Crisis	Terrain Managing Organizations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rapid assessment of fire risk based on biomass and dryness • Communication with fire services and crisis units • Damage and vulnerability mapping after incidents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Live fire hazard mapping • Vegetation dryness and topography-based fire spread modelling • Emergency infrastructure and access routes
	Agriculture and forestry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Immediate drought impact monitoring on crops and yields • Assessment of fire risks in rural forest/agriculture interface • Assessment of pluvial or fluvial flooding risks in rural forest/agriculture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time drought indices and biomass status • Fire risk near agricultural zones • Impacted areas and loss estimation
	Drinking water extraction companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crisis response regarding reduced recharge and water stress • Risk planning for temporary scarcity • Communication with authorities and public 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical groundwater thresholds • Temporary extraction limits and maps • Monitoring dashboard access for coordination
	Fire services and crisis management authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incident response coordination based on fire risk zones • Evacuation and access route planning • Fire behaviour modelling for resource prioritization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic fire spread predictions • Live vegetation moisture and meteorological overlays • Safe zones, shelters, and critical infrastructure layers
	Municipalities and collaborative organizations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crisis communication and regional coordination • Management of visitor flows and area closures • Emergency logistics planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emergency alert zones and population exposure • Crisis dashboards with EO layers and local data • Traffic and access overlays for evacuation

Code RSOC	Name lead BUYER/User		
REGULAR	Sector	Support Function	Information specs (based on requirements)
	Inhabitants and visitors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety alerts and fire prevention information • Evacuation readiness and public behavior guidance • Real-time updates on local risk conditions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobile-friendly fire risk alerts and status indicators • Maps of restricted areas and shelters • EO-based local updates translated for public use
Climate	Terrain Managing Organizations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning of long-term resilience to climate variability • Biodiversity strategy based on climate projections • Integration of EO climate datasets into nature policy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate change scenario datasets (2030–2070) • Vegetation shift models and habitat suitability layers • Long-term drought and groundwater simulation data
	Agriculture and forestry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crop and forestry planning based on future scenarios • Selection of climate-resilient varieties and rotations • Assessment of shifting water needs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Projected evapotranspiration and precipitation trends • Soil moisture simulation under climate scenarios • Maps of agricultural suitability under different climates
	Drinking water extraction companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic planning for extraction under future scarcity • Adaptation of protection zones to new recharge patterns • Investments in sustainable infrastructure and environment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-decade groundwater recharge trends • Climate-driven demand modelling • Catchment vulnerability mapping
	Fire services and crisis management authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long-term fire regime modelling • Adjustment of fire response protocols to new climate zones • Investment in early warning infrastructure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fire return interval projections • Vegetation and fuel accumulation under warming trends • Extreme event modeling (heatwaves, droughts)

Code RSOC	Name lead BUYER/User		
REGULAR	Sector	Support Function	Information specs (based on requirements)
	Municipalities and collaborative organizations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adaptation planning at municipal and regional scale Cross-border climate resilience frameworks Funding strategy alignment with climate goals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scenario-based land-use projections Risk exposure modeling for infrastructure and population Data layers for regional adaptation pathways
	Inhabitants and visitors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public engagement on long-term changes Awareness of climate adaptation policies Contribution to co-monitoring efforts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simplified scenario visualisations Information on evolving risks and how to prepare Participatory monitoring and climate apps

6.4. Cluster Group IV

Group 4 deals with **rural problems related to extremes in local climate variations (intensive rainfall) and enduring (structural/over the years) drought periods in the Southern European regions**, having an impact on seasonal processes in agriculture/nature and excesses like floods, wildfires, and agricultural production losses or even failure. These situations cause problems with water availability for rural populations and a high exposition at the risk equation to droughts and particularly floods because the anthropized territory.

The socio-economic impacts of climate change on water management are increasingly severe across Europe, particularly in regions already facing limited water availability or extreme weather events.

In southern Europe, within the Mediterranean basin, **Catalonia** is experiencing a historic **drought** that began in 2023, with critical effects on the Ebro basin in Lleida and the Ter basin in Girona. The prolonged water scarcity has led to stringent restrictions, significantly affecting agricultural production and causing broader regional repercussions. Beyond agriculture, the drought is straining water supplies for urban areas and industries, increasing the risk of conflicts over resource allocation. The prolonged water scarcity not only impacts agriculture but also increases the dryness of vegetation, heightening the likelihood of **fires**. The reduction in soil moisture and the loss of healthy forest mass further contribute to the rapid spread of fires and make ecosystem recovery more challenging after wildfires. At the same time, extreme rainfall events are becoming more intense, posing **flood risks** in highly urbanized coastal areas and river basins with limited capacity to manage sudden water surges. These dual challenges underscore the urgency of improving water management strategies and resilience planning.

Similarly, the **Region of Central Macedonia (RCM)** in Greece, has been repeatedly hit by extreme weather phenomena over the last 20 years, particularly **intense rainfall leading to extensive flooding**. The Mygdonia catchment area, home to major lakes and multiple river systems, has suffered recurrent flood events, such as the Melissourgos village flooding in 2006, the Assyros village flooding in 2009, and the overflow of the Bogdanas stream in 2020. These disasters have caused severe erosion, damage to infrastructure, and significant disruption to local communities, including loss of life and property. In response, the Region of Central Macedonia, in collaboration with local municipalities, has launched initiatives to repair critical infrastructure and implement flood prevention measures. The region also suffers from severe drought that affects agricultural production.

As climate change continues to intensify, these cases highlight the urgent need for proactive adaptation strategies, cross-regional cooperation, and innovative solutions to enhance resilience across Europe.

Common Use case description

Common problem are extremes (too wet, too dry) at rural areas

- Floods

- Drought
 - Agricultural production losses
 - Wildfires

Expected outputs:

- Regular: Soil Moisture maps at high resolution (at least 100m)
- Regular and Crisis: Risk maps (floods and wildfires) at high resolution. Taking into account the threat, exposure and vulnerability

Needs:

- Role of the soil (can be tested at the test site). It is necessary to have information of the soil moisture at surface level and at different depths to have better information of the soil saturation.

We will keep both limits on the test site and define different requirements for the different sites.

Only the test site involved in the validation. All sites involved in the demonstration. Common problems in these different regions are related to extremes (too dry and too wet) at rural areas: floods and droughts (affecting agriculture production and wildfires).

Addressing these challenges requires policies and measures for climate change adaptation and mitigation supported by multidisciplinary metrics and indicators for comprehensive monitoring, measurement, and evaluation.

A key aspect of this effort is the **monitoring of soil moisture**, a crucial variable for understanding and predicting too wet or too dry impacts. Surface soil moisture (up to 5 cm depth) is recognized as an Essential Climate Variable (ECV) by the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS), while root zone soil moisture (1–100 cm) is equally critical. One of the objectives of this use case is to identify, monitor, and map **surface and root zone soil moisture** to obtain the key indicators for detecting changes and assessing their impact on the territory. This will support continuous monitoring, evaluation, and the development of reactive mitigation and adaptation policies, considering weather conditions and climate variability. Deriving accurate soil moisture data requires integrating soil maps, Earth Observation data, and ground-based measurements to model soil moisture dynamics for agriculture, water management, and geomorphological risk assessments, such as landslides.

It is worth mentioning that we treat risk management as a function of threat, exposure, and vulnerability, meaning that the level of risk depends on the likelihood and severity of a threat, the degree of exposure to that threat, and the system's vulnerability to its impacts. Effective risk management involves assessing and mitigating these factors through proactive measures, such as reducing vulnerabilities, limiting exposure, and addressing potential threats before they materialize

Regular

- **Monitor and map surface and root zone soil moisture** to obtain key indicators for detecting changes and assessing their impact on the territory. This supports continuous monitoring, evaluation, and the development of mitigation and adaptation policies considering weather conditions and climate variability. To achieve this, remote sensing technologies will be integrated with in-situ soil moisture measurements to generate high-resolution soil moisture maps. These maps will help track long-term changes in water availability and improve early warning systems. Having soil moisture data at different depths, in addition to surface moisture, provides a better understanding of water retention and infiltration dynamics. Combined with soil type information, these data offer a more accurate estimate of the land's capacity to absorb and store water, with key implications for water resource management, agriculture, and the prevention of droughts, wildfires and floods.
- **Drought impact model on agricultural production at parcel level** can be used for predictions, enabling early anticipation of the effects of drought. By leveraging predictive models, stakeholders will be able to assess the potential impact of drought on agricultural yields before the effects fully materialize. This will enable policymakers and farmers to take preemptive measures, such as adjusting irrigation plans, selecting drought-resistant crops, or implementing temporary water conservation policies. In turn, these strategies can mitigate economic losses and enhance the overall resilience of the agricultural sector. Additionally, improved foresight into drought impacts will allow authorities to allocate financial aid more effectively, ensuring that support reaches the most affected areas in a timely manner.
- Precisely mapping of stream beds and stream banks throughout the Mygdonia Catchment Area – the map must be updated on a yearly basis so as to identify natural or man-made interventions at the stream banks and /or the stream beds.
- Have an FRA (Flood Risk Assessment) study that will estimate the danger of flooding along the river banks and at the estuaries
- Monitor water levels at pre-defined vital choke-points in real time, and notify appropriate authorities accordingly,

Figure 86: ICGC attempts, by airborne sensors data fusion over crops, to determine surface soil moisture at very high resolution (Catalonia region)

Crisis (extreme conditions)

- **During extreme drought conditions**, crop failure is one of the most severe consequences of prolonged drought conditions, leading to significant economic and food security challenges. Optimizing water allocation is crucial during drought conditions to minimize agricultural losses and ensure sustainable resource use. Additionally, the increased dryness of vegetation and soil creates highly flammable conditions, intensifying the risk of wildfires.
To assess and mitigate these risks, a combination of Earth Observation data and agricultural records will be utilized:
 - Additional high-resolution thermal imagery from satellites and airborne sensors can be incorporated to enhance the accuracy of water stress and wildfires assessments. This will allow for more precise estimation of crop water demand, identification of critical areas requiring immediate intervention, and early detection of potential fire outbreaks.
 - Integrating meteorological forecasts with soil moisture models will improve the predictive capability of the system, supporting adaptive water allocation, wildfire prevention measures, and emergency response strategies
- **During event of major floods**, monitoring flood situations with real-time data can be used by the Civil Protection agency so as to better manage available resources for the upcoming flood event.

Stakeholders & Sector

Droughts

Considering the diverse interests and impacts involved, collaboration among different stakeholders is essential to develop effective strategies for mitigating the impact of drought

on agricultural production and wildfire risk. Those are the **agricultural producers** as they are directly affected by changes in production due to drought, **water resource management authorities** as drought significantly influences water availability for agricultural activities, **environmental and agriculture government agencies** which play a role in implementing strategies to mitigate the impact of drought on the agricultural sector and fire hazards. **Meteorological and climate research institutions** provide critical data on weather patterns, rain or drought forecasts and fire risk assessments. **Insurance agencies** also need to account for expected yield losses and potential wildfire damages, which are increasingly linked to prolonged drought conditions.

Both for regular and extreme time: Policy makers and research and operational institutions in charge of surveillance, monitoring and generating recommendations, actions and policies related to water and fire management, local and autonomous government stakeholders and irrigation entities.

Floods

In times of no crises (regular water management): **water and shipping management authorities**, the **city council** and other **local authorities in charge of regular water management**. At regional and local level also their respective **Civil Protection Agencies and their Directorates of Technical Works**.

In times of crisis, response efforts involve regional and local governments through their respective **Civil Protection Agencies and Directorates of Technical Works**, as well as **First Responders**, including the **Fire Brigade, Police Departments, Road Traffic Police Departments, and Healthcare Institutions**. Additionally, **local water management authorities**. [Food security organizations, supply chain, economy stakeholders, ...]

Common Functional needs stakeholder

Droughts

- Actual crop evapotranspiration and soil moisture maps with better resolution and accuracy using EO data fusion approaches.
- Simulation tool capable of determining production losses at field and irrigation district level, under different scenarios of drought and irrigation water restrictions.
- Integration into an open access tool/ Geographic Decision Information System.
- Wildfires risk assessment maps
- Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis/Making

Floods

- Evaluate policies and actions concerning climate adaptation and mitigation measures towards a more resilience territory.
- Create dashboards on these subjects in order to monitor the situation and be able to make predictions, forecasts and planning as decision support tools.
- Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis/Making
- To improve planning and coordination in times of crises, focus on the reduction of vulnerability and exposition at the risk equation.
- To monitor flood situations and progression to provide better proposals for effective measures.

Common Required information

Drought

The development of a drought impact model on agricultural production necessitates a multidisciplinary approach, drawing from various data sources including satellite data (time-series of high-resolution (20 m) actual evapotranspiration (ET)), vector field boundaries, weather forecasts, land use and soil type maps, irrigation system maps, and irrigation district water allocations. In addition, it is recommended to use actual yield data in order to train artificial intelligence approaches, together with ET remote sensing data. These datasets are essential for simulating diverse scenarios and evaluating potential solutions tailored to minimize production losses at parcel level based on specific needs.

Earth observation data requires to translate data into knowledge just to provide the right information through user friendly interfaces with the capacity to exploit this information and interact with other sorts of geospatial data. Developing of interactive and friendly surface and root zone soil moisture viewers on weekly-monthly basis and detection of anomalies in a high latency will help in mapping potential risk areas to apply water management mitigation and adaptation actions in advance as well as for wildfire risk assessment.

Regular basis:

- Processing Earth Observation (EO) data to improve the spatial resolution and accuracy of actual crop evapotranspiration (researchers)
- Validation of the modelled production under actuals scenarios of water restrictions (researchers)
- Simulation exercises according to different scenarios to mitigate possible affectations (stakeholders)
- Analysis of the feasibility of decision support tools of estimation of risk integrating socioeconomic factors (stakeholders)

Crisis:

- Simulation tool that provides information and different scenarios to all involved stakeholders (water resource management authorities, environmental and agriculture government agencies) about water management, production losses, wildfire risk, etc.
- Validation of the modelled production (researchers)

Floods

Main goal for the data requirements is to be able to monitor the water content of the soil to be aware of trends and changes in the water/soil system.

Historic values as far as they can be accessed, hopefully since the beginning of this century.

Data collected twice per year on a 10x10 meter pixel size.

When tackling the crisis case, it would be preferable to have more recent data, maybe a week's old, hopefully much less. Though acquiring real-time data may be either not possible or simply too expensive, the possession of such a data map would be evaluated during a simulated crisis event (see chapter 6.2.2).

From the perspective of Emergency Response Agencies in an urban/municipal setting during the pre-disaster phase:

- Comprehensive overview of live water levels (water levels also at locations where no level measuring instrument is available – higher resolution of water level information)
- Historical water levels, high and low
- Prediction of future water levels
- Early warning information, that are not based on weather only, but consider the current "water" status (e.g. how saturated is the soil, how was precipitation in the last days/weeks) in combination with expected weather conditions, to be able to determine expected impacts as accurately as possible (essential for preparation and planning)
- High resolution flood hazard maps, that display flooded areas for certain water levels. To prioritize response and warning measures it is important to know, from which water level at which river which assets (building, infrastructure etc.) can be expected to be flooded.
- Assessment of the impact on flood protection infrastructure based on the water level predictions (identifying which dikes may be vulnerable to breaching first, determining when certain flood retention basins will reach capacity, etc.)
- Analysis of consequences/exposure on inhabited areas (for prioritizing protective measures and preparing for evacuations) -> Flood risk maps
 - Estimation of affected population, vulnerability factors (age structure, mobility, etc.)
 - Evaluation of affected residences and damage assessment (based on physical vulnerability)

- Examination of critical infrastructure within the affected areas and possible disruption of functionalities (power supply, roads, affected fire stations etc.)

Handling/Technology:

- Data intersection possibility for the integration with locally utilized command and control software/information systems (first responders probably have their own software established, it could be helpful if (parts of) our results can be transferred into that)
- Possibility to enter data manually from outside, e.g. discovery of dyke damages
- User-friendly and intuitive handling of core functions (considering that First Responders may use the system infrequently, leading to a gradual development of expertise despite training efforts)

Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis/Making:

Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis/Making (MCDA/M) is a set of methods used to evaluate and compare multiple alternatives based on several, often conflicting, criteria. It provides a structured approach to decision-making by combining quantitative and qualitative data, allowing decision-makers to assess trade-offs and prioritize options. MCDA/M involves defining the problem, selecting relevant criteria, assigning weights to reflect their importance, scoring each alternative against these criteria, and aggregating the results to rank or select the best option. It is widely used in fields like urban planning, environmental management, and public policy, where decisions must consider diverse stakeholder perspectives and complex factors.

In climate-related problem solving, such as managing floods, droughts, or food security, decisions must account for a complex mix of environmental, social, economic, and technical factors, often with competing priorities. MCDA/M is crucial in these contexts because it enables a transparent and systematic evaluation of diverse options under uncertainty. It helps integrate scientific data with local knowledge, balances short-term needs with long-term sustainability, and supports inclusive decision-making by incorporating the values of multiple stakeholders. By using MCDA, policymakers can make more informed, balanced, and resilient choices in the face of climate risks.

In a real-world drought management case, MCDA/M can be used to identify the most effective water-saving strategies for a region. First, data is collected on options like groundwater recharge, crop switching, rainwater harvesting, and water rationing, along with criteria such as cost, water efficiency, social acceptance, and environmental impact. Experts, including hydrologists, farmers, and policymakers, score each option based on these criteria and use pairwise comparisons to assign weights that reflect the relative importance of each factor (e.g., efficiency might outweigh cost in a severe drought). MCDA/M then aggregates these inputs to rank the alternatives, helping decision-makers choose the most balanced and sustainable response.

In summary, MCDA/M is a powerful tool for addressing complex climate-related challenges by combining data, expert judgment, and stakeholder values in a structured way. It is especially effective when integrated with GIS, where it supports the creation of risk maps and

spatial prioritization, for example, identifying areas most vulnerable to drought or in need of intervention. By weighing multiple criteria and evaluating trade-offs, MCDA/M helps decision-makers develop transparent, balanced, and context-sensitive solutions, making it invaluable for climate adaptation and resilience planning.

Benefits

Common benefits:

- Improve temporal and spatial resolutions on **surface soil moisture**
- Operational-feasible and viable method to derive **root zone soil moisture** to assess the availability and retention of water
- **Risk maps** (floods, droughts and wildfires) - threat, exposure and vulnerability
- Enable **predictions and early anticipation**
- **Reduction of the risk**
- **Better management of water resource**
- **Better practices during the design process for risk mitigation works**

In **Catalonia**, agriculture is the most water-demanding sector. In a drought context, as reservoir levels drop dramatically, some irrigated agricultural areas are compelled to impose water restrictions on farmers to enhance efficiency and protect crops. Similarly, as precipitation decreases, the amount of water available in the soil is lower.

Both the amount of water used by crops (ET) and the soil water available to them are critical parameters for monitoring and improving water management and have a direct impact on crop productivity. These factors depend on physical soil properties, total irrigation water allocation and management, and climatic conditions. Any reduction of these parameters will negatively impact yield. Therefore, there is an urgent need to determine the impact that different reductions in water resource availability may have on crop productivity. This should be known in current and future climate scenarios. Catalonia exhibits specific characteristics that make it particularly vulnerable:

- i) Droughts are common, and a significant portion of its forests have limited access to water resources, increasing the risk of wildfires.
- ii) Dominated by a Mediterranean climate, the region experiences high spatial and temporal variability in temperature and precipitation, making both modelling and resource management highly challenging.
- iii) The territory has significant spatial and orographic variability in climate and species distribution, including cold-climate species that reach their southernmost range in Catalonia.

The project's main benefits lie in enhancing the understanding of processes related to the conservation, management, and monitoring of the water cycle, and its impact on crop productivity. By translating scientific knowledge into decision-support tools, the project aims **to improve territorial water management in a Mediterranean country**, where water is a scarce resource. This will help ensure sustainable agriculture while promoting the socio-systemic and ecological value of natural landscapes and mitigating fire risk.

Figure 87: Soil moisture retrieval as a fusion of airborne passive L band radiometry and VNIR

In the **Region of Central Macedonia**, the benefits of implementing soil moisture data could potentially help in **reducing flood risk**, while also allowing for **better practices during the design process for flood mitigation works**. This means preventing damage to infrastructure and buildings and thus reduced costs for repairs and compensations.

The gathering of middle-term soil moisture data could potentially be used in formulating a **better flood mitigation protocol**, that would be centred in the use case (initially) and the rest of the region (secondarily). Also, should this pilot idea prove to be useful for local authorities in Central Macedonia, it could be suggested to the central government for implementation at a national level.

In the long term, better design of hydraulic works would help partially alleviate flood risk in the use case area and thus allow for better/safer land use from farmers and local industries. Also, lower flood risk would allow for the development of the local economy given that the area is in relatively close proximity to the local Thessaloniki Airport (SKG), and also to the railway network that connects the country with its northern Balkan neighbours.

As far as agricultural activity in the region is concerned, it is directly dependent on the adequacy and quality of water. Proposed strategies for adapting to climate change include restructuring crops, improving irrigation systems and promoting alternative solutions, such as the use of renewable energy sources for water pumping. A digital management tool could allow the optimal allocation of water to crops, reducing waste and ensuring the sustainability of the primary sector. The adoption and use of such a tool would contribute to the harmonization of the region with the European Directives on water management (Directive 2000/60/EC) and would facilitate access to financial programs and investments in order for the upgrade of water resources management infrastructure.

The existence of real-time soil moisture data could potentially be used in Civil Protection protocols, especially when faced with up-coming heavy rainfalls. However, designing a response mechanism that incorporates soil moisture data is new grounds for Central Macedonia and any suggestions/use cases by communities that have already integrated such a system will be greatly appreciated.

Generalisation of benefits for crisis time:

- Prioritization of response/resource allocation
- Decision support for flood response measures (alarming more units, declaring “state of crisis/catastrophe”, building mobile dykes, dyke relief measures)
- Overview of flood extent now and in the near future (impacted buildings, critical infrastructure and roads)
- Overview of affected population and assets
- Evacuation planning

Feedback from Miro Board:

- Reduce flood risk, improve water availability for agriculture
- Improve temporal and spatial resolutions on surface soil moisture
- Operational-feasible and viable method to derived root zone soil moisture
- Assess the impact of drought on agricultural production at parcel level
- Enable predictions and early anticipation of the effects of drought.
- Better management of water resource with lower impacts on production
- Hazard maps based on dynamic vegetation-water-soil data
- Trigger for an automated early warning system
- Reliable overview of water resources

Summary

Group 4 is dealing with rural problems related to extremes in local climate variations (intensive rainfall) and enduring (structural/over the years) drought periods in the Southern European regions having impact on seasonal processes in agriculture/nature and excesses like wildfires and production losses or even failure. These situations cause problems on water availability for rural populations and a high exposition at the risk equation to droughts and particularly floods because the anthropized territory.

Code RSOC	Name lead BUYER/User		
REGULAR	Sector	Support Function	Information specs (based on requirements)
<i>Urban</i>	Greek Municipal Directorates	Improvement of local measurements	SM data/maps for Mygdonia basin
<i>Regional</i>	RCM – Directorate of Technical Works	Enhance/Improve the Design of Flood Mitigation Works for the Mygdonia basin (primary objective)	SM data/maps for Mygdonia basin

Code RSOC	Name lead BUYER/User		
REGULAR	Sector	Support Function	Information specs (based on requirements)
	RCM – Civil Protection Agency	Create/Enhance maps indicating possible flooding danger within the Mygdonia basin (primary objective)	SM data/maps for Mygdonia basin
	RCM – Directorate of Rural Economy and Fisheries	Enhance/Improve Irrigation Systems and Restructure Crops for the Mygdonia basin (primary objective)	SM data/maps for Mygdonia basin
	Catalonia – Dpt. of Agriculture, Livestock, Fisheries and Food	Maintenance and policy management of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Green (tree's shrubs, grass, etc.) - Water and climate adaptation assets including new crops or cultures - Availability of groundwater for irrigation practices - Territorial management of natural covers: forestland and agriculture mosaics. 	<p>The development of a drought impact model on agricultural production and interactions with forestlands necessitates a multidisciplinary approach, drawing from various data sources including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Satellite data time-series of high-resolution (20 m) actual evapotranspiration (ET) - Vector field boundaries, weather forecasts, land use and soil type maps - Irrigation system maps, and irrigation district water allocations, irrigation needs per crop - Crops/yield declarations (CAP-UE) - Impact of the irrigation management on crops - Train artificial intelligence approaches, together with remote sensing data. These datasets are essential for simulating diverse scenarios and evaluating potential solutions tailored to minimize production losses at parcel level based on specific needs, better irrigation and water management and to evaluate the water cycle interaction between agriculture and forestland ecosystems - Pre-season predictions of the impact of irrigation restrictions in the crop production and quality, - Weekly soil moisture monitoring - Weekly groundwater monitoring (availability and quality) - Historical trends of water availability
	Catalonia - Water management Agency. Department of Territory, Housing and Ecological Transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Water management - Aquifer management - Water quality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Satellite data time-series of high-resolution (100 m or better) soil moisture - Vector field boundaries, weather forecasts, land use and soil type maps - Irrigation system maps, and irrigation district water allocations, irrigation needs per crop - Crops/yield declarations (CAP-UE) - Impact of the irrigation management on crops - Limits that define pre-crisis or crisis periods to be able to take informed decisions in advance. - Irrigation limits to support irrigation management - Inspection and control of illegal aquifers and irrigation practices

Code RSOC	Name lead BUYER/User		
REGULAR	Sector	Support Function	Information specs (based on requirements)
			- Damage assessment of crop production - Monitoring water levels, quality
National	Hellenic National Meteorological Service	Create models for preventing crisis events (flooding)	SM data/maps for Mygdonia basin
	Greek Ministry of the Environment	Create/Enhance maps indicating possible flooding danger	SM data/maps for Mygdonia basin
	Ministry of Rural Development and Food	Enhance/Modify agricultural policies	SM data/maps for Mygdonia basin
CRISIS	Sector	Support (function)	Information (requirements)
Regional	RCM – Civil Protection Agency	Issue warnings concerning the usage of the road network for an upcoming Heavy Rainfall event	Recent / Real Time SM maps for Mygdonia basin
	RCM – Civil Protection Agency	Issue warnings concerning populated areas (villages, industries) located close to the local river network for an upcoming Heavy Rainfall event	Recent / Real Time SM maps for Mygdonia basin
	Catalonia – Dpt. of Agriculture, Livestock, Fisheries and Food	Crop failure	- Crops/yield declarations (CAP-UE) - Satellite data time-series of high-resolution (10 m) actual vegetation index - Vector field boundaries, weather forecasts, land use and soil type maps
	Catalonia - Water management Agency. Department of Territory, Housing and Ecological Transition	Redistribution of water	- Satellite data time-series of high-resolution (100 m or better) soil moisture - Vector field boundaries, weather forecasts, land use and soil type maps - Irrigation system maps, and irrigation district water allocations, irrigation needs per crop - Crops/yield declarations (CAP-UE) - Impact of the irrigation management on crops
Climate	Sector	Support (function)	Information (requirements)
	Catalonia – Dpt. of Agriculture, Livestock, Fisheries and Food	<p>Short term:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Forecasting of annual crop production and quality - Assessment of the number of possible harvests, and amount of irrigations according to water availability. - Minimize future production losses during drought periods and improve water management practices - Improvement of risks maps of wildfires, models of ignition-propagation, due to drought conditions <p>Mid-term:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Modifications in production methods. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Satellite data time-series of high-resolution (20 m) actual evapotranspiration (ET), - Vector field boundaries, weather forecasts, land use and soil type maps. - Irrigation system maps, and irrigation district water allocations, irrigation needs per crop - Crops/yield declarations (CAP-UE) - Impact of the irrigation management on crops - Soil moisture maps at high resolution (100m or better) - Model of the impact of the drought on the crop production

Code RSOC	Name lead BUYER/User		
REGULAR	Sector	Support Function	Information specs (based on requirements)
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adaptation and resilience of crops to climate conditions and cultural practices towards drought-resistant species to new climate scenarios. - Introduce short-cycle crops that require less water and can be harvested more quickly to reduce the need for long-term water consumption and ensure production. - Promote regenerative agriculture techniques to enhance the soil's capacity to retain water and nutrients. - Promote minimizing the use of fertilizers and pesticides to improve water quality. <p>Long-term:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design and implementation of new scenarios such as change of the crop typology - Promotion of more efficient irrigation techniques and promoting the reuse of wastewater. All applicable to the agro-systemic value in the Mediterranean context. - New policy definition for land cover management or territorial planning adjustments based on available resources - Landscape transformation to increase the most efficient use of water and water harvesting. - Design and implementation of mosaicing landscapes strategies to foster environmental-social-eco systemic value to better adaptation and mitigation of climate change. 	
	Catalonia - Water management Agency. Department of Territory, Housing and Ecological Transition	<p>Short term:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Water restrictions according to their impact on crop production and quality. - Impact on the aquifers during summer season - Monitoring of water layer continuity on river basins to assure ecological and biodiversity issues <p>Long term:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adaptation of aquifer management policies to allow water extraction from deeper layers in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Vector field boundaries, weather forecasts, land use and soil type maps - Irrigation system maps, and irrigation district water allocations, irrigation needs per crop - Crops/yield declarations (CAP-UE) - Impact of the irrigation management on crops - Soil moisture maps at high resolution (100m or better) - Model of the impact of the drought on the crop production - Aquifers water level and quality maps - Reservoirs water level and quality maps

Code RSOC	Name lead BUYER/User		
REGULAR	Sector	Support Function	Information specs (based on requirements)
		<p>response to decreasing available water resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Regulating aquifer use through monitoring and controlling illegal extractions- Setting limits on the number of aquifers that can be exploited to ensure sustainable water management.- Protection of natural infiltration zones to prevent soil sealing and enhance groundwater recharge.- Salinization control in coastal areas to ensure the quality.	

6.5. Cluster Group V

This section provides a description of one of the five use case clusters, namely Group 5.

Common Use case description

This use case represents slow- and fast-onset crises in rural areas in northern Europe that are near to the coast or are relatively flat with varying degrees of surface near groundwater levels, where climate change is experienced in the form of increased occurrence of dry spells and heavy rainfall events resulting in further risks/ challenges/complications such as subsidence, floods and peatland fires. Subsidence, floods and fires affect agriculture, infrastructure and natural habitats with significant potential impacts on human lives and/or livelihoods.

Buyer group members are

FORENINGEN KLIMATORIUM (KLIMATORIUM) (Denmark), BUNDESANSTALT TECHNISCHES HILFSWERK (THW) (Germany) and HDSR Waterauthority (The Netherlands).

The primary objective for HDSR, THW, and Klimatorium within the PCP WISE project is to enhance rural water management, resilience against climate change and disaster preparedness by utilising space and Earth Observation (EO) data. This initiative includes monitoring diverse aspects of the rural water cycle, such as soil moisture, groundwater levels, and surface water, with the aim to both mitigate risks like flooding, drought, fire and subsidence, as well as improve responsiveness and long-term adaptability to these risks. The overarching goal is to develop more sustainable and resilient rural areas that are better prepared to address water-related challenges amplified by a changing climate.

Regular

All three buyer group members share a common interest in utilizing space and Earth Observation (EO) data to enhance their understanding of the water cycle and how it affects local conditions. However, HDSR and Klimatorium share the need of information for regular conditions, whereas THW needs information under extreme conditions, as other authorities oversee monitoring under regular conditions. There are common interests between all 3 use-cases though, and the focus areas for each use-case are shown below.

Buyer group member	Focus areas
Klimatorium	Groundwater monitoring, subsidence monitoring and modelling, effects on underground water infrastructure, agriculture, climate adaption, impact of heavy rainfall, water management
THW	Soil moisture, weather data, water resources, water conditions, drought and fire risk, flood risk, vegetation, hazard maps
HDSR	Drought, ground water monitoring, subsidence monitoring and modelling, agriculture, water management, nature conservation

Table 37 Focus areas

Common interests:**Drought:**

- The impacts of drought on soil moisture, groundwater levels, vegetation/agriculture (and subsidence).
- Using EO data to predict and monitor drought conditions is of interest.

Soil Moisture:

- Monitoring soil moisture for mitigating risks for fire and subsidence.

Groundwater level:

- Monitoring ground water levels for improving water resource management and mitigating risks for fire and subsidence.

Subsidence (Common interest of Klimatorium and HDSR):

- Soil subsidence caused by changes in groundwater levels and oxidation.
- Monitoring subsidence of larger rural areas
- Understanding the influence of measures on soil and water to mitigate subsidence.
- Managing shallow groundwater levels to protect infrastructure.
- Managing shallow groundwater levels to protect agriculture and nature
- Understanding subsidence patterns to improve water management and climate adaptation.
- Understanding and connection with the influence of the general rise in water levels on the groundwater level.

Common Concerns:

- Drought and flooding events in rural areas
- Increased risk of fire and subsidence
- Impact on nature and agriculture

Timeline and Scenario Evaluation:

- Interest in historical data.
- Focus on both regular monitoring and crisis situations.
- Need for continuous monitoring and modelling.

Crisis (extreme conditions)**Common interests:**

Using PCP Wise data is expected to enable better crisis management strategies for all stakeholders represented by the buyers under extreme conditions. There is a shared focus on prevention and preparedness, however, in the case of THW detailed information in the run up and during a water-related crisis remains the priority:

In order to improve planning in such operations and to have a better overview of the overall situation, data from the PCP Wise project should be used. This should include soil moisture, availability of free water areas in the vicinity for water extraction, existing routes into the fire or flooding area and free logistics areas around the incident. Weather data is also important to predict the spread of fire and smoke or the evolution of floods and to be able to take appropriate response measures.

Stakeholders & Sector

Stakeholders by Sector:

Water management

- Water boards
- Water and waste-water utilities

Agriculture

- Farmers
- Agriculture consultants (in Denmark: SEGES (national), local consultancies such as Fjordland)

Emergency services

- Incident command staff at municipal level
- Emergency responders (e.g. fire brigades, rescue services, technical disaster relief agencies, police)
- Local technical experts (e.g. forest managers, lower water authorities)

Climate adaption

- Municipalities
- Coastal protection agency
- Governmental departments for environment and climate adaption

Infrastructure

- Municipalities
- Construction companies
- Road and railway authorities (in Denmark: Vejdirektoratet og BaneDanmark (national), local private railways)
- Owner, operator and developer for transmission systems for electricity, district heating and natural gas.
- CCS and Geothermal facilities

Common Functional needs stakeholder

HDSR Waterauthority:

Policy Evaluation: Primarily observational.

Impact and Scenario Analysis: Primarily model based.

A "best-of-many-worlds" approach—where observations and models inform one another—appears most suitable to address diverse information needs.

Foreningen Klimatorium (KLIMATORIUM):

Impact and scenario analysis of groundwater levels and subsidence in relation to both agriculture and impact on water and wastewater utilities infrastructure

Bundesanstalt Technisches Hilfswerk (THW):

In times of crises the THW can provide and translate relevant spatial data for local authorities and emergency response units to improve their planning and coordination efforts. The THW seeks to be able to better monitor vegetation fire and flood situations and predict their progression to provide better suggestions for effective counter measures.

Stakeholders' functional needs will vary depending on the type of natural disaster (flood vs. fire) and local organizational conditions.

Commonalities:

Main Service: Regular (and historical) rootzone soil moisture and groundwater (inherently evapotranspiration) monitoring fed by smart meteorological (spatio-temporal) inputs, development of risk indicators for drought and flood-related (fast onset crises) problems impacting ecosystems, agricultural productivity and rural townships.

Next to this long term (climate) monitoring of water shortage (and abundance) based on past (spatio-temporal) trends for future climate scenarios (local and surrounding river basin region), it is important to develop risk indicators per sector (nature, agriculture, rural settlements)

Specific Service:

Rural subsidence monitoring (decadal period), (spatio-temporal) Risk indicator monitor per sector (slow onset/ long term), (spatio-temporal) risk intelligence monitor in fast onset situation (fires, floods).

Combine satellite-borne observations with data and near-surface geological/geotechnical/hydrological models of the subsurface and climate data.

Build warning systems and develop risk indicators for use in both acute crisis preparedness, long-term planning and scenario calculations of future climate change.

Build a model for risk mapping/projection of the consequences of vertical subsidence for waterways (extreme surface rain) and the underground infrastructure as well as security of supply (lack of subsidence or rupture of pipelines)

Common Required information

For FORENINGEN KLIMATORIUM (KLIMATORIUM) and HDSR Waterauthority:

Stakeholders require a spatially comprehensive subsidence map (in mm/year) that most users can recognize and accept. This map should be built using publicly available data, tools, and expertise. Achieving this may involve integrating datasets such as water levels, soil composition, meteorological data and groundwater trends, alongside satellite data and related techniques. The map can also be combined with analyses and 3D multifunctional voxel models of the subsurface. The Danish hydro-geological model “GeoAtlas Live” is an example of such a model.

Temporal dimensions are also critical. Subsidence must be assessed over longer periods (e.g., 10+ years for structural trends) and short-term dynamics (e.g., annual or seasonal variations) to better understand driving processes.

For BUNDESANSTALT TECHNISCHES HILFSWERK (THW):

Emergency response agencies require spatial data and modelling tools to better anticipate and respond to natural disasters.

As for the **fire scenario**, the required information for the **pre-disaster phase** encompasses real-time fire hazard maps based on weather conditions (e.g. heat and wind), water cycle information (e.g. how were the drought conditions in the last days/weeks) and status of the vegetation cover (e.g. how dry is the vegetation) to better predict outbreaks and send automated alerts to emergency response agencies. In addition, they require an overview of the water system and information about (ground)water levels to take better informed decisions (e.g., about holding back water resources in areas that are at high risk) to prepare for a potential fire scenario. As for the **response phase** they need spatial data to identify safe areas for staging/deploying firefighting resources like trucks, command units, etc. and access roads for fire trucks. They require real-time information on potentially available water sources (e.g. underground pipes, lakes, rivers) and levels to decide where and how much water can be pumped out to fight the fire, and they would benefit from fire spread prediction data/models based on the aforementioned hazard maps, starting point of the fire and current weather conditions.

As for the **flood scenario**, the required information for the **pre-disaster phase** encompasses real-time, high resolution flood hazard and risk maps based on topology data, an overview of live water levels, soil conditions, recent, current and expected weather conditions and precipitation coupled with information about the potentially affected population (e.g. density, vulnerability factors) and infrastructure. As for **the response phase**, information about real-time flood extent and predicted spread are crucial as well as information about retention areas, dyke capacities, access roads, etc

Benefits

Water and waste-water utilities:

By using knowledge of the relationship between ground water level changes and rate of subsidence, daily ground water level information (and thereby opportunity to manipulate it) could help keep subsidence rate to a minimum - thus protect infrastructure. Also help predict future subsidence rates and better planning of future construction of water infrastructure. Knowledge of terrain settlements will serve water and wastewater utilities in several ways:

1. Improve identification of damaged infrastructure and Water Losses
2. Improve planning and Decision-Making: Knowledge of terrain settlements can support water resource planning and decision-making processes by providing spatially detailed information on land surface changes, hydrological dynamics, and environmental impacts. This information can help water companies anticipate future challenges, such as changing groundwater conditions, land subsidence risks, or water quality issues, and develop proactive strategies to address them.
3. Financial benefits: Sustainable financial management and maintenance strategy (condition-based maintenance)

Satellite data will enable utilities to move to a more condition-based maintenance of water infrastructure, as opposed to reactive maintenance strategy. This will improve the sustainability of utilities' economy and strengthen security of supply. Better data on subsidence will not only provide benefits for water and wastewater utilities, but also other infrastructure stakeholders, both above and below ground. It will also serve municipalities and other national authorities working with climate adaptation planning, where modelling future risk of floods and land-use planning are on the agenda

Furthermore, knowledge of subsidence and soil moisture will help agriculture in relation to planning of future land-use and better planning of drainage

Policy evaluation

Sustainable water management

Sustainable agricultural practices

Emergency services:

Some benefits for crisis time preparations:

- Situation monitoring for early warning and preparation
- Fire and flood hazard and risk maps support in preparation and pre-event decision-making
- Validating that enough response capacities (firefighters, trucks etc.) are available to adequately respond to certain scenarios (input for civil protection planning of local authorities)

- Raising awareness and alerting (possibly affected) population, house owners, infrastructure operators, etc.
- Providing scenario-adjusted training to first responders and incident command staff with realistic simulation exercises
- Aligned taxonomy helps in cross state, cross border situations and inter-organisation collaboration

Some benefits for crisis time:

- Same information basis for all involved stakeholders

Prioritization of response/resource allocation

- Decision support for flood / fire response measures (e.g. alarming and mobilizing more units, declaring “state of crisis/catastrophe”, creating fire breaks)
- Estimation of the extent and spread of the fire / flood
- Overview of possible affected population and infrastructure
- Evacuation planning

Summary

Cluster Group V addresses climate-related water management challenges in rural, low-lying, and coastal areas of Northern Europe, with a focus on slow- and fast-onset crises such as droughts, heavy rainfall, floods, peatland fires, and soil subsidence. These phenomena impact agriculture, infrastructure, and natural habitats, and are expected to increase in frequency and severity due to climate change.

The group, led by Klimatorium (Denmark) in collaboration with THW (Germany) and HDSR (The Netherlands), shares a common goal of improving monitoring and resilience of rural water systems through the integration of Earth Observation (EO) data and local in-situ measurements. While HDSR and Klimatorium focus on regular monitoring, THW emphasizes extreme event preparedness and response.

The use case emphasizes the need for integrated data on soil moisture, groundwater levels, and surface water to support predictive capabilities and decision-making across crisis and routine contexts. A local test site and corresponding sub-basin area have been defined to enable validation of innovative EO-based solutions for rural climate resilience. These efforts contribute directly to the objectives of the PCP WISE project by enabling more adaptive, data-driven rural water management across European regions.

Code RSOC	Name lead BUYER/User		
REGULAR	Sector	Support Function	Information specs (based on requirements)

Regular	Water and waste water utilities and waterboards	Policy evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring of groundwater levels and terrain subsidence to inform infrastructure planning and maintenance - Use of EO data to support sustainable water resource management and condition-based maintenance
	Water and waste water utilities and waterboards	Impact and Scenario Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Combined use of EO and hydrogeological models to understand soil moisture, groundwater dynamics, and climate trends - Development of risk indicators for drought, flood, and subsidence - Long-term monitoring for policy and land-use planning
	Agriculture and nature conservation	Land-use and environmental planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Soil moisture and groundwater data to support irrigation planning and nature protection - Subsidence data to guide future agricultural practices and preserve sensitive ecosystems
Crisis	Emergency services	Planning and coordination in times of crises	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Real-time EO-based situational awareness for fire and flood response - Mapping of access routes, available water sources, logistics zones, and hazard spread - Tools for coordination, prioritization, and resource allocation across agencies
	Emergency services	monitor fire and flood situations and predict their progression to provide better proposals for effective measures.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fire/flood hazard maps and spread prediction based on weather, vegetation status, and water availability - Data to support early warnings, evacuation planning, and effective countermeasures - Support for scenario-based training and civil protection planning

7. Annex C: Annex of the tender (Work in progress)

PCP WISE is an EC funded project which aims at the creation of hydrological information products and derived risk indicators (in the form of grid based maps) for general (non-crisis) and crisis water management and related problems such as wild fires, biodiversity loss, the urban heat island effect et cetera.

The general objective of PCP WISE is the creation of new information for land and water managers to overcome the challenges climate change, urbanization, demographic and geopolitical developments brings us in the (near) future.

The main focus of PCPWISE is on the unsaturated zone states and fluxes (in rural and urban areas) and their relationship with the groundwater system, crops, ecosystems and urban areas. See the General Tender Document for more information and context.

This program of requirements dictates the necessary requirements on which your offer has to be based on.

The core of the Tender

The tender within the PCP WISE project will focus on the development of innovative information products to support improved water management in both urban and rural areas. The assignment has two closely linked main objectives:

1. From Information Gap to Integrated Insight: The Foundation for Day-to-Day Water Management

One of the key challenges is to develop a robust, validated, and standardized information base on the soil-water-vegetation (SWV) system. This foundational data is currently largely lacking, yet it is essential for gaining daily insight into the local water balance in both urban and rural environments. Without this information, a reliable and integrated soil-water information system cannot be realized.

The market is therefore challenged to develop this foundation in collaboration with public authorities. This requires combining various types of data — such as remote sensing, field measurements, and model outputs — into a coherent SWV system insight that can be applied consistently across different European contexts.

Based on this integrated SWV information, a continuous stream of actionable data should be created to support water managers in their routine tasks. This information must be made accessible through user-friendly tools, such as standardized dashboards tailored to local practices.

This task thus forms the first fundamental building block of the challenge.

2. Information Products for Anticipating Extreme Events

In addition to support daily management, the challenge specifically emphasizes developing solutions that are highly context-dependent, varying greatly between urban and rural settings, as demonstrated by the different use cases.

The market is asked to develop information products that present these risks in an up-to-date and user-friendly manner. This includes spatial maps updated daily, featuring indicators tailored to the needs of different users — from water managers to emergency response agencies. The maps should be relevant for both preparatory actions (such as planning and prevention) and operational response during incidents.

Where the first point forms the foundation of an integrated information system, this component represents its application for risk management and climate adaptation. Together, these two pillars contribute to resilient water management in a changing climate (as a basis for hind-now- & forecasting intelligence)

Additional EO-based services tailored to specific use cases may be requested to provide more localised insights. Generally, two levels of service will be applied at each test site:

- A detailed service at the local test site;
- A contextual service at the intermediate (river basin) scale.

In Summary

This broad scope calls for information that is still largely missing today: validated and standardized information on the SWV system, built upon a robust interoperable hydrological model. This model is essential for achieving integrated, climate-resilient water management. The market is therefore challenged to help develop this SWV model and to seamlessly integrate it with other necessary data sources. Only then can a future-proof soil-water information system be created — one that supports both regular operations and crisis situations.

7.1. PCP Challenge summary

The envisaged future PCP – i.e. a joint cross-border procurement of R&D services – is launched to reinforce public demand-driven innovation on the climate adaptation domain. PCP has the potential to be an effective demand-side innovation action and a useful tool to close the gap between supply and demand for innovative solutions. Solutions are expected to achieve TRL 7-8 at the end of Phase 3 as depicted in figures 1 and 2.

The PCP should deliver successful innovative and fully tested product(s) and/or service(s) that meet the common challenge of the Public Buyers Group to procure research, develop innovative marketable solutions, speed up the time-to-market and provide best value for money.

The Public Buyers Group aims to develop an innovative solution to tackle the five use cases concerning climate adaptation, namely:

Use Case 1: Urban Drought (North Europe)

It focuses on urban drought issues in North-Western Europe, dealing with water distribution problems in city undergrounds due to various human and external factors. This use case aims to mitigate water shortages impacting infrastructure and living conditions.

Use Case 2: Urban Flooding (North-Central Europe)

It addresses urban water excess in Eastern and Northern Europe, where the abundance of water affects city infrastructure. This use case focuses on managing issues exacerbated by regional factors like sea-level rise.

Use Case 3: Rural Drought (Northwest-Central Europe)

It tackles rural drought in North-Eastern Europe, where extreme climate variations impact agriculture and nature, leading to issues like wildfires and production losses.

Use Case 4: Rural Drought & Flooding (Southern Europe)

It deals with rural drought and flooding in Southern Europe, where structural drought periods and intense rainfall affect agricultural processes and cause significant production challenges.

Use Case 5: Rural Drought & Flooding (Northern Europe)

It focuses on rural drought and flooding in North-Eastern Europe, addressing problems caused by extreme groundwater conditions that impact land use and infrastructure. This use case aims to manage soil moisture conditions to prevent issues like organic oxidation and underground peat fires.

7.2. PCP WISE Requirements

Each requirement will identify by a unique ID and name.

The requirements are categorized as follows:

- **Functional Requirements:** These describe the core actions the solution must perform, aligned with the project's primary challenges and expected system behaviour.
- **Technical Requirements:** Technical requirements define the specific implementation to fulfil functional or non-functional requirements. They outline the technologies, protocols, standards, system architecture etc. that must be followed to ensure the overall quality of the developed solutions. In layman's terms: they describe not what to implement, but how to implement it.
- **Contract Performance Requirements:** These requirements cover operational and management considerations, including prototype deployment and feedback mechanisms from pilot activities.

7.2.1. Functional Requirements

Information Requirements

General

ID	Name	Short Description	Mandatory
FRIGE 1.1.	Prediction Error Estimate	All information products should be accompanied with a prediction error estimate, preferably design based and if not possible model based	X
FRGE 1.2	Storage	All information products and Risk Indicators shall be stored at the contractor's premises or designated sites. The contractor shall ensure that end users receive the relevant data at the start of each day.	X
FRGE 1.3	Viewer (GUI)	A viewer (GUI) and related to that the API should be provided to present/disclose all WISE products to the 5 groups. An option could be to combine it with the opensource (hydrological) presentation suite of iMOD (related to MODFLOW-6). Alternatives can be used/proposed. Please refer for more information on the Data Viewer requirements (FRDV1.1.- FRDV1.31)	X
FRGE 1.4	Access to information	All generated information products and risk indicators should be distributed, without any restriction, to other partners of the involved users & buyers of the Consortium.	X
FRGE 1.5.	3 day Hind- & forecast of WISE products	All urban regular (FRUR1.1.-FRUR1.6) and rural regular (FRRR1.2 -FRRR 1.6) and All urban crisis (FRUCR 1.2) and rural crisis (FRRCR 1.2) shall 3day hind- & forecast of WISE products based on 3day hind & forecast of ECWMF meteorological forecast	X
FRGE1.6	Delivery through webservice/API	All information products & risk Indicators should be delivered using a webservice/API on a daily basis	X

Data Viewer

ID	Name	Short Description	Mandatory
	Management Component	The viewer shall be used by technical and non technical people per sector ranging from water authorities, nature/forest-, city-, crisis-, climate-, etc. entities	
FRDV 1.1	Data set management.	The application shall provide functions to manage datasets based on their technical characteristics, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access interface - License - Provider - Data quality 	X

		- Data type	
FRDV 1.2	API Management	The application shall support management of remote APIs, such as REST APIs, in accordance with INSPIRE and OGC standards.	X
FRDV 1.3	Technical Functions	The application shall support full CRUD operations (create, read, update, delete) for datasets and their metadata.	X
FRDV 1.4	Data set search	The application shall provide search functionalities for all managed datasets using filters such as category, name, and description.	X
FRDV 1.6.	Data set filtering	The application shall support filtering of datasets based on their technical properties.	X
FRDV 1.7.	Data set filtering view	The results of filtered datasets shall be displayed in a list view.	X
FRDV 1.8	Dataset meta data filtering.	The filtering functionality shall allow viewing of detailed metadata for each API.	X
FRDV 1.9	Visualization	Selected datasets shall be transferable to and visualized in the viewer component.	X
	Workspace Component	The workspace component comprises both map and table component.	
FRDV 1.10	Workspaces	The application should support creation and management of custom workspaces.	
FRDV 1.11	Colour configuration	Users shall be able to assign colours and display styles to individual datasets to illustrate risk scenarios or use-case-specific visualizations.	X
FRDV 1.12	Risk classification	The application shall allow users to define rules that determine when a dataset is visualized how, based on rules (e.g., water level > 3m = high risk).	X
FRDV 1.13	Workspaces	The application shall support creation of multiple workspaces.	X
FRDV 1.14	Workspace import and export	Workspaces shall be exportable and importable.	X
	Map Component	The base representation of the data viewer shall be a map.	
FRDV 1.15	Map data	All added datasets shall be displayed on the map according to their geospatial location.	X
FRDV 1.16	Map based visualization	The basic representation of data should be map-based.	X
FRDV 1.17	Time Slider Component	The application shall include a temporal visualization feature allowing users to view the geotemporal development of datasets via time-parameter manipulation (time-slider component).	X
FRDV 1.18	Point-based POIs	Points of interest (POIs) from datasets shall be represented on the map by their geospatial location.	X
FRDV 1.19	Geometry of POIs	POIs with spatial extent shall be visualized with their geometry on the map.	X
FRDV 1.20	POI popup	Clicking on a POI shall display a popup containing detailed information about the POI's properties.	X
FRDV 1.21	Table integration	The map shall integrate with a tabular component listing all POIs currently displayed.	X
FRDV 1.22	Legend	The map shall include a legend describing all visual elements currently displayed.	X

FRDV 1.23	Timeseries data	POIs with linked timeseries data shall have a dedicated graph, that shows the timeseries.	X
FRDV 1.24	Timeseries combination	Several graphs shall be combined over one another.	X
	Table Component		
FRDV 1.25	Supplementing table visualization	The table can be added and removed from the workspace.	X
FRDV 1.26	Table and map integration	The table shall list all POIs currently shown on the map.	X
FRDV 1.27	Table filtering	The table shall provide filtering and sorting functionalities.	X
FRDV 1.28	Cognitive table and map support	Clicking a row in the table shall highlight or focus the corresponding POI on the map.	X
FRDV 1.29	Table export	Tabular content shall be exportable.	X
	Detail View		
FRDV 1.30	Detail Page	Each dataset shall have a dedicated detail page listing its properties.	X
FRDV 1.31	Data set preview	The detail page shall provide a data preview appropriate to the dataset's type and content.	X

Urban Regular: Management/measures: water, infra, green, heat, etc

ID	Name	Short Description	Mandator y
FRUR 1.1.	Spatial and Temporal Resolution	Data shall be provided at a spatial resolution of 15–30 meters and updated on a daily basis to ensure sufficient detail for urban-scale assessments.	X
FRUR 1.2.	Soil water balance components	The solutions shall monitor and report all the soil water balance components: <i>P = Precipitation</i> <i>If = Infiltration</i> <i>I = Irrigation</i> <i>Cr = Capillary Rise</i> <i>ET = Actual Evapotranspiration</i> <i>Sr = Surface Runoff</i> <i>Gr = Groundwater Recharge</i> <i>ΔS = change in storage</i>	X
FRUR 1.3.	Soil moisture conditions	Soil moisture conditions in the unsaturated zone (0-5cm; root zone; percolation zone) should be provided as in the figure (on a daily basis):	X

FRUR 1.4	Actual Evapotranspiration & Evapotranspiration Deficit	The solution shall calculate and report the Actual Evapotranspiration & Evapotranspiration Deficit $= (ET_{pot} - ET_{act}) / Ratio (ET_{act} / ET_{pot})$	X
FRIUR 1.5	Phreatic Groundwater Levels	The solution shall provide the Phreatic Groundwater Levels	X
FRUR 1.6	Seepage/Deep infiltration	The solution shall provide the Seepage and Deep infiltration	X

Urban Crisis: Risk reduction/measures, Risk priorities/crisis handling

ID	Name	Short Description	Mandatory
FRUCR 1.1	Risk Indicators representation	The risk indicators shall be represented in a traffic light approach; sector related ³⁹ ; user specified per Group)	X
FRUCR 1.2	Must Have Risk Indicators	<p>The below mentioned ('Must Have' or MH) risk indicators (input SWV extremes per user sector) shall be derived from 1 or more of the Urban Regular Information Products in combination with user/sector knowledge.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil Drying & Wetting (in terms of severity, magnitude, duration, and spatial extent; Risk maps: where does it become drier, where does it become wetter in the unsaturated zone) • Saturated top soil moisture conditions (prior to heavy rainfall) <p>Risk of Urban flooding/inundation (extreme wet conditions) of city infrastructure Urban Heat Island Effect</p>	X
FRUCR 1.3	Wanna Have Risk Indicators	<p>The 'Wanna Haves' (WH) are specific separate remote sensing-based risk indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • City infrastructure (street/building) subsidence • Green vegetation health (biomass productivity) • (open) Surface Water temperature 	

³⁹ Definition sector: e.g. city Green Park division, City Hydrology Division, City Infrastructure (street/assets) maintenance division, City Living Health/Climate social division, etc

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Infrastructure temperature (Urban Heat Island Effect) 	
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Urban Climate: Evaluation/measures (LT), Re-analysis, scenario/forecast

ID	Name	Short Description	Mandatory
FRUCL 1.1	Re-analysis dataset	A re-analysis ⁴⁰ dataset (2000-2025) of: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> I. The soil water balance components II. Soil moisture conditions (0-5cm; root zone; percolation zone) III. Soil Drying & Wetting (in terms of severity, magnitude, duration, and spatial extent; [...]) In other words: We want grid-based maps that gives us information about where it becomes drier and where it becomes wetter in the unsaturated zone) 	X
FRUCL 1.2	Climate forecasted dataset	A climate forecasted (based on the national climate scenarios and if not present, use the ECMWF scenarios) dataset (2026-2050/2070) of: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> I. The soil water balance components II. Soil moisture conditions (0-5cm; root zone; percolation zone) III. Soil Drying & Wetting (in terms of severity, magnitude, duration, and spatial extent; In other words: We want grid-based bhmaps that gives us information about where it becomes drier and where it becomes wetter in the unsaturated zone) 	X
FRUCL 1.3	Spatial and Temporal Resolution	Data shall be provided at a spatial resolution of 100-250 meters and updated on a daily basis to enable accurate assessment of urban-scale climate dynamics.	X

Rural Regular: Management/measures: water-soil, nature, agriculture, etc

ID	Name	Short Description	Mandatory
FRRR1.1	Spatial and Temporal Resolution	Data shall be provided at a spatial resolution of 100 meters and updated on a daily basis to enable accurate assessment of rural regular dynamics.	X
FRRR1.2	Soil water balance components	The soil water balance components: <i>P = Precipitation</i> <i>If = Infiltration</i> <i>I = Irrigation</i>	X

⁴⁰ A historical reconstruction of the past hydrology using a combination of model data & satellite data.

		<p><i>Cr = Capillary Rise</i> <i>ET = Actual Evapotranspiration</i> <i>Sr = Surface Runoff</i> <i>Gr = Groundwater Recharge</i> <i>ΔS = change in storage</i></p>	
FRRR 1.3	Soil moisture conditions	<p>Soil moisture conditions in the unsaturated zone (0-5cm; root zone; percolation zone) as in the figure (on a daily basis)::</p>	X
FRRR 1.4	Actual Evapotranspiration & Evapotranspiration Deficit	Actual Evapotranspiration & Evapotranspiration Deficit (ETpot-ETact)/Ratio (ETact/ETpot)	X
FRRR 1.5	Phreatic Groundwater Levels	The solution shall provide the Phreatic Groundwater Levels	X
FRRR 1.6	Seepage/Deep infiltration	The solution shall provide the Seepage and Deep infiltration	X

Rural Crisis: Risk reduction/measures, Risk priorities/crisis handling, etc.

ID	Name	Short Description	Mandatory
FRRCR 1.1	Spatial and Temporal Resolution	Data shall be provided at a spatial resolution of 100 meters and updated on a daily basis to enable accurate assessment of rural regular dynamics.	X
FRRCR 1.2	Risk Indicators	<p>The below mentioned ('Must Have' or MH) risk indicators (input SWV extremes per user sector) shall be derived from 1 or more of the Rural Regular Information Products in combination with user/sector knowledge.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I. MH: Soil Drying & Wetting (in terms of severity, magnitude, duration, and spatial extent) II. MH: Saturated soil moisture conditions (prior to heavy rainfall) III. MH: Risk Wildfires IV. MH: Floodrisk in rural areas 	X
FRRCR 1.3	Risk Indicators	The 'Wanna Haves' (WH) are specific separate remote sensing based risk indicators:	

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I. WH: Structural rural subsidence (caused by enduring drought) / or top surface uprise (shallow water or seepage pressure) II. WH: Risk of Crop failure or (significant) reduction in yield III. WH: Risk lack of irrigation water IV. WH: Risk Water quality of (surface/ground) water systems due to enduring drought V. WH: Risk Desiccation of environment⁴¹ (of natural areas by definition) VI. WH: Risk Biodiversity Loss (habitat and species loss) 	
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Rural Climate: Evaluation/measures (LT), Re-analysis, scenario/forecast

ID	Name	Short Description	Mandatory
FRRCL 1.1	Spatial and Temporal Resolution	Data shall be provided at a spatial resolution of 100-250 meters and updated on a daily basis to enable accurate assessment of rural climate dynamics.	X
FRRCL 1.2	Re-analysis dataset	A re-analysis dataset (2000-2025) of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I. The soil water balance components II. Soil moisture conditions (0-5cm; root zone; percolation zone) III. Soil Drying & Wetting (in terms of severity, magnitude, duration, and spatial extent; In other words: We want grid-based maps that gives us information about where it becomes drier and where it becomes wetter in the unsaturated zone) 	X
FRRCL 1.3	Forecasted dataset	A forecasted dataset (2026-2050/2070) of: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The soil water balance components 2. Soil moisture conditions (0-5cm; root zone; percolation zone) 3. Soil Drying & Wetting (in terms of severity, magnitude, duration, and spatial extent; In other words: We want grid-based maps that gives us information about where it becomes drier and where it becomes wetter in the unsaturated zone) 	X

⁴¹ **(Soil) Desiccation:** Soil can dry out due to factors like evaporation, plant uptake of water, and lack of rainfall, leading to changes in soil properties and impacting plant growth.

General Crisis Management Intelligence Output requirements

ID	Name	Short Description	Mandatory
FRGCM 1.1.	Early Warnings	The solution shall provide Early Warnings (saturated conditions; too dry conditions; a heavy rain forecast; a no rain forecast; for instance, communicated through WhatsApp, Signal, Telegram and/or SMS)	X
FRGCM 1.2.	Awareness & preparedness	The solution shall provide information that creates awareness & preparedness (among citizens & water authorities)	X
FRGCM 1.3.	Data Output Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Filetype output: NETCDF ⁴² Data-type information products & Risk Indicators: Grid-based maps 	X
FRGCM 1.4.	Output Scale Requirements (on top of the above products)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Spatial Rural: 100x100m [relevant for future European scaling in future] Spatial Urban: 1x1m-10x10m [depending on the spatial situation of the testsites embedded in the surrounding (sub)watershed envelope (per group to be delivered, see in general the scoping documents on section testsite); relevant for future European scaling in future] Temporal Rural: day Temporal Urban: day 	X
FRGCM 1.5.	Simulation requirements	<p>The solution shall provide the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Nowcast (= estimation of the actual situation (= "today") using an extrapolation of the states & fluxes "yesterday", preferably based on satellite-based information (but model data can also be used), extrapolated with a model to "today") Forecast (3(-10) days ahead hydrological forecasts using ECMWF meteorological (ensemble) forecasts and/of an AI based) Re-analysis (= the weather & hydrological past; (for instance) 2000-2025) Climate prognostics (2026-2050/2070; based on IPCC scenario's & standard (= much used in EU countries) European derivative(s). need to get input from involved MS climate/meteorological institute 	X
FRGCM 1.6.	Software requirements for the creation of the information	<p>The solution shall:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use a groundwater model code (for instance MODFLOW-6, but an AI-based model is also possible) for the estimation of the lower boundary 	X

⁴² NETCDF (a European dataformat-standard) can be used in all GIS-systems, Python, R et cetera. NETCDF cannot be read in to Excel directly. However, with a rather simple Python or R script NETCDF can be converted into CSV which can be read in to Excel.

ID	Name	Short Description	Mandatory
	products & risk indicators	<p>condition for the unsaturated zone flux & state estimates.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The unsaturated zone flux & state estimates must be based using both remote sensing data (satellite and radar⁴³/grid-based rainfall) and a hydrological model (or combination of models; an AI based model is also possible) that is broadly used within the hydrological community of Europe/EU countries. Based on the analysis relevant models are HYDRUS, SWAP, HYDROGEOSPHERE, OpenGeoSys, PanFlow, Richards FOAL, VS2DT / VS2DI (USGS)) The unsaturated zone modelcode should be open source, well documented with a broad user community, compatible with for instance MODFLOW-6 The to be used software for the creation of risk indicator maps should be well documented and open source. 	
FRGCM 1.7.	Requirements regarding the use of parameterization data, boundary conditions & other prior data & information for the modelbuilding process	The contractor shall to use European standard datasets regarding land use, pedotransfer functions, DTM, soil types, meteorology, hydrogeology, open water bodies, catchment boundaries and test site specific data)	X
FRGCM 1.8.	Requirements regarding the use of remote sensing data	The data to be used (both satellite data (information) and radar-based rainfall estimates) should be freely available based on data and information generated by 1 or more EU organizations.	X
FRGCM 1.9.	Requirements regarding the integration of remote sensing end model (output) data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The integration (through pre- or postprocessing methods) of the remote sensing data en unsaturated zone model (output) data should be merged in a statistically sound way which is published in a peer reviewed paper and/or well documented. The result of this integration should also create an estimate of the trend: will it become wetter or drier (including a bandwidth). 	X

⁴³ If available. Otherwise you should upscale ground-based measurements using a peer reviewed geostatistical method.

7.2.2. Technical requirements

Data Handling

ID	Name	Short Description	Mandatory
TRDH 1.1.	OGC Standards Compliance	When working with time series data, the solution shall support OGC standards (SensorThings API). When working with geo-registered map images, the OGC standards WMS, WFS, WMTS shall be supported.	X
TRDH 1.2.	Open European Data	It is mandatory that the solution uses use European basic data for input for the integrated solution, like Copernicus data, the European Soil Grid, EuroDEM, meteorological ECWMF (like ERA5 etc. or e.g. International (Radar) Rain composite data, etc. Potsdam Soil moisture data (SOMMET), ESDAC European soil database, etc.	X
TRDH 1.3	Data Formats	The solution shall offer a generic and lossless data export. The solution shall provide a generic, configurable and pluggable data import, allowing the import of arbitrary data.	X
TRDH 1.4	Multi-Source Integration	The solution shall allow real-time ingestion of heterogeneous data sources via both push and pull mechanisms.	X
TRDH 1.5	Update Frequency	The solution should support regular updates (weekly/bi-weekly) and hourly updates in crisis mode.	
TRDH 1.6	Spatial Resolution	Map data within the solution shall support satellite imagery with spatial resolution $\leq 30 \times 30$ m.	X
TRDH 1.7	Temporal Coverage	The solution should support historical, real-time, and forecasted data for time series analysis and risk forecasting.	
TRDH 1.8	Data Fusion / Normalization	The solution should harmonize and fuse data from multiple diverse sources (e.g., evapotranspiration, groundwater, land use).	
TRDH 1.9	Data Quality	The solution shall include administrative metadata on data quality, including validation flags and provenance information, licenses.	X
TRDH 1.10	FAIR Data	All managed data shall be findable, accessible, interopareble and reusable according to the FAIR principle.	X
TRDH 1.10.1	Unique Identifiers	Data sets managed in the system must have unique identifiers.	X
TRDH 1.10.2	Stable URL Access	Datasets must have stable URLs for (meta)-data access.	X
TRDH 1.10.3	Rich Meta Data	Data sets shall have rich metadata including descriptive, structural and administrative metadata.	X
TRDH 1.10.4	Meta data availability	Preserve metadata independently from the data set itself.	X
TRDH 1.10.5	Shared Languages for Data Description	Use machine-readable formats and adopt existing ontologies to describe the data.	
TRDH 1.10.6	Licensing	Licenses shall be assignable to data sets.	X

Analysis and Intelligence

ID	Name	Short Description	Mandatory
TRAI 1.1.	Custom Algorithm Integration	The solution shall offer a plug-in architecture and standardized interfaces for integrating user-defined algorithms and models.	X
TRAI 1.2	System Indicators	The solution should include performance indicators in a liveliness probe/metrics probe, that give information about the status of the service.	
TRAI 1.3	Trend and Anomaly Detection	The solution should enable continuous monitoring of trends and anomalies using real-time and historical data.	
TRAI 2.1	Event Detection and Automation	The solution should support real-time event triggers and automated workflows (e.g., alerts, authority communication).	
TRAI 3.1	Scenario Simulation	The solution should support simulations for various risk and impact scenarios, including drought, flood, wildfire, and green infrastructure.	
TRAI 3.2	Dynamic Risk Mapping	The solution should provide real-time and regularly updated spatial risk maps.	

Interfaces and Interoperability

ID	Name	Short Description	Mandatory
TRII 1.1 (FRI 1.3)	Webbased User-Friendly Viewer (GUI)	The solution shall provide a web-based, configurable human-readable viewer (GUI).	X
TRII 1.2	Technical Configurability	The solution must provide information for technical personnel to configure and enhance all functions of the system.	X
TRII 1.3	Real-Time and Event-Based Communication	The solution should support real-time updates and event-driven communication using protocols such as MQTT or WebSockets.	
TRII 1.4	Offline/Low-Bandwidth Use	When provided as mobile application, the solution should support offline access and data queuing for field users with no connectivity.	X
TRII 1.5	Multilingual and Accessible Design	The solution shall offer an internationalisation-based, multilingual and accessible interface. All functions must be accessible through short-cuts; texts and layouts must be accessible for screen readers.	X
TRII 1.6	Responsive Design	When provided as multi-platform application, the solution shall natively offer reactive support for various screen sizes, from smartphones to large displays.	X
TRII 1.7	Role-Based API Access	The solution shall expose machine-readable APIs (e.g., REST, SensorThings) with secure, role-based access for integration with third-party tools (e.g., SCADA, GIS, control systems).	X
TRII 1.8	Interactive GIS Interface	The solution shall provide an interactive map-based interface supporting multiple geospatial layers (e.g., risk maps, satellite, field data). The timely development of a	X

ID	Name	Short Description	Mandatory
		parameter must be made approachable through a time-based parameter.	
TRII 1.9	GIS Platform Integration	The solution should provide options to seamlessly integrate with municipal, regional, and national GIS tools for spatial data management and decision-making.	

Governance and Security

ID	Name	Short Description	Mandatory
TRGS 1.1	Role-Based Access Control (RBAC)	The solution shall support role-based access, enabling configuration of user rights by group.	X
TRGS 1.2	Fine-Grained Permissions	The solution shall allow permissions to be configured at multiple levels (e.g., data layers, tools, functions) to reflect institutional needs.	X
TRGS 1.3	User Action Auditability	The solution should log and audit all user interactions (e.g., data edits, configurations) to ensure traceability and accountability.	
TRGS 1.4	Secure Access, Data Protection, GDPR	The solution shall implement secure access protocols and protect sensitive data. The demands by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) shall be respected.	X
TRGS 1.5	Availability & Resilience	The solution shall ensure operational continuity and data integrity during emergencies.	X
TRGS 1.6	Legal & Regulatory Compliance	The solution should support compliance with public sector regulations regarding the use case domain.	

Operational Support

ID	Name	Short Description	Mandatory
TROS 1.1	Training and Test Mode	The solution shall provide safe practice environments for user training and testing with dummy data.	X
TROS 1.2	Calibration and Validation	The solution should include tools to calibrate and validate models and data layers for operational accuracy.	
TROS 1.3	User Guidance & Help Tools	The solution shall include built-in user guidance, contextual help, and interface-based support tools.	X
TROS 1.4	Notification System	The solution should offer communication capabilities outside of the system such as email or SMS.	
TROS 1.5	Automated Reporting	The solution should enable automated generation of periodic or event-based reports (e.g., weekly summaries of drought, flood, or wildfire risks).	
TROS 1.6	User Support Communication	The solution shall integrate a communication mechanism for reporting bugs or feature requests, e.g. a ticket system.	X
TROS 1.7	Announcement Mechanism	The solution should integrate an announcement mechanism, that can inform either all or certain users about	

ID	Name	Short Description	Mandatory
		relevant news, such as maintenance or security relevant events. This shall contain an informational banner, as well as a dedicated detail page for the announcement.	
TROS 1.8	Installation Routine	As part of the deliverable software artifact, an installation routine shall be provided that performs the complete setup of the application on the target system. This routine must be delivered as an executable installation package (e.g., .exe, .msi, .sh, .deb, depending on the target platform) and must guide the user through the necessary configuration steps required for proper operation.	X

7.2.3. Contract Performance Requirements

ID	Name	Short Description	Mandatory
CP1.1.	Testing Sites	<p>The 5 main sites and their respective countries are as follows: Kalmthoutse Heide in Belgium and the Netherlands, Helsinki in Finland, Bratislava in Slovakia, Lemvig in Denmark, and Catalunya in Spain. These locations will be used for both validation and verification activities. The contractor should introduce the solution at the premises of each of the procurers in close collaboration with procurer representatives and their end users (potentially including end users without a technical background). System introduction includes installation of the solution and preparation of all necessary equipment and processes that are necessary for the solution to work. Pre testing will be done to reveal and resolve any issues that prevent the system from working properly at the premise (e.g. during pilots).</p> <p>In addition, several partner test sites will be involved, including locations in Greece (Region of Central Macedonia) Rotterdam and HDSR (the Dutch regional water authority). These sites will not be used for validation and verification. Please refer to ANNEX 10 for more details. Please refer to Annex 7 for more details, As part of PCP WISE, THW will also organize two TTX in order to test, demonstrate and validate the PCP WISE prototypes of the two suppliers/consortia in phase 3 in an operational emergency response (crisis) environment. Please refer to ANNEX 10 for more details.</p> <p>Other users (internal or external to the Consortium may be included in the testing activities.</p> <p>[A map and X-Y coordinates is included in Annex 1]</p>	X
CP1.2	Test site locations of 5 lead partners for validation,	Use the Area of Interest (AOI) per group (lead group partner), 2 scales of action: test site (detailed, measurement point locations) & surrounding (sub)	X

ID	Name	Short Description	Mandatory
	testing & demonstration	Watershed (100x100) for Phase 2 and 3 I, see links for location in 5 group descriptions mentioned earlier	
CP1.3	Test site from partners in the 5 groups for demonstration only	Use the Area of Interest (AOI) per group (lead group partner), 1 scales of action: surrounding (sub) Watershed (100x100) for Phase 3, see links for location in 5 group descriptions mentioned earlier	X
CP1.4.	Testing compliance	The contractors should demonstrate in Phase 3 compliance with the requirements listed in the current Annex 8 as well as the metrics defined in Annex 7.	X
CP1.5.	Pilot (Phase 3) Feedback	The contractor will make sure to receive answers on evaluation questionnaires to be filled out by end users during the pilot testing.	X
CP1.6.	Bug reporting	The contractor should set up a helpdesk and maintenance support as well as create a simple, easy to use error/bug reporting and general feedback mechanism / module that allows end users to submit feedback on the solution. This feedback should be reported on how it has been taken into account in the end of Phase 3 deliverable.	X
CP1.7.	Pilot Maintenance	The contractors will make sure to maintain the operation of all systems at each site at full quality for the duration of the pilot. A team will be available to physically or remotely resolve any issues and problems that prevent the system from working as desired.	X

